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Inequality in the 21st Century**

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Collaborative Housing WG

Co-residential Living Arrangement Strategies. A Multiple Case Study from South America

Juan Pablo Urrutia

Complutense University of Madrid

Darinka Czischke

TU Delft, Vincent Gruis, TU Delft

Global issues, such as the housing crisis, an aging population, and the energy transition, are shaping our daily lives and challenging fundamental notions of life paths. Co-residential living arrangements respond to this changing context as housing alternatives emerging from the experiences of ordinary people who have already faced these challenges (the need for housing, care, and reduced consumption) on their own.

South America has a rich tradition of self-produced housing practices, dating back to the site-and-services projects of the 1960s and to incremental housing programs, reflecting an important history of self-provision of housing. These practices nowadays allow us to observe how households continuously develop their dwellings in response to their families' growth.

The research examines self-produced homes in South America to understand their distinct decision-making processes and the spatial layout of their dwellings that facilitate co-residence. First, a conceptual discussion from a life-course perspective is presented to explain a model of self-production of space and residential satisfaction in co-residence.

To show it empirically, the research involves multiple case studies in Santiago de Chile with fieldwork visits to homes with extended households undergoing self-initiated adaptations to observe the social and physical dimensions of co-residence strategies. Semi-structured and life-grid interviews, measured building surveys of the dwellings, content analysis, and space syntax of spatial layouts will reveal how co-residence strategies could favour cohabitation.

Expected results* will present a set of alternative socio-spatial practices that enable extended households to live together as a micro, self-organized housing community. Preliminary results of this research will be available in May 2026.

Designing Encounter? A Spatial Study of Access Galleries in Collaborative Housing in Germany

Maria Schluter

Technical University of Munich

Within the discourse on collaborative housing, there has been a comeback of access galleries (Laubengänge) as a popular circulation type (Dürr & Kuhn, 2022). This renaissance is accompanied by the promise that this circulation type fosters neighborhood interaction, as it is credited with the ability to promote communication and encourage spontaneous encounters (Dürr & Kuhn, 2017; Förster et al., 2020).

Despite the indications in literature hinting at correlations between access galleries and social interaction in collaborative housing projects, no in-depth spatial science analysis has been conducted to date. This PhD research project aims to address the literature gap by analysing the architectural elements and spatial attributes of this interface. The study examines the design of boundaries between public, semi-public and private areas, as well as forms of co-design by residents.

The research considers factors such as proportions, materiality, facade design, fire safety requirements and how residents use the space. The research employs a multi-methods research design, with a focus on qualitative analysis of two case studies in Germany. Firstly, the case studies are examined from the perspective of the 'built environment' through architectural analyses, site visits and photographic documentation. At the same time, they are examined through the lens of 'social interaction' by means of participatory workshops and interviews with residents.

This PhD research is embedded within the research project 'FaGeNa' at the Professorship for Urban Design at the Technical University of Munich. The research project is carried out in collaboration with the German Youth Institute (DJI) and is embedded within the research cluster 'ForFamily', which is funded by the Bavarian State Ministry of Science and the Arts. The dissertation project is supervised by Prof. Dr. Benedikt Boucsein (TUM) and Prof. Susanne Dürr (HKA). This paper presents the current state of the PhD research.

Researching Work on Participation: An Ethnographic Approach to Urban Development

Nina Vogel

HSLU

Miriam Meuth

HSLU

Sandrine Gukelberger

HSLU

This paper reflects the methodological approach of an ongoing qualitative-ethnographic case study within the SNFS-funded project “Urban Development: Participation ‘from Below’ and ‘from Above’”. The focus lies on a large-scale urban development project in Zurich, where one of the last unbuilt areas – including parking lots and allotment gardens – will be transformed into cooperative housing, a green park and social institutions. By employing Grounded Theory methodology, qualitative methods provide access to everyday practices, imaginaries and power relations surrounding future-oriented housing and planning processes that remain largely immaterial during fieldwork.

Methods include door-to-door encounters, ethnographic walks, interviews, document collection, participant observation of residents’ and planning practices, and researchers’ positioning in urban space. Central to the research is the theoretical concept of “work on participation” (Bareis 2012), which frames participation as a labour-intensive process including breaks, difficulties, and alternative pathways. To operationalize this perspective, the research team developed a project-specific coding paradigm as heuristic instrument for analysing participation as situated practice.

Drawing on empirical material, the paper demonstrates how ethnographic methods trace anticipatory practices through which the future-oriented project produces present-day effects. The analysis captures how residents work on participation – from organized resistance to everyday appropriation of threatened spaces – well before construction begins.

The coding paradigm renders visible different participation logics operating simultaneously: participatory planning, grassroots mobilization, and individual practices of claiming space. The paper contributes methodological insights into researching participation in contexts where development projects remain anticipatory yet already reshape social and spatial dynamics.

Future research of collaborative housing: advancing collaborative auto/ethnography as a methodological framework

Tomas Horeni Samec
Czech Academy of Sciences

Recent studies of collaborative housing have either explicitly or implicitly provoked thoughts on how to scale up the specific collaborative housing models which are often embedded in variegated cultural, economic, legal and social contexts and settings. In focusing on these case studies, the involved researchers are often becoming also embedded in their field, in the social and material relations and sometimes even become part of the housing projects themselves non/intentionally involving the auto/ethnography as a method of research.

The methodological, and potentially political, challenge thus arise: how to provide an academic account which would go beyond the specific case study, which could be also scaled up and infrastructure; how to provide account which is rooted in subjective experience but has more general validity.

In this paper, we reflect on our previous research experience with auto/ethnography and suggest that accentuating, reflecting and nurturing the collaborative and collective aspects of auto/ethnography as a methodological framework may be promising avenue for future collaborative housing research.

Collective Property in Use: De-commodification, Institutional Fit and Adaptation Over Time

Phillippa Hughes
Universitat Rovira i Virgili

María Paula Rodríguez Liévano,
UNESCO Housing Chair, Universitat Rovira i Virgili

Collaborative housing models are often presented as a citizen-led response to the failure of the existing housing market to provide safe, secure and affordable homes. These initiatives typically operate through collective property structures, self-management, and (usually) some degree of intentional collectiveness in design (Griffith et al., 2024). They are generally intended to promote and protect affordability at the level of ordinary working households, though not necessarily those in the most acute or vulnerable circumstances (Archer, 2020).

In many cases, the collective or multi-stakeholder element is designed to remove housing from a purely commodified and financialised function (Ferreri & Vidal, 2022). These models have the potential to generate innovation within the existing housing market through the development of intermediate tenure forms that sit between full ownership and standard rental tenancy (Nasarre-Aznar & Simón-Moreno, 2022). All property must articulate itself through the legal structures and institutional forms of its jurisdiction. Each property relation is shaped by both formal legal frameworks and informal norms, which together structure how individuals, society and the state understand their rights, responsibilities and relationship to a housing unit (Blandy, 2023).

Collective property forms may require new institutional practices, adaptations of existing legal devices, or in some cases new legal provisions. This research examines how these complex collective housing arrangements articulate themselves within existing legal frameworks in England and Catalonia through case studies of projects in-use. It explores the degree to which these forms represent a secure institutional fit, where tensions or vulnerabilities may emerge over time. By focusing on in-use project the research gives a focus on how de-commodifying objectives are maintained, (re)negotiated or reshaped within broadly private property systems.

Locked into a green shell? Navigating the eco-social paradox in vienna's subsidised collaborative housing

Petr Kodenko Kubala

Institute of Sociology, Czech Academy of Sciences

Vienna's Nordwestbahnh of brownfield redevelopment encompasses a collaborative housing project funded through Vienna's social-housing scheme. The project seeks to reconcile housing affordability with ecological constraints that, under usual existing institutional arrangements, often pull in opposite directions. This process is sometimes called an eco-social housing (or "green") paradox. It therefore aims to deliver financially affordable housing while committing to a near-zero-carbon, bio-based timber-straw-clay building envelope.

This paper examines how spaces of minor or major conflicts arise not from public populist anti-green backlash but from within a pro-transition coalition of future residents, architects, developers, and public institutions confronting cost ceilings embedded in social-housing finance. Drawing on qualitative research (interviews with the resident group and key institutional actors, complemented by project documents), I trace three linked dynamics. First, the total-cost cap functions as an institutional lock-in

that shifts costs and risks from public budgets to a community pot and private co-payments, thereby reshaping what “affordable” means.

Second, resources absorbed by the green shell turn amenities and even basic fittings into negotiable add-ons, producing distributive and selective effects. Third, disputes over who classifies expenditures as “necessary” versus “optional” reconfigure governance, legitimacy, and recognition of competing visions of “green” and “affordable”.

By following how actors live with and reinterpret an earlier commitment to a bio-based shell as its implications unfold, the paper shows how eco-social transformation is negotiated through mundane collective discussions and budgeting decisions—and with what consequences for planning and public funding design."

Industrialised Housing Meets Collaborative Living: A Transdisciplinary Approach to Collective Futures

Alexandra Paio

ISCTE Conhecimento e Inovação

Emanuel Diego

DINÂMIA'CET-Iscte

ISCTE- Instituto Universitário de Lisboa

ISCTE Conhecimento e Inovação

Contemporary housing systems across Europe face converging pressures: affordability crises, demographic ageing, climate vulnerability, and the financialization of land and housing. These dynamics intensify spatial inequalities and expose the limits of market-led provision and regulatory frameworks unable to secure long-term affordability or restrain speculation. This paper explores how alternative governance arrangements—grounded in collaborative housing, democratic participation, and industrialized construction—can reorient housing provision towards social needs, resilience, and spatial justice. It assesses hybrid models combining technological innovation with collective ownership and public oversight.

The study is based on an international pedagogical experiment conducted in 2025 with five European universities, a Portuguese municipality, and local housing cooperatives. Designed as a real-world learning laboratory, the project brought together students, researchers, practitioners, and community actors to co-design housing scenarios integrating modular construction, circular materials, and care-based inhabitation models. The methodology combined conceptual inputs with fieldwork, participatory workshops, and cooperative design charrettes. Findings suggest that industrialized

building systems—often framed as technical efficiency tools—can acquire governance significance when aligned with collective decision-making and non-market actors.

Modular systems may reduce costs, accelerate delivery, and enhance adaptability while supporting resident involvement. However, their transformative potential depends on supportive planning instruments, land policies, municipal capacity, and resistance to speculative pressures. The paper argues that design experimentation can function as a platform for governance innovation beyond conventional procurement models.

‘A Little Shared, Mostly Private’: Consumer Attitudes Toward Shared Amenities in New Owner-Occupied Housing

Jannes Van Loon

Kyri Jansen

Woning Bouwers NL

Housing financialization is pushing more and more households into precarious renting arrangements. Increasingly, co-living and housing shares are not only pushed by financialized housing providers but, are also found as ‘solutions’ by households searching for housing as a way to dwell more affordably. However, there is limited insight into the broader housing preferences of potential residents. Are housing seekers primarily driven by a constraint of regular housing, or are there changes in housing preferences that make households prefer more shared spaces in their living arrangements?

This study addresses this gap by exploring to which extent the housing preferences of Dutch consumers, actively searching for newly built housing, also include a preference for more co-living, i.e. more shared space and shared amenities. The study is based on a questionnaire survey completed by 2,101 prospective homebuyers actively seeking newly built owner-occupied housing through the platform www.nieuwbouw.nl. The findings reveal a strong demand for shared amenities among respondents, though only a limited proportion expresses willingness to share private living spaces. This suggests that prospective homeowners prioritize the privacy of their individual residences while remaining open to communal facilities such as gardens, gyms, or playgrounds.

Additionally, the results indicate that tailored approaches to shared amenities are warranted, as distinct segments of homebuyers—including equity-rich elderly, first-time buyers without equity, and affluent families—exhibit divergent preferences regarding shared housing arrangements. These insights underscore the importance of aligning shared amenities with the specific needs and preferences of different demographic groups in the development of new owner-occupied housing.

Housing cooperativism: concepts, confusions and politics

Henrik Gutzon Larsen

Daisy Charlesworth

Department of Human Geography, Lund University

We have in recent decades seen a rising interest in housing cooperatives, and 'cooperative' as a notion is looming large in much research on collaborative housing. This has led to rich and evolving bodies of research. However, we argue that this research in aggregate can tend towards conceptual as well as analytical confusions. For example, it is a fundamental source of conceptual confusion that 'cooperative' is employed both as verb and noun in relation to housing; it can refer to processes of collaboration as well as political-economic and legal modes of organising property. Such confusions rarely undercut individual research contributions, but they can work to inhibit comparison and learning between and across cases and housing systems, further obscuring the involved politics.

Through a reflexive engagement with research focusing on housing cooperatives as a political-economic category, we propose that the richness of existing scholarship can be better understood and employed through an explication of underlying dimensions on the phenomenon of housing cooperativism. Provisionally, this involves core dimensions on what housing cooperatives 'are', but also on what they 'do' and 'how', and 'why' they are evoked politically in housing studies.

Our aim is not to propose a uniform terminology; rather, by explicating mostly tacit dimensions in existing scholarship, we seek to further dialogue on housing cooperativism.

Rethinking Cohousing: Lessons from International Examples of Inclusive and Affordable Housing

Ella Hancock

World Habitat

This research examines whether cohousing can provide an inclusive and affordable housing option for people on low incomes, including those at risk of or experiencing homelessness and refugees. While cohousing is often associated with small, owner-occupied communities developed by relatively affluent households, this study explores how its principles of shared space, resident participation and collective governance can be adapted within social and affordable housing systems.

The research draws on a literature review, international field visits and interviews with residents, practitioners and housing providers. Case studies were examined in the Netherlands, Sweden and the United States, alongside examples from the United Kingdom, Belgium and Spain. Projects were analysed through a consistent framework considering development models, tenure and land arrangements, affordability mechanisms, governance structures and community outcomes.

Findings suggest that cohousing can support wellbeing, social connection and housing stability, particularly for groups experiencing housing insecurity such as young people leaving homelessness, refugees and older adults at risk of isolation. Shared spaces and collective governance can strengthen everyday relationships and informal support networks, helping reduce loneliness and increase residents' sense of belonging. However, the research also identifies significant barriers to participation. In many countries cohousing remains difficult to access for people with limited financial resources or social capital due to development costs, lengthy planning processes and expectations of intensive resident involvement.

International examples demonstrate that inclusive cohousing becomes viable when embedded within public or non-profit housing systems. Access to public land, regulated rents and long-term stewardship by housing associations or community organizations are key enabling conditions. When supported in this way, cohousing can function as ...

Expanding the Institutional Imagination: Cooperative Housing, Structured Deliberation, and the Pursuit of Degrowth in Dublin

Kasia Wodniak

Trinity College, Dublin

This paper presents the results of a deliberative forum on cooperative housing held in July 2025 in Dublin, examining its potential as a method for fostering collaborative housing models. Moving beyond a conventional research methodology, the forum was adapted from Fishkin's Deliberative Polling (2009) to function as a structured, microcosmic public sphere. Its design intentionally scaffolded what Elinor Ostrom identified as the essential social infrastructure for commoning: building trust, navigating conflict productively, and co-producing knowledge among potential co-housers.

Findings from qualitative discussions and pre/post-forum surveys with participants, predominantly young adults locked out of traditional housing markets, reveal that they framed cooperative housing not as a mere shelter solution, but as a holistic vehicle for integrating social cohesion with practical sustainability. They articulated a vision where

shared resources and collective design enable more sustainable lifestyles, directly challenging neoliberal narratives of individual homeownership.

The study demonstrates that such deliberative interventions can be vital leverage points for collaborative housing development, expanding what we term the ‘institutional imagination’ required to materialise housing as an urban commons. It concludes that policies aimed at supporting collaborative housing must prioritise creating enabling environments for such polycentric co-production, positioning the deliberative forum as a replicable prototype for building the social preconditions for cooperative living.

Importing Models. Pilot Community Led Housing Projects in Eastern Europe

Oana Andreea MATEI
TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF CLUJ NAPOCA

This paper explores how community-led housing programs can emerge in places where such approaches are singularities. Through one or more case studies of projects that were community led, involved community participation and aimed to offset speculation, the analysis highlights project particularities. Semi-structured interviews are used to examine legal and financial aspects, design and social constructs are embodied into a building placed in a context where this model did not previously exist. They were not imagined either but adopted. The interviewees are architect, public policymakers and founding residents.

As pioneers of community led projects these practices offer valuable insight on the development of a housing sector that wasn’t addressed by any national housing actor. It also shows how models can’t just be implemented. They need to adjust and adapt to meet the set and setting. Furthermore, through their developmental process, we are able to identify setbacks in terms of funding or building regulations, while understanding the participatory process and desired outcome.

Conclusion drawn from this paper’s empirical data shows how community led models can be presented, perceived and finally, implemented. It also discusses possible prescriptions that can facilitate a wider scale implementation. The aim is to show how by adapting community led theories and practices, in ways that are compatible to specific conditions and cultural norms, gives way to a lacking residential model.

Modern Need Models as Drivers of Collaborative Housing: Evidence Across Urban, Suburban and Rural Contexts

Pia Westford
RISE

Nils Björling
Chalmers University

How we understand human needs shapes housing policy. This paper argues that the historical shift in operational need models, from Maslow's hierarchical pyramid to modern systemic frameworks, in which needs and their satisfiers interact in complex ways, can drive transformation in housing provision and institutional structures.

Early welfare-state housing policy prioritised subsistence and protection needs such as shelter, food, and transportation. As these were largely met, social needs such as participation, and autonomy have become increasingly central. Yet, the institutional structures capable of satisfying these needs have not gained traction in Sweden.

Structured interviews with 800 residents across a suburban environment (Gothenburg), a small town (Mariestad) and a rural setting (Tanum) show that the most pronounced need gaps are social, although with significant differences between geographies. Rural gaps centre on subsistence needs such as public transport and access to food stores, while suburban and small-town residents experience larger deficits in participation and autonomy, such as community activities, participation in community life and influence over local development. Need satisfaction has significant associations with tenure, country of birth, age and labour market status, adding complexity to geographic comparisons.

We argue that closing these need gaps requires institutional innovation at the municipality-civil society interface, inclusive organizational models and working methods, offering residents genuine autonomy, opportunities for shared activities and collective influence over housing and local development.

The paper offers a needs-based framework accessible to both researchers and practitioners working across diverse urban, suburban and rural contexts.

From Stockholm to Tokyo: Transnational Pathways of the Self-Work Model in Collaborative Housing

Ivette Arroyo
Lund University

Gwendoline Schaff
Housing Development & Management, Lund University

Kerstin Kärnekull
Kollektivhus Nu

Population ageing and changing family structures underscore the urgency of housing forms that support social connection and care in later life. Collaborative housing (CH) re-emerged in Sweden in the late 1970s as a bottom-up response to the gendered burden of domestic work and the social shortcomings of large housing estates, with a main wave of construction in the 1980s. Through academic transnational exchanges, the Swedish CH based on the self-work model was introduced in Japan, initiating a cross-cultural transfer of knowledge and practice. Doctoral research on CH Färdknäppen in Stockholm further inspired study visits by Japanese actors, exchange of knowledge and contributed to the creation of Japan's first CH, Kankanmori, in Tokyo in 2003.

This paper examines how the Swedish CH self-work model has been translated and transformed in the Japanese context by analysing how its principles of self-organisation, shared responsibility, and self-determination are reinterpreted under distinct socio-cultural and policy conditions.

Methodologically, the paper draws on long-term Swedish–Japanese study visits to collaborative housing settings and fieldwork in three Japanese cases –Kankanmori, Seiseki, and Hon-Machida– which form its empirical core. While the Swedish reference model Färdknäppen targets residents in the “second half of life,” Japanese CH has developed predominantly intergenerational forms. Kankanmori enables older residents' social connection across generations in shared spaces. Seiseki introduces shared spaces at the apartment-unit level addressing both affordability and mutual care for older adults. Hon-Machida, combines regular rental units with a collective with shared practices involving older adults from the surroundings.

Preliminary findings suggest that Japanese CH has evolved hybrid forms that merge the Swedish self-work model with locally embedded norms of community and mutual care, underscoring its potential for policy innovation in ageing societies.

Exploring boundaries of housing co-production: an emerging alternative model for tight extra metropolitan housing markets in France?

Adriana Diaconu

Université Grenoble Alpes/ Laboratoire Pacte

Emerging practices of socially and ecologically-minded housing professionals blur the boundaries of collaborative housing. In France, such initiatives are supported by national programmes that encourage innovation in housing design and local development, as well as the creation of links between academic research and professional practice.

The ethnographic study over several years of such a collaborative project situated in an extra metropolitan alpine region close to the Swiss border explores the levers for changing dominant housing production practices. These include reinventing developers' position in the housing construction market, increasing affordability, broadening the choices and engagement of future home owners and involving local public, private, cooperative actors and citizens in the co-production of homes and of common spaces associated with them.

Rural extra metropolitan areas with a tense housing market are quite atypical situations, less addressed in the literature on affordable housing provision in Europe. Even if within a national housing systems qualified as "mature", such as the French one, they are situated in local housing systems that are institutionally less well-equipped and with fewer resources for action than major cities. Here, housing co-production initiatives draw inspiration from collaborative housing whilst seeking to push the boundaries of this model and make it more viable in a tense market-driven context.

The paper examines how such a process redefines the boundaries between the private, the public and the commons in housing development. It also examines the boundaries between different fields of practice and expertise (of the developer, designers, local authorities, specialized experts and intermediary organizations, among others) in co-design. More generally, this study examines the added value of involving academics in such a co-production process in order to foster reflexivity and collective learning.

Evaluating Top-down Collaborative Housing: a mismatch between discourse and practices?

Lucia Chaloin

Grenoble Alpes University

Richard Lang

Freie Universität Bozen

Libera Università di Bolzano

Alessandra Piccoli

Freie Universität Bozen

Libera Università di Bolzano

Collaborative housing (CH) is emerging in a variety of forms, generating a growing scholarly interest to understand the differences. Among these, a growing number of initiatives involve institutional actors and are characterized by limited participation of the residents. These initiatives can be grouped under the label of top-down collaborative housing and are often linked to policies promoting social mix and inclusion of vulnerable groups. However, relatively few studies have examined these projects and their outcomes, particularly in relation to whether they represent functionalist or transformative forms of innovation.

This paper addresses the limited knowledge on top-down CH projects developed in Europe, and especially the scarcity of studies focusing on Southern Europe. If these projects are critically considered as socially innovative, what are their outcomes for the vulnerable groups targeted by these projects? And what are the specificities of these participatory processes compared to other cooperative or collaborative housing projects?

Focusing on the analysis of values and assumptions embedded in the discourses of the initiators of the projects, the study provides a critical perspective on the practices of social inclusion produced in these projects. The research draws on four Southern European case studies, three in Italy and one in Portugal, representing four top-down CH types with different target groups and housing configurations. Italy and Portugal have been selected for their shared housing challenges in terms of the unaffordability of the housing market and scarce public resources for welfare and housing. Ethnographic observations, focus groups, and interviews with initiators, managers, and residents have been conducted.

The paper concludes with a discussion of the mismatch between the project's innovative conceptual design and the everyday practices of residents and managers of the projects.

Urbanizing Collaborative Housing: Architectural Trajectories of Urban Kibbutzim in Israel

Dikla Yizhar
Technion, ITT

In recent years, collaborative housing has gained renewed attention as a viable urban residential framework. Collective living arrangements are increasingly seen as ways to strengthen social solidarity and share resources and responsibilities in contexts of urban uncertainty.

This paper examines how the architecture of collaborative communities developed through continuous interaction with wider urban socio-spatial contexts including housing regimes, planning systems and everyday urban life. It focuses on urban kibbutzim in Israel as a historically grounded case. The Kibbutz is a form of collective organization structured around shared property and communal life. Although commonly associated with rural settlement, Kibbutzim have long been integrated into urban environments. From the twentieth century to the early twenty-first century, dozens of collaborative kibbutz communities were established in Israeli cities under shifting conditions.

The study analyses the architectural development of urban kibbutzim across three phases: (1) temporary urban training communities in the 1920s-1940s; (2) urban kibbutzim formed during privatization processes in the 1980s-1990s; and (3) the relocation of entire kibbutz communities into urban complexes following the October 2023 war. Based on archival documents, interviews and secondary literature, the paper traces how collaborative housing typologies evolved through ongoing interaction with urban conditions.

The analysis shows that the architecture of collaborative housing was shaped through three key processes. First, typologies developed at the intersection of changing urban governance with collectivist ideologies. Second, incremental practices of construction and adaptation continually redefined the relationship between private dwellings and collective spaces. Third, collective living operated through dispersed spatial arrangements linking housing, institutions and everyday life across the urban environment.

Comparative Housing Policy WG

Key Worker Housing: A Conceptual Framework for Comparative Policy Analysis in the UK and Australia

Nicky Morrison

Western Sydney University

Across many advanced economies, rising housing costs are undermining the ability of essential workers to live near their workplaces. Health workers, teachers, emergency service personnel and other key workers are increasingly priced out of metropolitan housing markets, creating challenges for workforce retention, service delivery and regional equity.

This paper develops a conceptual framework for comparative policy analysis of key worker housing, using the United Kingdom and Australia as cases. Rather than reviewing programme mechanics, it examines how key worker housing is positioned within wider housing, planning and labour market systems, and how institutional settings shape which policy responses are feasible. The framework structures comparison across recurring design choices: how eligibility boundaries are defined and justified; where responsibility for provision sits across levels of government and delivery partners; how housing measures connect with workforce strategies; and how affordability is embedded and retained over time.

Applied to the UK–Australia comparison, the framework highlights a key institutional contrast: the UK’s more established planning-based affordable housing mechanisms have historically provided clearer pathways for intermediate and workforce housing, whereas Australia’s planning levers are generally weaker and more negotiated, increasing reliance on public land strategies, partnerships, and intermediate rental options.

The paper argues that key worker housing is not only a housing affordability issue but an urban infrastructure and workforce policy challenge. It offers a practical template for comparative analysis and for debates on how cities can maintain access to essential workers in constrained housing markets.

Time makes a fool of us all? Young Adults and the decline in Homeownership across OECD countries, 1970-2022

Bastian Mjærum

University of Bergen

Young adults today appear to face increasing difficulties in purchasing their first home, but has the transition into homeownership become more challenging than in previous decades? This article examines changes over time in the probability of homeownership among young adults across 20 OECD countries. Drawing on a two-by-two housing regime typology based on countries' promotion of homeownership versus renting and households' reliance on mortgage markets, I formulate four hypotheses about how the probability of homeownership for young people has evolved within these regimes.

The analyses use repeated cross-sectional time-series survey data from the Luxembourg Income Study, covering the period from the 1970s to 2022. Preliminary findings indicate that while age remains positively associated with the likelihood of becoming a homeowner, this effect appears to diminish with each passing year, suggesting that young adults must now wait longer to reach the same levels of homeownership that previous generations achieved at earlier ages.

Housing Regimes and Residential Mobility in Europe

Tommaso Frangioni

Politecnico di Milano

Alessandro Coppola

Politecnico di Milano

Marta Cordini

Politecnico di Milano

Barbara Brollo

Università la Sapienza, Politecnico di Milano

Residential mobility impacts on socio-spatial diversity, territorial inequality, and cohesion at a variety of scales and in differing ways depending on its contextual drivers and determinants. Residential mobility may be sparked from three – often intertwining – sets of variables: ones that are related to the household status, needs, conditions, and

often to their changes; ones that are related to the position of the individual/household in terms of present or aspired tenure – social or private rental, homeownership; lastly, is connected to specific policies that may sustain or hinder such choices.

These three aspects – families, (housing) markets, and public policy – directly address the theme of residential mobility and its relationship with housing regimes. “Housing regime” is here framed as a loose conceptual matrix that allows to develop idealtipic descriptions and comparisons of different local contexts. The housing regime influences important dimensions such as the relevance of certain tenures within the supply and how different social groups access them, the incidence of variably public/social housing supplies, the protective dimensions concerning the security of different tenures.

Surprisingly, after a systematic literature review, we found scarce evidence of scholarly work directly framing residential mobility in the context of different housing regimes in Europe. This outcome signals a potential research gap that would be relevant to fill for housing scholars. Based on the evidence gathered in the literature review and on further theoretical speculation, we attempt to identify some key analytical dimensions between housing regimes and regimes of residential mobility to directly address the relationship between housing regimes and residential mobility in Europe. In particular, we consider tenure distribution; access to different housing conditions; regulation concerning security of tenure; existing financial support to develop a conceptual framework.

Diversity of housing regimes across Europe

Adam Czerniak

SGH Warsaw School of Economics

Understanding the diverse forms of residential capitalism in Europe is crucial for formulating effective housing policies at the EU level in the future. This study re-examines the concept of housing regimes by identifying distinct institutional clusters across Europe and their evolution following the housing boom and bust of the early 2020s. Building on the analytical framework established by Czerniak & Maszczyk (2019), I employ an advanced subspace clustering technique, specifically the ORCLUS algorithm, to identify clusters of countries that share a similar institutional architecture within the housing sector. The identification of these clusters is based on both input and output variables that capture four key institutional domains: the housing market, housing policy, financial intermediation, and housing construction for 2024 (or the earliest available) and 2014.

The findings reveal several coherent models of residential capitalism in Europe that transcend simple regional or welfare state boundaries. These clusters illustrate how

various interactions between sociodemographic factors and diverse public policies influence affordability, tenure structures, and resilience to housing market volatility. This study contributes to ongoing debates on housing regime classification by providing an empirically grounded and methodologically refined perspective on Europe's institutional heterogeneity.

Transferring Social Housing Financing Instruments Between European Countries: An analysis of the adoptability of the Danish revolving fund model in Latvia.

Lucy O'Hara

Michelle Norris

University of Dublin

In countries with a large and well established social housing sector a similar suite of instruments are used to finance the capital costs of providing and upgrading social housing. Consequently, governments or social landlords that wish to increase social housing provision in countries where the tenure is currently very small or non-existent, have a relatively small choice of financing instruments which they can 'adopt' from more well-developed social housing systems to achieve this.

Drawing on policy transfer literature, this paper analyses the 'adoptability' of revolving fund model used to finance social house building and renovation in Denmark, where the 22% of households live in this tenure, in Latvia, where 2.5% of households currently live in social housing but the government aims to expand this sector. A revolving fund is a ring-fenced fund that provides loans or equity contributions to finance new social housing development or the refurbishment of existing dwellings.

Critically, this investment is then replenished by revenue from rents on these dwellings, which allows the funding to be 'revolved', i.e., invested again in social housing provision. As social housing systems are deeply embedded in nationally specific public and commercial housing financing systems, property rights, legal frameworks, and often complex implementation arrangements, these factors contribute to various 'implementation gaps' when policies are applied to the receiving country.

In this paper we investigate the various factors which support and impede the transfer of the Danish revolving fund in Latvia and how capacity of the latter to finance the expansion of social housing provision can be strengthened. The findings highlight the limitations of replicating 'best practice' models between countries and indicate that

institutional capacity is required when transferring housing policies from well-established affordable housing sectors to countries in early development stages.

Spouses in Houses: Political Drivers of Inheritance Tax Exemptions for Housing and Families

Frida Von Zahn

Humboldt University Berlin

Stephan Köppe

and University College Dublin

In the wake of rising wealth inequality, inherited wealth plays a crucial role in the reproduction of social mobility, class, and economic security. We stress housing as a unique asset that is central to understanding socioeconomic inequalities. Therefore, we argue that inheritance tax should be understood as a housing policy that targets the intergenerational transfer of housing wealth. Building on previous comparative research that highlights the historical developments of inheritance taxation, we provide a systematic comparison of housing and kinship exemptions in inheritance taxes.

This article presents the first descriptive and comparative findings of the novel ‘Taxation of Housing in Inheritance’ (THIN) dataset. We examine familial and housing exemptions within inheritance tax legislation across 40 OECD and partner countries between 2012 and 2024. We find that housing remains largely untaxed when bequeathed within families, despite rising house prices and increasing concentration of housing wealth. Hence, inheritance tax policies demonstrate incongruity between use value and capital value of housing and further incentivize intergenerational housing wealth accumulation. Tax policies remain remarkably stable across countries, highlighting the embeddedness of inheritance tax regimes despite the growing importance of inherited housing wealth. In a second step, we analyse the political and economic drivers of inheritance tax policies, particularly focusing on family and housing exemptions.

We model the association of political and economic drivers with inheritance tax thresholds, family exemptions, and housing regulations to understand the underlying factors for the variation in how housing is exempt from inheritance taxation. In the analysis we explore standard political economy theories (e.g. power resources, welfare state spending and political institutions), while also accounting for housing specific country variations.

Comparing Embedded Cooperativism: Continuity, Drift, and Change of Housing Cooperatives in Finland and Sweden

Daisy Charlesworth

Lund University

This paper explores and compares housing cooperativism as a political-economic category, asking under what conditions housing cooperatives (both in the realms of housing production and consumption) can sustain decommodification and democratic governance over time. Empirically, it traces the historical trajectories of two union-founded building cooperatives in Sweden (Riksbyggen) and Finland (VVO) from the 1940s to the present, with a focus on their engagement with decommodified and, at times, democratized modes of housing provision and intermediate tenure (e.g. kooperativ hyresrätt in Sweden and asumisoikeusasunto in Finland).

The analysis pays particular attention to how institutional embedding within broader labour and civil-society structures shapes the endurance or transformation of cooperative principles. Findings are drawn from a combination of archival research, policy and organizational documents, and semi-structured expert interviews. The paper develops a comparative framework to assess cooperative trajectories along three dimensions: durability (institutionalization and reproduction of cooperative principles), drift (hybridization and weakening), and conversion (corporatization or assetization).

This paper contributes to comparative housing policy scholarship by reconceptualizing housing cooperatives not as inherently decommodified or democratic, but as contingent, historically shaped, and politically contested institutions. It also offers a lens for understanding the structural ambiguities of labour-linked housing actors and the conditions under which housing cooperatives may resist or succumb to market pressures.

Introduction of a New Eligibility Criterion for Access to Social Housing in Flanders: the Asset Test

Jill Schoeters

Vrije Universiteit Brussel

This report evaluates the asset test (“middelentoets”), introduced in 2024 as an additional eligibility criterion for social housing in Flanders (Belgium). The measure excludes applicants for social housing whose balances in savings, current, term, or

securities accounts exceed certain thresholds. As it was implemented without prior scientific justification and concerns have been raised about privacy, stigmatization, administrative burden, and the exclusion of particular vulnerable groups, the report examines the asset test in the Flemish context, drawing on international comparison.

Based on this analysis, complemented by additional qualitative and quantitative research, it identifies a set of building blocks to guide decision-makers in designing a more equitable and effective asset test within the Flemish context. The international comparison is based on a screening of EU Member States, Norway, and several Anglo-Saxon countries. It shows that asset testing to determine eligibility for social housing is rare in Europe. The countries that do apply an asset test are comparatively analysed and categorised, taking institutional differences into account.

This categorisation is based on a conceptual framework drawn from the international literature, which distinguishes between different types of asset tests. In the final part of the report, the identified building blocks are translated into concrete recommendations across three core scenarios for the Flemish context. The first scenario provides a conceptual basis for setting fixed asset thresholds, the second proposes an alternative, potentially more robust and equitable form of asset testing, and the third explicitly considers not implementing an asset test, based on multiple arguments. In doing so, the report fundamentally questions the desirability of applying an asset test for access to social housing, especially in its current form.

A path dependence approach to comparison of social rental housing provision in Croatia and Slovenia

Marko Horvat

University of Zagreb, Faculty of Law

Gojko Bežovan

University of Zagreb, Faculty of Law

Path dependency has proven to be a valuable theoretical approach for the qualitative and quantitative comparison of housing systems in post-socialist countries. However, there is a lack of empirical evidence on the specific mechanisms of path dependency that have characterised the provision of social rental housing in Slovenia and Croatia and the extent of its influence. After the fall of communism, both countries underwent similar institutional transformations, abolishing old institutions and structures while retaining the cognitive legacies of the previous system, but housing provision remained a major source of social inequality. Slovenia and Croatia have since developed significantly different frameworks for social rental housing provision.

The aim of this paper is to provide a qualitative comparative framework to analyse the role of path dependency mechanisms in shaping social housing policy in these two post-socialist contexts. By identifying these mechanisms, we seek to elucidate the nuanced factors that contributed to policy divergences following the privatisation of the public housing stock.

With this approach, we address the central question of how and why different mechanisms of path dependency have influenced the development of social housing provision in Slovenia and Croatia. These findings will help housing researchers and policy makers to identify the obstacles to the successful implementation of social rental housing policy, especially in countries that are significantly influenced by historical shifts in power relations and institutional change.

Categorisation of Social Housing in EU National Accounting Rules: a comparative analysis of Ireland, Finland and the Netherlands

Michelle Norris

University College Dublin

Bob Jordan

University College Dublin

Recent years have seen significant changes to the categorisation of social housing providers and financing mechanisms in national accounts of several EU member states. In the majority of the Northwestern European countries, where social housing sectors are large by international standards, most providers of these dwellings were categorised as non-profit institutions serving households (NPISH) in these accounts until recent years.

Consequently, their borrowing, income and expenditure was classified 'off balance sheet', i.e. not included in government borrowing, revenue or spending in the national accounts. This situation has changed since then in some countries, while further changes are currently under active consideration in others.

This paper examines the diverse character and significance of these changes for the provision of affordable housing in Europe. It begins by outlining the historical development of national accounting rules and their standardisation across countries before explaining the rules currently used in the EU and highlighting the elements most relevant to the social housing sector. The paper then details the changes made or under discussion in three EU member states (Ireland, Finland and the Netherlands) in recent

years and examines the implications of these for the social housing sectors in these countries. The closing section considers the implications of the preceding analysis for affordable housing policy more broadly in EU member states and outlines suggestions for addressing these.

The Development and Institutional Embeddedness of Community Land Trusts in Scotland, England and Ireland between 2000 and 2025

Johanna Wiedermann

The Housing Agency

This paper examines the development and institutional embeddedness of Community Land Trusts (CLTs) in Scotland, England, and Ireland between 2000 and 2025. Although CLTs are now recognised as a mechanism for delivering long-term affordable housing, their origins lie in wider movements for land reform and collective land ownership.

Using historical institutionalism as a theoretical framework and document analysis to construct comparative timelines, the paper identifies key policy decisions, legislative developments, and critical junctures shaping CLT trajectories in each country.

The findings show that CLTs have become increasingly embedded in legislation and national policy in Scotland and England, though through different pathways: a rights-based land reform agenda in Scotland and a housing-focused policy approach in England. In contrast, Ireland's CLT sector remains relatively underdeveloped, with limited legislative and policy recognition.

The comparative analysis highlights significant potential for CLTs in Ireland to support long-term affordable housing while also strengthening community land ownership and local decision-making.

Global Policies, Local Translations: Thinking Beirut's Humanitarian Housing Governance through Bogotá

Bruna Rohling

ETH Zurich

Federico Ruiz Carvajal
Universidad Nacional de Colombia

David Kostenwein

ETH Zurich

This paper traces the trajectories of humanitarian housing policies from 2025 to 2015 by comparing how globally introduced policies have been 'landed' and subsequently transformed through local governance and contextualities in Beirut, Lebanon, and Bogotá, Colombia. It has indeed been a decade since the UNHCR global policy on alternatives to camps was launched in 2014. As a result, urban displacement has gained increasing attention in the humanitarian approach to refugees seeking shelter in cities. Meanwhile, the Syrian civil war (2011-2024) caused an unprecedented wave of refugees to its neighbouring countries, including Lebanon. The influx led to the establishment of the Regional Refugee and Response Plan (3RP) and the Lebanon Crisis Response Plan (LCRP). A very similar setup can be found in Bogotá and Colombia to address the influx of Venezuelan refugees: The 2018 regional Inter-Agency Coordination Platform for Refugees and Migrants (R4V) and its city-level subsidiary, El GIFMM.

A decade in, this paper examines how these global, regional, and national policies have been received and translated at the city level in Beirut and Bogotá. Mitchell and Pallister-Wilkins (2023) argue that humanitarian policies, established on a global level, contribute to a globally connected humanitarian agenda while creating distance from local political, economic, and historical contexts. However, this paper departs from the hypothesis that local housing governance and contextualities, too, shape these global housing programs and policies, significantly impacting those at the (non-)receiving end. The paper thus aims to think the humanitarian housing governance of Beirut through the Bogotá (Robinson, 2015) by bringing the relevant programs, policies, and actors from the two cities into conversation.

Methodologically, the paper builds upon an urban historical-comparative case study, stakeholder and policy mapping, and semi-structured interviews with housing actors in both cities.

Crisis, Conflict and Recovery WG

Seismic risk and building: mandatory Multirisk Insurance for Housing

António Duarte Santos

CEU-Coop Ensino Universitário

CRL (PT501641238)

Earthquakes are classified according to their magnitude as micro (less than 2.0), very small (2.0-2.9), small (3.0-3.9), light (4.0-4.9), moderate (5.0-5.9), strong (6.0-6.9), large (7.0-7.9), major (8.0-8.9), exceptional (9.0-9.9), and extreme (greater than 10).

Nevertheless, for large earthquakes (greater than 7), the moment magnitude scale (M_w) is more frequently used today, as it measures the total energy released more accurately. If we cannot overcome the earthquake or prevent our homes from being damaged, at least we can, and should, ensure that after the shake, we have financial assistance to rebuild our lives. How? By subscribing to a multi-risk insurance policy.

Earthquakes don't kill people. What kills people are the buildings themselves, depending on the robustness of the housing construction and of the building as a whole. Regarding the insured capital, it is advisable that it be identical to the total reconstruction value of the property and, whenever renovation works or structural alterations are carried out, it should be increased so that the building is 100% covered. In the event of a claim, the insurer will only pay for damages that are within the insured capital amount, in the case of housing bank loans.

This paper aims to estimate which explanatory variables could justify the requirement for all homes to have seismic coverage through multirisk insurance based on the Portuguese experience. After reviewing the literature, we applied a probabilistic model with data from various databases, analysed results and drew relevant conclusions. Finally, we believe this study could be extended to other European countries' policy makers. Keywords: seismic risk; multirisk insurance; housing; construction.

“I live under my boss's roof”: Employers, Private Actors and Housing Access in Rural Housing Crises (France)

Solène Gaudin

Université Rennes 2

Violette Mével

Laboratoire ESO Université Rennes 2

In a context of deepening housing crises, access to housing has become a major constraint for workers in many rural territories. Housing shortages increasingly affect rural regions marked by low vacancy rates, seasonal employment, and limited public housing provision (Marinos, 2024; Sencébé, 2014). In this context, employers and other private actors are increasingly involved in the housing trajectories of their employees. The recurrent expression “I live under my boss's roof” encapsulates both the material arrangements and the power relations embedded in these practices.

Based on in-depth interviews conducted in three rural territories in France—Brittany, Creuse, Drôme—this paper analyses how employer-mediated housing emerges as a response to housing crises and labour shortages. These territories share common structural constraints—tight rental markets, low vacancy rates, and precarious or seasonal employment—while differing in their economic profiles and institutional configurations. Through the perspectives of workers, employers, and housing actors, the paper examines how private actors step in where public housing policies prove insufficient or ineffective.

The analysis highlights hybrid arrangements situated at the intersection of private capital (Fields, 2017), labour markets, and state policies, often shaped by crisis management rather than long-term housing strategies. Employers’ involvement in housing provision appears both as a pragmatic response to labour shortages and as a mechanism that reshapes dependency, and power relations in everyday life. The paper focuses on workers’ lived experiences: What compromises are made between job security and residential autonomy? How do these arrangements affect daily life and perceptions of housing justice (Fijalkow, 2018)?

By focusing on rural housing crises, this contribution highlights the growing role of private actors in housing provision (Madden & Marcuse, 2016), questioning their implications for housing justice.

Following the Money in Crisis: risk, trust and incomes and finance mediating Ukraine's housing outcomes

Julie Lawson
RMIT University

This paper investigates how housing finance mediates crisis recovery in Ukraine, where war has destroyed or damaged approximately 13 % of housing stock and displaced over 2.5 million households. While international actors have underwritten macro-fiscal stability, housing investment flows remain fragmented, dominated by repair grants, compensation schemes, and state-subsidised mortgages, reaching only a fraction of urgent needs.

This analysis adopts a housing-systems perspective, viewing housing as a dynamic system shaped by interconnected institutions, property, finance, labour, and welfare. Risk and trust serve as organising concepts: risk is socially produced and unevenly allocated, while trust is an institutional achievement embedded in guarantees, laws, and intermediaries that enable long-term commitments under uncertainty.

Empirical evidence traces three decades of income dynamics and housing finance evolution, revealing a persistent misalignment between volatile, weakly institutionalised wages and the requirements of mortgage-based finance. Wartime conditions have intensified these constraints: rent burdens exceed 50–70% for many displaced households, while subsidised mortgage programmes such as eOselia operate as selective stabilisers for formally employed borrowers, excluding renters and vulnerable groups.

Responding to two research questions, the paper first examines how existing instruments allocate housing-related risk across households, municipalities, financial intermediaries, and the state. It then identifies institutional arrangements necessary to shift from crisis substitution toward cumulative, mission-locked investment in inclusive housing. Contrasting Ukraine's ownership-biased instruments with European models of mission-driven finance, the paper argues that durable recovery depends not on capital volume alone but on institutional architectures that mutualise risk and stabilise incomes.

Disadvantaged Neighbourhoods and Communities WG

Experience of overcrowding as a child and school outcomes

Ida Borg

Sociology Department at Stockholm University

Ben Wilson

Sociology Department at Stockholm University

Elena Pupaza

Sociology Department at Stockholm University

Rosa Weber

Sociology Department at Stockholm University

Children's educational attainment may be determined by the material circumstances they experience throughout childhood, particularly if they experience household poverty or overcrowding. However, there is a lack of research examining whether the link between household deprivation and educational attainment varies across different groups of children. This is an essential gap because social and spatial theories predict variation by sex, migration background, and parental socioeconomic status.

We address this gap with a case study of Sweden, which has high-quality data and is notable due to recent concerns about increasing poverty and overcrowding, particularly among children with a migration background. Using longitudinal microdata, we follow all children born in Sweden in 2007. We measure poverty and overcrowding using annual data for their entire period of compulsory schooling, typically from age 6 or 7 until age 15 or 16. We then examine whether these measures account for grades at the end of compulsory education, overall and for separate groups of girls and boys with varying levels of parental educational attainment.

Finally, we test the robustness of our findings by examining the role of unobserved confounding, including by comparing children from the same families who experience different trajectories of household deprivation, i.e., comparing siblings who spent different durations in overcrowding. To further assess whether language ability plays a role, we also distinguish between math and Swedish and compare children versus grandchildren of immigrants, with the latter being less likely to have language issues.

Ethnic segregation and housing inequalities as explanations for increasing socioeconomic segregation in the largest Finnish urban regions

Timo Kauppinen

Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL)

Socioeconomic residential segregation has been increasing in Finnish cities, and the reasons for this are not clear. It could be related to the development of income inequalities, but that may not be the only reason. One potential explanation is the increasing significance of ethnic segregation, as the foreign-origin population has been growing quickly, and its share is largest among low-income households. Increasing socioeconomic segregation can also be related to increasing socioeconomic differences in housing.

This study assesses the contributions of ethnic income inequalities and segregation and differentiation of housing tenures and types by income to increasing income segregation in Finnish urban regions. Register-based data covering all households with 25–59 years old members in the largest urban regions in 1998–2021 are used. Segregation between low- and high-income households is measured by the index of systematic dissimilarity.

The results indicate that mechanisms related particularly to increasing differentiation in housing conditions by income but increasingly also to ethnic income inequalities and segregation help to explain the increasing income segregation. The importance of different explanations varies by region. Effects of new housing construction on segregation also differ between cities, aligning with differences in anti-segregation policies.

The role of neighbourhood occupational composition on occupational status in adulthood

Nickella Annmarie Jose

Stockholm University, Human Geography

This paper will analyse the extent to which neighbourhood occupational composition shapes adults' occupational status and how this relationship varies across spatial scales and occupational groups. Neighbourhoods are understood not only as residential areas but also as social environments where everyday encounters and local networks condition access to resources such as job information, support and opportunities for

social mobility. Building on previous neighbourhoods' effects and segregation research, the study aims to highlight how residential clustering by income, tenure and migration background shapes the diversity of potential social ties and in turn occupational status in adulthood.

Thinking “Community” Outside the Box: Dense Settlements and the Baan Mankong Programme in Bangkok

Fanny Gerbeaud

Laboratoire PAVE - ENSAP Bordeaux

Bangkok, Thailand, is home to a large number of informal settlements, where around 20% of the city's population lives. The commonly used Thai term – “chumchon ae-at” (dense community) – refers to a typological classification within the broader landscape of residential communities in the capital. It highlights these neighbourhoods' intrinsic social and urban characteristics: some historically-rooted communities became illegal over time; others occupy urban wastelands as a result of migrations and rural exodus.

While coping with the inherent pitfalls of informal urbanization – unsanitary conditions, eviction threats, flooding – they actively contribute to the urban fabric and economy. “Communities of shared conditions” develop, sometimes providing mutual aid and integration networks. When facing eviction threats, the notion of “community” can operate as a lever to assert one's space and place in the metropolis. Long-established communities might claim legitimacy through heritage preservation, canal communities may gather around environmental actions. It becomes a requirement in the Baan Mankong public program, led by CODI (Community Organization Development Institute), which only accompanies organized communities with a collective project to negotiate their regularization.

Through a participatory process involving multiple stakeholders, on-site renovation projects are designed to allow residents to remain in place while strengthening community bonds. As residents gain collective tenure security and neighbourhood stability, CODI's architects aim to empower civil society and to develop community networks that have gradually become international references.

Based on extensive fieldwork (PhD research) including on-site spatial analysis and semi-structured interviews with stakeholders, this paper explores the means and meanings of the notion of “community”, from an administrative category to collective action among engaged Bangkok residents.

From Mild to Increasing? Measuring Residential Segregation and Concentration in Prague

Jan Sýkora

The Prague Institute of Planning and Development

Similarly to other Central and Eastern European (CEE) cities, Prague has long been seen as a capital with relatively mild socio-economic residential segregation, even as income inequality has grown. Yet recent developments may be reshaping Prague's socio-spatial structure, as more than three decades of post-socialist urban development under various institutional and societal processes have passed, and the city has experienced housing-market shifts (rapidly worsening affordability and the completion of housing privatisation) and intensifying immigration.

This paper analyses residential segregation among different socio-economic groups in Prague since 2001. It tracks changes in segregation levels, maps the citywide distribution of socio-economic groups, and identifies local concentrations by synthesising three concentration metrics. The paper distinguishes four socio-economic groups – high, upper-middle, lower-middle, and low – based on nine ISCO occupational categories, refined using median income data for clearer delimitation. Segregation levels remain low, but they have increased over time, as reflected in growing unevenness and spatial separation across the city. The greatest unevenness is found at the high and low ends of the socio-economic spectrum, while the rising segregation of the upper-middle group coincides with the professionalisation of Prague's workforce.

Concentrations of marginal groups are often tied to micro-spatial land uses, such as clusters of new high-status residential developments and workers' dormitories near industrial areas on the urban fringe. These emerging hotspots deserve closer, mixed-method investigation to inform City of Prague policies aimed at sustaining the social and spatial cohesion outlined in its strategic documents.

Who stays, who moves? Determinants of post-renovation (im)mobility in the Swedish rental sector

Ana Tramosljanin

Dept. of Human Geography, Stockholm University

Extensive renovations of rental properties in Sweden are followed by significant rent increases, sometimes exceeding 40 percent, which has sparked a critical debate regarding "renoviction" and displacement pressure (Baeten et al., 2017; Elmgren,

Björkvald and Svanberg, 2017). While existing literature has documented the experiences of those who move, highlighting the risks of displacement for low-income households, there remains a significant gap in understanding the “stayers” – residents who stay in renovated properties and bear the subsequent housing cost burden (see Wang, 2020).

This study addresses two primary research questions: to what extent does housing renovation affect a tenant’s likelihood of moving out in the years following the renovation, and how does this vary across socioeconomic, demographic and life-course characteristics? The study utilizes an aspirations-capability framework to nuance post-renovation residential outcomes (Schewel, 2020; de Haas, 2021), distinguishing between voluntary and involuntary forms of mobility and immobility. This approach aligns with the “post-displacement” agenda, seeking to understand processes where residents may feel trapped or displaced within their own homes and neighbourhoods (Atkinson, 2015; Wang, 2020).

The study employs a quasi-experimental design using longitudinal Swedish administrative registers. The analysis focuses on large renovations and utilizes propensity score matching at the property level to create a comparable control group of non-renovated properties. Following the matching process, logistic regression models are applied to analyse the probability of staying or moving based on socioeconomic, demographic, and life-course characteristics. By focusing on both movers and stayers, this study aims to challenge displacement narratives and provide a more comprehensive understanding of how urban redevelopment affects residential stability and socioeconomic vulnerability.

Stigmatization and socio-spatial segregation: (de)constructing the narrative of the marginal in the urban periphery of Seville

Jose De Jesus Calderon Anton

University of Seville

Urban planning decisions reinforced segregation: the neighbourhood was physically separated from central Seville by major roads and industrial land, with limited connectivity and scarce economic opportunities. Over time, chronic unemployment, underinvestment in public services, and the spatial concentration of poverty contributed to processes of social exclusion. The area gradually became symbolically associated in media and political discourse with marginality and criminality, shaping its stigmatized public image.

This paper examines how media and digital platforms contribute to the symbolic construction of marginality in neighbourhoods such as Tres Barrios – Amate and Polígono Sur. The research analyses the discursive mechanisms through which stigmatization and criminalization are reproduced, amplified, or contested in both traditional and social media environments.

A large-scale extraction and computational analysis of social media comments was performed. Using Apify, comments were collected from YouTube videos and TikTok videos published between 2009 and 2025. Content centred on segregation, stigmatization, identity, and activism was excluded to focus on external representations. Comments were processed using the pysentimiento library, based on BERT/RoBERTa transformer architectures. Each comment was automatically tokenized and classified according to sentiment (negative, neutral, positive) and emotion (anger, disgust, fear, joy, sadness, surprise). The system also detects hateful, selective, aggressive, and ironic tones, as well as emojis and colloquial expressions.

Probabilistic outputs enabled a systematic quantification of affective and evaluative trends across the corpus. Preliminary findings reveal a predominance of negative and fear-based narratives, reinforcing socio-spatial stigmatization while also exposing moments of resistance and counter-discourse. By integrating qualitative press analysis with computational sentiment modeling, this research advance ...

Residential Segregation of Work and Family Life Courses in Finnish Metropolitan Areas

Nayara Machado

University of Turku

Aleksi Karhula

University of Turku

Timo Kauppinen

Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare

Anette Fasang

Humboldt University of Berlin

Recent research has documented increasing levels of residential segregation in Finland. However, less is known of how much this trend leads to more general segregation of life course trajectories. Using longitudinal register data, this study examines whether

individuals following different work and family trajectories are unevenly distributed across neighbourhoods. It further assesses whether the level of such life course residential segregation differs across regions, and how it varies across cohorts. The study population included individuals born between 1965 and 1981, observed annually from age 22 to 40, with residential context observed when each cohort is aged 40 years old.

We analyse work and family trajectories using sequence analysis. Similar to some previous sequence analysis studies we construct work trajectories consisting of spells in unemployment, education and work with varying income levels and family trajectories describing move out of parental home, partnering and number of children. Clustering is performed on random 20,000-person subsample using OM distances and partitioning around medoids (PAM) clustering with initial partitions from hierarchical clustering. Spatial segregation of work and family trajectory clusters is measured annually using the Entropy index.

The results show clear differences in how work and family life trajectories are sorted across neighbourhood contexts and how these patterns vary over time and between metropolitan areas. Overall, residential segregation of different life courses does not seem to follow similar patterns to socioeconomic segregation although it is clearly related to socioeconomic factors. How and when socioeconomic segregation is translated to segregation of life courses is complex and merits more study. At least in Finnish context the strong increase in socioeconomic segregation have not straight forwardly translated to increases in the segregation of life courses.

Residential stability and perceived safety in Sweden: The role of tenure, residential time and turnover rate

Madeleine Frisk Garcia

Malmö University/RISE

Perceived neighbourhood safety influences everyday mobility and access to urban space, yet little attention has been paid to how residential stability influences safety perceptions and behavioural responses. This study examines how residential stability, neighbourhood exposure, and social–interactive mechanisms relate to two dimensions of safety: perceived safety in the evening and avoidance of going out due to unsafety. Using data from the 2020 Swedish Neighbourhood Survey linked to population registers for urban residents ($N \sim 3,000$), multilevel ordered logistic regression models are applied.

The results show that partly different mechanisms shape perceived safety and avoidance behaviour. Residential stability has a limited direct association with perceived safety, but longer residential tenure and homeownership are statistically significantly associated with lower avoidance behaviour. Gender, trust in neighbours, and the neighbourhood context emerge as strong predictors of both outcomes.

By distinguishing between perceived neighbourhood safety and avoidance behaviour, the results show that policies targeting safety must address not only how safe residents feel, but also how safety concerns shape everyday mobility and access to urban space.

Social and housing characteristics of low-status areas in Budapest

Balázs Szabó

HUN-RENCSEK

Zoltán Kovács

HUN-RENCSEK

The proposed paper examines the historical roots of and social mechanisms behind concentrated poverty and socio-spatial segregation. It presents the development trends of post-socialist cities on the basis of a Budapest case study focusing on the bottom decile of neighbourhoods. It explores how the general trends have affected these most deprived areas of the city for the last decades.

The development of the post-socialist cities was fundamentally determined by the privatization of housing, deregulation, and the collapse of public housing construction in the 1990s. At the same time, the society also changed: the population declined due to suburbanization, and the economically active population flowed into the service sector due to deindustrialization. The economic recovery began at the end of the decade, with the start of housing construction, followed by urban regeneration projects and individual housing renovations in the late 2000s. There are parts of Budapest where the low-status population is concentrated. These are mainly old working-class neighbourhoods with low-comfort houses located in the outskirts and in the transitional zone, but the inner residential zone also has deprived parts.

The article explores where the low-status areas were located in the turn of the millennium, whether their status improved or deteriorated in the next decades, and how their housing stock changed. The public intervention is negligible in Budapest, new housing is built almost exclusively by private investors, so the development is fundamentally market-driven, social policy considerations rarely apply. The number of new dwellings is an important indicator of development not only within the deprived

areas, but also in their surroundings. Housing prices of old and new dwellings reflect the social differences between the old inhabitants and newcomers. The difference in housing prices between the low-status and the neighbouring areas can be used as a segregation indicator.

Impacts of New Housing Development on Residential Composition Across Different Geographical Contexts in Norway

Marieke Elisabeth Van Der Star

Norwegian Social Research (NOVA), Oslo Metropolitan University – OsloMet
University of Oslo

Janis Umblijs

Norwegian Social Research (NOVA), Oslo Metropolitan University – OsloMet
University of Oslo

This paper examines the socio-spatial consequences of new-build housing across different geographical contexts in Norway. While existing research has largely focused on major cities, international studies indicate that the degree of social inclusion in new housing varies between large cities and medium-sized towns, with differences by life stage and household composition. Moreover, new construction has been identified as a driver of gentrification, particularly through price increases in low-income neighbourhoods, areas with a high share of public housing, and districts with many immigrants, as well as in locations close to public transport nodes.

This study investigates both the characteristics of new-build developments and their effects on the residential composition of the neighbourhoods in which they are located, as well as surrounding areas. We analyse how new-build housing fits into broader gentrification processes, by examining how new-build housing affects neighbourhood development and social composition, compared to similar areas without new housing construction. In addition, we analyse how the degree of social inclusion and the composition of residents in new-build areas vary across different geographical contexts.

The analysis uses full population Norwegian register data for the period 2010–2023 at the neighbourhood level and applies a difference-in-differences design. Study areas are selected to capture variation in housing market structures, price levels, and population composition, enabling comparisons between large cities, medium-sized cities, and municipalities at the fringes of larger labour-market regions.

Urban Form and Residential Segregation: A Morphological Perspective on Disadvantaged Neighbourhoods

Pavλίna Suchá

Czech Technical University in Prague, FA

Residential segregation emerges from interconnected social, economic, political, and spatial processes. This study focuses on urban form as one material dimension of segregation, while recognizing that it represents only a partial expression of a broader structural phenomenon. Urban form does not, in itself, produce socioeconomic exclusion; rather, it may shape how disadvantage is distributed, experienced, and reproduced.

The study asks to what extent exclusion can be understood as embedded in the morphology of the built environment and how this relates to neighbourhood-level concentrations of deprivation. The empirical focus is Ústí nad Labem, a post-socialist, post-industrial city in northern Czechia characterized by deindustrialization, population decline, and persistent structural disadvantage. In such contexts, patterns of segregation differ from those observed in Western European cities, raising questions about the spatial specificity of exclusion under post-socialist transformation and the neighbourhood mechanisms that maintain it.

Drawing on recent approaches in quantitative urban morphology, the study conceptualizes urban form as a conditioning framework rather than a primary driver of exclusion. Morphological characteristics are analysed in relation to indicators of socioeconomic disadvantage in a classificatory first stage of research. The aim is to identify urban environments associated with higher concentrations of exclusion and to clarify the types of neighbourhoods involved. By shifting attention from social attributes to spatial structure, the study explores how exclusion may become stabilized in material form.

The findings contribute to debates on segregation in post-socialist cities and support more context-sensitive neighborhood-level interventions, highlighting how certain urban configurations may constrain mobility, reinforce isolation, and limit access to opportunity.

Growing Up in Municipal Housing and Social Mobility in Oslo

Janis Umblijs

Norwegian Social Research (NOVA), Oslo Metropolitan University – OsloMet
University of Oslo

Kristin Aarland
NIBR, OsloMet

Our study examines how growing up in municipal housing in Oslo is associated with later educational, economic, and housing outcomes. Using longitudinal register data from Statistics Norway, we follow a cohort of 4,293 children aged 0–15 who lived in municipal housing in 2001 and observe their outcomes as young adults in 2021. The study focuses particularly on how neighbourhood context within Oslo, especially differences between more deprived eastern and better off western parts, relates to social mobility.

The main research questions are: (1) How is growing up in municipal housing associated with later education, income, and housing conditions? (2) Do outcomes differ depending on whether children grew up in municipal housing located in eastern versus western parts of Oslo? (3) To what extent do neighbourhood characteristics shape opportunities for upward mobility among children from disadvantaged housing contexts?

Existing research shows that municipal housing in Norway is strongly associated with socioeconomic disadvantage, including low income, immigrant background, overcrowding, and stigma. Our preliminary analyses reveal substantial variation in outcomes among individuals who grew up in municipal housing.

Overall, young adults from this group have lower average income and educational attainment than the Oslo population as a whole. However, we also observe important differences within the group. Individuals who grew up in municipal housing in western districts are more likely to complete long higher education (17 percent versus 9 percent in eastern districts) and to enter prestigious fields such as STEM, law, and medicine. They also tend to have higher earnings and are less likely to live in overcrowded housing as young adults. Interestingly, these differences are not explained by variation in upper secondary school grades, suggesting that contextual factors such as neighbourhood resources, networks, and social environments may influence educational trajectories.

Who Gets Access to New Housing? Socio-Tenorial and Socio-Spatial Differentiation in Market-Rate Housing

Iselin Hewitt

University of Oslo

Drawing on Sonia Arbaci's perspective on how housing systems shape residential segregation, this article conceptualises housing production as a mechanism through which housing opportunities are allocated across social groups and urban space.

The article addresses three related questions. Where and what types of housing are produced within a liberal and market-oriented housing system? How does access to newly produced housing vary across socioeconomic groups and socio-spatial contexts? And how do dwelling characteristics, particularly tenure and dwelling size, shape social differentiation in access to new housing? Together, these questions speak to the broader issue of how housing production contributes to socio-spatial stratification and segregation.

The analysis is based on longitudinal register data from the Oslo region covering the period 2007–2022. Descriptive analyses and logistic regression models are used to examine socioeconomic inequalities in access to newly produced dwellings. The results show that newly produced dwellings are disproportionately occupied by higher socioeconomic groups, although the degree of selectivity varies substantially across contexts and housing types. Inequalities in access are strongest in central and socioeconomically disadvantaged neighbourhoods and weaker in several outer-suburban contexts. Dwelling size and tenure further structure these patterns.

The findings suggest that market-rate housing is not a socially neutral addition to the housing stock. Rather, it operates as a context-dependent mechanism of socio-spatial and socio-tenorial differentiation. By linking housing production to residential sorting and urban stratification, the article contributes to debates on housing systems, segregation, and the distributive consequences of market-led urban development.

Residential Neighbourhood Patterns in Norway, 1960–2021: From the Segregation of Poverty to the Segregation of Affluence

Rolf Golombek

Frisch Centre

Simen Markussen

Frisch Centre

Knut Røed

Frisch Centre

Ingar Brattbakk

Norwegian Social Research (NOVA), Oslo Metropolitan University – OsloMet
University of Oslo

Jardar Sørvoll

Norwegian Social Research (NOVA), Oslo Metropolitan University – OsloMet
University of Oslo

By combining population and housing censuses from the 1960s and 1970s with more recent register data, we analyze the development of income-based and ethnic residential segregation in Norwegian neighborhoods over the past 60 years. We focus on what we refer to as “systematic segregation,” meaning segregation that exceeds what can be attributed to pure chance. A methodological challenge is that the extent of random segregation has changed over time, due both to shifts in neighborhood size structures and changes in the size of population groups included in the analysis. We develop new segregation indicators that are neutral to such changes. We find that income-based residential segregation declined substantially up until the turn of the millennium. This was followed by a period of stabilization in most parts of the country, but income segregation increased sharply in the Oslo region. Whereas the poorest were previously the most segregated, it is now the richest who most strongly isolate themselves in their “own” neighborhoods. Ethnic segregation (the segregation of non Western immigrants) increased until around 2010, but has since shown a declining trend, particularly in the largest urban regions.

Energy, Efficiency & Environmental Sustainability of Housing WG

Targeting Serial Retrofit for a Just Transition: Mapping Energy Performance, Rents and Income in a German Rental Housing Portfolio

Mirjam Sophie Mael

Chair for Real Estate Development (iPE) [214220]

Elisabeth Beusker

Chair for Real Estate Development, RWTH Aachen University

The European Union aims to significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions in the building sector by 2050, with Germany targeting a climate-neutral residential building stock by 2045. At the same time, rising housing and energy costs raise concerns that decarbonization measures could exacerbate energy poverty and spatial inequalities. In this context, serial retrofit, an innovative approach to the energy-efficient modernization of buildings using off-site production and prefabrication, is promoted as a key strategy to accelerate deep renovation at scale.

This study explores how a substantial German rental housing portfolio can be directed towards serial retrofit in ways that both maximize CO₂ reductions and minimize energy poverty risks. The study draws on portfolio data for multi-family buildings, combining structural, technical and energy-related characteristics (year of construction, gross floor area, energy performance, heating systems and primary energy consumption) with socio-economic metrics (small area income indicators, rent levels). Using exploratory spatial analysis and regression models, the study assesses the interplay between "serial retrofit suitability" and "just transition risks".

Preliminary results reveal distinct spatial clusters, particularly in post-industrial regions, where buildings with high technical suitability for serial retrofit (simple geometries, high energy demand) coincide with lowest-quartile household incomes. These findings challenge the reliance on market returns for deep retrofit, highlighting areas where subsidies are required to bridge the gap between investment costs and tenant affordability, due to the limited capacity to finance deep renovation through market returns alone. The objective of the study is to ultimately develop a "serial retrofit suitability" map, thereby providing an evidence base for governance strategies that prioritize industrialized retrofit where it yields the highest social and ecological advantages.

Innovative Planning-Led Sustainability Model to Deliver Low-Energy Rural Housing in Net-Zero Transitions in England

CHIENLING LO

Birmingham City University

Timothy Lee

Birmingham City University

Sana Malik

Birmingham City University

Frederick Stone

Birmingham City University

This paper aims to present an Innovative Planning-Led Sustainability Model developed through a research project funded by the Cal Henderson Foundation. This innovative model is designed to leverage local planning powers by requiring the use of environmentally sustainable materials and design principles as a condition for planning permission. Focusing on the case of Cornwall, the model seeks to promote the delivery of low-energy housing and strengthen environmental priorities within local communities, supporting progress toward net-zero policy targets in rural areas in England.

Drawing on the expertise of our interdisciplinary team, the project integrates the latest technologies and sustainable home-design practices to enhance energy efficiency and demonstrate a replicable approach to future housing development. This model provides a valuable tool for local planning authorities to address the overheated rural housing market—particularly the growing influx of second-home buyers. This contributes to addressing the inefficiency of the planning system in England, where planning obligations have been widely criticised for failing to capture development value.

The model was developed in two stages. The first stage involved extensive secondary research drawing on academic literature, government policy, and industry reports to construct an initial conceptual framework. This framework was then refined through two project-team workshops. The second stage adopts a participatory approach, inviting 15 academic staff and 15 postgraduate students at Birmingham City University to critique and revise the emerging framework in a dedicated workshop. Their collective insights were subsequently analysed and incorporated into the final model.

Eliciting Preferences for Collective Energy Renovation in French Condominiums

Véronique FLAMBARD

LITL and Lille Catholic University

Fateh Belaïd

KAPSARC

Joffrey Stary

University of Nantes

Collective decision-making is a central bottleneck for upgrading energy performance in co-owned residential buildings. This study quantifies the preferences of owner-occupiers living in co-owned residential buildings across France based on a representative sample of 2,966 respondents. Respondents evaluated a hypothetical comprehensive renovation and reported their likelihood of voting in favour of the renovation under varying conditions. These conditions included the level of public subsidies per co-owner, monthly out-of-pocket payments, uncertainty about total costs, expected return on investment (7, 12, or 20 years), and the distribution of costs and benefits across co-owners, with equity tested through alternative allocation rules. Financial parameters dominate stated voting intentions. Subsidies exhibit strong responsiveness: increasing support from €5,000 to €10,000 per co-owner raises intentions by 123% (elasticity = 1.23), while increasing from €10,000 to €15,000 yields a higher elasticity (1.47). Remaining monthly payments show moderate elasticities (1.21 for €65?€85; 1.13 for €85?€125). By contrast, the return on investment horizon is largely inelastic, indicating a relatively high tolerance for longer repayment periods.

Distributional design is decisive: perceived inequities significantly reduce support, and respondents display a clear preference for equal gains across co-owners. An ordinal logit model explains renovation intention (1–5 scale, from no intention to full intention). Beyond financial incentives, support increases with expected thermal-comfort gains, perceived fairness in financial returns, social norms, confidence in influencing collective decisions, and pro-environmental preferences. Policy design in condominiums should therefore pair salient subsidies with allocation rules that are perceived as fair, while foregrounding comfort co-benefits and strengthening co-owners' sense of agency in collective governance.

Beyond Technical Renovation: Social Innovation and Niche Experimentation in Neighbourhood-Based Renewal of Large Housing Estates

Anneli Kährik

University of Tartu

Mari Kirss

University of Tartu

Accelerating the energy renovation of residential buildings is a central challenge of the European energy transition. While policy initiatives such as the Renovation Wave have increased attention to the decarbonisation of the building stock, the implementation of large-scale renovation remains constrained by institutional, organisational and social barriers. These challenges are particularly pronounced in large housing estates characterised by fragmented homeownership structures, where renovation decisions depend on collective action among multiple stakeholders. In response, new approaches are needed that combine technological innovation with novel forms of governance and community engagement.

This paper examines the role of social innovation in neighbourhood-based housing renovation through the case of the SOFTacademy prototype in the Mustamäe housing estate in Tallinn, Estonia. Drawing on the frameworks of sociotechnical transitions, systemic social innovation, and reflexive governance, the initiative is conceptualised as a niche experiment within the broader housing renovation system. The analysis is based on qualitative interviews with key stakeholders involved in the project. The findings identify three interrelated dimensions of innovation emerging from the prototype: (1) technological solutions, (2) institutional and procedural innovations enabling new governance arrangements, and (3) participatory practices fostering social learning and community engagement. These innovations illustrate how neighbourhood-scale prototypes can function as experimental spaces for developing integrated renovation models.

The paper highlights the conditions under which neighbourhood-based initiatives may generate scalable models for accelerating sustainable renovation in housing estates with fragmented ownership structures. The prototype was studied within the framework of the Horizon Europe project PREFIGURE.

The Political Ecology of the Rent Gap: Redeveloping the Südtiroler Siedlung in Salzburg

Philipp Leserer

Goethe-Universität Frankfurt

In my presentation, I analyse the ecological and social consequences of closing rent gaps through the demolition and reconstruction of the Südtiroler Siedlung in Salzburg, the city with the fastest rent increase in Austria. The study asks: How are processes of rent gap closure intertwined with socio-ecological crises in contemporary urban capitalism?

Built between 1939 and 1942, the Südtiroler Siedlung—now owned by BUWOG, a subsidiary of Vonovia SE - has undergone decades of disinvestment, social marginalization, and displacement. Following its privatization in 2004 and ongoing financialization, the estate is scheduled for demolition in August 2025 under an agreement between the Social Democrats (SPÖ) and Communist (KPÖ) led city government and BUWOG. The redevelopment will replace 220 subsidized units with 382 apartments, of which only 170 remain subsidized, illustrating the contraction of public housing under financialized urban regimes.

Using this case study, I illustrate the ecological and social consequences of closing rent gaps as an inherent outcome of capitalist valorisation. I demonstrate the specific roles of state regulation and financialized organization in closing rent gaps and their associated ecological and urban impacts. In the Austrian context of social housing—where long-term rent controls are intrinsically tied to the buildings—the demolition process terminates these restrictions, enabling the construction of freely financed apartments and the destruction of embodied grey energy. Furthermore, I focus on the role of housing financialization, emphasizing how financial actors generate and organize knowledge on where and how rent gaps can be closed. By extending beyond the local case, this analysis situates Vonovia's strategies within a broader global context.

The heterogeneous effects of housing energy efficiency on housing prices: utilising the emerging Causal ML approaches

Yunbei Ou

University of Glasgow

To achieve a fully decarbonized housing stock by 2050 which has been the priority in many governments to reach net-zero, it is fundamental to improve energy performance

of existing residential buildings. However, the large-scale energy efficiency improvements of homes require substantial investment, which predominantly relies on two approaches: market incentives and government subsidies. To decide which buildings to target for prioritized subsidies and which to take advantage of market incentives, it is necessary to gather evidence on heterogeneity of price effects of home energy efficiency.

Therefore, this study sets out to provide data-driven evidence on heterogeneity of energy efficiency price premiums to inform policy making. It innovatively applies the causal ML approach of meta-learners (including X-/DR-/R-learners) which offers valuable data-driven insights. Focusing on the Greater Manchester housing market from 2017 to 2024, it is found that more energy-efficient properties, signalled by EPC band above C, are averagely sold at about 2% higher prices than inefficient ones. Furthermore, older properties, terrace/leasehold homes, lower-priced properties, as well as those located in lower-income/higher-density/higher accessibility neighbourhoods are found to demonstrate a more pronounced price premium from energy efficiency improvement.

Overall, this study offers granular insights into policy design on allocating government subsidies and leveraging market incentives to facilitate the achievement of net-zero goals in the residential sector.

Between Dormitory and Family Home: Social Networks and Energy Behavior among University Students in Istanbul

Ebru Karahan

Ozyegin University

Occupant energy behavior in residential settings is shaped not only by individual attitudes or physical conditions, but also by social relations and networks. Recent studies show that social capital dimensions, trust, reciprocity, and collective norms influence energy-efficient practices at the household level. However, student populations and their diverse arrangements are underexplored. Students in urban settings occupy markedly different configurations, dormitories, shared rentals, solo apartments, or family homes, each embedding them in distinct social networks and relations of responsibility. Despite growing research on energy behaviour in dormitories, comparative studies across housing types remain rare.

This study addresses that gap by investigating how housing type influences energy awareness, consumption practices, and perceived responsibility among university students in Istanbul. The paper presents a mixed-methods study combining surveys and semi-structured interviews across four groups: dormitory residents, students living

alone, students sharing with peers, and students co-residing with family. Drawing on Putnam's bonding and bridging capital, Bourdieu's field theory, and Coleman's emphasis on trust and norms, the study examines how each configuration mediates students' information access, sense of responsibility, and capacity for action. Students living alone are expected to show the highest cost awareness but weakest social support, while dormitory residents may exhibit stronger collective norms but limited agency. Set in Istanbul, amid rising energy costs and a large student population, the study aims to contribute to the literature on occupant energy behaviour and to inform housing and energy policy targeting young adults.

Digital Building Logbooks and Renovation Passports: Enabling Efficient and Effective Renovation Towards a Climate-Neutral Housing Stock by 2050

Henk Vissher

Delft University of Technology

The European Union's ambition to achieve a climate-neutral building stock by 2050 is one of the most pressing challenges of the 21st century. Buildings account for approximately 40% of the EU's energy consumption and 36% of its greenhouse gas emissions, making the renovation of the existing building stock a critical priority. Digital Building Logbooks (DBLs) and Renovation Passports (RPs) are considered to be effective tools to support renovation processes, enhance data transparency, and support staged, cost-effective interventions.

This paper explores how DBLs and RPs can facilitate efficient and effective building renovations, drawing on the latest EU policy frameworks, insights from the Horizon Europe project Demo-BLog, and the Dutch NWO project RenoDat. The analysis highlights the technical, organizational, and social innovations required to operationalize these tools, including data harmonization, interoperability, user engagement, and the development of supportive business models and legal frameworks.

The paper also addresses the challenges of fragmented data sources, inconsistent standards, and the need for user-friendly interfaces and behavioural nudges to encourage participation. By synthesizing insights from policy documents, project reports, and academic literature, this paper provides a comprehensive roadmap for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers to ensure the successful deployment of DBLs and RPs across the EU.

Gender and Housing Feminist Housing Research WG

A feminist critique of dominant paradigms in housing studies: housing welfare regimes, asset-based welfare and financialization

Tahera Bilger

Université Paris-Est Créteil

This presentation, based on the preliminary results of my PhD research, seeks to open a conversation on how feminist theory can help reframe and critique dominant paradigms in housing studies. I will successively engage with three frameworks that have been central to my literature review, showing how the feminist lens I adopted during my fieldwork in Bologna (Italy) enabled me to approach them critically.

First, I will examine the now-classic theory of housing welfare regimes. By modelling welfare systems through different configurations of relationships between the state, the market, and the family, this framework successfully highlights regional similarities. However, it often fails to interrogate the gendered, heteronormative foundations of its three core components.

Similarly, the growing emphasis on asset-based welfare, in a context of increasing individualization of wealth and persistent gendered wealth inequalities, risks placing women at a structural disadvantage, which is seldom acknowledged.

Finally, I question the ubiquity of financialization as an analytical framework in housing studies. Although its effects are profound in some contexts, they are more limited and uneven in others. During my fieldwork on the private housing market in Bologna, corporate landlords and the threat of international investors were at the centre of nearly every activist discussion.

Yet paying close attention to more ordinary, everyday interactions between homeowners and renters allowed me to highlight the continuing importance of less formal, family-based property management strategies, which remain deeply reliant on naturalized gendered norms.

Beyond domestic violence: Residential Terror and Postcolonial Housing Regimes Affecting trans migrants in Brussels

Ansao Totolehibe

UClouvain

Building on my 2025 ENHR presentation in the Gender and Housing panel, this paper presents consolidated findings from completed fieldwork on the housing trajectories of trans* (self-identified as transgender or transexual) migrants from postcolonial regions living in the Brussels-Capital Region. While the previous contribution mapped racialized transmisogyny within institutional and informal housing systems, this second stage advances the concept of residential terror, drawing on Pain's (2014) notion of everyday terrorism and postcolonial critiques of governance (Mbembe, 2003).

Moving beyond domestic violence, I argue that participants experience a cumulative and spatialized regime of violence exceeding the private sphere. Residential terror names the structural and anticipatory production of housing insecurity at the intersection of cisnormativity, racism and migration control (Fassin, 2011; Ticktin, 2011).

Three forms emerge: (1) bureaucratic violence within asylum and social housing systems; (2) racialized and gendered exposure to eviction, exploitation and sexualized coercion in informal markets; and (3) chronic institutional abandonment producing hyper-mobility and unstable inhabitation (Warrington, 2001).

The research also identifies three forms of residential care work (CTRL+H, 2025) sustaining survival and collective agency: racially self-organized housing collectives, queer-of-color mutual aid networks, and negotiated alliances with selected institutional actors. Drawing on feminist ethics of care (Tronto, 1993), these practices operate as counter-infrastructural dwelling strategies.

The paper concludes with three policy recommendations for Brussels: embedding intersectional anti-discrimination in housing allocation, structurally funding community-led safe housing initiatives, and recognizing trans* migrant housing precarity as structural violence.

Unpacking Structural Pathways into Homelessness for Women and Gender-Diverse People: A Realist Review

Melissa Perri

MAP Centre for Urban Health Solutions, St. M Hosp

Patricia O'Campo

MAP Centre for Urban Health Solutions, St. M Hosp

Background: While existing research documents the prevalence of women's and gender-diverse people's homelessness, less is known about the mechanisms through which patriarchy and other forms of structural violence constrain access to housing for these groups. This realist literature review explores how patriarchal systems produce and sustain experiences of absolute and hidden homelessness among women and gender-diverse people.

Methods: Informed by an initial theory created using conceptual literature, a search string was developed. Empirical literature focused on women and gender diverse people's pathways to homelessness was included. Studies were iteratively coded to identify Context-Exposure-Mechanism-Outcome configurations, with main outcomes being absolute and hidden homelessness.

Four primary mechanisms were hypothesized and assessed through: (1) Intimate Partner Violence & Homelessness, (2) Gendered Housing Systems, (3) Feminization of Poverty, and (4) Intersectional Structural Violence. Results: Evidence was found to support all four hypotheses. Patriarchal norms constrain housing security by normalizing intimate partner violence and limiting institutional protections, forcing survivors to remain in unsafe relationships or enter homelessness. Gender-absent housing policies and structural economic inequities (i.e., labour market disparities, caregiving expectations) further obscured gendered experiences, leading to hidden homelessness. For Indigenous and racialized women, patriarchal forces intersected with colonialism and systemic racism, producing disproportionate experiences of both absolute and hidden homelessness.

Conclusion: This review demonstrates that innovative realist methods can elucidate how patriarchal structures and intersecting oppressions shape homelessness pathways for women and gender-diverse people. Findings emphasize the need for gender-transformative, intersectional, and rights-based housing approaches.

Housing insecurity in domestic violence settings – implications for feminist housing research

Friederike Frieler

Leipzig University of Applied Sciences

Selma Matzberger

Leipzig University of Applied Sciences

The presentation addresses the debate on the interconnectedness of housing crises and domestic violence. It outlines theoretical approaches and practical consequences for ensuring safety and emergency assistance in women's shelters, as well as approaches to violence prevention and intervention that are relevant to (feminist) housing policy.

In Europe, one in five women is affected by physical or sexual violence in relationships or in their own homes during their lifetime. Individuals who face other forms of discrimination, such as migrant women, women with disabilities or TIN persons, are particularly affected by violence.

The phenomenon of domestic violence contrasts with the social concept of a 'safe home'. Even more paradoxical to this notion is the realisation that the privacy of the home structurally favours the occurrence of domestic violence. Violent behaviour is still more socially accepted or normalised in the family context than in other social contexts.

Following the theoretical input, research results from a German project implementing a housing agency for victims of domestic violence will be presented. In addition to findings from qualitative data on personal experiences of (in)security in various housing and accommodation contexts, a critical reflection on the use of a scale to measure housing instability will be discussed. It becomes clear that some material and immaterial aspects of housing cause those affected to remain in violent living situations or limit the capacities of the support system for victims of violence.

From this, approaches and proposals are derived as to how housing policy can also contribute to the prevention and intervention of domestic violence.

Gendered Inequalities, Intergenerational Wealth, and Family Practices Structuring Housing Affordability in Taipei

CHIENLING LO

Birmingham City University

This research investigates the role gender plays in worsening housing affordability, partially derived from the positive intergenerational correlation in homeownership access between parents and their adult children in Taipei, the capital of Taiwan. As housing prices have risen sharply, barriers to independent household formation have intensified, contributing to the growing prevalence of adult children co-residing with parents. The increase in co-residence among married couples signals a regressive shift in family practices, reflecting structural constraints faced by young and particularly single women. Housing inequality is further complicated by gendered disparities.

Existing research shows that escalating housing prices disproportionately disadvantage young single women in Taiwan, limiting their access to secure and affordable housing. Meanwhile, current policy interventions—especially the expansion of social housing—remain insufficient. Such policies do little to challenge dominant cultural narratives that frame homeownership as a key marker of adulthood, nor do they disrupt the broader commodification of housing within Taiwan’s market-driven system. As a result, structural gendered inequities persist, reinforcing intergenerational and gender-based disparities.

This study employs a mixed qualitative approach, combining content analysis of academic literature with policy analysis of government documents published between 2018 and 2025. The findings reveal that young single women in Taipei face the most severe disadvantages, as economic pressures and social norms converge to limit their housing mobility and independence. Ultimately, the study highlights the need for more transformative housing policies addressing both affordability and the cultural and structural forces sustaining inequality.

Housing and Materialist Feminism: New Perspectives on a Long-standing Theory

ROSSIGNOL Lilite

Gustave Eiffel University

Materialist feminism has analysed women’s professional and family spheres jointly (Kergoat, 2012), highlighting the centrality of atypical and part-time employment as a

consequence of the persistent assignment of domestic labour to women (Hochschild, 1989). Within this theory, home is as a place of work, yet its accessibility is rarely questioned through gender perspectives (Lambert et al., 2018). Meanwhile, in a context of an affordable housing crisis in metropolitan areas (Frayne et al., 2022), incomes often fail to secure access to the private market and waiting lists for social housing continue to grow (Dietrich-Ragon, 2013).

My research focuses on the spatial dimensions of women's subsistence strategies in the Paris metropolitan area, adopting a materialist feminist perspective that conceptualises paid and unpaid domestic labour as an interconnected system. I focus on paid domestic work, a significant labour market for working-class and racialized women (Falquet & Hirata, 2010) that is characterised by precarious and underpaid employment. In this paper, I ask: to what extent does engagement in precarious domestic work limit women's access to stable housing, and how do they navigate these overlapping constraints?

Based on 43 biographical interviews conducted with domestic workers recruited through online platforms, my analysis reveals two main findings. First, access to stable housing is often a precondition for entering and sustaining domestic work. In trajectories marked by violence and precarity, domestic labour can represent agency and economic independence, but its feasibility depends on residential proximity to client markets. Second, social housing is not equally accessible: women without children or those in exile must rely on alternative strategies, including diasporic networks or employer relationships, as the private market remains largely inaccessible due to financial, gendered, and racial barriers.

Navigating the secondary housing market in Stockholm from a gendered perspective

Lenita Kefala

Dep. Of Human Geography, Stockholm university

As housing inequalities worsen in many cities, the secondary housing market has become the primary—and often only—route to housing. This presentation examines temporary and insecure forms of housing in Stockholm, including subletting, shared housing, and short-term contracts. These arrangements are characterized by limited security, frequent moves, and constant uncertainty. However, less attention has been paid to the gender-related inequalities that affect individuals' ability to navigate such precarious markets.

The presentation focuses on the experiences of female subtenants and is based on ethnographic material and in-depth interviews collected between 2020 and 2023. The results show how gender-related inequalities interact with housing insecurity in ways that limit women's housing opportunities and reinforce broader sociocultural norms related to care, vulnerability, and gender-related responsibilities and exposure.

The analysis, which is based on feminist phenomenology and an analysis of 'lived experiences', shows how gender is embedded in temporary housing solutions and reproduced through both interpersonal interactions and structural conditions, giving rise to an idealized image of the "female subtenant." The presentation contributes to feminist housing research by conceptualizing how access to housing and insecurity in the informal secondary housing market are gendered and draws attention to structural inequalities that risk being rendered invisible.

LGBTQ's Housing issues in Japan

Lisa Kuzunishi

Otemon Gakuin University

In our society, which is deeply ingrained with gender binary norms (the idea that there are only two genders: male and female), it is inevitable that sexual minorities—hereafter referred to as LGBTQ individuals—face difficulties in all aspects of their lives. Since the 2000s, there has been an increase in worldwide movements demanding an understanding of diverse sexualities. These movements include campaigns to eliminate prejudice and discrimination against LGBTQ individuals. Although same-sex marriage is not recognized in Japan, the Shibuya and Setagaya wards pioneered the implementation of partnership declaration systems in 2015. This system has since spread nationwide. According to a report by the NPO Rainbow Diversity, as of May 31, 2025, 532 municipalities out of 1,788 nationwide had adopted the system, and 9,837 couples had utilized it.

Within academia, research on LGBTQ issues spans diverse fields, including education, welfare, law, and sociology. However, studies addressing this theme from the perspective of housing are scarce. It is often noted that inheritance issues arise for same-sex couples who own property. Furthermore, data from the Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism from 2020 indicates that some real estate companies discriminate against LGBTQ+ tenants.

Therefore, this study aims to clarify the housing issues faced by each gender category based on the results of an online survey of 1,754 individuals. In a society that champions diversity, some argue that categorizing by gender is nonsensical. However, in

Japan's traditional housing market, the status of housing likely differs significantly depending on one's gender and the gender of one's roommate.

Progress Isn't Shelter: Trans Homelessness and the Feminist Politics of Housing Justice

Carin Tunaker
University of Kent

This paper argues that feminist and intersectional approaches are essential to reveal how contemporary housing systems render transgender and gender diverse people structurally invisible. Drawing on arguments developed in my book *The Paradox of Progress* (forthcoming 2026), I examine how dominant narratives of LGBTQ+ social advancement create a temporal illusion of improvement that conceals the ongoing precarity faced by queer people.

Legal reforms and cultural recognition are often celebrated as linear progress, but these narratives obscure persistent exclusion, discrimination and homelessness among those at the intersections of gender, sexuality, age, disability and race. Transgender youth are disproportionately pushed into hidden homelessness such as sofa surfing, unstable informal arrangements and unsafe temporary stays and these experiences unfold in private or relational spaces and therefore remain uncounted within official housing data. Feminist scholarship on care, kinship and adulthood helps explain why these forms of precarity are misrecognised. Gendered and racialised expectations about family support and normative life trajectories shape who states see as homeless and who they presume to be safely housed. The temporal gap between celebrated progress and lived precarity, which I conceptualise as the paradox of progress, produces epistemic blind spots that sustain the invisibility of queer homelessness.

By reframing housing precarity as a temporal, intersectional and epistemically unjust phenomenon, I challenge definitions of homelessness that privilege visible, street based forms of precarity. I call for feminist housing research and policy that centre trans lived experience, recognise the unevenness of social change and foreground the knowledge of those who remain invisible within dominant narratives of housing, gender and progress. Progress is not shelter and housing justice for trans people requires a feminist politics attentive to both visibility and time.

Female Baby Boomers Living Alone and the Gendered Dynamics of Housing Vulnerability in Switzerland

Maria Grazia Bedin

La Source, HES-SO University of Applied Sciences

This contribution examines housing dilemmas among Female Baby Boomers Living Alone (FBBS) through a feminist lens, foregrounding how gendered life trajectories shape housing opportunities and constraints in later life. FBBS constitute a rapidly growing group in Switzerland, yet their experiences remain largely invisible in mainstream housing research and policy. Their residential choices are deeply influenced by cumulative gendered disadvantages across the life course, including lower lifetime earnings, unequal care burdens and higher risks of social isolation.

Drawing on a mixed-methods design—statistical analyses of the Swiss Household Panel, an online survey with 388 FBBS, interviews with municipal officials and focus groups—the study reveals how gendered structures interact with ageing to produce specific forms of housing precarity.

Although most FBBS wish to age in place, many occupy dwellings increasingly unsuitable for autonomous ageing. Requests for adaptations are often avoided due to fears of rent increases, reflecting power asymmetries between women tenants and housing providers.

The scarcity of affordable alternatives reinforces a central dilemma: remaining in inadequate housing or relocating at the cost of financial strain and weakened social ties. Municipal interviews show that younger women seniors living alone are insufficiently recognized as a policy target group, despite their distinct gendered vulnerabilities.

The findings call for feminist-informed housing strategies that strengthen public and cooperative housing, promote innovative and collective living arrangements and improve access to information and rights. They also highlight the need to support FBBS in anticipating housing transitions while fostering social connectedness. Keywords: feminist housing research; gendered housing inequalities; ageing women; single-person households; residential precarity; life course; Switzerland.

Conceptualising housing as care infrastructure – conditions for caregiving within small housing estates in East Germany

Hannah Mueller

Bauhaus- Universität Weimar

The home remains the primary setting for daily care work, encompassing tasks such as meal preparation, laundry, childcare, caregiving for relatives, and providing emotional support, performed predominantly by women. Care facilities such as daycare centres, schools, pharmacies and family centres are closely linked to the home through everyday care practices. These facilities are described by Binet et al. (2023) as the 'urban infrastructure of care'. The availability, affordability and quality of housing as care infrastructure, as well as the surrounding urban environment, are crucial for people's capacity to care. If cities fail to provide adequate care infrastructure, caregivers must compensate for these deficits, which increases their care burden (Binet et al., 2023).

While the provision of housing determines the possibilities for care, with a few exceptions there is still a lack of broad discourse and systematic analysis of the care–housing nexus under current conditions (Aulenbacher, 2025; Baumgartner et al., 2021; Madden, 2025; Power & Mee, 2020). There has been a growing interest in the concept of Caring Cities as an approach to combat socio-economic as well as care inequalities (Müller et al., 2025). However, so far, little attention has been paid to the relevance of housing within the Caring City approach.

The lecture conceptualises housing as care infrastructure. Based on case studies of small-sized towns in East Germany, the lecture explores the social as well as the material conditions for caregiving within former German Democratic Republic (GDR) housing estates. The small housing estates from GDR times are a relevant resource for the social provision of housing but face several challenges. The lecture aims to bring in care inequalities as a new perspective on the challenges faced by housing provision in former GDR housing estates.

When Women Have No Home: Gendered Expectations and the Moral Meanings of Homelessness

Daniela Leonardi

University of Turin

In many Southern European contexts, and particularly in Italy, dominant cultural imaginaries associate femininity with domesticity, care and motherhood. Feminist scholarship has shown how the home functions not only as a material dwelling but also as a key site in the social organization of gendered identities (Blunt 2005).

Within this normative framework, the figure of the homeless woman represents a disruption, as the absence of a home challenges expectations that position women as moral custodians of the domestic sphere. Despite extensive research on homelessness, the phenomenon has largely been conceptualized through frameworks reflecting predominantly male trajectories or through policy-oriented approaches.

Feminist scholars have shown that women's homelessness is often less recognized and shaped by specific gendered dynamics, such as stigma, safety concerns and pressures to maintain forms of respectability (Mayock and Bretherton 2016). Less attention, however, has been devoted to the cultural and moral meanings that homelessness acquires when experienced by women in contexts where domestic stability remains a central marker of femininity.

The presentation addresses this gap by examining how gender norms related to domesticity shape the ways women experience and narrate homelessness. Drawing on more ten years of research on housing precarity, the analysis explores how women negotiate stigma and position themselves in relation to dominant ideals of womanhood and respectability (Skeggs 1997).

The paper argues that women's homelessness should be understood not only as housing deprivation but also as a disruption of gendered moral expectations surrounding motherhood, care and social worth. By foregrounding women's narratives, the analysis develops a gendered understanding of the moral economy of home, showing how the absence of a home becomes a site where femininity, respectability and social legitimacy are internalized, negotiated and sometimes contested.

A feminist approach to 'sufficiency' in housing

Heidrun Wankiewicz

Planwind.a &Corrina.eu

Lidewij TUMMERS

Corrina.eu

Main topic of the 2025 'Fourth Report on Gender Equality to the German federal government' is the social-ecological transition (Sachverständigenkommission 2025). In the report, 'sufficiency' is proposed rather often as a concept and as a field of action for energy and climate transition for housing policies (ibid: p24, 44-49, 71, 169-71 etc), however, without any differentiation of sex, age, lifecycle or care responsibilities.

Examples of sufficiency practices which according to the report have the potential to increase quality of life by reducing consumption are: 1 reduction of square meters for flats or for buildings 2 replacing, e.g. from car to bike or public transport or 3 Sharing of common spaces, or energy provision (p46). In housing such principles can often be found in co-housing projects.

In our contribution we present the concept 'Less for More', developed by the Scandinavian women's group 'BIG' in 1994 (Sangregorio 1995; Horelli and Vepsä 1994) as one of the feminist origins of co housing. It proposes -less individualism, for more communal resources, opportunities and exchange. Less individual household time, but more free time for care-givers. We argue that sufficiency is not suitable for a transformative German Gender Equality Policy. Rather, sufficiency is linked to situational and qualitative notions such as 'quality of life' and "good life". In order to overcome the care crisis and achieve a more gender-equitable everyday practice in care work, it is essential to see not only space and energy as a resource, but also personal time.

Consequently, when individual space is reduced, a simultaneous provision of (more) services and facilities in shared (collective) spaces and the neighborhood is required for gender fair, energy efficient and climate neutral housing. Special attention is needed on the tension between surface reduction (make rents cheaper) and accessibility for disabled persons in housing projects.

Self-help housing against turnkey products: A feminist perspective on participatory and incremental design

Elif Cemre Çelikcan

Baskent University

Traditional homeownership models, centered on completed and standardized 'turnkey' products, are increasingly functioning as mechanisms of social and spatial exclusion. By prioritizing market-driven property rigidities, conventional housing policies and programs deepen gendered inequalities by reinforcing the difficulty of accessing adequate housing for women.

This study posits that self-help housing programs' participatory and incremental qualities offer a transformative path toward inclusive housing production. It is highlighted how self-help programs' recognition of housing as a participatory process rather than a static commodity can be uniquely responsive to non-traditional household structures—such as single-parent collectives or multi-generational care networks—which requires adaptable spatial configurations. These programs' vast ability to cooperate with incremental design is focused for allowing a shift toward staged ownership or usage rights models, which provide immediate security of tenure without the prohibitive barriers of market-driven mortgages and enhance the affordability of housing.

The paper presents a critical policy analysis of social housing in Türkiye (1923–2025), identifying a systemic misalignment: while early and mid-20th-century policies once allowed for various forms of self-help housing, contemporary frameworks have evolved into a turnkey mass housing paradigm. The issue of inequality is addressed by exploring the ability of alternative architectural design models to tackle it, by highlighting the participatory and incremental characteristics of self-help housing. The focus is on affordability, tenure security, spatial agency and the plurality of tenure types.

Ultimately, the paper calls for a feminist housing policy that prioritizes inhabitant-led agency and incremental growth over the rigidity of market-driven property deeds, which is essential for dismantling the gendered inequalities embedded in the 21st-century built environment.

Housing Otherwise. Queering the Home as a Critical Spatial Practice

Bernadette Krejs

TU Wien

Housing Otherwise raises the question: How can we move towards a more just future of living together? What can an architecture of empathy, solidarity, generosity, and circularity offer to housing? In times of multiple crises—from the climate catastrophe to growing social segregation – a queer feminist perspective can offer possibilities to imagine, plan and build housing otherwise. The city of Vienna has a long history of social housing, from the settler movement and the housing blocks of Red Vienna to pioneering projects such as the One-Kitchen House. But where do we stand today? How can a feminist approach to social housing be practiced, taught, and imagined?

This contribution offers historical, contemporary, and imagined housing experiments (in Vienna), seeking multi-perspective and previously underrepresented concepts of cohabitation to advance spatial justice in housing. The proposal investigates the home as a normative spatial construct and a site of socio-political negotiation. Far from being a neutral container, the home has historically functioned as a powerful architectural device through which ideas of gender, kinship, sexuality, productivity, and care are organized, stabilized, and standardized. The contemporary western home educated us about domesticity while simultaneously operating as the material condition of a spatial regime of control (Preciado, 2013). Halberstam describes architecture as an agent of normativity—one that not only shapes how we live, but also constructs normative bodies, sheltered through spaces. (Halberstam, 2018)

Drawing on queer-feminist theory and connected to critical spatial practices, the research approaches queering as a method rather than an identity category. (bell hooks, 1994). Queering design is centered on care, reflecting on a planet in crisis, the proposal explores alternative narratives of domesticity and offers approaches and possibilities for a better living for all.

Does Housing Change Housework? Gendered Domestic Labour in Housing Co-operatives

Eleanor Ferguson

University of Brighton

Gender inequalities in domestic labour remain a persistent feature of everyday life despite decades of feminist scholarship documenting the uneven distribution of unpaid

work within households. Yet most research centres on nuclear family households pays limited attention to how housing tenure structures may shape domestic labour. This raises an important question: does changing tenure change the gendered distribution of housework?

This paper examines whether housing co-operatives—often imagined as alternatives to the nuclear household—alter gendered divisions of domestic labour. Drawing on feminist social reproduction theory, the paper conceptualizes tenure as a relational formation constituted through three interacting dimensions: housing ideology, land relations, and co-resident social relations. These dynamics operate within broader social and economic conditions under which housing increasingly functions as a financialized commodity.

The paper draws on qualitative research with women living in housing co-operatives in the UK. Based on long-form interviews with residents, the study examines how domestic labour is experienced and organized within collectively governed housing environments. The findings suggest that while co-operative housing reconfigures certain economic and social relations within the home, it does not necessarily transform gendered divisions of domestic labour. Rather, gendered labour patterns persist across both physical domestic tasks and the governance, democratic, and emotional labour required to sustain communal living arrangements.

The paper argues that understanding gendered domestic labour requires analysing the interaction between housing tenure, domestic arrangements, and the wider housing system.

Spatial uncoupling: Liminal practices of parental separation and childcare

Carina Sacher

ETH Zurich, ETH CASE

Parental separation is a prevalent social phenomenon which is inevitably linked to the reorganisation of reproductive practices such as childcare and its spaces, particularly the shared domestic household. Transitioning between a shared household and separated living arrangements is a phase that is highly related to questions of gender and class as well as to housing. In the context of financialised housing markets, the critical phase of family household dissolution may result in longer periods of cohabitation despite separation (living together apart) or temporary overnight stays with relatives and friends or in hotels and accommodations. While studies have extensively documented post-separation housing situations, little attention has been devoted to the

process of parental separation, and in particular spatial uncoupling—its inseparable spatial dimension.

My dissertation investigates on these liminal spatial practices to illuminate how unequal access to housing, gendered care responsibilities, and normative expectations of family and home intersect. First findings suggest that there is a necessary simultaneity of relational and spatial uncoupling in which the domestic sphere becomes a contested site of emotional, spatial, material, and legal negotiation processes between the parties. The former couple's routines are interrupted and carried out asynchronously, while family and childcare activities might be maintained. Conflicts and outbreaks of domestic violence can intensify or occur for the first time.

The conference contribution is based on qualitative data which was collected in the context of the interdisciplinary research FamyCH conducted in Switzerland. By applying a praxeological, feminist, and critical housing studies perspective, it sheds light on what these individual practices can reveal about the hegemonic housing and gender regimes that structure parental separation and reproduce inequalities in housing.

Everyday practices towards home: the case of older unhoused women in the Czech Republic

Petra Tamasova
Masaryk University

Older women experience houselessness as an intersection of gender, age, worsening physical health, and precarious housing condition. They age in unsuitable/insecure flats, dormitories or shelters, which are often not prepared to meet their needs. Research has shown the positive effects of aging in familiar surroundings—in one's own home, in a long-standing neighbourhood and in a physically familiar environment. However, unhoused or displaced people often lack the means to achieve this state.

In this study, I will discuss what home means for older women in unstable housing situations. With help of critical gerontological theories, diverse understandings of what home means and the existence of the political "selves" (de Certeau 1984) of older women in inadequate housing, I seek to look critically at the social construction of marginalized people as passive and older people as weak, dependent, or pitiful, without denying the structural factors defining their living conditions. The research partners in this study are women over 50 years old from two Czech cities – Brno and Prague. I conducted ethnographic observations over a period of 7 months and made qualitative semi-structured interviews with 13 women. I applied Reflexive and Codebook Thematic Analysis to my data.

The results show that for unhoused women, home manifests itself as home-making in different places and resistance to home-making in others. Home is created and sustained with and through other people, or despite other people and by self-care and hope. They develop various everyday strategies to overcome unstable periods. They wait, they maintain the idea of home, and they secure a realistic possibility of having a home in the future, with third places being important aspects without having the first one. Finally, they resist death, even if this is what one would expect amidst lack of public and state attention on their condition.

Diffuse urbanisation and the gendered city: Urban form, housing systems and the long-term costs of sprawl for women

Ivana Katuric

Urbanex

Cécile Houpert

European affairs policy officer and urbanist

Lucijan Cernelic

Urbanex

Diffuse urbanisation, persistent across European urban regions, has attracted criticism for its environmental, fiscal and social costs, yet its role as a structural driver of gender inequality remains underexamined. This paper argues that urban form is one of the key, though largely invisible, mechanism through which gendered inequalities are produced and reproduced over time.

Drawing on feminist geography the paper shows how low-density, mono-functional, car-dependent development institutionalises the male breadwinner/female caregiver model in space. A defining feature of diffuse urbanisation is the chronic inability of the public sector to sustain adequate densities of social infrastructure and reliable public transport across dispersed territories. Women, as primary bearers of care work, disproportionately absorb these deficits and bear a "commute penalty": accepting shorter, lower-paid or part-time employment, with cumulative effects on lifetime earnings and pensions.

The paper links this to comparative housing systems literature, arguing that diffuse urbanisation is necessarily embedded within welfare and housing systems that distribute responsibilities between state, market and family. Systems characterised by universalist provision and service-rich urban environments support women's economic

independence and cope better even with the diffuse urban form, while familialist regimes reinforce domestic roles. when faced with spatially inefficient territories bring even greater hidden costs largely borne by women. The particular focus is on the transformation in the territories of post-socialist countries and the predominant mode of urbanization.

The paper concludes by arguing for compact, mixed-use, care-sensitive urban forms as central instruments of gender equality policy, and that gender mainstreaming in planning must interrogate the implicit norms shaping built environments, the tools planners use, and the voices that are heard or ignored.

Who Cares? Gendered and Generational Dynamics in Brussels' Home Sharing

Chloé Salembier

UCLouvain

This paper explores the dynamics of home sharing (colocation) in Brussels, focusing on how gender and age shape social relationships within these living arrangements. Drawing on qualitative research, it examines the exchange of care—emotional, practical, and social—among co-tenants, questioning whether these configurations constitute "chosen families." By analyzing how care practices are negotiated, distributed, and valued, the study highlights the interplay between structural constraints (e.g. housing precarity) and individual and collective agency in redefining domestic solidarities.

The findings contribute to debates on alternative housing models and their potential to challenge or reproduce traditional gendered and generational hierarchies. Key words: home sharing, Brussels, gender, age, care, chosen family

Housing and labour precarity through the lens of social reproduction

Ifigeneia Dimitrakou

University of Zurich

Across Europe, post-COVID pandemic urban policy debates have only recently recognized the effects of the affordability crisis (Wetzstein, 2017) on urban workers essential to the functioning of cities (Farris & Bergfeld, 2022; Fernando & Hearne, 2017). Urban workers who sustain city life through activities, such as delivering goods across

neighbourhoods, cleaning workplaces, or caring for children and the elderly, are often exposed to both precarious labour and housing conditions. Yet, while housing precarity has become a central concern in housing research, labour conditions are frequently reduced to formal employment (Arundel & Lennartz, 2020; Desmond & Gershenson, 2016) or treated as a secondary dimension of housing precarity.

Drawing on feminist geography, this paper develops a perspective that brings housing research into dialogue with broader debates on labour and social reproduction. To do so, it adopts an expanded understanding of labour beyond wage employment to include unpaid, affective, and care-based work that sustains everyday life. From this perspective, housing emerges as a key infrastructure of social reproduction (Madden, 2025), through which people recover from wage labour and a site where labour itself takes place, including the organization of care and the everyday work of sustaining households and social life (Power & Mee, 2020).

By bringing these strands of scholarship together, the paper outlines an analytical approach for examining housing precarity through the everyday practices of social reproduction, highlighting how labour, housing systems, and social reproduction intersect in shaping precarious urban lives.

Governing Metropolis – Land and Housing WG

Densification and increased complexity in the cities' interplay of social dynamics and spatial environments

Knut Boge

Norwegian University of Life Science

Yoel Siegel

Bezalel Academy of Arts and Design Jerusalem (and InterLoc Development)

In several European cities, decades of sub-urbanization led to reduced density. However, since the 1990s many European countries have established policies for limiting land use and increasing urbanization and densification. But these policies might have side effects. Policies for limiting and reducing urban sprawl have effectively reduced the supply of land. On the other hand, increased internal migration, substantial immigration and increased urbanization have led to increased demand for land uses. The net result is increased densification in the cities and a substantially more complex

interplay of social dynamics and spatial environments. Densification means more concentrated and diverse uses of the same parcel of land at one time and over time. This is not just an increase in the number of people in the same space. It also represents a geometric growth in the intensity and complexity of interactions that involves a rapid pace of adaptation required by people, institutions, uses of resources and of urban form.

To understand the complex dynamics entailing increased densification requires a multi-dimensional approach, such as studies of social goals, physical constraints, and economic feasibility translated into land-use functions. These dimensions and the ongoing process of structuring interactions create the context for human interactions. In complex systems, the whole is greater than and different from the sum of each individual part, and the interaction of its constituent parts create a dynamic whole.

This paper's contribution is applying the concepts of complex systems in studies of urban development to better understand how urban densification increases the multiple types and scopes of interactions.

Integrated Investment Plans and Lex Developer in Polish Regional Capital Cities

Magdalena Zaleczna
University of Lodz

Agata Antczak-Stepniak
University of Lodz

Integrated Investment Plans were introduced in Poland as part of the 2023 spatial planning reform, representing a further step in fostering cooperation between investors and local authorities in spatial development. The Lex Developer (special privileges for developers) is seen as the first step. Under the new mechanism, investors may independently prepare land development projects at their own expense and submit them for approval to municipal authorities.

In this article, the authors analyse how new instruments have been used in provincial cities, comparing the application with that of the previously implemented Lex Developer solution. The authors examined whether cities that had previously utilized the Lex Developer tool also attracted investor interest in Integrated Investment Plans. They assessed the level of investor engagement with the new solution in Polish provincial capitals, comparing both the number and scale of projects completed under Lex

Developer and Integrated Investment Plans. The findings indicate that there is no clear evidence to suggest that investors who used Lex Developer continued their activities under Integrated Investment Plans.

Housing Need, Housing Demand and National Planning for Housing Provision in the Netherlands: Towards a Third Period of National Spatial Planning for Housing Production

Willem Korthals Altes

TU Delft

The Netherlands is going through a housing affordability crisis. National planning authorities are preparing a response to tackle this crisis. This response would be the third time National spatial planning would launch a mass housing programme, after the growth center (new-town) policies in the 1970s and the VINEX (large-scale housing extensions of big cities) policies in the 1990s and 2000s.

The current paper analysis these three periods on the following dimensions, firstly, the relationship between national and local authorities and the role of strategic spatial planning, secondly, the relationship between state and market actors and the role of land policies to connect these and, thirdly, the spatial vision behind the spatial planning for housing production. Based on these analyses the role of spatial planning in tackling the current housing crisis is discussed.

Metropolitan Degrowth? Governing Land and Housing Beyond the Growth Paradigm in Central European Metropolitan Areas

Ivan Tosics

Metropolitan Research Institute, Budapest

Adrienne Csizmady

Loránd Eötvös University, Centre for Social Research

Andrea Tönkö

Metropolitan Research Institute, Budapest

Metropolitan governance in Europe has traditionally followed a growth-oriented paradigm, prioritizing competitiveness and infrastructure expansion. However, climate

change, socio-spatial inequalities, and demographic shifts—particularly in Central and Eastern Europe—challenge the feasibility of continuous growth.

This paper introduces the concept of metropolitan degrowth as a strategic reorientation of land and housing governance. The central research question asks: How can metropolitan governance move beyond growth-led logics to incorporate principles of sufficiency, equity, and ecological limits? Using comparative strategic analyses from the Interreg project MECOG-CE, the paper examines Berlin, Brno, and Budapest, operating largely through EU cohesion policy tools, such as Integrated Territorial Investments (ITI), and voluntary cooperation.

The analysis identifies three core tensions in current strategies: 1. Land take vs. planetary boundaries: Continued land consumption despite demographic stagnation. 2. Densification vs. social justice: Displacement and polarization resulting from "hard" redevelopment. 3. Climate targets vs. expansion: Conflicts between strategic infrastructure (e.g., highways) and decarbonization goals.

The paper defines metropolitan degrowth governance not as economic shrinkage, but as a shift from quantitative expansion to qualitative improvement. This involves prioritizing brownfield regeneration over greenfield expansion, embedding affordability and anti-displacement criteria into projects, and linking land-use to carbon budgeting. Empirically, the research demonstrates that even in weakly institutionalized settings, degrowth principles can be introduced via integration matrices and social inclusion benchmarks.

The paper concludes that metropolitan areas, as flexible action spaces, offer a critical scale for operationalizing de-growth transitions, reframing policy as an arena for negotiating ecological limits and social justice.

An examination of how land policies support affordable housing and address inequality

Julie Lawson

RMIT University

Alice Earl

RMIT University

Philip O'Brien

RMIT University

Oleksandr Anisimov

RMIT University

This paper presents findings from the Equal House project (WP5.3), which evaluates how land and planning instruments shape affordable housing provision and distributional outcomes across five European cities: Vienna, Helsinki, Brussels, Paris/Île-de-France, and Valencia.

Using a critical realist framework, the study examines how “open housing systems” are structured by land institutions and how these in turn influence affordability, access, and equity. Evidence is drawn from documentary analysis, semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders, and site-based observation, producing a harmonised cross-case matrix of policy rules, financial logics, and realised outcomes.

The comparative fieldwork reveals that diverse institutional arrangements—Vienna’s land banking and four-pillar competitions, Helsinki’s long-leasehold stewardship, Brussels’ community land trust model, Paris’ combination of SRU quotas and ZAC development zones, and Valencia’s reparcelación process—share a common capacity to embed affordability within land governance. Yet their effectiveness is contingent on path-dependent factors including fiscal architecture, legal competences, and the maturity of non-profit providers.

Across cases, public landholding, cost-rent regulation, and participatory governance emerge as robust mechanisms for securing durable affordability and resisting speculative pressures. At the same time, risks of exclusion, residualisation, and governance overload underscore the limits of institutional design when confronted with financialisation, uneven capacities, and persistent inequality.

Applying an open housing systems lens highlights how these land policies operate not in isolation but within wider circuits of investment, regulation, and social support. The

study argues that effective land policy must both constrain speculative value extraction and enable cooperative, mission-driven provision, while being adaptable to shifting socio-economic conditions.

Land Assembly and Housing Development: The Taiwan Experience

Tzu-Chin Lin

National Chengchi University

Jia-Huey Yeh

Chinese Cultural University, Taiwan

Taiwan's urban areas are densely populated and dominated by small individual land parcels, posing severe challenges for land assembly prior to residential development. Over the years, local governments have frequently employed land readjustment not only to provide essential public facilities but also to reshape land configurations and boundaries so as to create suitable sites for future development. However, numerous studies indicate that respect for private property rights has hindered land readjustment's capacity to reconfigure parcels effectively.

This study examines data from a typical large-scale land readjustment project in Kaohsiung City over the 30 years following its completion to assess the long-term effectiveness and limitations of land readjustment for housing construction. Drawing on detailed land transfer records, we find: (1) Over the 30-year period, the area of developed sites far exceeded that of undeveloped vacant sites by a factor of three. (2) A high proportion of developed sites underwent land assembly with an average duration of 10 years. (3) Compared to sites without involvement of assembly, those that experienced it were one to two times more likely to be developed subsequently. (4) Although land assembly is necessary for residential development, an optimal scale of assembly seems to exist; this likely stems from diminishing returns or escalating costs as assembled sites enlarge.

Statistical evidence confirms that protracted land assembly remains unavoidable, even in government-initiated projects. While land readjustment aims to guide population movement and facilitate urban growth by providing public facilities and ready-to-develop sites, a substantial number of undeveloped sites continue to waste public investment and delay planned development. Accelerating land assembly in large-scale projects remains a daunting challenge for Taiwan. This study also underscores the intricate interplay between housing and land markets.

The Role of Land Readjustment in Supplying Land for Social Housing in Taiwan

Hsiu-yin Ding

National Chengchi University

Taiwan faces a paradoxical housing situation characterized by high housing prices, high vacancy rates, high homeownership rates, and a shortage of social housing. In response, social housing has become a central component of government housing policy. As of 2023, approximately 97% of social housing units had been directly constructed by the government. By the end of May 2024, 219 potential sites had been identified across Taiwan with a total capacity of 71,234 units.

Despite this progress, a substantial gap remains relative to the government's target of constructing 200,000 social housing units between 2017 and 2024. One of the key constraints is land acquisition: most projects rely on state-owned land, but the limited availability of such land constrains further development. Land readjustment has long served as an important institutional mechanism for supplying urban residential land in Taiwan and providing land for public facilities to local governments free of charge. Under this arrangement, landowners contribute a portion of their land—referred to as cost-equivalent land—which is auctioned to finance project costs and may generate financial surpluses. In response to the growing shortage of land for social housing, the government has proposed requiring new land readjustment projects to allocate an additional share of land free of charge for social housing development.

This study examines the institutional framework of land readjustment and the market dynamics of land supply to evaluate whether requiring land allocations for social housing is consistent with the mechanism's foundational principle of providing public facilities. Specifically, it explores whether residential land produced through land readjustment can help alleviate land shortages for social housing and analyses the potential role and effectiveness of land readjustment in supporting social housing provision.

Instrumentalisation of Spatial Planning and the Housing Paradox: An Institutional Analysis of Istanbul

Cansu Çiçek Aydın

Elif Alkay
Istanbul Technical University

This research conceptualizes contemporary housing policies as the instrumentalization of spatial planning to facilitate construction-led growth. In the Turkish context, this shift has repositioned planning from a regulatory framework into a strategic tool for real estate expansion, primarily aimed at increasing housing supply. Istanbul represents a critical case for examining how centralized policy interventions and pro-growth institutional settings are reshaping the relationship between planning institutions, housing markets, and urban space. Urban regeneration has emerged as a primary arena for these institutional transformations.

In practice, Turkish urban regeneration operates through two main pathways: planning-led redevelopment and the designation of 'reserve areas' under Law No. 6306. These mechanisms reveal how formal and informal rules prioritize construction output while neglecting the socio-spatial dynamics of the city. Although regeneration policies are often justified as mechanisms to improve urban resilience and housing supply, housing prices continue to rise while the socio-economic composition of the city transforms and central districts experience population decline. From an institutional economics perspective, this paradox stems from cumulative, self-reinforcing cycles within housing supply regimes.

This ongoing PhD research aims to analyze the housing supply regimes in Istanbul by developing a framework to examine how these institutional settings restructure urban space. By exploring the trajectories of residents and displaced communities, the study seeks to uncover the broader social implications of planning instrumentalization in Istanbul.

The cost of urbanisation: How variation in land policy shapes housing affordability and urban development sustainability across Europe

Ivana Katuric

Lucijan Cernelic

Urbanex

Land use planning reforms aimed at increasing housing supply are increasingly promoted at the EU level as a tool to address the housing affordability crisis. However, as European states, regions and cities differ in the ways in which the costs and gains of urban development are distributed between the public and private sectors, the impacts of spatial planning reform on the cost and sustainability of urbanization and the resulting housing prices remain insufficiently understood.

The paper discusses this relationship and illustrates it by comparing cases of how the costs of urbanization and the financial gains accruing to landowners and developers through public interventions are structured in two European countries and analyses their impacts on the mode of urbanization (compact, polycentric or diffuse) and housing affordability.

The analyzed cases in the Netherlands, Germany and Croatia differ in spatial planning systems and the sets of policy tools and practices at the disposal of local governments to capture land values. Public land banking, developer charges, urban development agreements are used with differing levels of institutionalization and effectiveness, and in differing levels of coordination with land use planning mechanisms.

The paper analyses the impact of these land policy arrangements on short-term and long-term fiscal impacts, the distribution of developer's gain and housing affordability. It also seeks to uncover the mechanisms through which the land policy arrangements shape the predominant modes of urbanization – compact, polycentric or diffuse - and evaluate the outcome of land policy on the sustainability of urbanization.

We argue that these institutional differences in divergent land policy systems underscore the significance of considering land value capture and planning gain regulation, and highlight their importance in informing current debates on the design of planning and housing policies across Europe.

“The Path Not Chosen”: Etrimo, Amelinckx and the Reconfiguration of Collective Housing Provision in twentieth-century Belgium

Laurence Heindryckx

Université libre de Bruxelles

Private housing developers played a major role in shaping post-war living environments in Western Europe, yet their contributions have been largely neglected in architectural, urban and housing historiography and often dismissed as solely profit-driven, detached from societal needs.

This paper argues that developers were key agents within welfare state housing systems, influencing both institutional configurations and the material production of housing. Focusing on Belgium, a country with comparatively limited state-built housing, it compares the trajectories of its two largest twentieth-century developers, Etrimo and Amelinckx. Through a relational production perspective it analyses their roles within professional and political coalitions, the financial and technical expertise they mobilised, and the spatial outcomes of their development strategies.

The analysis shows that, under unambitious planning policies and risk-averse governance, collective housing was steered towards conservative models closely aligned with the existing city. A decisive turning point came in 1970, when the Belgian government refused to collateralise Etrimo’s land reserves while financially supporting Amelinckx and enacting legislation suited to its model. Etrimo combined housing provision with investment in infrastructure, collective amenities, and high-rise urbanity; its demise signalled political distrust toward urban collective living and the co-production of urban surplus value.

By contrast, support for Amelinckx reinforced a conservative and specialised model prioritising cost-efficiency and controllability, contributing to a sector increasingly focused on predictable housing output rather than complex urban projects. Reconstructing this “path not chosen,” the paper positions developers as co-producers, rather than external antagonists, of Belgian welfare housing systems, illuminating the historically constrained role attributed to private actors in co-producing the city.

Housing and Living Conditions of Ageing Populations WG

Japanese Social Housing 'DANCHI' and ten years changes of the residents and the surroundings after 2015

Yoko Matsuoka

Tokyo Kasei University

Shizuko Yanagisawa

Tokyo Kasei University

Japanese social housing complex 'DANCHI' is in the spotlight of the issue of super aged society. We conducted a quantitative survey at a 'DANCHI' in Tokyo metropolitan area in 2015. The purpose of this study of 2025 is to clarify the residents' changes of ten years after 2015 by qualitative survey.

One-to-one semi-structured interviews were conducted with nineteen residents and health professionals including community-based facility staffs for older persons. After analysing of 'Qualitative data analysis' method, we got twenty meaningful codes and eight categories were abstracted such as; 'promotion of ageing and difficulty of life', 'a rise in frailty after COVID-19', 'more weakened connectedness', 'foreign residents', 'No shop and many vacant flats', 'hidden reserves of residents' strength' 'many historical community-based association'. While super aged society have been promoting, many social problems occur, such as single family of older persons, isolation, collapse of resident's association, threat by swindlers. On the other hand, the strength of the residents was brought to light. This Japanese social housing is one model of super aged society. At the conference many findings will be proposed, and the implications will be useful not only for Japan but also all other countries.

Age-Friendly Housing in Spain: Opportunities and Experiences

Judith Gifreu-Font

Universidad Aut3noma de Barcelona

The age of the Spanish housing stock, coupled with the progressive ageing of the population, makes it imperative for the public authorities to establish mechanisms to increase actions aimed at housing rehabilitation. Despite the regulatory impetus provided by Law 8/2013, the effects of the 2008 real estate crisis and Covid, together

with the high economic cost of intervening in the consolidated city, have slowed down the implementation of this objective in practice. However, the ERESEE strategy (2020), together with the PNIEC 2021-2023, the Spanish Urban Agenda and the Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan, all within the framework of the Next Generation EU, have brought about a paradigm shift that will make it possible to address not only issues linked to energy rehabilitation (the EU's main objective), but also the demands of what have come to be called "ageing cities", with measures aimed at the elderly (a group that has not been given special attention until now, being included in the generic category of disabled people, a concept that in recent years has been replaced by that of "functional diversity"), in order to reduce architectural barriers and improve accessibility within the framework of housing functionality.

The progressive loss of physical and mental faculties that are inherent to the ageing process and the use that older people make of urban space and their homes makes it necessary to programme public policies that promote active ageing to optimize opportunities and improve quality of life, such as the pioneering Age-Friendly Cities Programme (WHO). The design of housing for this group should be based on a comprehensive approach, combining physical aspects with others linked to interaction and ageing in place. For this reason, new typologies such as senior cohousing are making headway in our country as an alternative to traditional residences for the elderly.

“In Due Time”: Senior-Led Cooperative Housing Projects through the Lens of Ageing

Fanny Gerbeaud

Laboratoire PAVE – ENSAP Bordeaux

In France, seniors account for a large share of cooperative housing initiatives. Historically associated to a socially oriented model, this politically grounded form of collaborative housing has regained momentum since the 2014 ALUR law, supported by committed organizations and networks promoting its development, while housing cooperatives have long been established in Europe and North America. Bringing a cooperative housing project to completion generally remains a long and challenging process, and this complexity appears heightened when the initiative is led by seniors.

This paper draws on qualitative research based on numerous interviews with stakeholders involved in the Boboyaka senior cooperative housing project. Labelled by the French Ministry of Culture, the project comprises senior flats, shared spaces, a kindergarten and student housing located in Bordeaux. Within this initiative, temporality and transmission are particularly salient. While retirement might rime with seizing the

day thanks to consolidated assets, this project represents a significant economic and existential risk, described by its members as a “last adventure”. Later life may nonetheless constitute a favourable moment to embark on such an undertaking: although vulnerabilities arise, the desire to plan ahead persists. Financial, intellectual and social resources accumulated over time, when pooled together, enable the creation of distinctive and culturally vibrant living environments embedded in their neighbourhood. However, the collective’s decision to limit the entry share, combined with geographical, programmatic and socio-economic complexities, considerably slowed the project.

This paper examines the conditions under which senior-led cooperatives are realized and analyses their model through the lens of ageing, highlighting tensions between aspirations to engaged and intangible forms of transmission, forms of institutional ageism, and the pragmatism required to cope with uncertainty.

Neighborhoods as socio-spatial infrastructures for ageing in place: a comparative study of two contrasting areas in Gothenburg, Sweden

Gwendoline Schaff

Lund University

Pimkamol Mattsson

Lund University

In a context of housing affordability crises and increasing wealth disparities, housing and the surrounding environments can reinforce inequalities and segregation, shaping the conditions in which older adults age in place. However, age-friendly and 15-minute city principles are often seen as one-size-fits-all. We know less about how they operate in areas with different socio-economic conditions and migration trajectories, and how neighbourhood settings shape older adults’ social and spatial experiences across different contexts.

This paper examines the role of neighbourhood environments as socio-spatial infrastructures supporting or constraining everyday mobility and social connection among older adults. The study took place in Högsbo and Angered, two economically and socially diverse areas in Gothenburg, which is part of the WHO Global Network for Age-friendly Cities and Communities. Twelve walking interviews were conducted with older people (mostly 75+) and 72 short neighbourhood observations were carried out across nine locations at different times of day and week. The walking interviews captured

participants' perceptions and experiences, while the neighbourhood observations documented age-friendly spatial features and temporal patterns of presence and use.

Data will be analysed using thematic analysis of the walking interviews transcripts and observation notes, followed by comparative analysis between the two areas. Preliminary findings indicate that both neighbourhoods foster ageing in place through accessible transport, walkable public spaces, and opportunities for social possibilities.

However, differences in social diversity, active involvement in meeting places, individual characteristics, and perceived safety, for example, influence how older adults engage with their local environment and other people. The study informs more inclusive and context-sensitive approaches to age-friendly neighbourhood planning.

Housing an ageing population in the Swedish countryside

Marianne Abramsson

Dept of Human Geography, Stockholm University

This chapter deals with the housing situation of older adults in the Swedish countryside and municipal strategies to combat these. The population in many rural areas has declined over time, resulting in demographic changes as the young population has moved.

The population in rural areas is older than in more densely populated areas, and a larger proportion of the rural population lives in detached houses and is to a large extent dependent on driving. The dominant housing policy is ageing in place, i.e., that older adults should remain in a home on the ordinary housing market for as long as possible, when the need arises, with the support of home care and home medical care.

The challenge for the municipalities is therefore to meet the housing needs of an increasing number of older adults that are expected to reach a high age, but also to cater for their need for care and support, and to maintain an adequate level of service, such as public transport and other basic public and commercial services.

The chapter is based on the discussion on how to handle the consequences of the demographic change, on government reports, planning documents, and experiences of rural municipalities.

Home ownership among the baby boomer cohort

Andreas Hartung

RPTU University Kaiserslautern-Landau

Annette Spellerberg

RPTU University Kaiserslautern- Landau

Home ownership is a key factor in wealth accumulation, and its unequal distribution is an important aspect of social inequality. Although home ownership plays a minor role among the wealthiest individuals, it is crucial for retirement planning and wealth accumulation among the middle classes. Germany is a so-called “tenant country,” with only 44% of households living in owner-occupied housing (2022 census), with the regionally varying proportions. The east-west divide is particularly noteworthy due to the former housing politics in the socialist GDR.

This study analyses inequalities in access to home ownership among the baby boomer cohort (born between 1955 and 1969). This group were young adults at the time of German reunification and had the opportunity to become homeowners during their lifetime.

Next, we analyse the importance of home ownership in building wealth. The retirement of the large baby boomer cohort, which accounts for around one-fifth of the population, will significantly impact a large proportion of society. Home ownership is associated with reduced financial burdens in older age but can contribute to social inequality.

Our study aims to highlight the development of a cohort-specific 'structural property gap' in recent decades. We will examine the according role of socio-structural factors and inheritance. We use data from the German Socio-Economic Panel. In addition, we use a survey from 2022 of approximately 3,100 baby boomers from three German federal states (Baden-Württemberg, Rhineland-Palatinate, and Thuringia).

Preliminary results show that the eastern cohort was able to significantly close the gap. Settlement structures also play a role, as eastern Germany is much more rural than western Germany.

Learning from Daily Life – Engaging Students in Housing Innovations for Older Adults

Birgit Jürgehake

Tu Delft

This article explores an anthropologically inspired approach to investigating how housing and innovation can respond to the changing needs and preferences of older residents. Students engage directly with older adults in their home environments, spending one week on site to gain insight into everyday residential practices, as well as residents' needs and aspirations.

The study also provides deeper insight into the human-centred methodology introduced in master's-level courses. Population ageing, increased life expectancy, and limited care resources generate a growing demand for living environments that enable older adults to maintain independence for as long as possible. Concepts such as multi-generational housing, collective living, and new senior almshouses promise mutual support; however, it remains unclear whether they adequately reflect the diversity of lifestyles and preferences among older adults. During their stay, students observe daily routines, spatial use, and social interactions, and conduct conversations with residents about their experiences and aspirations. This anthropologically inspired fieldwork identifies recurring core aspects of older adults' everyday lives. Based on these insights, students develop design approaches and spatial strategies that move beyond conventional assumptions and standard typologies.

The article presents both the methodology and key findings. It demonstrates how direct engagement with users—here, between younger and older adults—fosters mutual interest and can lead to more appropriate housing innovations, contributing to the development of responsive living environments for an ageing society.

The Era of Ever-Larger Dwellings in Germany Is Coming to an End

Konstantin Kholodilin

DIW Berlin

Sebastian Kohl

DIW Berlin

Since at least the 1940s, there has been a significant increase in both home size and housing availability. Improved welfare enabled the construction of larger homes, both in

terms of square footage and number of rooms. This trend was likely fuelled in part by the baby boom. Larger homes meant improved housing conditions, but also higher energy and building material expenses. However, a pivotal turning point emerged in the early 2000s, leading to a reversal of this trend. In many countries, including Germany, the floor area of newly built dwellings, particularly multi-family buildings, began to shrink. Here, we explore the evidence of this shift.

We find that three main factors have contributed to the shrinking size of newly built housing. First, smaller households make large dwellings less in demand, forcing builders to focus on smaller dwellings instead. Second, rising housing prices led investors to construct taller buildings with smaller dwellings. Third, some regions have issued new land-use regulations that restrict the construction of single-family homes due to their higher energy consumption. According to our projections, within a few years, this will lead to a decline in the average size of existing dwellings. However, this process will likely be very slow due to low construction rates compared to the already substantial and aging housing stock.

Testing Decision Making Instruments for Collective Housing in The Netherlands

Dort Spierings

HAN Civil Society Lab

P. Huijbregts Bouwstroom

HAN University of Applied Sciences

Nuenen N Bolster

HAN University of Applied Sciences

B. Evers

HAN University of Applied Sciences

S. Weijers

HAN University of Applied Sciences

This research was commissioned by the De Derde Bouwstroom foundation as part of the Co-Create Urban Transition minor at HAN University of Applied Sciences. The study was prompted by the continuing growth of interest in cohousing and the observation that new collective groups often encounter obstacles during the initial phase. The research

focuses on developing a tool to help these groups visualize and structure their housing needs, enabling them to better arrive at feasible design choices together.

The housing market in the Netherlands is under pressure, and there is a significant need for affordable, social, and sustainable housing. Collective living can contribute to this and to more cohesion and informal care, but the complexity of the initial phase often poses a barrier. The lack of structure, overview, and concrete tools leads to a significant loss of time, energy, and motivation.

This research is relevant because the tool addresses the aforementioned bottlenecks and contributes to making collective living more accessible. The central question of the research is: "What tool can be developed to help emerging collective housing groups visualize how they want to live?"

The narrative research, stakeholder analysis, literature studies, and various test rounds show that housing groups primarily need a clear and user-friendly tool. A tool that provides insight into the various housing typologies, concepts, and choices. Both literature and practical research show that social dynamics and joint decision-making play a significant role, as does the balance between private and collective life. It can be concluded that a tool that provides structure offers significant added value for emerging collective housing groups. It can contribute to improved collaboration, a greater likelihood of a feasible housing initiative, and a structured process. The research thus confirms the problem definition and underscores the importance of an accessible and easily accessible tool.

Reframing Assisted Living for Ageing Populations: Design Research Strategies for Housing Adaptation and Urban Retention

António Carvalho

Politecnico di Milano

Population ageing is transforming housing demand and living conditions across Europe, particularly in Portugal, where demographic projections indicate a significant increase in the number of residents aged 65 and over. Responding to this shift, this paper reframes assisted living not as an institutional model of transference, but as a retention-based strategy embedded within existing urban housing. Grounded in design research, the study combines demographic analysis, a survey of assisted living facilities in Greater Lisbon, and a comparative review of 78 international case studies to identify the essential spatial and programmatic components of effective assisted housing.

These findings are applied to the modernist Av. do Brasil housing ensemble (1958) in Lisbon's Alvalade neighbourhood, exploring how conventional multifamily housing can

be incrementally adapted to support ageing in place. Through spatial analysis and minimal architectural interventions, the project proposes two adaptive scenarios—intergenerational cohousing and shared living arrangements—that enhance internal connectivity, improve universal accessibility, and introduce core shared amenities such as living, dining, and care spaces. Underused rooftop areas are transformed into collective environments for social interaction, physical activity, and mutual support. By prioritising housing adaptation over relocation, the research demonstrates how modest spatial modifications and strategically integrated communal facilities can prolong autonomy, reinforce intergenerational exchange, and revitalise neighbourhood life.

The paper positions architectural design as both an investigative method and a practical tool in advancing inclusive housing solutions for ageing populations within consolidated urban contexts.

When the burden of ageing and loneliness turn into wellbeing gold

Nicoline Foulon Nørgaard

OsloMet – Oslo Metropolitan University

John Östh

OsloMet – Oslo Metropolitan University

The burden of an ageing society is a challenge addressed in many parts of the world. It is feared that the elderly will strain public budgets with less hands and taxes to cover necessary health care. This paper investigates how an older generation can remain in better health, experience safety and contribute to solve urban student housing shortages. The three modes of unhealth: disease, illness and sickness, is analysed in terms of ageing. In addition, the concept of generational living is discussed in a historical perspective, supported by a rapid scoping review of student living in nursing homes.

Findings indicate that loneliness and multimorbidity can be reduced, and the view that ageing only has negative consequences is challenged when the normative perspective is applied. The paper concludes that although ageing can be seen as a disease, there are reduced loneliness and housing benefits when students find gold living with grandparents.

Housing for active ageing: Architectural solutions

Eli Støa

NTNU

Randi Narvestad

NTNU

As a response to the challenges connected to an increasingly aging society, the Norwegian government in 2023 imposed the 'Safe at home' (Bo trygt hjemme) reform (2024-2028). The reform has four focus areas: Vibrant local communities, Housing adaptation and planning, Competent and empowered employees and Safety for users and support for family members. Along with the reform, the Norwegian Directorate of Health engaged OsloMet/NIBR to carry out an evaluation of the work (2025-2029). As a part of this evaluation, researchers at the Faculty of Architecture and design at NTNU, have carried out casestudies of two housing projects.

The casestudies are the first step within the workpackage dealing with the second focus area: Housing adaptation and planning. Two housing projects, one in a suburban part of a large city and the other in the center of a small rural community, were selected. In both cases, it was an ambition to create age-friendly housing that would support a social community among neighbours. Although the projects had similar overall ambitions, they are also quite different when it comes to housing typology, shared social spaces and access to public spaces in the close vicinity. The differences are much due to the suburban/rural contexts and to the size of the projects. The study explored how the physical design of the housing projects, both indoors and outdoors, was perceived by residents.

The paper presents findings of this study with emphasis on how architecture may support active aging. The following questions are discussed: How do the various design solutions work for senior residents, practically and socially? What are the main reasons for this residential group choosing to move to the area, and are there any aspects of the projects that create uncertainty? The discussion is based on qualitative interviews with senior residents, architects, developers and representatives from the two municipalities.

How near-home open spaces can operate as everyday infrastructure for ageing in place in old residential areas: the case of Quartiere Feltre, Milan

Tianqin Chen

Politecnico di Milano

Antonio Carvalho

Politecnico di Milano

Our ageing society has made ageing in place a core issue in urban renewal and housing research. In past design practices, open and green spaces have often been seen as elements to enhance the aesthetic value of buildings. On the contrary, this study argues that in residential environments inhabited by many older people, the role of open spaces should be re-examined: Their value lies not only in the visual openness or green landscape, but also in the actual use of spaces by residents, to linger in and benefit from. It should be considered as an everyday infrastructure, supporting older people's daily life, providing spaces for low-intensity movement, short stays, triggering social interaction and leisure activities.

This paper takes Quartiere Feltre in Milan as a case study. Built between 1951-1961, this area is an important part of the post-war Italian INA-Casa public housing project. As a neighbourhood with clear modern residential types and dynamic community support facilities, it has a large amount of middle-aged and older residents, providing an ideal case for studying how older residents use different types of near-home open spaces.

This study adopts a design-driven research framework, comparing three typical open spaces within the residential area: open spaces around the residential entrance, shared spaces in the community center, and pathways connecting to nearby facilities. Each space was evaluated across five dimensions: proximity, accessibility, threshold conditions, stayability, and social visibility.

The study found that the most suitable spaces for ageing in place are not necessarily those largest or greenest, but rather spaces that offer shading, high legibility, strong social permeability and good connectivity. Based on the above findings, this paper proposes an analytical framework and design principles for the renovation of older residential areas.

Ageing in Place or Institutional Care? Housing for Older People in Japan

Kentaro Yamaguchi

Kindai University

Since 2000, Japan has introduced many care and housing policies to respond to the rapid growth of its ageing population. This study aims to describe the structure of housing for older people in Japan since 2000 using statistical data and previous studies.

Two main housing models are often discussed: the ageing-in-place model and the relocation model. In the ageing-in-place model, older people stay in the same home while receiving care as their needs change. In the relocation model, residents move to different facilities according to their care needs. Nordic countries are often seen as examples of the ageing-in-place model, where fewer institutions exist and strong home-care services support older people living in the community.

Before the Long-Term Care Insurance system was introduced in 2000, Japan's elderly care system was mainly based on the relocation model. Facilities were organized by care level and income group. After 2000, policies focused on improving living conditions in nursing homes and creating new housing types.

In 2003, a "private room plus small group unit" model was introduced in nursing homes for residents with severe care needs, creating more home-like environments. However, many older facilities with multi-bed hospital-style rooms still remain. In 2011, Service Housing for the Elderly was also introduced and has expanded through private development to more than 290,000 units. Many units, however, are close to the minimum size of about 18 m² and house residents with higher care needs.

As a result, housing for older people in Japan is becoming polarized between living at home and entering facilities for those with severe care needs. While market-based policies increased the supply of housing, they have not greatly improved housing quality or diversity. This study examines this structure and discusses its policy implications for ageing societies.

Cocreating with residents for intergenerational renewal : the case of a large public housing development in the Parisian suburbs.

Thomas Watkin

Unîmes

The social housing development known as Youri Gagarine, located in Romainville, was selected following a call for proposals launched by the CNSA as part of the 'Ageing in QPV' program. This program aims to improve the conditions for ageing in deprived social housing developments that benefit from a range of public policies (urban policies: QPV).

The case study presented in this paper aims to shed light on how Cohabilis, the national federation of associations specializing in intergenerational homesharing, responded to this call and embarked on an innovative co-creation process with residents affected by this major urban renewal project. The aim is to explain the origins of the renewed national urban renewal policy within the context of the Youri Gagarine project. I will then demonstrate how this policy develops a hybrid approach combining research and action, drawing on field research and engagement with residents and users to support the transformation of this neighbourhood.

Emptynester's housing mobility patterns in Danish single-family houses

Nino Javakhishvili-Larsen

BUILD-The department of the Built Environment, Aalborg University

Jesper Ole Jensen

BUILD-The department of the Built Environment, Aalborg University

It is a general experience that emptynesters in single-family houses prefer to stay in their home when their children have left the home, resulting in a high housing consumption per capita. This is increasingly seen as a problem as the housing crisis implies a pressure on the housing market with higher prices, while also representing a climate challenge due to high consumption per capita of energy for heating and electricity. Higher mobility pattern amongst empty nesters could reduce the need for new housing constructions, and perhaps also reduce demolitions rates leading to more affordable and sustainable housing provision. However, the knowledge about these mobility patterns and the specific motivations for housing choices are limited. This paper presents findings from a comprehensive study of the housing mobility of Danish empty

nesters in single-family houses, drawing on Danish micro register data (2014-2023), a survey, and qualitative interviews.

The study examines how demographic profiles and geographical location shape the mobility patterns of Danish empty nesters leaving single-family homes, and to what extent these moves contribute to downsizing of their housing consumption. More specifically, we investigate how ‘push’ and ‘pull’ factors influence housing mobility and what role the availability of local housing options plays in enabling empty nesters to downsize while maintaining established social networks.

Our preliminary findings reveal a consistent pattern of strong local attachment among empty nesters, with most relocations occurring within the same municipality. However, since 2021, this pattern has begun to shift, as fewer moves take place locally and relocations across municipal borders have become more common.

The analysis also shows that certain demographic groups are more likely to move: women, single individuals, and retirees display higher mobility than couples and those still employed. In terms of housing transitions, the study identifies housing mobility implies a clear trend toward downsizing in terms of space consumption. Empty nesters tend to relocate to newer and smaller dwellings, and many opt for housing types and tenures that reduce maintenance demands, including a significant movement toward apartments and rental housing.

Geographically, the mobility pattern reveals that major metropolitan areas and the smallest rural communities tend to lose empty nesters, whereas medium-sized regional centers gain them. These areas appear attractive because they combine more affordable housing with better local services and access to nature.

The findings also suggest that facilitating housing mobility requires providing suitable housing options close to existing social networks, particularly in these well-functioning regional hubs. The study has been carried out with support from the national campaign “Preserve More” (Bevar Mere).

Through its mixed-methods approach, the research contributes new insights into the mobility patterns, motivations, and behavioural traits of empty nesters - an issue of significant policy relevance for creating modern and sustainable housing systems.

Social Selectivity and Resident Benefits in Senior Cohousing

Gunvor Christensen

FOB – non-profit housing organisation, Slagelse, Denmark

Mette Lunde Christensen

The Danish Centre for Social Science Research (VIVE), Copenhagen, Denmark.

In Denmark, senior cohousing is a growing form of housing supported by politicians and stakeholders based on the presumption that it reduces loneliness and enhances quality of life for residents. However, causal studies identifying such benefits are limited; existing quantitative research primarily finds correlations between senior cohousing and increases in measures such as social engagement, sense of community and safety. Utilizing unique data on individual preferences combined with Danish administrative records, we investigate social selectivity in the choice of senior cohousing.

Our findings indicate that residents tend to have higher educational levels, incomes, and employment rates, suggesting social selectivity. Additionally, when comparing survey respondents preferring senior cohousing with those who do not, the former report better health, a more positive self-image, and greater social activity, further supporting the notion of social selectivity.

This paper demonstrates that while benefits may exist for specific senior cohousing residents, such benefits cannot be generalized to the elderly population more generally. Therefore, senior cohousing should not be promoted as a broad policy to combat loneliness or improve quality of life among the elderly in general, but rather as a housing option with potential benefits for a selected group.

Housing migration and family dynamics

Intergenerational Wealth Transfers and Housing Advantage Across Occupational Classes in Europe

Alejandro Fernandez Perez

Rowan Arundel

Ricardo Duque-Calvache

Universidad de Granada

Across Europe, housing markets have become increasingly decoupled from income, particularly in high-demand urban regions. As house prices outpace earnings, wealth transfers are becoming more central to housing outcomes. While prior research documents a strong association between inheritances and entry into homeownership, less is known about how wealth transfers influence the value of housing acquired, the financial structure of purchases, and whether these effects vary across occupational groups.

This paper examines the role of intergenerational wealth transfers across three dimensions of housing advantage: (1) access to homeownership, (2) housing value at purchase, and (3) loan-to-value (LTV) ratios. Using European microdata, we exploit the timing of transfers relative to housing acquisition and apply inverse probability weighting and matching to identify heterogeneous treatment effects across occupational groups.

We find that wealth transfers increase the probability of becoming a homeowner, raise purchase values, and reduce loan-to-value ratios. The effects follow a dose-response pattern across all occupational groups: larger transfers are linked to higher ownership rates, more expensive homes, and lower debt ratios. Differences across occupations are clearer for purchase values, where larger transfers lead to especially strong increases among manual and technical workers.

Overall, transfers increase housing advantage across all occupations but with particularly strong effects among low- and medium-skill groups, and less so in high skill ones, which may help explain lower-class resistance to transfer taxation.

Housing and family functioning: evidence from subdivided units in Hong Kong

Man Tsun Wong

Y.W. Frances at

The University of Hong Kong

Child-rearing families living in cramped subdivided rental units encounter persistent challenges to caregiving, child development, and family functioning, yet housing research remains largely individual-centred.

Drawing on environmental affordance theory, we conducted a qualitative study that investigates how inadequate housing environments shape or constrain core family functions. Thirty-two families, recruited through four non-governmental organisations, participated in semi-structured, in-depth interviews analysed through reflexive thematic and abductive methods.

Findings reveal seven interrelated family–housing functions: adaptation to external conditions; management of household utilities and finances; safeguarding children and managing risk; maintaining efficient caregiving routines; enabling rest and recovery; spatial organization of domestic supplies; and fostering child development.

Severe spatial limitations generate “forced synchronicity,” compelling members to synchronize daily activities at the cost of privacy, differentiated caregiving, and restorative rest. While neighbourhood infrastructure and social networks offer limited compensation, they cannot offset the stress and managerial burdens imposed by housing inadequacy.

The study extends the affordance framework to family households and calls for family-centred housing and energy policies, alongside targeted building management and neighbourhood interventions, in high-density cities affected by acute housing shortages.

Besides the qualitative study, we are also conducting a scale development and validation study on family housing needs satisfaction, which is intended for policymakers and social work practitioners to assess the satisfaction of family housing needs through the dimensions of utilities, personal development, caregiving and familial interaction, and safety and comfort.

Housing Needs in the Barcelona Metropolitan Region: insights from the atomistic assessment of households

Karen Ortega Burgos

Juan Antonio Módenes Cabrerizo

Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics

The assessment of the rate of household formation is a key indicator for estimating housing needs. However, processes such as delayed residential independence, rising divorce rates, the growth of single-parent households, the return of adults to their parental homes, and migration have produced increasingly complex household structures that challenge the traditional nuclear family model. Consequently, the household has become a diffuse analytical unit that only partially reflects residential behaviour, so a more detailed approach is required to examine its internal composition while maintaining minimum social links among co-residents.

This study adopts the concept of Minimal Household Units formulated by J.F. Ermisch & Elizabeth Overton (1985), to better capture these internal dynamics. The coexistence of multiple domestic units results partly from family-based residential strategies established within the traditional Spanish model, and from shared housing arrangements among migrant families. It can also arise from households composed of unrelated individuals who cohabit without direct family ties.

These structural changes occur within a context of housing supply and demand imbalance in the Barcelona Metropolitan Region, and Spain overall, where the scarce availability of housing (particularly in the rental sector) combined with affordability constraints, restricts early residential independence and the dynamics of household formation compared to other European contexts.

This analysis aims to uncover the potential housing demand concealed within households, using microdata from the 2021 Population Census to examine these dynamics in the Barcelona Metropolitan Region, comparing patterns between native and migrant populations.

Housing Agricultural Workers: Key Findings from the California Farmworker Housing Study

Robert Wiener

Luisa Cafe

University of California, Davis

California has been called the “breadbasket of the world”. Produce from its orchards, field crops, and vineyards are world-renowned and exported globally. California accounts for 80% of the country’s wine and the Central Valley, alone, comprising 11% of its land area, produces nearly half of U.S.-grown fruits, nuts, and vegetables. In a state with the world’s fourth largest economy and vaunted high-tech, financial, and entertainment industries, agriculture is a foundational, multi-billion-dollar industry.

Highly dependent upon low-wage immigrant labour, an estimated 882,000 people work all year or seasonally in agriculture, often traveling from crop to crop, pruning, weeding, harvesting, and packaging by hand and machine.

Our paper focuses on a singular problem facing most farmworkers and immigrant migrant workers – where to live. In the U.S., this problem is compounded by low wages, community resistance, lack of housing options, and, more recently, fear of immigration enforcement and deportation. In 2022, the California Legislature passed Assembly Bill (AB) 1654 directing the California Department of Housing and Community Development to conduct a first-ever California Farmworker Housing Study agricultural labour housing conditions, needs, and solutions.

The State commissioned the University of California, Davis, Western Center for Agricultural Health and Safety (WCAHS) and California Coalition for Rural Housing to perform research. About 450 farmworkers in five agricultural regions and 40 stakeholders were surveyed and interviewed.

We report the key findings from interviews with affordable housing developers, growers, local governments, and grassroots organizations. The paper reveals the continuing need for decent and affordable homes for California farmworkers, who are increasingly year-round state residents, compares and contrasts U.S. and European policies and programs to house this population, and proposes financing, land use, and planning reforms.

Housing-Market Pressure and Fertility Realisation in Germany

Sebastian Will

Bundesinstitut für Bevölkerungsforschung

This paper examines whether housing-market pressure impedes fertility realization in Germany. The empirical focus is the gap between short-run fertility intentions and subsequent births. We combine the German Family Demography Panel Study (FReDA) with geographically linked housing-market measures and estimate person fixed-effects models that relate within-person changes in local housing pressure to fertility intentions, fertility realization, and the intention-realization gap. To move beyond baseline association estimates, we implement an instrumental-variables design that interacts local supply constraints with national housing-demand shocks. We also test whether the estimated relationship is stronger among households with tighter baseline space constraints.

The paper's contribution is to integrate repeated fertility intentions, realized fertility outcomes, and local housing market exposure. The findings are consistent with the view that housing-market pressure operates primarily on the realization margin, limiting the translation of fertility plans into births.

Housing Cost Burden of Families: Explaining the Difference Between Objective Measures and Subjective Burden

Susanne Elsas

Simon Grömer

Ifb State Institute for Family Research at the University of Bamberg

In official statistics, the objective housing cost (OHCB) burden is assessed using the share of housing costs in disposable income. The corresponding subjective measure – referring to the household head's evaluation of their costs – reveals that parents perceive a higher subjective housing cost burden (SHCB) than the objective measure suggests (Elsas and Rinklake, 2024). We therefore analyse in depth whether the SHCB of families exceeds their OHCB and why.

To this end, we propose a model of SHCB depending on OHCB and family situation. Since households with children typically consist of more individuals, the proposed model further accounts for the c.p. higher consumptive needs of multi-person households. Using panel data from the German SOEP and linear fixed effects

regression, we find that even when controlling for OHCB, SHCB of parents is higher than SHCB of childless individuals. Second, we find that in two-parent families, this is mitigated if consumptive needs are controlled for. As an additional mechanism, we examine the denominator in OHCB. We hypothesize that children who earn income themselves may keep their earnings private, causing household income to overestimate the income that is actually disposable for household ‘public’ spending.

Results confirm that living with children is associated with a higher housing cost burden – particularly in single-parent families – and that these results partly from an income measure that overestimates disposable income. Our contribution is twofold: results demonstrate that the most widely used objective measure systematically underestimates the housing cost burden of families and that this could be mitigated by redefining the OHCB measure. Second, the excessive burden of single-parent families points to further substantive issues deserving future research.

Homeownership, family-friendly housing and subsequent childbearing: Evidence from Estonia

Mark Herman Ilumets

Mark Gortfelder

Allan Puur

Anneli Kährik

Tallinn University and University of Tartu

Homeownership is a central housing institution shaping family formation and life-course trajectories. Families with children typically require adequate space, quality housing, safety, and long-term residential stability, which are conditions often associated with owner-occupied housing and lower-density environments. While research documents fertility differences between urban and rural contexts and highlights tenure-specific mechanisms, it remains unclear whether homeownership influences childbearing primarily by enabling access to larger, family-appropriate dwellings or whether it retains an independent association with subsequent births.

Estonia provides a compelling case. It combines a high homeownership rate with rapid housing-market change. Rising affordability pressures in the capital city Tallinn have made entry into ownership increasingly difficult for young adults, while suburbanisation and remote work have reshaped residential mobility patterns among family-age households. These developments offer an opportunity to examine how housing tenure and residential context interact with family trajectories in a transforming ownership

regime. This study asks: What is the association between dwelling characteristics (tenure, type, size and location) and the probability of having a subsequent child in Estonia?

Using linked 2021 Population and Housing Census and register data, women aged 20–44 are followed prospectively. Logistic and discrete-time event-history models estimate parity-specific transitions, controlling for socio-demographic characteristics. By treating housing conditions as baseline constraints and enabling factors, the analysis assesses whether homeownership has an association with childbearing beyond dwelling size and residential context, contributing to research on the interdependence of housing and family dynamics.

Residential mobility and urban transformation: structure and agency, a case study of Bugaoli, Shanghai, China

PEI DING

University of the West of England (UWE)

This study examines how urban transformation and residential mobility interact to reshape socio-spatial dynamics in Shanghai, China. It investigates how patterns of residential mobility both reflect and influence the city's evolving urban structure. In particular, it shows how shifts in housing reform, economic transformation, and urban regeneration have reconfigured residents' movements, choices, and social positioning over time through interacting institutional and social logics.

The research is grounded in an in-depth case study of Bugaoli, a historic longtang neighbourhood characterized by distinctive local culture and preserved residential architecture in Shanghai, to examine how residents' life-course intersect with rapid urban change. Drawing on 30 interviews, the findings show that the hukou system (China's household registration system) establishes the structural framework of residential mobility by governing access to education, welfare, housing benefits, and redevelopment compensation, shaping residential choices and migration trajectories across different periods. Residential mobility is therefore driven not only by individual preferences but also by how households are positioned within institutional opportunity structures.

The study also shows that residents are not passive recipients of institutional constraints. Households develop strategies to navigate them, including maintaining hukou registration in valuable locations, enduring poor housing conditions to preserve school access, or circulating between neighbourhoods while retaining institutional footholds. In this way, residents strategically "play system" to secure advantages for

themselves and their children. By conceptualizing residential mobility as an institutionally differentiated and temporally structured process, this research contributes to debates on urban transformation and socio-spatial inequality in rapidly changing cities.

Young adult marginalization in Norway: What role does childhood residential mobility play?

Kristin Aarland

NIBR, Oslo Metropolitan University

Anna María Santiago

Michigan State University

Norwegian policymakers have had a longstanding concern about the long-term effects of early school leaving, the lack of participation in the labour force, and sustained reliance on “last resort” social assistance affecting approximately 10% of Norwegian young adults. Previous studies have underscored the deleterious economic, behavioural health and societal effects of such marginalization (Gunnes et al., 2025). Yet, few studies to date have examined the role that childhood residential mobility plays in exacerbating marginalization.

In this study, we assess the long-term influence of childhood residential mobility on two indicators of young adult marginalization: (1) the incidence of being NEET (neither in education, employment or training); and (2) receipt of social assistance (Norwegian discretionary welfare program of last resort for those with insufficient income to meet basic needs). We employ register data for the 1990-1993 cohorts of youth born in Norway in order to trace NEET status and social assistance receipt from age 18 through age 29 while controlling for childhood residential mobility as well as extensive socioeconomic background variables and childhood place characteristics. For a subsample of the youth we also control for potential endogeneity of childhood residential mobility using data on mother’s residential mobility during her childhood and an indicator of whether mother and father were born in the same place.

Our findings suggest that the negative influence of childhood residential mobility on marginalization in young adulthood is indeed strong and not the result of selection.

Ukrainian Families in Displacement: Housing Precarity, Family Dynamics and Participatory Ethnography

Miroslava Hlincikova

Martina Wilsch

Institute of Ethnology and Soc. Anthropology SAS, Slovak Academy of Sciences

The full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine has displaced over 120,000 Ukrainians, seeking temporary protection in Slovakia, of whom women and children constitute the vast majority. This situation creates distinct gendered challenges, including single parenthood, heightened vulnerability, low socioeconomic status, extensive caregiving burdens, and inadequate institutional support. In a housing system characterised by limited social housing provision, private ownership, and ad-hoc state interventions, access to stable accommodation has emerged as a central structuring condition of refugees' everyday lives. In this context, women, often single mothers, bear disproportionate burdens of securing stable and affordable housing.

This paper examines how displaced families navigate social, economic, and political landscapes to secure housing and presents the first results of an ongoing participatory ethnographic study of care, social support, and housing, among Ukrainian refugee families in Slovakia. The authors argue that the Slovak state rigidly defines vulnerability. As a result, the tightening of eligibility criteria for housing allowances and the near-impossible access to social housing exacerbate insecurity and reinforce the sense of liminality among refugees.

Our contribution proposes a combined theoretical and methodological design that integrates ethnographic enquiry with participatory methods. The crucial part of the research is collaboration with diaspora-based community co-researchers in the problem identification, methodological design, data interpretation, and knowledge dissemination. Participatory methods can bolster participants' credibility and epistemic authority (Fricker, 2007; Medina, 2012) while also contributing to methodological innovation. The paper is part of the research project's methodological component, *Family on the Edge: Current Contexts of Vulnerability and Transnational Family Transformations* (September 2025 - December 2028).

Family Wealth and Assetisation – How Do Families Construct Their Dwellings in the Increasingly Assetised Housing Systems of the Netherlands and Germany?

Judith Körte

University of Amsterdam

This paper examines the lived experience of housing under assetisation through an intergenerational lens. In both the Dutch and German contexts, housing inequalities are increasingly shaped by family wealth and assets. Rising house prices and restricted access to home ownership for first-time buyers have heightened the importance of family and intergenerational wealth transfers for securing housing for some, while others must navigate these systems without family wealth to draw on.

At the same time, the Dutch and German housing systems are characterised by comparatively large rental sectors, strong tenant protection, and weaker homeownership norms, making housing pathways beyond the ownership ladder common well into the middle of their societies.

However, these rental sectors have undergone far-reaching financialisation, and historically decommodified housing stock is dwindling, creating new pressures to leave the rental sector. These developments raise the question of how renters and owners themselves experience these transformations through their relations to their dwellings.

Drawing on semi-structured interviews with adults aged 25–45 and their parents in Amsterdam and Berlin this paper analyses how individuals and families with and without housing assets negotiate between the economic asset character and the affective home character of their housing.

The intergenerational lens allows us, first, to understand families as networks beyond the household that both adapt to and actively shape changing housing systems, thereby reshaping housing inequalities and intergenerational social (im)mobility. Second, it allows us to examine how different historical moments within the same housing systems shape each generation's housing experiences and spatial opportunities, and how these differ across generations within the same kinship networks.

Family Support Attitudes and Housing Support in “Individualistic” Contexts

Gabriela Sepúlveda-Vásquez

University College Dublin and University of Amsterdam

Stephan Köppe

University of Amsterdam

Rowan Arundel, Richard Ronald

University of Amsterdam

Family solidarity attitudes are an understudied yet crucial dimension of housing when it comes to accessing homeownership and mutual housing support. Research on intergenerational support highlights three key dimensions shaping behaviour: family formation patterns, cultural norms of solidarity, and institutional arrangements in welfare and housing regimes.

Existing research has focused on the latter, while the cultural dimension has rarely been examined empirically. Cultural country differences are usually framed through the familistic–individualistic divide, with Nordic and Western European countries commonly classified as individualistic, with weaker family obligations and stronger reliance on public provision. Yet research shows that in generous welfare states, family support is not absent but rather complementary alongside public provision. At the same time, rising housing unaffordability, labour market insecurity and broader cost-of-living pressures may be reshaping intergenerational dependencies, potentially contributing to processes of re-familiarisation even in contexts labelled as individualistic.

This paper asks: How do family support attitudes align with housing-related support practices, and how have these patterns evolved between 2005 and 2022? Specifically, it examines (1) whether these attitudes and housing-related support practices have changed over time, (2) whether patterns differ between young adults (potential recipients) and mid- and older adults (potential providers), (3) and how these differences are stratified by socioeconomic status.

Using the Gender & Generations Survey, we construct a cross-national index of family support attitudes and assess how these attitudes change over time and across cohorts in Austria, Germany, Netherlands, and Sweden. The study contributes to housing research by stressing the role of cultural norms in shaping intergenerational dependencies and access to homeownership.

Returning Home: Family Strategies and Counterurban Migration in Peripheral Czechia

Marie Sýkora Hornáková

Charles University, Faculty of Science

Petra Špacková

Czech Academy of Sciences, Institute of Sociology

Viktor Kveton

Charles University, Faculty of Science

Anja Decker

Czech Academy of Sciences, Institute of Sociology

Population movements from metropolitan areas to non-metropolitan regions have gained renewed momentum in recent years. This counter urbanisation trend is increasingly visible, even in peripheral regions, where new in-migration flows are reshaping local demographic structures and housing markets. While often discussed through the lens of rural gentrification, these changes are fundamentally rooted in shifting migration patterns and residential preferences. The expansion of remote work has weakened the traditional link between residence and workplace, enabling households to reconsider where and how they wish to live, particularly at key moments of family formation and life-course transitions.

This paper presents a case study of return migrants to the Jeseník region, one of the most peripheral areas in Czechia. Drawing on qualitative research, it examines the motivations and decision-making processes behind their relocation from large cities back to their region of origin. These return movements reflect evolving lifestyle preferences, family strategies, and housing considerations, while simultaneously contributing to socio-spatial restructuring. Many of these returnees are highly educated and possess substantial socio-economic and social capital. Preliminary findings show that their return unfolds amid an escalating housing crisis. Rising housing costs and limited affordability in large cities act as important push factors, while lifestyle considerations—particularly those related to family formation—as well as the perceived attractiveness of the region function as pull factors. Remote work plays a crucial enabling role, allowing migrants to retain urban-based employment while relocating.

This detachment from the local labour market differentiates newcomers from long-term residents and may deepen social inequalities. Counterurban migration thus represents an important driver of rural gentrification and socio-spatial change in peripheral regions.

Housing Inequality and Politics: Untangling the Relationships between Welfare State and Housing Regimes, Election Manifestos and Housing Inequalities

Tomáš Horení Samec

Czech Academy of Sciences

Petr Soukup

Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences

Various studies document important role of housing policy in either mitigating or reproducing the housing inequalities. However, surprisingly, there is a substantially less studies focusing on the relationship between the housing inequality and politics.

Filling this gap, this article explores relationship between the housing inequality and politics operationalised (1) on the macro institutional terms as welfare state regime and housing regime and (2) on micro level represented by election manifestos of ruling political parties. The article thus combines the outcomes from qualitative content analysis of political parties' election manifestos with the quantitative statistical data and indicators of housing inequality in the long-term, international perspective.

Our findings show that there is, surprisingly a rather weak relationship between the declared political orientation and ideology and the resulting housing inequalities when focusing on the housing manifestos. However, the analysis reveals relationship between the politics represented by the welfare state regime and housing regime and housing wealth inequality.

The results could be interpreted as corresponding with broader arguments in housing political economy literature which describes the structural changes such as the shifts to asset-based welfare. Such structural changes which occur in specific institutional and policy frameworks (i.e., housing and welfare state regime) are then more relevant for housing inequality outcomes in the long-term perspective.

Who Is Responsible for Housing? Family Support and the Intergenerational Contract in Southern Europe

Gaini Yessengarayeva

University of Granada, University College Dublin

Stephan Köppe

University College Dublin, School of Social Policy, Social Work and Social Justice
Ireland

Ricardo Duque Calvache

University of Granada, Department of Sociology, Granada, Spain

In Southern European welfare contexts, housing access for younger generations is largely mediated through family relations rather than public provision. Spain represents a paradigmatic case: high homeownership rates, weak rental markets and limited state intervention have produced a familistic housing regime in which families act as primary providers of housing security. This reliance on kin support reflects not only cultural norms of family solidarity but also the limited capacity of welfare and housing systems to offer alternatives. Housing thus becomes a key site where intergenerational obligations, solidarities and tensions are enacted and renegotiated.

This paper examines intergenerational housing support in Granada, Spain, focusing on how individuals interpret implicit responsibilities associated with such support and position themselves in relation to changing housing conditions. Drawing on qualitative interviews with adults aged 25–45 and their parents or other kin who provided assistance, the study engages with the notion of the intergenerational contract while examining how it is understood and reinterpreted by actors themselves.

Interviews reveal a strong “family-first” orientation: when asked about broader or formalised notions of the intergenerational contract, participants redirect discussion to their own family situations, framing responsibility almost exclusively within kinship boundaries. Although support for housing is described as contingent on parents’ financial capacity and not as formal duty, it is nonetheless treated as expected and morally appropriate.

The findings highlight how familiarization of intergenerational responsibility shifts welfare provision toward private moral economies of kinship while obscuring the role of state and market forces in reproducing intergenerational inequalities.

The impact of intergenerational within-family transfers on housing wealth outcomes and inequality in European countries

Martin Lux

Institute of Sociology, Czech Academy of Sciences

Petr Sunega

Institute of Sociology, Czech Academy of Sciences

Housing wealth inequality is becoming an important axis of social stratification in Europe. The paper shows significant differences in the nature and strength of the impact of intergenerational resource transfers on housing wealth inequality across different European housing regimes. Specifically, in countries with a 'dualist' or 'familial' housing regime and a high homeownership rate, the transfers have a significant impact on all the tested households' wealth outcomes, and the impact of transfers is often stronger than the impact of traditional socioeconomic factors.

However, when transfers are equally distributed, they may effectively decrease housing wealth inequality incurred by economic (housing price) growth and work as wealth equaliser in these regimes. In countries with a 'unitary' housing regime and a large rental segment, where housing wealth inequality has the highest level and growth rate in Europe, the impact of transfers on wealth outcomes is weaker, and their distribution does not have a uniform effect on the wealth inequality trend.

The transfers may thus both equalise and catalyse household wealth inequality, depending on how (un)evenly they are distributed and on the type of housing regime. These results have important policy implications, especially for the taxing of wealth and transfers in different contexts.

From City to Suburb? Classifying Long Term Housing Pathways in Post Socialist Bucharest

Cristian Tosa

University of Stavanger

Long-term residential trajectories are essential for understanding patterns of suburbanisation, housing, and demographic change in post-socialist metropolitan regions. This study reconstructs housing and family histories (1990-2016) for 960 respondents in the Bucharest-Ilfov metropolitan region. It uses geocoded residential coordinates, administrative boundaries, and survey-reported tenure and dwelling

characteristics. Coordinates were matched to municipal and county polygons and merged with questionnaire data to derive annual housing states. After quality filtering, 553 complete trajectories were retained for descriptive and clustering analyses.

The results demonstrate how mixed administrative and survey data can be integrated into full life course sequences, offering new insight into long-term residential behaviour in rapidly changing metropolitan regions.

Caught in Between: Housing Precarity among Doctoral Students in Poland

Justyna Orchowska
University of Warsaw

Across Europe, young adults face growing housing affordability challenges, reflected in prolonged dependence on private rental markets, reliance on family support, and delayed access to homeownership. Students are among the groups most affected due to low and often unstable incomes. However, relatively little is known about how housing precarity is experienced by doctoral students, whose age and life-course position often distinguish them from undergraduates. At the same time, doctoral candidates constitute the next generation of academic professionals, producing knowledge of high social value. Understanding their housing experiences is therefore particularly important.

This presentation examines how PhD students navigate housing constraints in Poland, a country characterised by a “super-homeownership” tenure structure and a residualised public housing sector. The analysis explores both the structural factors shaping doctoral students’ housing situations and the ways in which housing conditions influence their broader life choices. It draws on qualitative research based on 40 in-depth interviews with PhD candidates aged 25–35 conducted in three major academic centres—Warsaw, Kraków, and Łódź—covering diverse academic disciplines, genders, and living arrangements.

The findings show that doctoral students’ housing experiences are deeply embedded in the structural conditions of academia, particularly low remuneration, unstable employment arrangements (including the absence of formal employment contracts), and weak institutional housing support. Combined with their ambiguous status – situated between student and university employee – these conditions produce a persistent sense of being “in between”, marked by academic prestige alongside material insecurity. Most interviewees rely on private rental housing or family support, often

associating these arrangements with a prolonged “student life”, while homeownership – particularly mortgage-financed – emerges as a dominant.

Stigma of claiming housing benefits: cross-country quantitative study

Michael Skvrnak

Institute of Sociology, Czech Academy of Sciences

A sizable gap exists between eligible households and households receiving social benefits, including housing benefits (e.g. OECD 2024). The non-take-up of benefits is usually explained by the costs associated with claiming, including psychological costs driven by stigma. However, extant research on benefits stigma is largely limited to single-country studies, rarely distinguishes personal stigma (one's own view that claiming is shameful) from stigmatisation (the perception that others hold this view), and lacks cross-nationally comparable measurement instruments.

This paper aims to fill this gap using the HouseInc 2025 multinational survey from eight countries (Belgium, Czechia, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Italy, Romania, and the United Kingdom), representing different welfare and housing regimes. The survey replicates Baumberg's (2016) validated instrument distinguishing personal stigma, stigmatisation, and claims stigma, providing the first cross-nationally comparable prevalence estimates using this framework. We explore how the three components of benefits stigma vary across countries and within countries based on respondents' socio-demographic characteristics (including ethnic background), economic status, and use of the social welfare system.

Housing access as a constraint on migrant integration: the case of Paris

Anna Pereti

Sciences Po & Luiss

Across European cities, housing has become a structural crisis marked by declining affordability, increasing scarcity, and growing pressure on urban welfare systems. These dynamics intersect with migration governance as large metropolitan areas concentrate migrant populations while operating under tightening national regulations and constrained public resources. Paris provides a particularly relevant context in which to examine these dynamics. In 2025 France registered 145,210 asylum applications, while an estimated 500,000 refugees and around 600,000 undocumented migrants live in the

country. Both these populations and the emergency accommodation system are concentrated in Île-de-France, and particularly in Paris, where pressures on the housing system are most acute. The French state finances an emergency accommodation sector of around 320,000 places and €3.3 billion annually, including €2.3 billion for the general emergency housing system. Yet, many migrants experiencing legal and social precarity remain in street situations or circulate between shelters and unstable housing arrangements.

This research draws on two strands of literature. Studies of urban migration governance have largely focused on labour markets and education, leaving housing relatively marginal. By contrast, scholarship on housing regimes has mainly examined national welfare arrangements and their protective effects, paying less attention to how housing governance operates for migrants with different legal statuses in urban contexts. The paper thus asks: which mechanisms related to accessing housing act as constraints on migrant integration in Paris?

Empirically, the analysis draws on qualitative fieldwork conducted in Paris in 2026, including 20 semi-structured interviews with municipal officials, NGO representatives and migrants experiencing legal and social precarity, combined with document analysis of national and municipal housing policies and reports produced by third-sector organisations.

Who leaves a wealthy, safe country? Emigration from Norway 2000-23

Marianne Tønnessen

Oslo Met

Overshadowed by the high immigration to Norway in recent decades, emigration from Norway has also increased substantially. Currently Norway has more annual emigrations (ca 30,000) than during the large emigration waves to America in the late 1800s.

Until now, little has been known about those who emigrate from today's Norway, or why they leave. However, the research project EXITNORWAY has uncovered characteristics of those who opt to leave a wealthy, safe country such as Norway, and explored their reasons for doing so.

We have analysed rich register data, and interviewed emigrants about their perspectives. In June 2026, most of the results from the project will be ready, and this presentation will give an overview of emigration patterns from Norway – including differences across the urban-rural spectrum, between immigrants and natives, and between those who emigrate for good and those who come back to Norway after a

period abroad. Not surprisingly, immigrants are more likely than natives to leave Norway, and less likely to come back – but refugees have a clearly higher propensity to move within than out of Norway.

The presentation will also present some main reasons our interviewees had for leaving. Among them are issues related to Norwegian social culture, as well as aspects of the Norwegian welfare state that emigrants found problematic.

I'm Leaving, or Am I? Regional Disparities in Young Adults' Intentions to Leave the Parental Home in the Czech Republic

Jana Zavodska
Masaryk University

Zuzana Žilincíková
Masaryk University

This paper examines whether the intention of young adults aged 18–35 to leave the parental home varies by regional context in the Czech Republic. The Czech Republic belongs to super-homeownership regimes, with a minimal social rental sector and high dependence on intergenerational asset transfers for housing access (Lux and Sunega, 2014; Chelcea and Druta, 2016).

While the role of parental financial support in housing trajectories is well documented (Lux et al., 2018), the regional dimension of leaving-home intentions remains underexplored. Schwanitz, Rampazzo and Vitali (2021) identified unexplained variation in barriers to home-leaving across twelve countries but could not account for within-country differentiation. Such variation matters in contexts where housing markets, labour opportunities and family support structures differ across regions.

Using Czech GGS data, the analysis asks: whether intentions differ by region; who realised them and who did not, and what role partnership formation, entry into employment, and parental support play in this process. The findings extend Schwanitz et al. (2021) to the sub-national level and contribute to debates on refamilialisation and intergenerational dependence in Czech housing (Horení Samec and Kubala, 2022).

Beyond net migration - exploring age-specific moving within and out of Norway

Marianne Tønnessen

OsloMet

Migration is an important contribution to a region's or city's growth or decline. Changes in net migration is often used to show how mobility patterns change over time. However, one challenge when interpreting changes in such overall trends is that migration patterns are closely linked to age: Many people move to cities when they are in their late teens and early 20s, usually to work or study. After a few years, when approaching their 30s, some move out of the city, perhaps to (back) to a small-town region.

The number of in- and out-movers (and hence net migration) to different regions is thus strongly influenced by the size of different age cohorts. If the country has large cohorts in their 20s and small cohorts in their 30s, this can contribute to high net migration from small-town regions to city regions, while the picture can be the opposite if cohorts in their 30s are the largest, even though the probability of people of different ages moving has not changed.

This paper uses detailed individual-level register data on migration within and out of Norway, to map whether the probability of different types of migration at different ages has changed over time. Preliminary results show that mobility both into and out of cities, has increased for young adults, and that emigration propensities have increased for older persons, due to more immigrants in these age groups.

Family life in collaborative housing. Relief or burden?

Lisa Abbenhardt

German Youth Institute

Martina Heitkötter

German Youth Institute

In our contribution we discuss how family life is affected by the housing environment. Our research focuses on families living in collaborative housing projects in which existing buildings have been communally transformed into living and working spaces. Based on explorative group discussions with parents living and working in collaborative housing as well as expert interviews, we analyse how this environment affects the reconciliation of work and family life. As a conceptual framework we refer to Doing

Family (Jurczyk 2020) and to Housing as a Social Practice (Beck 2021). The data were collected in 2024 during the first phase of the interdisciplinary research project BegeFa („Using existing buildings communally. Perspectives for Families?“). BegeFa is a collaboration between the Professorship of Urban Design (TU Munich) and the Department of Family and Family Politics (German Youth Institute). We are currently conducting additional interviews to verify and further refine our initial findings.

Our results indicate that families benefit from close social networks as well as from formal and informal infrastructures within communal housing projects. Also, working from home can ease everyday life. However, we also find, that collaborative housing requires considerable commitment such as contributing to the collective project. These findings suggest extending the bipolar understanding of work–family reconciliation by a third sphere: engagement in the collaborative project.

Our research also indicates that growing up in a community may influence young people’s social skills and vocational orientation. However, the presentation will focus on these initial findings while also reflecting on insights emerging from the ongoing data collection.

Divorce and Diverging Housing Careers: Homeownership, Tenure, and Financial Implications

Helena Bohman
Malmö University

Martin Grander
Malmö University

Divorce has profound and long term consequences for homeownership, housing tenure trajectories, and the financial wellbeing of individuals. In Sweden, where nearly half of all marriages end in divorce, understanding these housing pathways is essential for interpreting household economic conditions and identifying structural vulnerabilities. In the present political context, that strongly emphasises homeownership, we consider it extra important to understand the importance of rental housing, and the interplay between different tenure forms during this process.

Preliminary findings suggest that women show a stronger shift to rental housing post-divorce. This study examines tenure and homeownership trajectories before and after divorce or separation, drawing on Swedish population register data. We follow multiple cohorts over time to analyse how housing outcomes differ between men and women, and how these differences evolve in the years surrounding a marital dissolution. In

addition to housing outcomes, we incorporate financial data to explore patterns in income, wealth, and economic stability. A further aim is to assess how divorce shapes individuals' access to labour markets, given the long term implications for lifetime earnings. By combining housing, demographic, and financial registers, the study provides a comprehensive picture of how divorce restructures both housing careers and economic opportunities.

Housing and theory

Rethinking Housing Vacancy and Its Structural Causes: Evidence from Istanbul, Turkey

Safiye Özge Subasi

University Of Glasgow

Housing vacancy is often explained as a temporary imbalance between housing supply and demand. However, in many cities facing housing affordability crises, significant numbers of housing units remain unoccupied despite growing housing need.

This research examines housing vacancy not as a short-term market inefficiency, but as a structural feature of contemporary housing systems. It focuses on the concept of empty housing and investigates the underlying mechanisms that sustain vacancy, drawing on initial empirical findings from Istanbul, Turkey. The research adopts a qualitative approach based on semi-structured interviews with property owners, real estate professionals, and public actors, complemented by analysis of housing market dynamics and policy frameworks. Initial findings suggest that vacancy is closely linked to investment-oriented housing production and the treatment of housing as a financial asset rather than primarily as a social good. Housing units are often kept vacant as part of speculative holding strategies, expectations of future price appreciation, or risk-avoidance practices in rental markets. In addition, regulatory and institutional gaps appear to play a significant role in enabling the persistence of vacancy.

These findings challenge conventional explanations that frame vacancy as a natural or temporary market condition. Instead, vacancy emerges as a socially and institutionally produced outcome, shaped by investment practices, housing governance, and policy environments.

The research contributes to conceptual debates on housing vacancy by highlighting the importance of examining vacancy as part of broader processes of financialization and housing inequality. By focusing on Istanbul, a rapidly transforming housing market, the

research provides insights into how vacancy is produced and sustained in contemporary urban contexts. It emphasizes the importance of understanding the structural causes of vacancy in order to inform housing policy response.

Centring Social Reproduction: Towards a Feminist Political Economy of Housing

Tabea Carlotta Latocha

Housing theory has offered powerful political-economic accounts of commodification and financialisation, yet it often treats dwelling primarily as an asset class and policy field.

This paper develops a feminist political economy of housing that recentres social reproduction in order to theorise housing as both a key circuit of capital accumulation and an indispensable infrastructure for sustaining life. Building on feminist Marxist critique and Social Reproduction Theory, I conceptualize the contemporary “housing question” as an expression and field of the contradiction between capital and life, rather than only between capital and labor. This shift foregrounds how the subordination of housing’s use value to its exchange value reorganizes the conditions under which households reproduce themselves—and why housing crises are simultaneously crises of care, time, belonging and political capacity.

I propose an integrated framework—*ge-wohnte Vergesellschaftung* (habitualised dwelling-as-socialization)—that specifies four interlocked dimensions through which housing mediates between everyday life and the capitalist totality: (1) state regulation of housing as governance of social reproduction; (2) housing as a spatial resource for social reproduction; (3) lived housing experiences as a field of situated subjectivation, including alienation and depletion; and (4) housing as a terrain of social struggles over reproduction relations.

The perspective enables housing theory to connect macro-structural transformations to the micro-politics of everyday dwelling without reducing the latter to “outcomes”. It offers concepts to analyze how class is structured and lived through housing, how gendered and racialised reproduction is organized through domestic spatialities and housing policy, and how the affective and embodied burdens of housing insecurity shape possibilities for political agency. Finally, it reframes tenant politics and anti-displacement mobilization as reproduction

Regulating Heat and Bodies: Building Legislation and the Ordering of Inhabitants

Martine Buser

Chalmers University of Technology

Marli Swanepoel

Chalmers University of Technology | Department of Architecture and Civil Engineering

Building codes do more than regulate construction; they define the limits of architectural obligation. By specifying acceptable thermal conditions, they determine which bodies architecture must sustain, which discomforts count as failure, and which adjustments are presumed reasonable. Thermal standards thus participate in what Jacques Rancière calls a distribution of the sensible: a partitioning of roles and capacities within a shared spatial order. As summer overheating intensifies in Sweden and the 2024 revision of Boverket's building codes (BFS 2024:8) removes detailed thermal standards, the allocation of thermal responsibility is unsettled.

The question is no longer only what buildings must guarantee, but how inhabitants are positioned within that frame: How does Swedish thermal regulation construct the role of occupants in relation to indoor climate? To do so we build on archival analysis of legislation and regulatory assessments between 1960s- 2024 traces a gradual reconfiguration of the inhabitant within the domestic thermal order.

Over six decades, regulation has shifted from prescriptive spatial guarantees to defining comfort as contingent on performance metrics and occupant behavior. What was once an architectural obligation secured through measurable standards is now framed as dependent on clothing, activity, duration of use, and the capacity to adjust the indoor environment. Thermal adequacy moves from building responsibility to inhabitant management. Read through Rancière's notion of police order, this trajectory constitutes a redistribution of roles within domestic architecture. Thermal responsibility shifts from collective provision to individual adaptive capacity, transforming the inhabitant from protected beneficiary into the bearer of adaptive obligation.

Contemporary building codes thus reorganise not only standards of comfort, but the distribution of roles through which thermal experience becomes a matter of public claim or private endurance.

More than rent, less than human: strategies and discourses of property actors pushing housing hyper-commodification

Constance Uyttebrouck

Luxembourg Institute of Socio-Economic Research

Antoine Paccoud

Luxembourg Institute of Socio-Economic Research (LISER)

Sila Demirörs

Luxembourg Institute of Socio-Economic Research (LISER)

Housing regimes have undergone dramatic transformations post-Global Financial Crisis, under combined processes of financialisation, assetisation and platformisation. Concomitantly, real estate and capital accumulation have come to dominate all facets of housing provision – a process that Madden and Marcuse have named ‘hyper-commodification’.

This paper argues that housing hyper-commodification progresses through the practices of particular property actors who mobilise dehumanising discourses to construct an ‘other’ who can be pushed further than is currently socially acceptable. We hypothesise that such dehumanisation renders acceptable housing commodification, while yielding the actors involved in this process more than just rent extraction. We explore these practices and discourses at three stages of the housing provision chain – land ownership, property development, and property management. We focus on Luxembourg, where both property ownership concentration and housing prices are high, resulting in a fragmented access to homeownership, an inaccessible private-rented sector, and scarce public housing. We draw on the discourse analysis of 50 semi-structured interviews, conducted with individual landowners (land ownership stage), property developers (development stage), and co-living and short-term rental operating companies (property management stage).

We show how the discursive framing of each actor’s actions, their relation with privileged actors contra their construction of a dehumanised ‘other’ in the provision landscape – relatives vs ‘strangers’ for landowners, investors vs homebuyers for property developers, property owners vs tenants for operating companies – opens a discursive space that some actors exploit to push the limits of commodification. We see these practices as forms of lawful violence (Deleuze & Guattari) that are legitimised by the laissez-faire behavior of different government levels, and progressively socialised when successful.

Perceptions of power in English social housing: A systems thinking approach to housing politics

Anna Pagani

King's College London

Livia Fritz

University of Geneva

The erosion of affordable and secure housing in England prompts questions about power and its role in the 'housing crisis'. While crucial for understanding housing politics, theory-grounded, actor-based analyses remain rare.

This study combines theories of power and systems thinking to examine perceptions of power in the English social housing sector. Using thirty-eight interview-based systems maps, we trace instrumental, structural, and discursive power, and their material and social outcomes.

A sample of maps exemplifies how power is mobilised in decisions to retrofit or demolish social housing estates, and the perceived impacts on health and the environment. Our interviews identified six critical actors: central government, local government, the third sector, the private sector, architects, and residents. Their responsibilities and capacities are embedded in a complex web of (perceived) housing politics, (re)producing dominant narratives - privatisation and financialisation, stigma, public interest, and sustainability – that act as infrastructures legitimising choices and normalising trajectories.

The maps selected to show tensions between demolition and retrofit decisions crystallise these dynamics, displaying demolition as embedded in discourses – the sector's privatisation and vulnerability, the climate emergency, and appeals to the public good –, which ultimately shape housebuilding policies (structural), enable greening manipulations (instrumental), and affect residents' health and wellbeing (outcomes).

Acknowledging the need to deconstruct 'systems-maintaining' power structures, we discuss the use of our approach to conceptualise and empirically trace power as a first step towards rethinking power constellations for housing provision in a way that prioritises residents' health and wellbeing, ecological sustainability, and justice.

Discursive Institutionalism, homelessness and death

Ed Kirton-Darling

University of Bristol

Discursive Institutionalism focuses on how institutions gradually change, and the role of persuasion and advocacy (or discourse) in that change. Emerging from (and critiquing) New Institutionalism thought, it has been little deployed in either housing or socio-legal scholarship, but contains rich and productive possibilities as a conceptual framework for both fields of study.

This paper introduces Discursive Institutionalism, and applies it to a case study of deaths of people experiencing homelessness. There is extensive evidence that homelessness causes early death, and that many such deaths are preventable 'deaths of despair.' In England and Wales, deaths are investigated by Coroners, locally appointed judicial officers with a duty to identify issues which might lead to further deaths in the future. They have a wide discretion in relation to this report, including who to send it to and what it needs to focus on.

Using a Discursive Institutionalist approach, this research analyses 8 years of reports where the deceased was homeless or precariously housed. In five years, 2017-21, there were 18 reports in which the deceased could be identified as homeless and in almost all cases, homelessness was peripheral to the concerns raised by the Coroner. In three years, 2023-25, there were 38 reports.

The analysis identifies that many more of these reports treat housing/homelessness as central rather than peripheral; more are sent to housing/homelessness authorities and more of these are only sent to housing authorities; more investigations engage with housing issues at an earlier stage; more are directed to national level actors; more engage with prevention of homelessness, and more are focused on the need for substantive and system-level change.

The paper argues that, analysed collectively, these reports constitute a discursive argument for a change in the institution of the inquest, to place greater importance on housing and home as determinants of health and mortality.

Defining and measuring housing deprivation in the UK & Europe: A systematic scoping and data review.

James Wright

City St George's University of London

This paper explores how housing deprivation is defined and measured across the UK and Europe. Housing deprivation is widely recognised as a multidimensional problem, spanning multiple issues which sit on a continuum from relative housing inequality to acute forms of exclusion and homelessness. Yet there is limited consensus on how best to define housing deprivation, which dimensions are important to monitor, and what indicators should be used to monitor various aspects of housing quality. To address this, the study undertakes a systematic scoping review of academic and grey literature (n = 4,021) and a structured review of survey datasets held by the UK Data Service and GESIS repositories (n = 300).

The analysis uses thematic analysis to group key theoretical perspectives on deprivation, recurrent dimensions of housing deprivation studied in previous research, and which survey-based indicators and methods of analysis are commonly used to measure them. A complementary data matrix highlights the availability and limitations of key housing datasets across the UK and Europe.

Results show that research frequently defines housing deprivation through affordability metrics, bedroom standards, and measures of housing adequacy centred on measures focusing on access to basic amenities and physical quality. In contrast, tenure security, environmental conditions, and housing suitability are less frequently measured, despite many recognising their importance as dimensions of housing quality. This dissonance reflects gaps in existing survey data, which offer strong coverage of affordability and dwelling characteristics but weaker coverage on indicators of environmental quality, access to services, tenure security, and households' capabilities to improve their own conditions. The paper argues for better alignment between conceptual frameworks and data provision to support more comprehensive population-level monitoring of housing conditions.

Non-Hierarchical Need Models and Housing Policy Gaps Across Urban, Suburban and Rural Contexts

Pia Westford

RISE

Nils Björling

RISE

How we understand human needs shapes housing policy. This paper argues that the historical shift in operational need models, from Maslow's hierarchical pyramid to Max-Neef's systemic framework, in which needs and their satisfiers interact in complex, non-linear ways, parallels broader transformations in urbanisation, housing provision and institutional structures. Early welfare-state housing policy prioritised subsistence and protection needs such as shelter, food, and transportation. As these were largely met, social needs such as participation, and autonomy have become increasingly central. Yet, the institutional structures capable of satisfying these needs have not gained traction in Sweden, despite evidence of their potential. Structured interviews with 800 residents across a suburban environment (Gothenburg), a small town (Mariestad) and a rural setting (Tanum) show that the most pronounced need gaps are social, although with significant differences between geographies. Rural gaps centre on subsistence needs such as public transport and access to food stores, while suburban and small-town residents experience larger deficits in participation and autonomy, such as community activities, participation in community life and influence over local development. Need satisfaction has significant associations with tenure, country of birth, age and labour market status, adding complexity to geographic comparisons.

We argue that closing these need gaps requires institutional innovation at the municipality-civil society interface, inclusive organizational models and working methods, offering residents genuine autonomy, opportunities for shared activities and collective influence over housing and local development. The paper contributes a historically grounded, needs-based framework for analysing policy gaps in housing, and evaluating institutional innovation across urban, suburban and rural contexts, with potential for application in comparative welfare state research.

Housing Cooperatives as Real Utopias: A Theoretical Framework for Emancipatory Housing Research

Lena Radau

LMU Munich

Housing research has long been criticized for its theoretical poverty (Kemeny 1992, Ruonavaara 2018). While housing scholars have extensively documented the failures of capitalist housing markets – from financialization and displacement to discrimination

and precarity – the field lacks a normative framework to systematically evaluate which forms of housing organization are desirable.

This paper addresses this gap by drawing on Erik Olin Wright's concept of Real Utopias as a theoretical resource, applied to housing in the sense of Ruonavaara's (2018) theory about housing. Wright's emancipatory social science provides three evaluative criteria – desirability, viability, and achievability – to assess institutions for their transformative potential. This paper applies these criteria to different forms of housing organization in Germany, including for-profit rental housing, owner-occupation, municipal housing, and housing cooperatives, arguing that cooperative housing most closely approximates a Real Utopia: it is democratically organized, oriented towards the common good, and has demonstrated long-term viability within capitalist markets.

The paper further argues that assessing cooperatives as Real Utopias requires distinguishing between housing as organizational form and housing as lived practice. While cooperatives formally fulfill Wright's criteria, whether their emancipatory potential is realized in practice remains an open empirical question, generating a concrete research agenda around the conditions under which cooperatives translate formal principles into genuinely democratic lived experience.

The paper makes a twofold contribution: it applies Wright's framework to housing, demonstrating its value for normatively grounded housing theory, and it refines Wright's concept by specifying conditions under which Real Utopias in the housing domain can be said to exist.

From Generation Rent to the New Age of Renting: Toward a Research Agenda on Enduring Housing Precarity

Santiago Leyva Del Rio
University of Amsterdam

This paper examines the expanding phenomenon of precarious shared housing among mature private renters in homeownership societies. By exploring how post-2008 wealth-driven housing financialisation increasingly produces lived experiences of precarious renting in mid and later life, it contributes to advancing life-course theory within housing studies. Eighteen years after the Global Financial Crisis, increasing numbers of tenants aged 40+ struggle not only to access homeownership but also to afford renting on their own, and even to secure decent shared housing. Yet life-course perspectives often focus on 'generation rent,' obscuring emerging forms of housing insecurity.

By shifting the analytical focus from 'generation rent' to a 'new age of renting,' this paper advances a research agenda that examines housing insecurity in mid- and later life,

highlighting how it intersects with broader structural inequalities and the care crisis in ageing societies. It also emphasises the need for place-based research that captures both the quantitative and qualitative dimensions of this phenomenon.

Advancing nascent strands of housing research, this research agenda explores (1) how digitally mediated access to shared housing creates distinct barriers and higher rejection rates for older tenants, pushing them toward greater informality and insecurity; (2) how precarious house sharing impacts ageing tenants' well-being and safety, and (3) how the reality—or even the prospect—of house sharing shapes intimate decisions and caring arrangements.

By integrating these three dimensions, it contributes to a better understanding of housing precarity across adulthood and how it shapes emotional attachments to the future and ideas of personal and social progress. It also underscores the need for housing research, policy, and solutions that recognise and support the increasing diversity of household arrangements and the plurality and non-linearity of life-course trajectories.

Land is not a commodity

Trine Olsen Møgster

Institutt for arkitektur og planlegging, NTNU

Why is affordable housing so difficult to produce in contemporary cities? This paper argues that conventional explanations — insufficient supply, high construction costs, restrictive planning — miss a more fundamental shift in what land and housing have become.

Drawing on multi-year ethnographic fieldwork in Fornebu, Norway's largest privately owned urban development area, the paper introduces assetization as a precise analytical concept for understanding this shift. Unlike a commodity, which realizes its value through sale, an asset realizes its value through holding and control over future returns. When land and housing become assets, the logic of production inverts: delays become profitable and opacity becomes strategic. This paper traces the mechanisms through which assetization operates in practice and shows how it produces a structural barrier to affordable housing.

The paper concludes that affordability interventions need to directly address the two cost drivers of assetization: pricing risk and pricing time. Redistributing who bears risk and who controls the timeline of development is a critical precondition for making affordable housing producible again.

Outrage and Happiness in Housing Policy

Aleksandra Zubrzycka-Czarnecka

University of Warsaw

This article examines how emotional narratives shape housing policy in the Polish controversy over micro-apartments. Analysing a corpus of public statements, media texts, expert commentaries and organisational positions from 2016–2025, it identifies two competing storylines centred on outrage and happiness.

Using the Narrative Policy Framework (NPF), complemented by selected elements of the Social-Affective Citizenship (SAC) framework, the study treats these storylines as rival regimes of affective citizenship that connect policy narration to institutional change. The outrage narrative frames micro-apartments as a symptom of market failure and declining standards of dignified living; it positions residents as misrecognised and insecure citizens and legitimises the state as a guardian of minimum standards. The happiness narrative frames micro-apartments as microliving and lifestyle flexibility; it elevates autonomy and consumer choice, casts regulation as misrecognition (paternalism), and normalises minimalist housing as a desirable “happy object.”

The findings show that these narratives shape housing policy by (i) reorganising mediation claims around recognition, dignity and security (SAC Level 2), and (ii) generating feedback loops through which emotional legitimacy supports regulatory tightening (2017, 2023) or fuels deregulatory pressure (2018–2025) (SAC Level 4).

Owning Without Speculating: The Changing Meaning of Homeownership in French Shared-Equity Housing

Claire Carriou

Lab'urba, Ecole d'urbanisme de Paris - UPEC

Hélène Morel

Lab'urba, Ecole d'urbanisme de Paris - UPEC

Claire Simonneau

Lab'urba, Ecole d'urbanisme de Paris - UPEC

Sonia Guelton

Lab'urba, Ecole d'urbanisme de Paris - UPEC

Claire Aragau

Lab'urba, Ecole d'urbanisme de Paris - UPEC

Lab'urba,

Ecole d'urbanisme de Paris – UPEC

Recent research has highlighted the growing dominance of an asset-based model of homeownership in many housing systems, increasingly linking access to property to wealth accumulation and profit expectations, whereas it long served as a pathway to security and social mobility. Yet in high-cost housing markets, buying a home is increasingly out of reach for large segments of the population. As housing prices rise and wealth inequalities widen, shared-equity housing has emerged as a policy response aimed at maintaining affordable access to property while limiting speculative dynamics.

Drawing on a qualitative survey of buyers (133 questionnaire respondents and 52 interviewees), this paper examines how households experience and interpret one such model: the Bail Réel Solidaire (BRS) implemented by Organismes Fonciers Solidaires (OFS) in the Paris region since 2019, where property rights are limited and resale prices regulated in exchange for a reduced purchase price. What does it mean to access homeownership in a system where its speculative dimension is deliberately constrained? The findings show that most buyers turn to this model after facing a prolonged "residential deadlock" in conventional housing markets. Entering this form of limited ownership involves adjusting expectations-foregoing capital gains on resale and accepting restrictions on certain ownership rights. Yet households do not perceive this arrangement solely as a compromise. They emphasise benefits such as residential stability, improved housing conditions, homeowner status, and the possibility of remaining in socially valued urban areas-an "added value in use" that partly compensates for the absence of speculative gains.

The paper argues that shared-equity homeownership reveals an emerging shift in the meaning of property, from an asset for accumulation toward a source of residential security and social anchoring in increasingly unequal housing markets.

Inheritance or Struggle? The Role of Taiwan's Housing System as an Inequality Amplifier

YING HUI CHIANG

National Chengchi University

Hui-Pei (Terry) Cheng

Soochow University

This study argues that Taiwan's housing system has transformed from a ladder for social mobility into an Inequality Amplifier that consolidates class structures. We contend that in contemporary Taiwan, socio-economic status is shifting from a logic of meritocracy (what you do) to one of inheritance (who your parents are), with housing ownership serving as the core mechanism of this transition. Existing data reveal that Taiwan's high homeownership rate masks severe intergenerational inequality. Amid soaring housing prices, the younger generation increasingly relies on parental resources, making entry into the urban housing market nearly impossible for those without family support. This has created a profound divide between "Inheritors" and "Strugglers," challenging the traditional belief in upward mobility through hard work. To empirically test this argument, this study will construct a household-level, intergenerational property-ownership database by linking property tax data from the Ministry of Finance, land administration records, and household registration data. Using quantitative analysis, we will investigate: (1) how intergenerational housing transfers impact wealth accumulation, and (2) whether this phenomenon exhibits significant regional disparities. This research is expected to demonstrate that real estate, as the primary vehicle for intergenerational wealth transfer, has become a key mechanism for class reproduction in Taiwan. The findings will not only contribute to understanding inequality dynamics in high-cost housing societies in East Asia but also highlight the limitations of current tax reforms in addressing hereditary wealth, providing an empirical basis for future housing policy.

Housing Economics and Market Dynamics

Housing Tenure and Labour Market Outcomes among Refugees: A Quasi-Experimental Study in Norway

Liv Osland

Western Norway University of Applied Sciences

Kristin Aarland

NIBR OsloMet

Labour market integration is a key policy objective for vulnerable groups, such as refugees. Yet their employment rates often lag behind those of the general population due to a combination of individual, structural, and contextual factors like low level of education, limited skills transferability, and weak social networks. In this study, we investigate the link between housing tenure and labour market outcomes by examining the impact of initial housing tenure allocation on labour market integration among refugees. We focus on whether residing in municipal social housing limits employment prospects compared to living in private rental housing. One reason for this approach is that social housing frequently is means-tested. This important feature may imply that these renters will lose this type of tenure if income increases or if they move to another municipality with e.g. improved employment prospects. Hence, social rented housing may create a lock-in effect, which may prolong unemployment spells.

Using high-quality national register data, we utilise a quasi-experimental design based on Norway's dispersal policy, which limits refugees' ability to self-select into a municipality, and in turn, into a residence within a municipality. We test the underlying exogeneity assumption of the quasi-experimental design and also employ suitable program evaluation techniques to minimize the problem of confoundedness. Moreover, we conduct analyses stratified by gender as prior research has revealed entrenched gender differences in labour market integration of refugees.

Our results show that being allocated to a social housing unit compared to a private rental unit yields a 3.3-5.4 percentage points lower labour market participation for men. For women, we find no statistically significant penalty of social housing tenure. Our findings are stable across model specifications and estimators used.

Birth origin, employment, and time to first property ownership in Luxembourg

Gulnoza Kuldosheva

Luxembourg Institute of Socio-Economic Research

This study analyzes timing differences in transitioning to first property ownership as the speed of entry has direct relevance for wealth accumulation and inequality. Real estate is the primary component in households' wealth portfolios in most developed countries, yet factors influencing who becomes an owner, and how fast they become an owner is poorly investigated, particularly for foreign-born populations. So we study time to first property ownership in Luxembourg using a unique individual-level administrative panel linking social security records to the national land registry over 2002–2022.

Luxembourg's exceptional context among the world's wealthiest countries, with non-

nationals accounting for around 34% of residents and aggregate real estate wealth nearly tripling since 2007 makes it an interesting case for studying nativity gaps in ownership timing.

Using Cox proportional hazard model, we find that all foreign-born groups enter ownership significantly more slowly than Luxembourg-born natives. Employment strongly mediates this gap: wage earners enter ownership twice as fast, while temporary contract holders face delayed entry relative to permanent employees. These patterns suggest that labour market segmentation constitutes a primary structural barrier to property market integration for immigrant workers.

Relationship between Co-Residence of Young Adults with their Parents and Later Life Marriage and Childbearing

Arthur Acolin

University of Washington

Desen Lin

California State University, Fullerton

Kwan Ok Lee

National University of Singapore

Susan Wachter

University of Pennsylvania

We examine how coresidence status of young adults in the US aged 25-34 in 2013 is related to marriage or childbearing outcomes 10 years later using data from the Panel Survey of Income Dynamics. Following a two-stage procedure that endogenizes the coresidence decision as the first-stage model, we estimate a probit model of coresidence status among young adults aged 25-34. The model controls individual, parental and market factors. The individual factors include income, age, gender, race and ethnicity, employment status, education, marital status and school enrolment status. The parental factors include marital status, income, and net worth. The market factors cover the metro-level rent-income ratio and unemployment rate. characteristics that affect the feasibility of hosting an adult child. Specifically, parental rooms per person and parental homeownership serve as instruments in the first-stage coresidence equation.

In the second stage, we use the linear prediction from the first-stage model to compute the inverse Mill ratio λ_i as an additional covariate in the second-stage model. This control function approach corrects for the unobserved characteristics that affect the coresidence decision, allowing us to partial out the effect of selection into coresidence from the effects of coresidence on the marriage and childbearing outcomes. The results indicate a large and significant negative association between co-residence while 25-34 and being married or having children 10 year later. This suggests that the increased co-residence of young adults with their parents maybe one of the pathways contributing to the decline in marriage and childbearing in the US and potentially other countries seeing a similar increase in coresidence.

Supply cycles & investment-driven construction

Magdalena Zaleczna

University of Lodz

Konrad Zelazowski

University of Lodz

In recent years, residential construction activity in Poland has been exceptionally high, among the most vigorous in the European Union. Developers, motivated by prior profits, have been the primary suppliers of new apartments. Currently, the number of households is lower than the total number of residential units. Many buyers have treated apartments as investment assets, driving up prices and creating a shortage of affordable housing. Recent tax regulations have limited investors' profits, and the requirement to register short-term rentals may further discourage investment purchases. In some areas, oversupply has become evident, leading to expectations of price declines.

The author examines residential construction levels and transaction volumes in provincial cities and considers their influence on price trends. Particular attention is given to developers' strategies, as they not only seek to sell units at market rates but also explore opportunities such as entering the rental market and partnering with municipalities.

Dynamic patterns and characteristics of Housing Vacancy: a parcel-level analysis of market transitions

Mathilde Flas

Université de Liège

Jacques Teller
ULiège

Mario Cools
ULiège

Housing vacancy is a complex, context-specific phenomenon with major implications for land-use efficiency. In Western Europe, vacancy is often attributed to owners' behaviour. Yet, we hypothesize that owners' decisions are influenced by market attractiveness and that the characteristics of housing vacancy may provide insight into small-scale market dynamics. Most research on vacant housing characteristics relies on aggregated data at neighbourhood or regional levels. There has been few research based on parcel data and - to our knowledge - none for Western Europe, probably due to the lack of data. Moreover, vacancy is often examined from a static perspective.

This study adopts a dynamic approach, analysing which housing become vacant, remain vacant, or are reintroduced to the market over time. We combine water and electricity consumption data (2023-2025) with field verification to identify vacant single-family housing and examine their characteristics. The Liège agglomeration in Belgium was chosen as a case study due to its complex urban and housing dynamics, including trends that are widespread in Western Europe: shrinkage due to industrial decline, suburbanization, and an increasing commodification of housing. Previous logistic regression models for 2023 compare variables related to the neighbourhood (e.g., socioeconomic precarity, age distribution, homeownership) and housing characteristics (e.g., building age, presence of a garage, cadastral income) and show high-vacancy areas are characterized by substandard, low-value housing, while low vacancy areas show vacancy patterns related to personal convenience and comfort preferences.

The methodology is extended to a dynamic framework to analyse transitions between 2023 and 2025, identifying which dwellings returned to the market, remained vacant, or shifted from occupied to vacant status and is further complemented by an ongoing survey of property owners.

Flood Risk: The different information channels in which flooding has an impact on house prices in England

Mark Andrew
Bayes Business School, City St Georges

James Culley
City St Georges, University of London

Flooding poses a growing challenge for real estate markets, households, mortgage lenders, and insurers, yet its economic impacts remain incompletely understood. This study examines the extent to which flood risk and different ways in which it is capitalised into property values. While prior research has established that flood risk leads to price discounts, the evidence suggests these effects are highly heterogeneous across property types, income groups, and regions. Lower-priced properties appear to suffer greater devaluation than high-value homes, raising questions about equity in climate risk exposure. Additionally, the persistence of these discounts is uncertain, as some studies suggest a market "amnesia" effect, where price penalties for flood risk diminish over time. Our investigation uses a micro-panel dataset to investigate empirically the effects of the different channels flooding has an impact on house prices in England.

Renewal without Revaluation? Housing Market Responses to the “Beautiful Homes” Program in Shanghai

Yimei Zhang
Technical University of Munich

Unlike the large-scale redevelopment and relocation strategies that characterized earlier phases of urban transformation, Chinese cities are now entering an era of piecemeal renewal, a process that can be understood through what David Harvey terms urban entrepreneurship. This shift is clearly illustrated by Shanghai’s ongoing housing renewal initiatives. Since 2018, the “Beautiful Homes” (Meili Jiayuan) program has replaced demolition-led redevelopment with government-funded improvements focused on façade renovation, infrastructure upgrading, and environmental enhancement within existing aging housing estates.

This paper examines whether such renewal is capitalized into housing prices. Using transaction-level housing data from Shanghai between 2016 and 2025, the analysis combines stepwise regressions and housing-age heterogeneity models to assess the relationship between renewal and housing prices. Models control for housing characteristics and year effects in order to account for broader market dynamics and cyclical fluctuations.

The results show that renewal does not generate stable positive effects, nor does it improve a housing estate’s relative position within local markets. This counter-intuitive

outcome can be explained by two interrelated mechanisms. First, macro-level housing market volatility absorbs any localized renewal premium. Second, the institutional design of renewal itself prioritizes physical maintenance and neighbourhood stabilization without reshaping long-term mechanisms of housing management, repair, and ultimately, valuation.

The absence of price feedback raises a broader policy question for China's aging-housing strategy: whether renewal can form a self-reinforcing and financially sustainable cycle in the absence of institutional arrangements that link renewal, valuation, and reinvestment.

Housing markets in an unequal economy: The interplay of macroeconomic shocks and socioeconomic status

Maria Belen Yanotti

University of Tasmania

Moses Kangogo

University of Tasmania

Danika Wright

University of Sydney

In the context of rising housing inequality and rising cost of living, we explore how do macroeconomic policy influence house prices across different socioeconomic groups. We examine this by constructing socioeconomic house price indices, and testing interest rate shocks on house prices across socioeconomic areas rather than geographical definitions.

A two-part structural vector autoregressive (SVAR) empirical exercise, testing the impact of official interest rate changes on house prices across socioeconomic areas, shows that a shock of a fall in interest rates increases house prices across all socioeconomic housing markets. However, there is some heterogeneity in terms of the response to the shock, revealing important distributional dynamics. The rise in house prices is smaller for middle socioeconomic quintiles, and much larger for the lowest and highest socioeconomic quintiles. This, in turn, suggests that affordability-driven and possibly investment-driven low and high-end housing segments are most sensitive to changes in interest rates.

These differential effects have important implications for housing wealth distribution and economic inequality. These findings underscore the need for policymakers to consider heterogeneous responses when calibrating interest rate settings and macroprudential tools.

Beyond Effectiveness: Evaluating Short-Term Rental Regulations Through Neighbourhood-Level Compliance

Yang Wang

CaCHE, University Of Glasgow

Kristóf Gyódi

Faculty of Economic Sciences, University of Warsaw

The rapid expansion of short-term rentals (STRs) has prompted different regulatory responses across Europe. Yet current policy debates have largely focused on regulatory design rather than on implementation and compliance, despite compliance determining whether policy instruments achieve their intended outcomes.

This paper examines how regulatory compliance varies across neighbourhoods and host types following the introduction of mandatory STR licensing in Edinburgh. By analysing compliance in addition to market responses, the study addresses a central question: under what conditions do regulatory interventions succeed in reshaping housing markets? Using a difference-in-differences design combined with pooled panel regression, we evaluate the scale and timing of market responses across submarkets and host categories. We distinguish between professional operators engaged in secondary letting and resident hosts engaged in home- or room-sharing. We then assess how neighbourhood educational attainment (as a proxy for social capital), STR profitability, and rent gaps interact to shape compliance behaviour. We find that licensing significantly reduced STR activity, but compliance patterns differed markedly. Professional operators adjusted early, while resident hosts concentrated adjustments near the deadline. Educational attainment consistently increases compliance, whereas high profitability weakens compliance among professional operators but reinforces it among resident hosts.

These findings demonstrate that regulatory effectiveness depends not only on policy design but also on local socio-economic context and market incentives. The paper contributes to debates on housing market dynamics under regulation. It suggests that transferable regulatory models need to account for both enforcement capacity and underlying market structure if they are to succeed across areas in Europe.

Beyond Neoliberalism: Economic Drivers of Declining Public Housing Production in Europe

Johan Albrecht
Ghent University

Odile De Vos
Ghent University

Annelies Van Maele
Ghent University

Housing scholars widely attribute the long-term decline in public housing production in Europe to neoliberal policy shifts. Using a newly assembled dataset on public and private housing output for a large set of European countries from 1950 onward, this paper examines whether structural economic dynamics provide additional explanatory power beyond policy-regime and ideological change.

A central policy concern is whether increases in private construction crowd out public production or whether both sectors operate independently. We further explore a largely overlooked dimension: does the density of the existing housing stock moderate this relationship in systematic ways?

Drawing on multiple empirical strategies — including first-difference models, interaction specifications, fixed-effects estimators, smoothing of statistical breaks, and targeted robustness checks — we find consistent evidence of short-run crowding-out, whereby increases in private construction reduce the public share of total housing output. Importantly, this crowding-out effect is significantly weaker in high-density housing systems: in the most mature and saturated contexts, the marginal effect of private construction on public output approaches zero.

These findings suggest that long-run structural features of national housing systems, rather than policy shifts alone, help shape the evolving balance between public and private housing provision.

Housing suppliers' response to housing needs: the case of Île-de-France

DUTHILLEUL Laura

ESPI Paris

Nicolas AUSELLO

ESPI2R

This paper aims to investigate the housing suppliers' response to current and future housing needs in Île-de-France region, at IRIS level (the finest geographical level). Using the estimation of housing needs from Depraz, Duthilleul and Mechide (2026) and developers' data (CAPEM) from 1990 to 2024, we analyze suppliers' construction dynamics. The research question is to verify whether housing suppliers are able to propose appropriate dwellings with regard to house-hold size. This is relevant because the mismatch between housing supply and needs increases between 2021 and 2030.

Analysing statistics from construction dynamics, our results provide a nuanced answer: in general, developers propose a new housing stock adapted to household size by increasing the supply of 1- and 2-room dwellings across all IRIS. However, they also favour 3-room dwellings, not to meet potential demand but to target high-purchasing-power households. This contributes to the mismatch between housing supply and needs, as these dwellings tend to be under-occupied. This first micro-level analysis opens avenues for further research on heterogeneous housing suppliers' response.

Price elasticity of housing supply in France: a multi-level estimation

Laura DUTHILLEUL

ESPI Paris

Jordan MOUREAUX

Université du Littoral Côte d'Opale (ULCO), ISI/Lab.RII

This paper proposes to estimate and compare price elasticities of housing supply in France between 2014 and 2023 at various levels : municipality, department and national levels. The first objective is to evaluate and quantify these price elasticities to understand the local adjustment of housing quantities in response to prices. The choice of a finer geographical estimation at the municipal level allows for understanding

territorial differences and highlights significant heterogeneity in price elasticity values across French municipalities. To estimate these elasticities, we followed the model proposed by Malpezzi and Maclennan (2001), incorporating cost-related variables and supply determinants such as land availability, population, construction costs, and capital costs. This methodology, common in many studies, facilitates international comparisons.

The second objective of this paper is to explain variations in price elasticities among territories by controlling for territorial, economic and regulatory variables. Using a panel dataset of 266,686 observations, collected annually for the 26,686 municipalities in metropolitan France between 2014 and 2023, the major contribution of this paper lies in its study area : no other article provides estimates of price elasticities of housing supply in France at these different levels, particularly at the municipal level.

Finally, incorporating variables specific to the French policy context, such as social housing quotas adds significant value to the existing literature on housing supply price elasticities.

Segmentation Policy and Congestion in Public Housing Market: Evidence from Singapore

Minghang Yu

Cristian Badarinza,
National University of Singapore / Frankfurt School of Finance & Management/

Kwan Ok Lee

National University of Singapore/

Hau Wei Teng,
Singapore Land Authority

Public housing systems designed to provide subsidized homeownership often face persistent excess demand, raising questions about how access to high-demand locations is allocated when supply is limited, and prices cannot adjust to clear the market.

This paper examines how households adjust their housing choices in response to a policy reform that introduced regulatory segmentation across public housing projects in Singapore while preserving the existing spatial structure of the market. We combine

administrative application data on new-sale public housing between 2019 and 2025 with a survey of 506 young households that elicit complete rankings of housing bundles under pre- and post-reform institutional regimes. The results show little systematic change in estimated preference parameters across regulatory contexts. However, nearly 30% of respondents revise their top-ranked option once expected allocation probabilities change under the new segmentation system. Administrative application data reveal a decline in congestion in previously oversubscribed locations following the reform, and further counterfactual exercises combining survey-based switching patterns with observed application data indicate that a substantial share of this change can be accounted for by the reallocation of demand across housing segments.

The findings highlight a diversion mechanism through which regulatory segmentation reshapes access to desirable housing locations by redistributing demand across segments, alleviating market pressure in oversubscribed areas while shifting demand elsewhere in the public housing system.

Mortgage risk in urban areas: a study of new homeowners

Terje Wessel

University of Oslo

Norway has one of the highest levels of household debt within OECD. This is the background for the present study, which explores geographic variations in mortgage risk among residents who transitioned from rental to owner-occupied housing during 2015-22. "Mortgage risk" is defined in line with OECDs concept "over-indebtedness", which includes households with a debt-to-income ratio above 300 percent. Altogether 25 cities and one outer-urban area are included in the study, added by a non-urban reference category.

Using proportional hazard regression and controlling for population confounders, I first explore whether patterns of risk vary across areas of different size and centrality. I next look at the association between house prices and risk for all 26 areas, employing population controls and area-fixed effects.

The results show huge subnational variations in risk, partly along the urban-rural axis and partly among areas of similar size and centrality. Only part of the variation can be explained by differences in house prices. I conclude by a discussion of policy implications.

Housing Dilemmas: Densification and Transformation of Established Urban Areas versus Housing Market Dynamics

Knut Boge

Norwegian University of Life Science

Since 1993, the Norwegian government's land-use policy has prioritized densification and transformation of already developed areas (brownfield) over development of greenfield sites. While densification and transformation of brownfield contribute to reduced land consumption and mitigate the encroachment upon natural environments, these strategies may also give rise to unintended consequences. Notably, housing prices in Norway have increased sharply since the late 1990s.

Oslo, the capital and most populous city, is also Norway's most densely populated municipality. This paper examines the impact of densification and transformation on housing prices in Oslo, and whether property development and housing construction based on these strategies have engendered unintended outcomes. The analysis utilizes a dataset comprising registered home sales (market transactions) in Oslo from January 2006 to December 2025 (381,273 transactions).

Densification and transformation of built-up areas frequently involve significantly higher development and construction costs compared to residential development on greenfield. Such approaches conserve land and can facilitate creation of residential areas with numerous desirable attributes. But since the late 1990s, the rate of housing construction in and around Oslo has not matched the pace of population growth. A key consequence has been a marked escalation in house prices.

On average, the prices of flats in Oslo have evolved similarly to those in the rest of Norway; however, the prices of small houses (such as terraced and multi-family houses) and detached houses have increased substantially.

Nevertheless, there are considerable variation in housing prices both between and within Oslo's various districts. Policies promoting densification and transformation have preserved land and mitigated ecological degradation, but they have also contributed to the persistence—and possibly intensification—of economic and social segregation within Oslo.

The Impact of Short-Term Rental Regulations on the U.S. Housing Market

Kristóf Gyódi

University of Warsaw

The short-term rental (STR) market - driven by the rise of platforms such as Airbnb - expanded rapidly throughout the 2010s, especially in major cities, reducing housing availability and affecting neighbourhood dynamics. In response, many U.S. cities implemented stringent STR restrictions prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (e.g., New York, Boston, Chicago, Denver), while others introduced regulations more recently (e.g., Philadelphia, San Diego, St. Louis) or maintained a relatively relaxed regulatory environment (e.g., Indianapolis, Tucson).

Regulatory efforts have typically aimed to preserve housing availability for local residents and to protect affordability. While existing empirical research has shown that enforced STR regulations reduce STR supply, less is known about the broader impacts on the housing market. This work seeks to fill that gap by identifying the effects of STR regulations on STR supply, home values, and rents. The analysis draws on ZIP code-level data from 2015 to 2023 for 27 U.S. cities. It integrates information on STR supply and performance (AirDNA), socio-economic and housing variables (American Community Survey), and housing market outcomes (Zillow Home Value Index and Zillow Observed Rent Index). By leveraging variation in the timing of regulations across cities, the study estimates their impact using Two-Way Fixed Effects and Callaway and Sant'Anna's (2021) doubly robust estimator.

The results show a strong and statistically significant reduction in STR supply: on average, ZIP codes in regulated cities have 40% fewer listings due to these policies. The impact on the housing market, while more modest, is still significant, with an estimated 6-11% decrease in property values, with considerable heterogeneity across cities.

Housing Finance

Balancing Stability and Accessibility: The Impact of Macroprudential Policy on Homeownership in Europe

Michael Voigtlaender

German Economic Institute

This paper examines the impact of macroprudential regulation on access to homeownership in the aftermath of the global financial crisis. While stricter regulatory frameworks have strengthened the resilience of banking systems, they have also altered the conditions under which households can obtain mortgage credit. In particular, higher equity capital requirements and stricter amortization rules have increased borrowing constraints for prospective homeowners. At the same time, the prolonged low-interest-rate environment of the 2010s contributed to substantial increases in house prices across many European countries, further affecting housing affordability.

Drawing on comparative evidence from seven European countries, the paper analyses how equity requirements relative to household income have evolved over time and assesses their implications for access to owner-occupied housing. By combining cross-country data with institutional analysis, the study provides new insights into the distributional and affordability effects of macroprudential policy. Building on the empirical findings, the paper discusses policy options aimed at reconciling financial stability objectives with broader goals of housing accessibility and social inclusion.

Measuring Precarity: How Affordability Standards Normalize Housing Induced Poverty

Yarin Shmerling

University of Basel

This paper interrogates housing affordability as a central yet politically obscured infrastructure of social reproduction. Focusing on the dominant use of income-based affordability standards it argues affordability functions less as a neutral measurement tool than as a normative device legitimising housing precarity.

Tracing the historical evolution of affordability thresholds from the low rent burdens of Red Vienna to contemporary standards of up to 40% of household income, the paper shows how rising ratios have normalised financial exhaustion, deprivation, and uneven exposure to displacement risks, particularly for low-income households. While housing-cost-to-income ratios are widely used as indicators, they simultaneously operate as standards that discipline tenants' expectations and justify escalating rents. This dual role obscures classed inequalities in social reproduction by ignoring differentiated household needs, uneven fixed costs, and more generally the limited flexibility of low-income budgets.

As an alternative, the paper discusses the residual income approach, which asks not how much income can be spent on rent, but what remains after housing costs are paid. This perspective shows the reproductive labour, unmet needs, and coping strategies – such as indebtedness, cutbacks in food, health, or education – through which households manage 'housing-induced poverty'. At the same time, the residual income approach exposes a political gap between recognised needs and institutional responsibility.

The paper conceptualises affordability debates as sites of political subjectivation, where technocratic metrics shape compliance and contestation, ultimately framing affordability not as a technical question, but as a struggle over dignity, security, and the collective organisation of social reproduction.

The Homelessness Crisis as a Fiscal Crisis: How Paying for Temporary Accommodation Affects London Borough Finances

Kath Scanlon

London School of Economics

Local authorities in England are required to provide temporary accommodation to households who are formally recognised as homeless while permanent housing is found for them. London's 33 local authorities, known as boroughs, currently house about 72,000 households. The severity of the city's housing crisis means that these 'temporary' stays commonly last for months or even years. Most temporary accommodation is owned by private landlords, who often charge by the night at high rates. Boroughs are required to cover these costs in the first instance and are partly reimbursed by central government. However the level of reimbursement has been frozen for 14 years, and boroughs are not free to raise taxes to meet these costs.

Our research looked at the following questions: How large is the gap between expenditure on TA and related income for London boroughs? How does covering the gap

affect borough finances, and what are the knock-on effects on other borough activities and services? We found that there was London-wide overall shortfall of more than £740 million. On average, the unfunded cost of TA was £202 a year per resident household. This was equivalent to approximately 11% of Council Tax, the main source of local authority tax revenue.

This represents a significant and growing drain on borough resources and means there is correspondingly less funding for other local services. Meeting the cost of TA is bringing some boroughs close to bankruptcy.

Taxation and Housing Affordability: Fiscal Barriers in Housing Development and Property Transfers in Europe

Luisa Esteve

Universitat de Girona

Taxes play a crucial role in determining both the final price of a dwelling and the total cost borne by homebuyers. The different phases of housing development are subject to taxation by multiple levels of government—central, regional and local. Taxes applied to land transactions, construction activities and property transfers accumulate throughout the development process and may have a significant impact on the final price of housing.

In addition, households purchasing residential property must bear substantial upfront fiscal costs, including transfer taxes or registration fees among others. While housing taxation has long been a traditional field of academic research, comparatively less attention has been devoted to the combined effects of development-related taxes and property transfer taxation on housing affordability. Furthermore, the design of certain taxes may unintentionally hinder initiatives aimed at expanding affordable housing. In Spain, for example, several local governments own land suitable for social housing but lack the financial resources required for its development.

One possible solution is to grant a building lease to a non-profit organisation that undertakes the construction of social housing and subsequently rents the units at affordable prices to low-income households. However, this arrangement is affected by the operation of value added tax (VAT): the non-profit organisation must pay VAT on construction costs but cannot recover it because long-term residential rentals are VAT-exempt. Consequently, VAT becomes an additional cost that may undermine the financial viability of such projects.

This paper does not advocate broad tax exemptions or general tax incentives. Instead, it aims to identify situations in which existing tax rules constitute barriers to housing

affordability and to encourage discussion of targeted and context-sensitive policy responses adapted to different institutional and national settings.

Housing Policy and Practice in the Global South

Impacts of Impoverishment Risks on Sustainable Housing Affordability: A Case Study of Kenya's Slum Upgrading Programme in Kibera

Vasiliki Apostolaki

Housing adequacy and the proliferation of informal settlements are major urban struggles in Nairobi. To address these issues, the Kenyan State has engaged in multiple types of housing interventions, such as slum upgrading programmes. However, there is evidence that beneficiaries of housing programs are vacating their assigned housing units due to affordability constraints.

To interrogate this phenomenon, the research selected the case study of Soweto East A public housing in Kibera, Nairobi, which is an example of on-site resettlement, implemented through slum upgrading. For this purpose, two theoretical models were selected, namely Impoverishment Risks (Cernea, 1997; Patel et al, 2014) and Sustainable Housing Affordability (Mulliner & Maliene, 2011; Ezennia et al, 2021). Impoverishment Risks can be described as the impact of resettlement on capital assets that enable people to pursue their livelihood (natural, physical, financial, human and social capital) (Cernea, 1997; Patel et al, 2014). Sustainable Housing Affordability (SHA) pursues a comprehensive assessment of affordability that integrates social, environmental, and economic criteria (Ezennia et al, 2019; Elghandour, 2024). The aim of the research was to determine how Impoverishment Risks affect Sustainable Housing Affordability in the case study, by employing a combination of qualitative and spatial methods of data analysis (primary & secondary).

The main findings were that Impoverishment Risks and Sustainable Housing Affordability are theoretically compatible and have valid application potential on precarious realities. It was also concluded that Impoverishment Risks were directly affected by resettlement distance. In the case study, residents were not notably impoverished by resettlement and their access to housing and infrastructure was generally enhanced. However, SHA struggles related to the inability of slum upgrading to holistically upgrade the slum dwellers' lives and directly uplift them from poverty.

Informal Gentrification and the Right to Stay: Housing Inequality in Global South Cities

JUAN PEREZ VENTURA

Complutense University of Madrid

Housing inequality in Global South cities is increasingly shaped by processes of urban revalorisation that do not necessarily result in immediate eviction, yet progressively undermine the ability of long-term residents to remain in place. In contexts characterised by widespread informality, hybrid tenure arrangements and fragmented housing governance, displacement often operates through indirect and cumulative mechanisms rather than through direct removal.

This paper examines how such dynamics affect the right to stay in three Global South cities: Mumbai, Mexico City and Johannesburg. Drawing on a comparative qualitative framework, the study analyses neighbourhood-level transformations where housing informality, rental precarity and everyday livelihoods coexist with rising land values, redevelopment initiatives and market-oriented urban policies.

The analysis focuses on three interrelated dimensions: tenure arrangements and housing security, the everyday viability of remaining in the neighbourhood, and the reconfiguration of informal housing practices under conditions of urban revalorisation. Across the three cases, residents frequently remain physically in place while experiencing increasing economic pressure, loss of affordable housing options, erosion of social networks and growing exposure to speculative dynamics.

The paper argues that these processes are insufficiently captured by conventional housing policy frameworks centred on formalisation or homeownership pathways. It therefore proposes the concept of informal gentrification to describe situations in which revalorisation processes coexist with, and selectively instrumentalise, housing informality, producing forms of indirect and exclusionary displacement without immediate eviction.

By foregrounding the right to stay, the paper links urban revalorisation to everyday housing insecurity in the Global South and exposes the limits of dominant housing policy frameworks.

Waiting for Transformation: Uneven Change in the Built Environment of Bomonti, Istanbul

Ezgi Bay-Sahin

Lancaster University

Yurdanur Dülgeroglu-Yüksel

Istanbul Medipol University

Urban regeneration processes often unfold unevenly across neighbourhoods, producing differentiated spatial outcomes within the same urban district. Istanbul's Bomonti district, a former industrial area currently undergoing rapid redevelopment, offers a clear example of such uneven transformation. While some parts of Bomonti have experienced visible regeneration driven by high-end residential projects and increasing real estate investment, other neighbourhoods remain caught in prolonged redevelopment processes.

This study focuses on the Pasa neighbourhood, where regeneration has progressed much more slowly despite its proximity to newly developed luxury residential complexes. Drawing on fieldwork conducted in 2025, including on-site observations and resident surveys, it explores how redevelopment delays are shaped by competing expectations between residents, developers and planning regulations. In Pasa, many informal housing residents seek to maximise housing rights granted through redevelopment, while developers often postpone investment decisions due to perceived limitations on permitted building heights and profit margins. As a result, regeneration in the neighbourhood remains suspended between anticipation and uncertainty.

This prolonged waiting period produces a distinct form of socio-spatial inequality. While adjacent areas rapidly attract capital and new middle/upper-income residents, Pasa experiences speculative delay, leaving residents to continue living in streets marked by unfinished construction and ongoing infrastructure works.

The research argues that this condition reflects a broader dynamic of speculative urbanism in which redevelopment does not simply transform neighbourhoods but also selectively postpones transformation where profitability is uncertain. By focusing on the temporal politics of urban regeneration, the study contributes to debates in urban planning and sociology on uneven development and spatial justice in rapidly transforming cities.

The challenges of Social Production of Habitat (SPH) in city creation and social fabric.

Erika Tupayachi

Universidad Politécnica de Cataluña

The issue of housing provision in a global context of housing deficit is a problem that has been addressed for several years and which, unfortunately, is increasing significantly. In Latin America, 67% of all housing production can be classified as Social Production of Habitat; that is, two-thirds of all housing is built without the involvement of the State and despite being part of a capitalist market model, which shows the relevance of studying these forms of occupation.

This research seeks to analyse, through a well-known Latin American case study such as “Villa el Salvador,” located in the city of Lima—winner of the Prince of Asturias Award for Concord and declared a City of Peace by the United Nations—the possible and main factors that directly influence the social production of co-managed housing.

This model will be analysed under three central and cross-cutting axes, which are the political, social, and economic aspects. This will allow us to extract a categorization of variables to examine the main combinations that favoured and enhanced the production of social housing in this specific case. The central and cross-cutting focus of the three axes mentioned above will be practices of self-management, cooperation, and collective participation by the community.

Thus, the research will provide a comprehensive overview of how Social Production of Habitat (SPH) projects are managed in Latin America, often generating marginal urban neighbourhoods, while also opening the way for reflection to understand, through a case study with a multifactorial approach, the indicators and variables that could largely determine the success or failure of the integration of any other social housing production project into the urban fabric.

Homelessness in Germany and Pakistan: Linkages with Urban Health and Multilocality

Sheikh Atif Bilal Aslam

University of Ostrava, Czech Republic

Heike Koeckler

Department of Health Sciences, Bochum University of Applied Sciences, Germany

Rizwan Hameed

Faculty of Architecture and Planning, University of Engineering and Technology Lahore, Pakistan

M Sanaullah Khan

Department of Urban Science and Policy, Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan

Urban homelessness across various parts of the world is increasing. Due to the inherent complexity involved with the phenomenon of homelessness owing to the interplay of various causes and consequences, the policy response to it is largely ineffective and non-inclusive. Literature identifies various causes of homelessness, including health issues and migration; however, limited research is available on how homelessness is affecting urban health and migration research.

This study, firstly, attempts to investigate the circular linkage of homelessness and urban health, and secondly, it aims to study homelessness through a multilocality perspective by comparing two case studies from the Global North and the Global South. Three separate sequential studies with the homeless people were conducted on a similar methodological basis (mixed methods) in Lahore, Pakistan (n=100 & 55), and the Ruhr area of Germany (n=47). Face-to-face interviewing of both unsheltered and sheltered homeless people was employed for data collection. Homeless people in the Ruhr area had significantly higher health insurance (87%), thus ensuring much better access to health facilities as compared to the situation in Lahore, where none of the homeless people found to have it. However, the homeless people in the Ruhr are significantly less connected with their family members than in the case of Lahore. Depression in German homeless people was significantly correlated with the variables of age, living conditions, food, and drug consumption. A strong multilocational householding evidence strengthened through joint planning character (47%) and remittances (66%) surfaced for Lahore, however a weak multilocational householding character was observed for the German case study.

The results offer a better conceptual understanding of homeless people's lives and assert the need to have a paradigm of inclusive planning that is context-specific and sensitive to the needs of homeless people

Minority Ethnic Groups and Housing

Residential integration of newly arrived immigrants: Interplay between locational and individual-level factors

Kadi Kalm

University of Tartu

Janis Zalite

University of Tartu

Anneli Kährik

University of Tartu

Tiit Tammaru

University of Tartu

European cities are becoming increasingly diverse, making migrant integration a key political and academic issue. Residential integration, understood as how closely immigrants' housing and neighbourhood outcomes resemble the majority's, is central to long-term inclusion, yet its drivers are complex. Although often viewed as one group, newcomers vary greatly in ethnic and socio-economic background, networks, and labour- and housing-market ties. Existing research points to locational factors such as labour-market opportunities and co-ethnic networks as key influences on immigrants' settlement choices, while individual-level characteristics remain understudied. Few studies address ethnic and socio-economic outcomes together, leaving gaps in understanding their interaction.

This paper addresses these gaps by examining how locational factors (e.g., ethnic-linguistic context) and individual attributes (e.g., occupation) shape immigrant residential patterns and trajectories. Focusing on Estonia, the study analyses newcomers' initial settlement and subsequent relocations. The country's large Russian-speaking minority and evolving linguistic environment, combined with increased and

diversified immigration since EU accession, create a distinctive context. While many recent immigrants are highly educated, their cultural and socio-economic backgrounds vary widely, adding complexity. Against this backdrop, we analyse how newcomers are spatially sorted by both locational and individual-level factors, and what drives their later moves. Using 2021 Census and 2025 register data, we examine settlement patterns of new immigrants. Most integrate spatially, yet notable group differences persist. Socio-economic status is the strongest predictor of residential outcomes, and relocations do little to change overall patterns of segregation or integration.

The results show how occupation, housing choices, and immigration policy jointly shape urban diversity and migrant integration.

Local tenure composition, social ties, and homeownership among migrant groups in the Netherlands

Aafke Heringa

Statistics Netherlands

Local tenure composition, social ties, and homeownership among migrant groups in the Netherlands immigrants often start their housing career in the host country in rental properties. As the duration of stay increases and their offspring matures, many proceed to home-ownership.

However, home-ownership rates tend to lag behind on the native population, even for the 3rd generation. An often-overlooked factor is that migrants often in neighbourhoods with high rates of rental housing. To move into home-ownership, they often need to leave the neighbourhood where they started. While some may welcome this move, others may be deterred by social ties with the ethnic community, relatives, or colleagues in the neighbourhood.

In this paper we look at the role of these social ties in moving into home-ownership and the necessity to leave the residential neighbourhood in order to achieve this. We use register data from Statistics Netherlands to analyse relocations of migrants groups in relation to tenure composition and social ties of the movers in these neighbourhoods.

Migrant Life Course Trajectories and Neighborhood Careers in Sweden: Sorting, Persistence, and Concentrated Poverty

Bo Malmberg

Stockholm University

Samaneh Khaef

Stockholm University

This paper examines how different migrant life course trajectories shape long-term neighbourhood careers in Sweden, connecting residential mobility patterns to the production of income-segregated neighbourhoods.

Drawing on Swedish longitudinal register data, we identify distinct migrant trajectory types and track how individuals within each trajectory are distributed across neighbourhood types — defined by the income composition of residents' nearest neighbours — from their first to their fifteenth year of residence in Sweden. The neighbourhood typology, derived from k-means clustering of pooled neighbourhood data from 1990 to 2015, captures a spectrum from very high-income to very low-income neighbourhoods. By mapping migrant trajectories onto this typology over time, we construct neighbourhood career profiles that reveal both the degree of spatial assimilation and the extent of persistent neighbourhood deprivation across different groups.

Our findings are expected to demonstrate considerable heterogeneity in neighbourhood outcomes across trajectory types, while confirming that upward mobility across neighbourhood types remains limited for many migrants — particularly those entering Sweden under disadvantaged labour market or family reunification conditions. The analysis thus contributes to debates around classical versus segmented assimilation, housing precarity, and the role of migrant sorting in sustaining concentrated poverty in Swedish cities.

The paper builds on prior work by South, Crowder and Chavez on spatial assimilation among US Latinos, Vogiazides and Chihaya on long-term residential trajectories in Sweden, and recent scholarship on housing precarity and internal migrant mobility in Europe.

Residential mobility of immigrants using population micro-data: does sorting into housing types work according to Schelling's model of segregation?

Martin Šimon

Institute of Sociology, Czech Academy of Sciences

Eliška Pospechová

Department of Social Geography and Regional Development, Faculty of Science,
Charles University

Martin Fleishmann

Department of Social Geography and Regional Development, Faculty of Science,
Charles University

Martin Ouredníček

Department of Social Geography and Regional Development, Faculty of Science,
Charles University

Anna Brázdová

Department of Social Geography and Regional Development, Faculty of Science,
Charles University

This paper is focused on residential sorting as a process where people move to a particular neighbourhoods or housing types based on their shared characteristics – ‘birds of a feather flock together’. This sorting was famously described by Schelling into a model of racial segregation. Recent comparative analysis of European capital city-regions shows that despite a presence of segregation mechanisms there is a slowdown in the rise of segregation and a tendency to shift to desegregation (Ubareviciene, et al. 2025; <https://doi.org/10.1177/00420980251378028>). Therefore, new insights into residential sorting and micro-segregation patterns are needed to understand this development.

Current paper uses geo-localised population micro-data of foreign immigrants for the 2012-2021 period in Prague, Czechia. As the share of non-native population is increasing, minority ethnic groups play increasingly important role in housing market. Prague is a city with relatively low socio-economic and ethnic segregation but increasing diversity and economic polarization (Křížková, Šimon 2022;

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2022.102730>). The analysis is structured in a following way: Firstly, the analysis of residential sorting is put into broader frames of migration to/from city and immigration to/from country. Key information about local context and immigrant structure is provided. Secondly, residential mobility and stability of immigrant groups within city is analysed at the building level, utilising recent typology of urban morphology and residential typology of neighbourhoods. Thirdly, selected examples illustrating upgrading and downgrading via residential sorting will be presented.

For example: 1) whether housing estates tend to get specific immigrant profile, or 2) whether residential mobility or stability is linked to temporary/permanent residential status of immigrants, or 3) whether different generations/cohorts of migrants differ in their position in housing hierarchy.

Beyond the Enclave? Emerging Residential Patterns and Homeownership Strategies among Korean Chinese in South Korea

Sujin Yoon

Seoul National University

In Kwon Park, Graduate School of Environmental Studies, Seoul National University

Korean Chinese (Joseonjok) constitute the largest immigrant group in South Korea. This study notes a gap between representation and reality: while their residential clusters are often represented as traditional urban enclaves in Seoul, the actual residential geography has extended toward surrounding cities in the metropolitan region, such as Bucheon and Bupyeong. Given that migration governance follows functionalist approach and residential access is structured by housing, this study reconstructs how settlement became possible for this migrant group. It draws on fieldwork and in-depth interviews with residents and local stakeholders in emerging migrant residential areas. Residential relocation toward Bucheon and Bupyeong is not simply a peripheral migration. Rather, it represents strategic movement to an intermediate urban space where accessibility to central Seoul, affordable housing, and existing migrant networks converge. Housing ownership does not function as a generalized pathway for all migrants; instead, for those with more advantageous legal status and resources, it becomes a turning point that stabilizes settlement.

These emerging residential clusters are not characterized by a single dense enclave but by a dispersed residential pattern organized around multiple transit-oriented neighbourhoods. At the same time, public discourse and regulations framing foreign housing ownership as speculation are often at odds with or even contradict the everyday settlement practices observed on the ground. Housing ownership should not be simply

framed as speculation but rather understood as one form of settlement strategy through which migrants seek to stabilize and reproduce their bases of everyday life. The findings suggest the need to move beyond treating such areas as objects of management and instead recognize them as living spaces where new multicultural neighbourhoods are taking shape.

Social service provision model and Roma housing interventions: implications on inclusion. The Italian cases of Milan, Venice and Bologna.

Anna Maschietto

University of Bologna

How does the choice between a specialised social service delivery model- targeted for specific groups -or a generalist model -based on the territorial presence of social services- address Roma housing marginality? The literature has demonstrated that Roma camps are places where segregation and vulnerability are actively produced, often as a direct result of public policies shaped by stereotypes. Heightened awareness has shifted Italian policy toward the closure of Roma camps as a primary goal, together with the provision of access to adequate housing. With respect to service provision models, the literature has mainly addressed two implications: the effect on users' access to services and the organisational structures each model entails. Although existing literature underscores relevant questions, the link between service provision models and housing interventions for Roma remains underexplored.

This study aims to fill this gap through an empirical study of the Roma housing integration process in Milan, Venice and Bologna. Document analysis and semi-structured interviews with the main implementing actors show that in Milan, a deliberate policy favouring a generalist model addresses Roma housing marginality similarly to that of other population groups. In Venice, following the closure of the camp through a public housing transition reserved for Roma, specialised services have formally dissolved; however, social workers have maintained a cultural mediation role, and specialised active labour-market programs remain in place. Bologna bases its services and housing solutions on a specialised mono-ethnic model, but is pivoting towards a generalist approach through co-design practices. These differences lead to diverse outcomes in housing and social integration for Roma.

Finally, this study aims to interrogate the embedded narratives and political underpinnings of specific service delivery models, assessing how these structures shape the social inclusion of Roma population.

Housing Law

The Administrative Abyss: Trust, Rights, and the Erosion of Institutional Legitimacy among Homeless Populations in Barcelona

Wellington Migliari

UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA

This paper presents the results of a mixed-methods study (N=24) exploring the lived experiences of homeless individuals in Barcelona, with a specific focus on their interaction with public administration and social services. Moving beyond a purely sociological analysis, this research adopts a legal and socio-legal perspective to examine how the perception of public support shapes the effectiveness of fundamental rights.

Our data reveals a critical paradox: while the primary objective of welfare policy is the (re)integration and protection of vulnerable groups, the manner of its implementation often generates profound distrust. Key findings indicate that participants frequently report a lack of autonomy, with service providers acting as gatekeepers to essential benefits (psychological care, financial aid) without consent. This perceived exercise of discretionary power, coupled with threats of sanction (e.g., withdrawal of benefits), frames the administrative experience not as one of support, but as an instrument of control.

By contrasting the legal promise of social rights with their empirical application, this paper contributes to the workshop's dialogue on the "significance of law" by highlighting how administrative practice can inadvertently undermine the very legal protections it is meant to enforce, perpetuating the cycle of exclusion.

Policing Public Space: Regulating the Margins: Local Governance and Homelessness in the Netherlands

Els Schipaanboord

University of Groningen

Homelessness in the Netherlands has increased significantly over the past fifteen years. Estimates from the Office for National Statistics indicate a rise from 12,000 - 16,000 homeless individuals in 2009 to 30,000 - 37,000 in 2024, with alternative counts pointing

to even higher figures. Over the same period, police reports of ‘nuisance caused by vagrants’ have grown by more than 250 percent since 2012. These trends have fuelled renewed debate about the governance of public space and, more specifically, the criminalisation of homelessness. Although national vagrancy laws were abolished in 2000, regulatory authority has shifted to the municipal level. Municipal bye-laws have since become the primary legal instruments through which behaviours associated with homelessness are regulated and, in some instances, penalised. Through provisions addressing activities such as sleeping in public spaces, begging, loitering, or other forms of perceived nuisance, municipalities shape the everyday conditions under which homeless individuals navigate urban environments. While extensive international scholarship exists on the criminalisation of homelessness, a systematic analysis of Dutch municipal bye-laws remains absent.

This paper addresses that gap by examining how local governments regulate homelessness and how these rules function in practice. Drawing on the typology developed by the UN Special Rapporteurs on extreme poverty and adequate housing, we apply a classification framework tailored to the Dutch context, categorising relevant provisions in different categories. Using data from the Dutch Central Judicial Collection Agency (CJIB), we further assess the extent to which these provisions lead to criminal penalties. The findings provide the first systematic overview of the local criminalisation of homelessness in the Netherlands and lay the groundwork for international comparison and debate.

Australia’s new protection of the Human Right to Housing: What Can we Learn from Europe and what Can Europe Learn from Australia?

Jessie Hohmann

University of Technology Sydney

In January 2027, Australia’s smallest jurisdiction, the Australian Capital Territory (ACT), will become the country’s first to give domestic protection to the human right to housing. Australia remains one of few States without a Federal human rights Charter. Repeated recommendations for Federal human rights have come to nothing, and only three states or territories have human rights Acts, offering only a smattering of protection. Meanwhile, the country is experiencing a significant housing crisis with rising housing inequality and unaffordability, and high levels of homelessness. Tenants’ rights are weak and mortgage stress high.

The new provision in the ACT Human Rights Act therefore presents a major development in human rights protection in Australia. The new section 27(D)(1) states that ‘Everyone

has the right to adequate housing', and in section (2) specifies three immediately realisable aspects of the right: (a) everyone is entitled to enjoy the right without discrimination; (b) no-one may be unlawfully or arbitrarily evicted from their home; (c) no-one may have an essential utility service to their home unlawfully or arbitrarily withdrawn. The Government characterises this as an 'exhaustive, rather than inclusive' list of immediately realisable aspects. Despite its significance, there are reasons for concern. First, the right is deliberately narrower than Australia's international human rights obligations. Second, Australia's courts have interpreted human rights very narrowly. For these reasons, it is imperative that Australian judges, activists and advocates learn from the more robust protection of the right to housing in Europe.

This paper suggests lessons Australia can learn from Europe as it embarks on the first protection of the right to housing in domestic law, and asks whether there are lessons for Europe in the ACT's framing of the right, recognising both the global nature of housing markets, and of activism for the realisation of the right.

Requisition Orders and the Constitution: Lessons on the State's Re-dimensioned Margin of Appreciation

Bryony Balzia Bartolo

Housing Authority

Dr Kurt Xerri

University of Malta

Emerson Gatt

Housing Authority

Brian Micallef

Housing Authority

Ray Zammit This paper examines Malta's legal institute of requisition orders, tracing its origins, legislative evolution, and contemporary relevance within the broader framework of property rights and housing policy. Requisition orders were instruments issued by the State on buildings, generally vacant and in a dilapidated state, to take full possession of such buildings to be allocated, mainly for housing purposes, in exchange of a compensation. Beginning with the historical context in which requisition powers were first introduced, primarily as an emergency mechanism to address acute housing shortages, the paper outlines the legal developments and the current legal position following years of judicial scrutiny and the latest legislative reforms. Particular focus is

given to case law that has shaped the modern understanding of requisition orders, especially decisions addressing the right of compensation and the quantum thereof, persons entitled to claim such compensation, and the courts' interpretation of the "public interest" requirement that constitutionally legitimises property interference.

The analysis also assesses alternative legal measures adopted by the State aimed at expanding Malta's housing stock while respecting the fundamental right to peacefully enjoy one's possessions. Recent reforms, policy instruments, and regulatory mechanisms are evaluated to highlight the State's ongoing effort to balance social needs with private property rights.

Ultimately, the paper provides a comprehensive overview of the requisition framework's legacy and assesses how contemporary housing strategies reflect the shift toward more proportionate and rights sensitive approaches to addressing Malta's accommodation challenges.

Children's Rights and Eviction Case Law: A Data-Driven Analysis of 10.000 Cases

Michel Vols

University of Groningen

Recent research indicates that nearly 20 percent of homeless individuals in the Netherlands are under the age of 18. This alarming statistic contrasts sharply with the country's ratification of the Convention on the Rights of the Child, which mandates that the Dutch government must take all necessary measures to prevent child homelessness. This obligation extends to the judiciary, which has a vital role in preventing evictions—one of the primary causes of homelessness. In eviction cases, the best interests of the child should be a primary consideration for the judge. In 2025, the Dutch Supreme Court clarified the extent of this obligation.

This paper seeks to examine how courts address the obligation to consider the interests of children in cases where there is a risk of homelessness. It utilises a data science approach to analyse a unique quantitative database comprising over 10.000 Dutch court cases related to eviction. The paper investigates the role minors play in these court cases, whether and how their interests are assessed by the courts, whether the presence of a minor influences the court's decision, and how the risk of homelessness affects this decision.

The findings will reveal that the protection against homelessness for minors varies significantly across different courts. Additionally, the paper will offer concrete

recommendations for policies that courts could implement to enhance protection for minors at risk of homelessness.

Towards an Cross-Regime Human Rights Framework for Eviction Adjudication

Michelle Bruijn

University of Groningen

Across Europe, eviction remains a widespread phenomenon, with devastating impact on people's well-being and society as a whole. International human rights law recognises eviction as the most far-reaching interference with the right to housing. At the same time, eviction disputes often hinge on the right to property, whether invoked by landlords to recover possession, or by homeowners facing state-ordered eviction. Eviction cases thus place housing and property rights in direct interaction. Yet, legal scholarship tends to analyse housing and property rights separately, treats them primarily as competing interests, and remains fragmented across institutional regimes.

This paper offers a systematic, cross-regime analysis of eviction standards under the ICESCR, CRC, ECHR, European Social Charter, and EU law. Drawing on treaties, interpretative statements, and case law in which both housing and property rights are engaged, it distils the procedural, substantive, and contextual requirements these bodies impose on national courts. Moreover, it synthesises these fragmented eviction related requirements and proposes a typology of housing-property interaction, examining whether international law reflects hierarchy, complementarity, or functional differentiation between these rights. Ultimately, the paper develops a cross-regime human rights framework for adjudicating national eviction disputes.

Cooperative housing as a locally embedded response to housing inaccessibility in European cities at the example of Barcelona, Spain

Janette Sesselmann-Huth

Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus

Across major European cities the increase of population and therefore, inequitable access to housing, represents a critical regulatory challenge for a society and its policymakers that is not only based on socioeconomic status but is fundamentally embedded in structural issues driven by the treatment of housing as a commodity rather

than a social right (Madden & Marcuse, 2016/2024). The ongoing negotiation process within a cultural and social group manifests itself not only in public protests, but also in institutional actions such as adjustments to regulations or legal frameworks. Especially in the housing sector and after major crises characterized by a "housing shortage", greater efforts can be seen to mitigate or eliminate these shortages (Tattara, 2021). In response to the increasing pressure on the housing market, alternative, non-market-oriented housing models, such as cooperative housing, are being examined more closely. They are to be discussed as instruments for improving affordability, social justice, and urban resilience (Wheeler, S. & Rosan, C., 2021).

Particular attention is given to the city of Barcelona (Catalonia, Spain) where cooperative housing has only recently entered the formal housing market, requiring legal adaptation. The research analyses the political, historical, cultural, and legal transformations the city has undergone, particularly before and after a pivotal moment in time (e.g. 2008 financial crisis), and the consequent effects on its housing market (Sostre Cívica, 2018). The findings contribute to ongoing discussions on European harmonization in housing law by illustrating how divergent national institutional systems can both hinder and inspire innovative housing solutions.

Methodologically, the study adopts a mixed-methods approach combining qualitative and quantitative data, which includes interviews and document analysis supported by local research institutions and collaborative networks.

Housing, residential segregation and equality in the EU: the Danish "Ghetto Law"

Juli Ponce Solé

UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA

The Danish "Parallel Societies Act," known as the "ghetto law" (introduced in 2018 and expanded in 2021), aims to eliminate areas with high percentages of "non-Western" residents by 2030. It mandates reducing social housing by 40% in designated areas via demolitions or sales to curb crime and increase integration. The Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) has recently issued a judgment concerning Denmark's social housing legislation (Case C-417/23 *Slagelse Almennyttige Boligselskab*, December 18, 2025). The decision addresses the compatibility of this regulation with Directive 2000/43/EC, suggesting that the Danish policies could constitute direct or indirect discrimination.

The presentation will deal with this judicial decision considering the concept of discrimination in the field of housing and land use.

Berlin – Pioneering Legislation? Expropriation, neighbourhood protection and social housing quotas

Alina Holze

Leibniz Universität Hannover

"Housing is the social question of our time" - these were the words of the German Chancellor upon taking office in May 2025. Equally, in the EU, housing is taking center stage with the New European Bauhaus and the European Affordable Housing Plan. Berlin is at the forefront when it comes to housing protection law and an active tenants' movement. The city is undertaking some courageous pioneering efforts when it comes to neighbourhood protection law, thereby pushing the boundaries of law with questions of expropriation, social housing quotas and prohibiting holiday flats.

In my paper, I would like to present the core findings of my doctoral thesis and show how neighbourhood protection can be achieved in conjunction with housing-oriented urban land-use planning, the promotion of social housing, the effective use of communal purchase options and tenant protection law. Drawing on an interdisciplinary framework that combines existing legal instruments with "Milieu Studies" developed by the Chicago School of Sociology, the paper analyses structural tensions within the current legal framework. I would like to demonstrate why the current legal framework often produces conflicts of interest between tenant protection, neighbourhood protection, and investment incentives and how we can overcome these conflicts.

My contribution aims to advance the debate on how planning and environmental law can support social, economic and sustainable housing markets not only in Berlin but in all urban areas across Europe.

Property's children: Law and the destruction of the home "from Galway to the Gaza Strip"

Mark Jordan

University of Southampton

The home is commonly imagined as a site of security, privacy, and belonging. Yet law plays a complex role in shaping the conditions under which homes are enjoyed but also in how homes may be rendered precarious and even destroyed.

Drawing on critical scholarship on property and housing rights, particularly the work of Brenna Bhandar and Patrick McAuslan, this paper explores how legal systems can both

facilitate the destruction of the home and provide spaces through which marginalised and oppressed groups may contest such processes. Particular attention is given to the implications of these dynamics for children's rights, given the central importance of the home to children's safety, development, and family life.

The analysis is developed through two case studies. The first examines eviction practices in Ireland during the 19th century, where landlord property rights and state enforcement enabled widespread evictions and the demolition of homes during and after the Great Famine. These practices, rooted in processes of settlor colonialism, illustrate how property regimes legitimised the destruction of homes, exposing families and children to extreme vulnerability, but also created spaces for subordinate groups to organise, mobilise and act for social change. The second case study engages with contemporary debates in international law surrounding the concept of domicide, advanced by Balakrishnan Rajagopal, UN Special Rapporteur on the right to adequate housing, in response to the mass destruction of housing and civilian infrastructure in various conflicts, but particularly in Gaza.

Taken together, the paper highlights law's dual role as both a mechanism of dispossession and a potential site of legal and political contestation, raising questions about how legal frameworks might better recognize and protect the home – particularly for children and other vulnerable groups.

Transcending territorial injustice in the public enforcement of housing rights

Mark Jordan

University of Southampton

Helen Carr

University of Southampton, Southampton University Law School

Public authorities play a vital role in enforcing housing rights across England. Yet despite a formally uniform legal framework, tenants' access to effective protection varies significantly by locality. This paper explores the entrenched "postcode lottery" in public enforcement of housing rights in England's private rented sector as a form of territorial injustice. Engaging with Bridget Hutter and David Cowan and Alex Marsh's work, this paper examines how the Renters' Rights Act 2025 seeks to transform the role of local authorities in regulating private renting and delivering more even enforcement in the sector.

Drawing on an ESRC-funded empirical study of enforcement in a local authority, we explore how uneven enforcement is produced, highlighting how legislation that extends housing rights for tenants is interpreted and applied by frontline officers, exercising discretion under conditions of limited resources, managerial pressure, and amidst legal and political contests. We conclude by reflecting on whether the Renters' Rights Act 2025 can transcend longstanding inequalities in the public enforcement of housing rights in England.

Digital inequalities and the management of rental properties

Tracey Varnava

University of Kent

Digital inequalities drawing on empirical data gathered for the Leverhulme Trust funded project Understanding Digital Justice Journeys, this presentation will discuss the increasing use of digital and AI interfaces in the management of rental properties (often referred to as RentTech) and how this development exacerbates existing vulnerabilities among those who rent. It will highlight how the proliferation of digitalisation and AI in the management of the rental sector is accompanied by reduced opportunity for human interaction, further alienating and disadvantaging those who struggle with digital forms of communication due to practical barriers (e.g. lack of access to the necessary technology), and/or personal barriers (e.g. poor mental health, illiteracy).

Employing 'digital legal consciousness' (Creutzfeldt, 2021) as a theoretical framework to better understand tenants' (lack of) interaction with the digital realm, the presentation will consider what capabilities, legal and digital, are demanded of tenants to successfully navigate the new digital/AI reality, and, where these capabilities are absent, what the consequences then are for the protection and enforcement of tenants' housing rights.

Right to Housing and Unfair Terms in Residential Lease Agreements: The Spanish Case

Rosa Milà Rafel

UPF, Barcelona Chair of Housing Studies

This article takes as its starting point that, within the current housing crisis, private law, and specifically consumer law, plays a crucial role in protecting the right to housing. In Spain, the massive litigation regarding unfair terms in mortgage loan agreements,

triggered by the 2008 economic crisis, is now being joined by an emerging wave of litigation concerning unfair terms in residential lease agreements entered into between a professional landlord and a tenant acting for private purposes. These lawsuits have often been driven by tenants' unions questioning the legality of the standard contract terms used by corporate landlords.

This paper analyses the jurisprudence of Spanish courts to date on this matter, considering the case law of the CJEU (notably *Asbeek Brusse and De Man Garabito*, Case C-488/11). It is worth noting that a significant consensus has emerged in Spanish case law regarding the unfairness of certain clauses. Specifically, these include penalty clauses for breach of the tenant's obligation to vacate the premises, imposing penalties of double or triple the daily rent per day of delay; and clauses requiring the tenant to pay for rent default insurance when the policy has been pre-selected and contracted by the landlord. Conversely, there is a lack of consensus regarding the unfairness of other provisions, among others, those reserving the landlord's right to conduct periodic inspections of the property to verify its condition.

This paper examines these clauses and the arguments for and against their characterization as unfair, pending a definitive ruling from the Spanish Supreme Court and taking into account decisions in other European jurisdictions.

Housing Freedom: Reframing Housing Justice Beyond Carcerality, Deservingness, and Control

Joana Pestana Lages
DINÂMIA'CET – ISCTE

Contemporary debates on housing justice have expanded beyond distributive concerns of affordability and access to include procedural and recognition-based dimensions. Yet, even critical approaches often remain constrained by liberal frameworks that treat housing primarily as a right to be allocated, regulated, or conditional upon behavioural norms. Building on critical urban theory, feminist ethics of care, abolitionist thought, and scholarship on punitive urbanism, the paper argues that housing systems are increasingly entangled with carceral logics. These logics operate through moralised distinctions between deserving and undeserving subjects, conditional access regimes, surveillance, and spatial exclusion. Housing injustice, from this perspective, is not merely a distributive failure but a mode of governance that actively constrains freedom, particularly for targeted populations.

The concept of housing freedom, insists that housing justice cannot be achieved without addressing the ways housing is mobilised as a disciplinary device within

welfare, penal, and migration regimes. Rather than positioning housing as an endpoint of social inclusion, the paper conceptualises it as an infrastructure that can either reproduce unfreedom or enable emancipation. Situated in the very initial phase of the ERC Starting Grant project ‘HOUSING FREEDOM – Housing as a Tool for Freedom: A Future Away from Incarceration’, this proposal deliberately resists premature empiricism. Instead, it advances an epistemological stance that treats concept formation itself as a site of political struggle.

Drawing on Ruth Wilson Gilmore’s insight that freedom is a place, produced through life-sustaining infrastructures, the paper positions housing freedom as a critical framework to challenge carceral assumptions embedded in housing policy, and to reimagine housing justice as an abolitionist, and fundamentally spatial, project.

Priority Housing in the Netherlands: Opening Doors in a Housing Crisis?

Stefan Van Tongeren
University of Groningen

Like many Western countries, the Netherlands is facing a severe housing crisis. Due to a persistent shortage of affordable housing and increasing pressure on social housing systems, the number of people experiencing homelessness has increased significantly since 2022. Nevertheless, the Netherlands has committed to ending homelessness by 2030 under the Lisbon Declaration on the European Platform on Combatting Homelessness. In Dutch housing allocation, priority housing is an important instrument that allows certain households to gain accelerated access to scarce social housing. Under current law, municipalities may implement priority schemes and determine eligibility criteria. This decentralised approach gives local authorities considerable discretion, resulting in significant differences between municipalities. In practice, even homeless individuals, including those with minor children, may be excluded from priority status.

This paper examines the role of Dutch administrative courts in reviewing refusals of priority housing for homeless applicants. Through a systematic analysis of case law, it addresses three questions: (1) how often homeless applicants successfully challenge refusals of priority housing; (2) which applicant characteristics, such as the presence of minor children or other vulnerabilities, influence judicial outcomes; and (3) whether and how human rights arguments play a role in judicial reasoning. Finally, the paper considers the implications of a pending legislative reform that would require municipalities to grant priority housing to certain categories of homeless persons. By

comparing current judicial practice with the proposed legal framework, the paper assesses whether priority housing can meaningfully expand access to housing for homeless people in the context of the Dutch housing crisis.

Policy and Research

Institutional Mechanisms for Affordable Rents: Lessons from Austria's Limited-Profit Housing Sector for Europe

Gerald Koessl

Austrian Federation of Limited-Profit Housing Associations

Jeremias Jobst

Institut für Management Accounting (Johannes-Kepler-Universität - JKU)

Across Europe, rising rents and widening housing cost burdens have intensified the search for policy instruments that can secure affordable rental housing beyond short-term demand-side subsidies. Austria provides a distinct case in this respect. Its limited-profit housing sector constitutes a comparatively large, privately organised rental segment that operates through cost rents, revolving funds, asset lock-in and reinvestment obligations.

The paper analyses how these institutional mechanisms shape rent formation and structure long-term housing provision. It argues that the relevance of the Austrian model lies less in direct policy transfer than in the institutional logic it reveals. Affordability can be stabilised when limited-profit provision is embedded in durable regulatory arrangements and linked to revolving-fund mechanisms. In this way, parts of the housing stock are kept outside speculative price formation and remain oriented towards long-term affordability.

The analysis shows that these mechanisms moderate rent dynamics, support stock expansion and reduce pressure on demand-side housing allowances. Against the background of the European housing crisis, the paper discusses which levers can be derived for EU housing policy, with particular attention to the design of funding programmes, EIB financing and State aid frameworks that could support the development of limited-profit or non-profit housing segments in other Member States.

Institutions and the Governance of Housing Inequality: Evidence-Based Housing Policymaking Practices in Sheffield

Enes Aydin

The University of Sheffield

Housing has become a prominent concern of public policy, affecting daily life and shaping current policy agendas. While housing inequalities are experienced directly through daily practices, their incorporation into policy responses raises important questions about how far housing policymaking is genuinely evidence-based. Existing research has often fallen short in critically examining how evidence is mobilised in practice and how social, economic, environmental and political dynamics influence decision-making processes.

This study examines how housing policymakers in Sheffield articulate housing inequalities and how evidence-based or evidence-informed approaches are implemented within local housing policymaking. Utilising a qualitative research methodology, the study integrates semi-structured interviews with key actors directly involved in housing policymaking, participant observation at forums, workshops, committee meetings and roundtables, along with a thematic analysis of policy documentation. The findings highlight three principal dynamics. Firstly, policymakers' understandings of housing inequality tend to prioritise a relatively narrow range of issues shaped by institutional frameworks and organisational responsibilities. Secondly, the evaluation and use of evidence are influenced by institutional cultures, cognitive capacities and individual worldviews, resulting in evidence being interpreted, prioritised and selectively mobilised within the confines of existing institutional and political frameworks. Thirdly, publicity and political legitimacy play a significant role in shaping housing policy priorities, influencing how evidence is framed, prioritised and articulated.

This research examines housing policymaking in Sheffield, contributing to broader debates on housing policy governance and underscoring the need for comparative studies that critically analyse how evidence informs housing policy responses across various institutional and political contexts.

Priority in social housing allocation in Amsterdam

Steven Kromhout

Amsterdam Federation of Housing Associations

In most European countries, social housing represents a relatively small portion of the total housing stock, aimed at households with the lowest incomes and other vulnerable groups. Social housing allocation policies are typically designed to prioritize households with the greatest housing needs. The Netherlands has traditionally had a relatively large social housing sector with a broad social function. This means that access to social housing is not limited to the very poorest, but is open to a wide range of relatively low-income households at various stages of life.

In Dutch housing allocation systems, various groups with an urgent need for rehousing are designated as priority groups and are given priority when applying for social housing. However, the share of priority housing is often capped to ensure sufficient housing remains for so-called 'regular home seekers.' Due to the housing crisis in the Netherlands, the share of priority housing has increased in recent years, putting pressure on the opportunities for regular home seekers. In Amsterdam, this has even led to a citizen's initiative to allocate more social housing without priority. In this paper, we discuss the background of this debate in the Netherlands, in the context of theories on needs-based versus choice-based housing allocation policies.

We use registration data from the social housing allocation system in Amsterdam to illustrate the different types of priority and their effects on the housing opportunities of various groups of home seekers.

Does urban densification enhance housing inequalities? An analysis of interlinkages in nine European countries

Rebecca Cavicchia

NMBU,
Nordregio

Roberta Cucca
NMBU

Jennifer Duyne Barenstein
ETH

Urban densification is widely promoted across Europe as a key strategy to limit urban sprawl and advance climate and environmental goals. Yet its relationship with housing policy remains uneven. Growing evidence suggests that when affordability objectives are weakly integrated, densification can contribute to rising housing inequalities. This paper comparatively examines tensions between densification agendas and housing affordability goals across nine European countries (Austria, France, Hungary, Italy, Norway, Poland, Spain, Switzerland and the UK). It explores the extent to which housing

affordability objectives are embedded in densification strategies and asks under which institutional and governance conditions densification may mitigate or intensify housing unaffordability.

The study draws on qualitative comparative policy analysis and expert country reports produced within the European research project ReHousIn. The comparison positions national systems along two dimensions: 1) the strength of commitment to densification and spatial containment, and 2) the degree of integration of housing accessibility and affordability objectives. Findings show that densification is often strongly institutionalised in planning systems (e.g. France, Norway and Switzerland), yet its connection to housing affordability goals is limited or indirect. In more market-led contexts such as the UK, Norway, Italy, Hungary, Switzerland and Poland, densification relies on private development with weak affordability requirements, increasing risks of price escalation and socio-spatial exclusion. By contrast, in Austria, France and partly Switzerland, stronger roles for non-profit and cooperative housing actors and inclusionary instruments help moderate inequality effects, though not consistently.

The paper argues that closer institutional coupling between densification and housing policy is essential to meet anti-sprawl targets without reinforcing existing housing inequalities.

Distributional effects of housing policies in Milan

Manos Matsaganis

Politecnico di Milano

Francesco Cellino

Politecnico di Milano/Polytechnic University of Milan

Andrea Parma

Politecnico di Milano/Polytechnic University of Milan

Milan, Italy's economic powerhouse, has faced in recent years an acute housing affordability crisis, as demand for housing outpaced supply, and house prices and rents rose faster than disposable incomes. In response to this, local authorities at city and regional level have put in place a set of policies to make housing more affordable for targeted groups.

The paper aims to evaluate the distributional impact of those policies. Microsimulation techniques have long been used by governments around the world for the analysis of the fiscal and distributional effects of public policies, typically at the national level. The

growing importance of the local level as the focus of analysis has exposed the limitations of relying on national-level data. The paper showcases a new spatial microsimulation model, EUROMOD-spatial (an extension of EUROMOD, the tax-benefit model for the European Union). Spatial microsimulation deals with the lack of geographically disaggregated microdata by combining survey microdata at national or regional level with population census data at small area level, together with registry (e.g. tax return) data in aggregate form, in order to create a synthetic population whose characteristics mirror as closely as possible those of the local areas under examination.

The paper evaluates the effects on poverty and inequality in the city of Milan of a set of housing policies, including housing benefits, mortgage interest tax relief, rent control, and social housing, operated by government at national, regional, and city level. Our results reveal considerable spatial heterogeneity, inform the debate on the optimal design of income support for housing costs, and illustrate the usefulness of spatial microsimulation as a tool for the analysis of the local effects of housing policies.

Utilising Bacchi´s what´s the problem represented to be (WPR) framework to the housing policy landscape in Sweden? What´s the promise for young housing customers?

Ylva Norén Bretzer

University of Gothenburg, School of PA

Marie Thynell

University of Gothenburg, School of PA

Public policies constitute normative choices among alternative courses of action and are formally decided upon by our elected parliamentary representatives. Such policies signal which societal problems are recognized, which instruments are considered legitimate, which courses of action are prioritized, and which objectives are to be achieved. Policies may be designed to apply universally to broad segments of the population or, alternatively, to address specific target groups (Schneider & Ingram, 2005).

This paper analyses adopted and implemented housing policies through the application of the WPR (What´s the Problem Represented to Be?) framework developed by Carol Bacchi (Bacchi & Goodwin, 2025). The analysis is guided by the following questions: To what extent are housing policies general or targeted in relation to the population at large, specific target groups, and socio-economically disadvantaged groups? What “rules of the game” are constructed for young adults, students, and young immigrants? Given the

hybrid character of the Swedish housing context – marked by a pronounced division between the rental sector and the market-oriented sector (Christophers, 2013) – the paper also examines whether housing policies address both sectors symmetrically or privilege one over the other.

By applying the WPR framework to selected general and targeted housing policies in Sweden between 2010 and 2022, the findings are presented within an analytical framework structured around three principal policy domains: (a) housing production (19 policies), (b) housing provision (37 policies), and (c) financial support for low-income households (8 policies) (Formas, 2024). The analysis identifies articulated policy targets as well as policy silences, particularly in relation to newcomers navigating Sweden’s dual housing market. The discussion pays specific attention to whether policies are formulated in general or selective terms and to which groups, particularly those in the early stages.

From Risk Removal to Housing Production: Legal and Procedural Discontinuities in Urban Transformation in Türkiye

Ceyda Nur YILMAZ

Sedef Özçelik

In Türkiye, earthquake-driven urban transformation has become a central policy instrument for renewing vulnerable housing stock and restructuring patterns of homeownership. Following major seismic disasters—most notably the 1999 Marmara Earthquake and the February 6, 2023 earthquakes—Law No. 6306 has enabled the rapid identification and demolition of “risky buildings.”

While these processes operate through accelerated legal and administrative mechanisms, considerably less attention has been paid to the subsequent construction phase, where housing production and social outcomes are expected to materialize.

This paper argues that the primary vulnerability of Türkiye’s urban transformation model lies not in the removal of risky structures, but in the legal and procedural discontinuities between demolition and reconstruction. Although existing frameworks facilitate swift clearance, the construction phase is frequently marked by prolonged legal disputes, ownership disagreements, licensing delays, and administrative appeals.

These dynamics generate extended periods of uncertainty, resulting in stalled or delayed projects that constrain effective housing supply and, in some cases, temporarily displace original property owners. Conceptually, the study reframes earthquake-driven urban transformation as a housing production regime rather than solely a risk mitigation policy. Empirically, it draws on a qualitative case study from the Marmara earthquake

region, based on semi-structured interviews with municipal officials and an analysis of planning documents and legal procedures.

The findings reveal a structural mismatch between the centralized logic of risk designation and the fragmented governance of housing production, highlighting the need to evaluate urban transformation not by the speed of demolition, but by the continuity and effectiveness of housing production.

Governing Location for Housing Adequacy

Kerstin Pluch

TU Wien

Housing policy debates are increasingly organised around affordability metrics, yet affordability captures only one dimension of housing adequacy. Adequacy also concerns whether households can secure stable, acceptable housing in locations that enable access to everyday services, opportunities, and social life.

This research centres the spatial dimension of adequacy by analysing a policy instrument that explicitly prices residential location within a regulated rental system. I analyse Vienna's location surcharge (Lagezuschlag) within the reference-rent system (Richtwertmiete), applied mainly to regulated private rentals in the pre-1945 housing stock. The surcharge legally defines "above-average" locations, stabilises these classifications through criteria and mapping, and turns them into a separate rent component. Rather than merely recording spatial differences, it helps produce a price order that structures access to urban space and can undermine planning aims such as affordability and social mixing.

Through a historical and regulatory analysis of its introduction in the 1994 rent reform and later shifts in justification and practice, I trace how "good location" has been defined, operationalised, and contested over time. The government's announced evaluation of the Lagezuschlag serves as a policy window. I argue that evaluations centred on transparency, calculability, and legal certainty risk narrowing the debate to correct computation. I therefore propose an adequacy-oriented evaluation frame that clarifies purpose, assesses distributive outcomes and implementation conditions, and makes explicit trade-offs between market-referential valuation and public-interest planning goals.

Vienna offers a particularly instructive context: widely portrayed as a model city of social housing and tenant protection, it illustrates how the governance of location within regulated private renting can shape inequality and belonging even in systems designed to buffer market pressures.

A national survey on housing experiences, aspirations and satisfaction in Malta

Brian Micallef

Malta Housing Authority

Housing dynamics are inextricably linked to the country's broader socio-economic fabric. In recent decades, Maltese society has experienced profound demographic shifts, many of which reflect longer-term structural changes that are likely to persist in the years ahead. These include a trend towards smaller household sizes, a sharp influx of migrants, and an ageing population. Such developments place significant pressure on national housing infrastructure, fundamentally reshaping demand patterns, tenure preferences, and the nature of state intervention required.

Ensuring a resilient and responsive housing system therefore depends on public policy being grounded in a clear and robust understanding of these evolving trends. To this end, the Housing Authority has commissioned a comprehensive survey on housing experiences, attitudes, and aspirations in Malta, with a particular focus on residential satisfaction.

The study is based on a nationally representative sample of 800 households and assesses levels of satisfaction with both dwellings and neighbourhoods, while also exploring future housing aspirations. The fieldwork for this survey was conducted in 2025Q4.

The findings highlight important differences between Maltese and foreign residents, as well as those with different tenure status. Around 12% of respondents plan to move out of their current dwelling in the next two years. This represents the first wave of a survey that is intended to be repeated every three years, thereby allowing for regular monitoring of trends over time.

While not conceived as a fully longitudinal study, future iterations may incorporate a panel component to strengthen comparability and provide deeper insights into evolving housing experiences and aspirations.

Profitability, Feasibility, and Public Competition: Renovation-Driven Rent Increases in an Integrated Rental Regime

Jordan Palma Tzakov

RISE

Tim Johansson

RISE

Housing policy in regulated mixed markets must balance affordability objectives with incentives for maintenance and reinvestment. This paper investigates how institutional design shapes landlord investment behaviour within Sweden's use-value rent regulation system, where municipal and private landlords operate side by side.

Focusing on Gothenburg, the analysis uses micro-level panel data (2015–2023) covering over 680,000 apartment-year observations. Renovations are identified through discrete rent increases of at least 30 percent, reflecting quality-enhancing investments.

The probability of renovation is modelled as a function of rent gaps (profit incentives), tenant turnover (implementation feasibility), neighbourhood income (demand conditions), and local public housing market share (competitive structure).

Results show that renovation is jointly determined by profitability and feasibility: larger rent gaps and higher turnover increase renovation likelihood, but the profitability effect diminishes where turnover is high. Furthermore, renovation probability declines in neighbourhoods with higher public housing share, indicating that public-sector presence disciplines investment incentives. Private landlords are more responsive than public landlords to both rent gaps and turnover, highlighting ownership-specific behavioural differences.

The findings provide policy-relevant evidence on how rent regulation and public housing presence influence reinvestment patterns. They suggest that local competitive structure and tenant mobility are central to understanding where renovation-driven rent increases occur. By linking micro-level investment decisions to institutional settings, the paper contributes to ongoing debates on effective policy design in regulated rental systems.

Between Solidarity and Scarcity: Ukrainian Refugee Inflows, Housing Affordability and Inequality Outcomes in Three Visegrád Economies (Czechia, Poland and Slovakia)

Piotr Lis

Poznan University of Economics and Business

Russia's invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 triggered the largest crisis of forced displacement in post-war European history. Three Visegrad Group countries: Poland, the Czech Republic and Slovakia, have taken in a disproportionately large number of refugees relative to the capacity of their housing markets. The response of the societies in these countries was characterized, especially in the first years of the war, by extraordinary solidarity, while the medium-term consequences for housing availability and socio-spatial inequalities have received limited attention from researchers.

This paper analyses how differences in national housing policy measures have led to divergent outcomes in terms of inequality in three structurally similar post-socialist economies. Despite comparable institutional conditions, membership in the European Union and a shared institutional heritage, we argue that differences between countries in policy-making are a key factor determining the divergent trajectories of housing affordability observed between 2022 and 2025. The analysis combines transaction price data, Eurostat EU-SILC microdata and administrative records on temporary protection holders with comparative policy analysis.

Findings suggest that more proactive responses — notably in Czechia — are associated with contained increases in housing cost burden, while in Poland the interaction between the refugee demand shock and the 'Bezpieczny Kredyt 2%' scheme amplified price pressures on lower-income households. Slovakia, with the weakest institutional response, exhibits patterns of refugee exclusion and overcrowding. This study contributes to debates on refugee housing integration, post-socialist welfare state adequacy and distributional consequences of housing policy design.

How to develop a housing podcast series, an example from Ireland

Roslyn Molloy

The Housing Agency

In 2025 The Housing Agency in Ireland set itself the task of developing a new housing podcast series. Titled Housing Insights, the series aims to deepen the public's understanding of housing in Ireland and highlight the work of The Housing Agency. The

podcast features informal, conversational interviews with housing experts, led by Housing Agency hosts David Silke (Director of Insights & Operations) and Roslyn Molloy (Head of Policy & Practice). Each episode focuses on a specific aspect of housing. The primary audience for the podcast is housing practitioners and others with a general interest in housing topics. The communications objectives are to identify The Housing Agency as a leading source of housing knowledge; broaden the methods the Agency uses to communicate with its stakeholders; deepen the listeners' understanding of housing issues. and profile the work of The Housing Agency. By July 2026 there will be three seasons of the Housing Insights Podcast series available on Spotify and Apple. To date 2 seasons and 8 episodes are available, covering topics such as community-led housing, apartment building, to what's happening in Europe in housing: Proposal for the ENHR Policy and Research Group I propose to provide a talk and presentation to the group on how to set-up a housing podcast series, with the key learnings from our experience.

This is a follow-on from the 2025 ENHR talk I gave on how the Housing Agency set up a series of housing policy insights papers. As co-creator and co-host of the podcast series I would like to present on the series and would aim to cover: Background? Concept and goals? Target audience and objectives? Preparing for the podcast? Production and Technical aspects? Dissemination? Impact

Municipal Housing Policy in Times of Crisis: Conflicts over Governing Power in Tübingen, Frankfurt am Main, and Dresden

Johanna Betz

Goethe- University Frankfurt

This paper examines municipal responses to the renewed housing question in three German cities — Tübingen, Frankfurt am Main, and Dresden — from a critical political economy and discourse-analytical perspective. The selected cases differ significantly in the strength of social movements, collaborative housing initiatives, ownership structures, the presence of financialized actors, party politics, and state-level housing policy contexts.

The study therefore asks whether municipalities, in the context of privatization, financialization, commodification, and the rescaling of housing regulation over the past three decades, face structural constraints in their capacity to intervene. It further explores how discursive configurations and actor constellations shape the expansion or restriction of municipal policy space, and to what extent tenants influence housing discourses and policy instruments. Drawing on Cultural Political Economy and the

concept of the regulatory state, the research investigates (1) the historical formation of local housing regimes, including ownership structures, administrative arrangements, and actor–discourse networks, and (2) dynamics of (de-)politicization, political innovation, and blockage in ongoing negotiation processes.

The findings indicate that municipalities have become more proactive but remain embedded in a multi-level governance trap characterized by limited support from regional and federal levels. The paper also addresses mechanisms of exclusion and the political agency of marginalized groups in housing governance. While these groups are disproportionately affected by depoliticizing tendencies and regulatory fractures, social movements have significantly shaped agenda setting. Despite the deepening housing crisis, recent years have produced promising municipal policy approaches and instruments that offer pathways for further development.

“Workers come first”: New prioritisation of workers in access to social housing (France)

Violette Mével

Laboratoire ESO Université Rennes 2

Solène Gaudin

Laboratoire ESO Université Rennes 2 (France)

In a context of increased tensions in the French housing market, subsidised housing appears to be the only solution for households seeking affordable and stable housing. However, the subsidised housing system, which until now had been organised around a generalist approach, has become significantly residualised in recent decades (Angel, 2023). The sharp reduction in the resources allocated to its production and its reorganisation around the prioritisation of specific vulnerable publics have made it difficult for some households to access it (Desjardins, 2008). Faced with growing residential immobility (Driant, 2014), economic actors are impacted in terms of recruitment and their economic activities. Their difficulties have contributed to the emergence of a discourse legitimising the prioritisation of the employed and workers: the figure of the jobless employee due to lack of housing and the employer without staff have thus emerged as the new face of poor housing, justifying the reintroduction of housing solutions tied to employment contracts.

Based on research conducted on the development of employer-landlord initiatives, using a qualitative methodology focused on the interaction of actors, this article aims to analyse the construction of this new public problem (Gusfield, 1989), its introduction

onto the French political agenda, and the implications of linking housing to employment in the vision of the 'good social housing occupant'. Through an analysis of the discourse of the key players in the housing industry and the legal changes introduced in recent years in support of this new prioritisation, it questions how this discourse serves as an interesting means of imposing a utilitarian dimension on subsidised housing (Raco, 2008), thereby legitimising the reconsideration of the protections implemented to ensure housing rights in the name of maintaining economic activity.

Student Housing in the European Affordable Housing Plan. A policy and research agenda.

Joris Hoekstra

Delft University of Technology

The European Affordable Housing Plan (EAH) identifies young people in general, and students in particular, as a priority group requiring improved access to adequate and affordable housing. The Plan argues that additional student housing must be developed, that students should receive stronger support when navigating the private rental market, and that innovative accommodation models for students and young people should be identified, promoted, and scaled.

This paper sets out a policy and research agenda to help operationalise these ambitions. The paper begins by assessing the current state of student housing across the European Union and by outlining the social and economic significance of secure, affordable, and high-quality accommodation for students. The paper then discusses key policy challenges shaping student housing provision, including its temporary nature, the limited recognition of students as a vulnerable group in housing policy, the transition from student housing to regular housing, and the role of financialization within the housing market for students. Building on this analysis and connecting it to EAH, the paper concludes with a forward-looking policy and research agenda that targets both the European Commission and individual Member States.

Recommendations focus on strengthening data collection, supporting innovative housing models, improving financial and regulatory frameworks, and ensuring that student housing is embedded more systematically in EU-level and national housing strategies.

The paper is based on a briefing note prepared by the author for the Special Committee on the Housing Crisis in the European Union (HOUS) of the European Parliament.

Social constructions of housing policy targets in the Spanish State Housing Plan 2022-2025: A policy design analysis

Sharon Bravo

University of Luxembourg

How are social constructions of target groups embedded in housing policy designs? The literature on the politics of housing has focused on the relationships between housing market dynamics and their effects on politics, as well as the role of different actors in influencing housing policymaking. Despite the evolution of research linking housing, politics and policies, the role of social constructions of policy targets in housing policy design remains underexplored.

This paper links housing to policy process studies by drawing on Policy Design Theory (PDT; Schneider and Ingram, 1997). The PDT suggests that policies reflect the targeted group's social constructions and political power. This paper utilises the PDT to analyse the Spanish State Housing Plan 2022-2025. The Plan includes fourteen programs to facilitate access to housing for different groups. This paper focuses on the programs targeting: (1) renters in need of assistance, (2) vulnerable persons, (3) tenants in vulnerable situations, and (4) young people.

The analysis adopts critical discourse analysis (CDA) to explore how political actors draw on groups' social constructions to advance specific housing policy designs. The data analysed includes speeches, public statements, party manifestos, and interviews with policy actors. The findings show how certain group characteristics are highlighted in discourse to justify housing policy solutions, particularly benefiting the youth and vulnerable groups.

Narratives of Rental Housing in Spain: A Discourse Analysis of the Press

Sonia Fernández-Herrera

Universidad de Granada

Ricardo Duque-Calvache

Universidad de Granada

Ricardo Duque-Calvache, Universidad de Granada In a context marked by rising housing prices (García, 2019; Gil et al., 2023; Vidal et al., 2024), processes of touristification

(Gutiérrez & Domènech, 2020; Etxezarreta-Etxarri, 2020), and the financialization of housing (Byrne, 2019; Escorihuela, 2019), the rental market has emerged as an issue of growing significance in public and political debate in Spain. According to the Spanish Center for Sociological Research (CIS), in 2026, housing became the primary concern for people in Spain. This phenomenon has also had implications for the political and social agenda, as evidenced by the approval of the Housing Rights Act (Law 12/2023). These factors underscore the importance of the theme and the need for further study.

This article applies framing and agenda-setting theory to analyse in a qualitative way how Spanish media construct discourse around rental housing, represent the actors and institutions involved, and frame the social and political positions surrounding the issue. This analysis is relevant, as the media reflect existing social values and can influence public opinion and the development of political agendas (Glenn, Champion, & Spence, 2012). A digital news archive was used to retrieve articles from the main national media outlets for the year 2025. Media selection was based on relevance and diversity of editorial lines, including far-right, liberal, progressive, conservative, and far-left outlets. Three main frames were identified, reflecting the complexity of this issue and its potential political and social implications in the coming years: the economic frame, the vulnerability frame, and the political claims frame.

These findings provide valuable insights into how public discourse shapes housing debates and inform potential policy responses.

Captured Financialisation: Affordable Rental Housing REITs and Vertical Fiscal Governance in China

Yiqi Li

Utrecht University

China's 1994 tax-sharing reform created a structural mismatch between local expenditure responsibilities and revenue authority. Market-based instruments such as Local Government Financing Vehicles, Special Bonds, and infrastructure REITs each emerged to bridge this gap. Affordable rental housing REITs (ARH-REITs), listed on the Shanghai and Shenzhen exchanges between 2022 and 2024, are the latest iteration of such instruments.

Existing scholarship interprets ARH-REITs through spatial fix, state entrepreneurialism, and state-led financialisation. These frameworks capture the state's intent to manage expanding governmental debts but still treat the state as a unitary actor. How market-based instruments are captured and mediated within the vertical relations of multi-level governance remains unexamined.

This paper investigates the ownership structure of all eight ARH-REITs issued to date, tracing subscribers to their ultimate controlling entities. The findings reveal a dominant ownership concentration by the state-owned system and patterns inconsistent with expected market-based allocative distributions. These patterns suggest that a coordinated flow of state-owned capital drives these ARH-REITs, rather than capital from the free market. The paper then argues that the entire apparatus of ARH-REITs, including its legal forms, disclosure regimes, and equity structures, has been captured and appropriated by multi-level government for vertical fiscal governance.

The paper contributes to financialisation theory by questioning its conventional narrative: financialisation, conventionally theorised as financial logic penetrating other domains, is here subordinated to intrastate fiscal control and hollowed out of its market-based allocative functions. This inversion suggests that the very institutional forms produced by financialisation to penetrate other domains have now become objects of institutional capture and alienation by powers beyond the reach of financial markets.

Alternate trajectories: the past, present and future role of homeownership in Australian housing policy

Tom Alves

Australia's postwar housing policy had the dual objectives of expanding access to homeownership and increasing the provision of public affordable rental housing. The aim of both was economic security and social stability. Throughout most of the 20th Century, Australia enjoyed one of the highest rates of owner-occupation in the world (>70%), while social rental housing peaked at little more than 5% of total stock nationally, despite sustained investment over almost three decades.

By the end of the century, homeownership was in decline (in marked contrast to most European states), and social housing was already on the way to becoming residualised. In line with the conference theme, Homeownership, Prosperity, and Inequality in the 21st Century, this paper will examine the changing role and focus of homeownership in Australian housing policy since the late 1990s and what this has meant for the wider housing system. Maintaining broad access to homeownership is still widely assumed to be the primary ambition of national housing policy, yet the strategic design and targeting of policies to achieve this has been lacking.

Over the last twenty-five years, policy has sought mainly to ameliorate the impacts of the broader shift towards prioritising the investment value of housing—notably intergenerational and income inequality—often with the unintended consequence of exacerbating these further. In the absence of adequate social provision, private rental has become the de facto second tenure but offers limited protections or security for

households. The paper will consider the potential impact of recent policy developments, whether a return to widespread owner-occupation is desirable or achievable, and options for how this might be implemented. Another, less explored aspect of changing tenure patterns in Australia, to be addressed in this paper, is the relationship this has to the processes of housing development, typology and urban form.

Conflicting ideas of a right to housing – a document analysis of universal and selective tendencies in the Norwegian housing policy

Mina Benjegård

UiT (the Arctic University of Norway)

This article analyses the contemporary development of the Norwegian housing policy and its implications for how the right to housing is upheld. Globally, the right to housing has increasingly been put under pressure through deregulation and financialization processes, when housing's role as a commodity is prioritized over housing's role as a human right (Rolnik 2013; Aalbers 2016, OHCHR No Year). As housing is generally provided by the market, the state's ability to ensure people's right to housing is done through corrections of the market (Bengtsson 2001).

It is thus necessary to understand how the policy of state corrections is designed to understand how the right to housing is ensured. By following Bengtsson (2001), the right to housing is operationalized into ideal types of a universal housing policy, aiming at the whole population, or a selective housing policy, aiming at specific groups. Norway is a relevant case for analysing housing policy design and change as a previous, universally oriented housing policy based on ownership "for all" was exchanged for a selective housing policy from the 1980's, directed towards a small segment of the population entitled to social housing (Nordahl 2012; Stamsø 2008; Annaniassen 2013). Questions are today raised about the existing housing policy due to difficulties entering the Norwegian ownership market (Gitmark 2021; Prosser 2020). By analysing public investigations and policy documents on housing over a period of 25 years (2001-2026) the article presents how the idea of a right to housing is perceived both between document types and over time.

By this, an understanding of how policy ideas may coexist, interact and change beyond the divide of the universal and selective ideal types is presented. This contributes to a more detailed understanding of the status of the Norwegian housing policy relevant for understanding how it can meet existing housing challenges.

Contested governance reordering: Spain's 2023 Housing Law, regional polarisation and the limits of state-centred analysis

Iago Martínez Durán

University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain)

Recent scholarship has identified a paradigm crisis in European housing policy, marked by challenges to neoliberal consensus and moves towards more interventionist frameworks. Spain's 2023 Housing Law — the first state-level housing legislation, reintroducing rent controls and expanded affordability obligations — is a significant expression. Yet state-centred analyses obscure equally consequential dynamics: how a policy shift is provoking a contested reordering of housing governance across a decentralised, plurinational state with an already differentiated regional landscape.

This paper argues the post-2023 landscape is best understood through this contested governance reordering. The state-level breakthrough has attempted to reassert central competencies where primary housing authority is regional, triggered counter-responses from right-governed ones, and opened spaces for local governments to emerge as distinct policy actors, in some cases because regions devolved initiative and political risk to the municipal level.

The result is accelerating internal differentiation, building on pre-existing regional divergences, whose overall balance remains an open empirical question. Drawing on multi-scalar policy analysis — central and sub-national legislative instruments, judicial rulings, local plans and rent control declarations, as well as statistical evidence — the paper examines how state policies embed deliberate reordering strategies; how polarisation has produced a governance divide between implementing and blocking regions; and how local governments, even in medium-sized cities, have begun constructing distinctive housing agendas.

The paper contributes to comparative debates by demonstrating that moving beyond state-centred analysis changes the substantive diagnosis, and by proposing contested governance reordering as a lens that captures dynamics paradigm-focused approaches miss in decentralised multi-level housing systems.

A Safety Net for the Advantaged? The Impact of Demand-side Rental Assistance on Housing Inequality in Shanghai

Qianwen Li

Division of Geography and Tourism, KU Leuven

This study moves beyond asset-based inequality to examine inequality of housing disadvantage within Shanghai's private rental sector, employing a mixed-method design that combines survey data and in-depth interviews. Methodologically, it advances measurement of housing inequality by complementing the current cumulative housing disadvantage framework with explicit consideration of locational choices. Theoretically, it develops a capital-based explanation for how access to demand-side rental assistance—including tax relief, housing subsidies, and the Housing Provident Fund—is structured, revealing systematic mismatches between the groups of cumulative housing disadvantage and the actual beneficiaries of policy support.

Findings indicate that such assistance flows disproportionately to individuals with greater economic, cultural, and social capital, whereas tenants lacking economic capital are often excluded by employment-linked eligibility criteria and administrative barriers. The unspoken age biases in policy design also overlook the disadvantages faced by mid-to-older tenants, who often face heightened life-course and intergenerational pressures. The study argues that current demand-side rental assistance functions not as an effective safety net for the housing disadvantages, but rather as a secondary distribution system for capital holders that reinforces existing inequalities. It concludes by calling for more inclusive policy design that accounts for tenant heterogeneity and life-course disparities, and that actively addresses the structural biases within the current rental assistance framework.

Private Rented Markets

The Role of Digital Platforms in Amsterdam's Private Rental Market

Meghan Flood

Utrecht University

Housing systems across the globe have become increasingly mediated by platforms. As housing has become a well of asset-based financial capital (Fields, 2018), platforms have integrated themselves into private rental markets to (Nethercote, 2023;

Wainwright, 2023). In Amsterdam, the Netherlands, digital platforms are heavily embedded into the private rental market, from platforms which advertise the rent of properties, to AI tools which scrape the web and send alerts to customers' nearly at the moment an ad is online, to Facebook or WhatsApp groups facilitating exchange of flat-share arrangements. While digital platforms are used by many, those at the 'bottom end' of the market use digital platforms as tools to reduce their housing precarity (Maalsen, 2020).

Recent scholarship on digital platforms and the private rental market is shown that platforms increase access to and availability of informal housing arrangements (Maalsen et al., 2022; Shrestha et al., 2021). Such informal arrangements are done in an attempt to increase stability in their housing situation (Hilbrandt, 2021; Maalsen et al., 2022; Ronald et al., 2024). Through qualitative investigation into use of digital platforms by private rental and/or informal dwellers, this project is concerned with the role of digital platforms in Amsterdam's private rental market, approaching the topic from the conceptual framing of housing precarity and housing informality.

Building off of research in Platform Real Estate (e.g., Fields, 2022; Fields & Rogers, 2021), urban informality (e.g., Roy, 2005), and society, science and technology studies (e.g., Bratton, 2015; Van Doorn et al., 2021), as well as wider critical housing studies scholarship of housing precarity (e.g., Dotsey & Chiodelli, 2021; Lombard, 2023; Waldron, 2022) this presentation details a conceptual approach to housing informality which understands the platform as a tool for reducing housing precarity and a negotiating actor in housing informality.

Does Institutional Build to Rent Deliver? Ownership, Amenity, and Resident Experience in England's Private Rented Sector

Yang Wang

CaCHE, University Of Glasgow

Nicola Livingstone

UK Collaborative Centre For Housing Evidence (CaCHE), University of Glasgow

Philip O'Brien

UK Collaborative Centre For Housing Evidence (CaCHE), University of Glasgow

Across Europe, the institutionalisation of private rental housing has accelerated as large-scale, professionally managed residential investment vehicles enter urban markets long dominated by small-scale landlords. In England, Build to Rent (BtR),

purpose-built, institutionally financed rental development, represents one of the most significant tenure transformations of the past decade. Proponents claim it raises management standards and stabilises the Private Rented Sector (PRS); critics raise concerns about affordability, market segmentation, and the exclusion of lower-income renters. Yet independent evidence on how institutional landlordism reshapes local rental markets and landlord–tenant relations remain limited.

Drawing on a Nationwide Foundation-funded research project, this paper examines BtR's local market impacts in London and Manchester, England's two largest BtR markets with contrasting development trajectories and affordability pressures. The project employs a mixed-methods design combining spatial mapping of BtR supply and development pipelines, longitudinal rental trend analysis, large-scale resident experience data, policy review, and interviews with developers, operators, planners and residents. Three interrelated questions structure the paper: how does BtR alter housing dynamics and affordability within local PRS markets? How does institutional management reshape landlord–tenant relations and perceptions of value for money? And to what extent does BtR expand or constrain housing access across income groups?

Early findings point to meaningful variation in resident outcomes between institutionally owned and other professionally managed developments, particularly in management quality and amenity provision, though more nuanced on value-for-money. The paper interrogates whether institutional landlordism delivers genuine improvements for renters or a spatially concentrated premium, with implications for tenure inequality and PRS policy in Europe.

Mixed Tenure in Ireland: policy and practice

David Silke

The Housing Agency, Ire

The paper will focus on the experience of mixed tenure in the Irish context. For many years, Ireland had a very high proportion of home ownership which resulted in a tendency towards tenure segregation. In recent years, the growth of private rental and social and affordable housing options has resulted in an increased interest in mixed tenure.

The paper will review the literature on mixed tenure and trace the policy shift towards an increased emphasis on its value in the Irish context. Drawing on the literature, it will discuss how mixed tenure is defined in Ireland. The paper will outline the role of the State in achieving tenure mix, particularly through funding of social and affordable housing (including cost rental) and regeneration projects. It will explore the links

between tenure mix and income mix and will conclude with a discussion of the role of diversity in achieving socially sustainable communities.

Sleeping on the Edge: Furnishing Quality in the UK Private Rented Sector, Sleep Inequality, and Mental Health — Emerging Findings and a Research Agenda

Tom Simcock

University of Huddersfield

Housing is recognised as a social determinant of health, yet research and regulation have focused predominantly on structural hazards such as damp, cold, and overcrowding. The material interiors of privately rented homes, particularly furnished accommodation, remain largely absent from healthy homes discourse.

This paper presents emerging findings from a scoping review examining relationships between private-rented housing, furnishing quality, sleep environments, and mental health in the UK. Across public health and sleep research, strong evidence links adverse housing conditions to poor sleep quality, and sleep disturbance is consistently associated with depression, anxiety, and psychological strain. Reviews further demonstrate that indoor environmental factors such as thermal comfort, ventilation, and noise affect mental wellbeing and can be modified to reduce health inequalities. However, housing quality is typically conceptualised at the dwelling or structural level, with little attention to furnishings, including mattress condition, despite their central role in supporting rest and recovery. Preliminary mapping indicates that furnishing quality and sleep-specific environments are rarely operationalised in housing research, and links to economic participation are seldom examined.

The paper outlines a research agenda to investigate furnishing standards, tenant experiences, sleep as a mediating pathway, and implications for housing-related mental health inequalities in the UK.

Beyond Conflict: Balancing Landlord Protection and Tenant Security to Unlock Affordable Housing in Croatia

Marko Horvat

University of Zagreb, Faculty of Law

Across Europe, housing affordability is increasingly shaped by what happens in rental markets rather than by access to homeownership. This is particularly visible in post-socialist countries, where rental housing has remained somewhat neglected in policy terms, even though market rental housing clearly outweighs subsidised options. In Croatia, the private rental sector is still weakly institutionalised and marked by fragmented regulation and widespread informal contracts, which creates uncertainty for both landlords and tenants. Many landlords are hesitant to rent out their properties on a long-term basis. They often point to concerns about rent collection, lengthy procedures in case of disputes, and a general lack of trust in enforcement mechanisms. At the same time, tenants frequently enter informal agreements, even when this limits their access to certain social rights such as housing allowances or transport subsidies. This combination of legal ambiguity, limited enforcement and informality reduces transparency and keeps the supply of rental housing constrained.

This paper explores the institutional and socio-economic factors that discourage long-term renting in Croatia. It focuses on three main questions: how landlords perceive risks in the rental market; how tenants navigate an insecure and often informal system; and what lessons can be drawn from EU countries that have managed to balance landlord protection with tenant security. The research is based on semi-structured interviews conducted in several Croatian cities, combined with a comparative review of selected European rental models.

By placing the Croatian case in a broader European context, the paper reflects on how institutional arrangements shape rental market outcomes and housing inequality, and outlines possible policy directions to strengthen legal certainty and tenure security.

Airbnb, Financialisation, and Evictions in Ireland: The 2020-21 Eviction Ban

Evan Carron-Kee

The Economic and Social Research Institute

At the centre of the political conflict over Short-Term Rental (STR) platforms is the claim that such platforms displace renters from their homes. However, no research has yet causally connected STR growth to large-scale displacement.

To investigate STR displacement in practice, I focus on a unique case study: the lifting of the covid-19 eviction ban in Ireland in 2021. I first describe how STRs benefit from and contribute to housing financialization and commodification, enabling accumulation for property-owners through the dispossession of tenants. I connect this to Ireland's turn

towards 'crisis post-neoliberalism' in housing policy since the Great Financial Crisis (Byrne 2024).

Under this framework, I argue that an STR rent gap opened after the covid-19 pandemic due to the recovery of tourist demand. This incentivised landlords to switch to the STR market, evicting their tenants in the process. As an empirical test of this argument, I exploit a natural experiment created in Ireland by the lifting of the covid-19 eviction ban.

Using a difference-in-differences approach, I find causal evidence that landlords evicted tenants to convert their properties to STRs. I estimate that between 500 and 2000 properties were converted. These properties were more likely to be in rural areas, in vulnerable Irish-language communities, and in areas without STR or rent regulations.

These findings provide empirical support for critiques which see STRs as a mechanism for the assetisation of housing and 'accumulation by dispossession' (Gil 2023). They also highlight the importance of expanding research on STRs to the national scale, with attention to impacts on rural areas as well as cities. References: Byrne, Michael. 2024. "Post-Neoliberalization and the Irish Private Rental Sector." *Housing Studies* 39(7): 1658–77. Gil, Javier. 2023. "Not Gentrification, Not Touristification: Short-Term Rentals as a Housing Assetisation Strategy." *Journal of Urban Affairs* 46: 1–21.

Addressing affordability needs and eco-renovation for the most precarious people in the private rental sector : the case of rental intermediation

Lola Vives
ENSEIS

Tofie Briscolini,
Lyon III, EVS

Housing production from existing buildings is a central issue to address homeless and poor housed needs. Currently, policy instruments to develop private rental and energy renovation appear as essential to address poor housing and homelessness in France. Our sociological research focuses on rental intermediation organizations associated with measures to support energy renovation work.

Those organizations are characterized by the intermediary function they play in managing relationship between landlords and occupiers as well as in the housing maintenance and renovation. So far there has been little discussion about intermediation organizations although they provide great analysis perspectives to understand how the private rented sector could be made available and renovate for the most precarious people.

Our presentation aims to characterize the role of the people who work as rental manager with “supportive landlords” and occupiers with social issues. How do they reach out and convince landlords to lend to poor people? What are the mains tasks during their daily work? What are the mains issues they encounter? And how do they respond to them? How do they interact with occupiers?

This presentation aims at providing a qualitative analysis (interview and documentary study) of the stakeholders’ system to a better understand the local market in two French departments according to distinctive territorial features (urban, midsized-city, rural area).

In the end, our proposal aims to share our analysis about how intermediation organizations, in conjunction with measures to support energy renovation work, are implemented to reduce housing inequalities with the support of private renters.

The Relationship Between Local Rental Market Ownership Concentration and Rent

Benjamin Preis

Urban Research Advisors

Over the last 30 years, the rental housing industry in the United States has seen a shift towards larger landlords who more often take a corporate form. At the same time, rental prices have continued to increase at a rapid pace.

This study examines the relationship between concentration of ownership of rental units and rent levels and rent changes. It uses rental registry data from seven large American cities — Boston; Columbus; Dallas; Kansas City; Minneapolis; Seattle; and Washington, DC. It first links disparate owners using machine learning software trained to group landlords based on similar names, related addresses, and additional information. It then calculates the level of concentration at a variety of geographical scales. At the city scale, rental markets are not particularly concentrated. However, all cities studied have postal codes, census tracts, and elementary school boundaries that have high levels of concentration. Using rent data from a variety of sources, it finds that higher levels of ownership concentration at the postal code scale are associated with higher levels of asking rents. Additionally, it uses a shift-share instrument to identify the effect of higher levels of concentration on changes in rent, when accounting for city-wide income shocks. It finds that higher levels of concentration likely lead to higher gross paid rents.

This research furthers our understanding of rental markets in the United States, pointing towards concerning levels of concentration in some urban neighbourhoods, and their impacts on asking and actual rents.

A Room of One's Own? Students coping with Milan's neoliberal private housing market

Giuliana Costa

Politecnico di Milano

Tommaso Frangioni

Politecnico di Milano

This paper investigates the housing pathways of off-site university students renting an apartment in Milan. Analysing students' housing needs involves an understanding of their transitions to 'adulthood' (Christie et al. 2002) and to autonomy while striving the

private housing market. In particular, we will focus here on two aspects: first, the material and emotional hustle and bustle attached to the process of searching for accommodation and secondly, on the relationship developed between co-resident students.

The process of looking for an apartment is only apparently a mundane task. It involves developing a relationship with an imagined territory, as the process often begins well before landing in the host city, seeking information through different channels, doing the intensive “leg- work” connected to combing rental agencies to find some opportunity, as well as the emotional work connected to staging the performance of the ‘good tenant’ (Power and Gillon 2022). The ‘hidden curriculum’ (Sotomayor et al. 2022), i.e. the set of uncodified skills that students need to acquire to cope with a neoliberal housing market, is showed and discussed in our case study, helping to identify the collective dynamics through which access and living in a students’ house is continuously negotiated. Sharing an apartment or a house is as a strategy to reduce costs associated with housing but can also be viewed as a lifestyle choice (Maalsen 2020).

However, in the context of the everyday neoliberalist rent extractivism, students often experience a forced privatization of housing due to the “roomification” (Frangioni & Costa 2024) of dwelling. Apartments are subdivided into rooms which become the only “legitimate” space to stay and take care of, while common spaces are reduced to an architectural waste. This is an important source of conflicts between tenants but can also be seen as a space of solidarity and bonding, where tenants are allied in an everyday fight against inhospitality.

Milan Inside Out. (Un)affordability and precarity in the rental market of the attractive city and its urban region

Lorenzo Caresana

Massimo Bricocoli (DASStU, Politecnico of Milan)

Marco Peverini

DASStU, Politecnico of Milan, Politecnico di Milano

In Milan, the widening gap between salaries and housing costs is deepening an affordability crisis (Bricocoli & Peverini, 2024). The rising unaffordability of homeownership, and changes in the social and economic structure, have resulted in a context in which renting – or relocating outside the main city – seems the only viable option for many low- to middle-income households. This pattern reflects the European debate on generation rent, which links the contraction of ownership pathways and the

expansion of insecure rental forms toward broader changes in the political economy of housing (Howard, 2025).

Drawing on the research of OCA (Housing Affordability Observatory: www.oca.milano.it), this contribution investigates conditions of access to housing through the private rented market in Milan and its urban region. The findings highlight both the depth of the affordability crisis in the urban region, where commuting costs erode most of the savings related to lower rents, and the parallel precarization of the rental market in the main city. While a recent local reform of the voluntary rent moderation scheme (*canone concordato*) nominally extends access to regulated rents, its mitigating capacity is rapidly eroding as price differentials with the free market are narrowing. At the same time, the expansion of temporary rental forms – student contracts, mid-term and short-term rentals – is eroding the share of new long-term contracts, compressing contract durations, inducing precarity, and reducing tenant security.

Interviews with local authorities reveal a shared perception of “playing in defence” in relation to the central city’s processes and policy strategies. By integrating quantitative data on rents and incomes across more than 330 municipalities with qualitative insights from civil servants, landlords’ associations, and tenant unions, this paper aims to contribute to the public and academic debate around the affordability and precarity crisis in European cities.

Monopoly power in build to rent: contesting affordability narratives in Australia and UK build to rent housing

Alice Earley

University of Glasgow

Private rental housing across UK and Australia has in recent decades come to be dominated by fragmented small scale landlords. Recent years has seen the emergence of a build to rent sector in response to shifting multiple market and policy dynamics. BTR has been proposed as a solution to many problems that exist in the fragmented private rental sector where decisions over maintenance, quality, rent, timing of resales are all mediated by thousands of amateur landlords. BTR landlords by contrast concentrate decision making into singular notionally professionalized entities. This concentrated power and decision making has been so far under explored.

Focusing on Glasgow in UK and Sydney in Australia, this paper will explore three emergent themes in built-to-rent housing and implication for private rental markets in each context. First, the geography of rent has seen a focus on high value housing

markets, with rents concentrated at the premium end. Second, feasibility and valuation methods place considerable emphasis on rent escalation, and simultaneously intense focus on operating costs. Third, holding periods and investment time frames measured in years, not decades, are critical aspect of investment strategies.

Cumulatively this paper argues that BTR introduces a monopoly power into both rent pricing and management dynamics that potentially sits at odds with claimed benefits of this model. In aggregate, this paper explores whether many of the assumed benefits of BTR may generate unintended market consequences may arise for tenants and the market.

Does Financialization Push Up Rents? Evidence from Pricing Mechanism in Shanghai's Private Rental Sector

Qianwen Li

Division of Geography and Tourism, KU Leuven

This paper investigates how financialization impacts rent levels and pricing mechanisms in Shanghai's private rental sector (PRS), offering both methodological and conceptual advancements in understanding landlord behaviours. Drawing on a city-wide dataset of 49,698 rental listings from Lianjia, we develop a validated operational approach to distinguish financialized and non-financialized landlords by tracing their capital sources and business models. Conceptually, we propose a framework that identifies the core motives and strategies of different landlord types, offering new insights into the differentiated market impacts of financialized corporate landlords (FCLs).

Our findings reveal two key dynamics. First, financial capital has been mobilized into the rental sector through a combination of state-led incentives, institutional investment, and innovative financing extended to non-financial firms. Second, Within this landscape, asset-light FCLs dominate, using economies of scale and market consolidation strategies to rapidly expand. These landlords often drive rent inflation by pricing premiums into structural housing features, such as design and amenities, rather than location. In contrast, asset-heavy developments—although slower to scale due to capital intensity and regulatory constraints—benefit from state support and rent caps (e.g., under the ARH program), resulting in generally lower rents. However, they still capture premiums through locational advantages, reflecting long-term asset appreciation goals.

These findings carry critical policy implications. To foster a more equitable PRS, it is necessary to address the risks of monopoly through inclusive financing mechanisms and to introduce targeted demand-side subsidies. Such measures can better protect

vulnerable tenant groups affected by increasingly strategic rent-setting practices in financialized rental markets.

Platform informality: a typology of online rental housing providers

Nicole Gurran

University of Sydney

Zahra Nasreen

Macquarie University

Pranita Shrestha

University of Sydney

With rising rental precarity and the platformisation of housing markets, alternative and informal accommodation providers have emerged. This paper reports on research efforts to understand these providers who target lower income earners, students, and new migrants via various online platforms offering rooms, share rooms, and other forms of non-standard rental housing.

Using time series data from the dominant shared housing platform in Australia, 'Flatmates.com.au', we focus on advertisements seeking or offering shared accommodation in the nation's most expensive three cities: Sydney, Melbourne and Brisbane, to identify a typology of providers ranging from self-organised households or owner occupiers offering space in their own homes, through to licensed or unlicensed commercial operators. In charting this typology we examine potential differences in the types of accommodation offered, rental costs and inclusions, duration of tenure offered, and target market.

Our study sheds light on changing trends in the provision of informal and share accommodation, particularly as it is occurring within the existing dwelling stock in contrast to the emerging purpose built student and co-housing markets. However, data limitations reflect the broader challenges of monitoring online rental practices which are concealed by opaque digital platforms. We conclude that better understanding the range of providers and their motivations and practices is critical to enforcing existing regulatory standards and tenant rights in this crucial but precarious sector of the rental market.

PRICE FORMATION OF FREE MARKET RENTS IN THE NETHERLANDS AND THE ROLE OF INSTITUTIONAL INVESTORS AND GOVERNMENT REGULATION

Erwin Evers

TU Delft / Vesteda

This paper analyses the determinants of rent developments in the Dutch free market rental sector and the role of institutional investors in price formation. Building on a mixed-methods study, it combines long-term time-series data on contractual rents (1960–2022), short-term data on market rents at tenant turnover (2016–2022), and macro-economic indicators, with in-depth interviews and a survey-based multi-criteria decision analysis.

The findings show that long-term contractual rents have risen moderately, largely following inflation due to rent regulation, while market rents in the liberalised segment have grown significantly faster, driven by scarcity and investors' pricing strategies. Institutional investors do not simply maximise rents, but balance financial returns, risk, ESG objectives and reputational considerations. Recent regulatory changes, especially the extension of rent controls to the mid-market, compress yields and have already altered investment behaviour. The paper discusses the policy paradox between affordability and supply and the relation to investment decisions.

Residential Context of Heath

Homelessness, older people's wellbeing and the role of support
services: Evidence from a longitudinal survey in Australia

Ngoc Thao Nguyen

Griffith University

Christopher Ambrey

Griffith University

Aims: This study aims to investigate the relationship between homelessness and older people's subjective and objective wellbeing. The study also examines how the relationship between subjective wellbeing and older homelessness is moderated by

support services. Methods: We use data from six waves of the Journeys Home, a longitudinal Australian survey which follows a nationally representative sample of people vulnerable to, at risk of, or experiencing homelessness. A key advantage of the Journeys Home dataset is that it is not limited to individuals who are currently homeless or to specific subgroups of the homeless population. This enables the ability to compare wellbeing of people experiencing homelessness with those who are not. Data will be analysed using panel data methods.

Approach: This study draws on the capability approach and the socio-ecological model as its theoretical frameworks. Two alternative definitions of homelessness are applied: literal and cultural. Literal homelessness refers to sleeping rough or staying in crisis accommodation, while cultural homelessness refers to those lacking access to accommodation that meets minimum community standards. Subjective wellbeing is measured using life satisfaction and domain-specific life satisfaction. Objective wellbeing measures include income, financial hardship, health, frequency in contacts with family, and frequency in contacts with friends.

Does how you rent matter for health? Interrogating within-tenure inequality in the private rented sector

Amy Clair

Adelaide University

Emma Baker

Adelaide University

Sha Liu

Adelaide University

Evidence suggests that living in the private rented sector (PRS) is associated with poorer health compared to other tenures in post-homeownership societies such as the UK and Australia. However, the PRS is not homogenous, and experiences within the sector vary. Given the increasing role of the PRS in housing more people for longer periods, understanding these within tenure differences is important for identifying how to ensure the best possible outcomes for private renters. One major cleavage in the sector is between those that rent directly from the owners of the home and those that rent via a letting/real estate agent.

This paper reports on differences in terms of housing conditions, affordability, and impact on health for private renters depending on whether they rent directly from a

landlord or via an agent, comparing results from Australia and the UK. Initial results from Australia suggest that conditions, affordability, and impact on health are worse for those who rent via an agent compared to those renting from a landlord directly. These results are a potential challenge to policy approaches that emphasise the professionalisation of private renting as a means of improving conditions for renters, e.g. recent emphasis on Build to Rent.

This paper will investigate whether the identified differences reflect composition effects or are characteristic of the rental approaches, and whether insights from these findings can be used to inform policy to raise standards and improve health for all private renters.

Virtual reality as a tool for representing urban design alternatives: A multi-methodological simulation validity test

Terry Hartig

Institute for Housing and Urban Research (IBF)
Uppsala University, Sweden

Páll Jakob Lindal

Center for Analysis and Design of Intelligent Agents, Reykjavik University, Iceland

Kamilla Rún Jóhannsdóttir

Department of Psychology, Reykjavik University, Iceland

Hannes Högni Vilhjálmsson

Center for Analysis and Design of Intelligent Agents, Reykjavik University, Iceland

Methods to fairly and accurately present environmental design alternatives to affected publics have important practical value. Immersive virtual reality technology offers advantages over widely used means such as architect renderings and aerial photos, but validation in terms of similarity to the experiences one would come to have in the actual environment remains an important need.

We conducted a simulation validity test by comparing responses to a multi-use urban area slated for residential densification as presented in situ or with immersive virtual reality. We framed the responses in terms of restorative quality, a basic concern in residential contexts. Forty-four adult residents of Reykjavik, Iceland provided affective, cognitive and physiological data during an initial stress/mental fatigue induction procedure and then during a period for restoration involving actual or simulated

movement through the area. The virtual simulation was a close visual and spatial approximation of the existing site, and our analyses focused on the similarity of restorative responses in situ versus in the virtual environment.

Small effect sizes for many of the contrasts indicated similarity in responding and encourage the use of virtual reality in anticipating restorative responses to residential environments that do not yet exist; however, more substantial differences in some contrasts indicate a need for caution.

"Cold, but Not Equally Cold": Socio-thermal Stratification in Beijing's Heating Season

Yuan Gao

The University of Hong Kong

Shenjing He

Department of Urban Planning and Design, HKU

While climate change brings more frequent, intense temperature extremes, the critical issue of indoor thermal comfort and winter cold's unequal burden remains largely understudied. This study investigates how thermal inequality is produced and experienced in Beijing, revealing cold exposure as a result of socio-thermal stratification driven by housing, infrastructure, and structural factors.

Using a mixed-method approach—combining continuous indoor temperature monitoring of 34 households and in-depth interviews—we examine thermal discomfort's lived experience across housing types. Findings highlight a stark “thermal fault line” driven by housing typology and tenure status. Residents in marginalized housing (e.g., huiqian apartments, self-built dwellings) endure a significant “thermal penalty”, with indoor temperatures consistently 2-3°C lower than in commodity or employer-provided housing. This occurs despite incurring exorbitant energy costs (1,000-3,000 RMB per winter) due to thermally inefficient conditions. Vulnerability is exacerbated by tenure status and structural constraints: renters face a “double bind”—beyond trading commuting for rent, they now face an emergent trade-off between energy expenditure and health risks especially during cold spells, limited by their inability to modify housing and thus suffer from cold living environment.

We argue that poor housing acts as an infrastructural “lock-in”, reinforcing socio-thermal stratification by preventing vulnerable residents from adapting to extreme temperature fluctuations. Thermal comfort is not a personal choice but structurally constrained by home materiality and systemic barriers limiting residents' ability to

address deficiencies. This research urges climate adaptation policies to move beyond technological fixes, addressing fundamental housing inequities and structural mechanisms that perpetuate socio-thermal stratification in megacities.

Living and Heating: The Body at Stake What Health Literacy in Housing Reveals through Home Automation

Yaneira Wilson

ENSAPVS

Yankel Fijalkow

ENSAPVS – CRH

Health in housing has long been addressed through a hygienist perspective focused on preventing disease by combating unsanitary conditions. Today, however, public health policies increasingly promote a model of individual health for all, transforming both their objectives and the ways in which everyday practices are governed. This shift introduces micro-politics that normalize bodies and behaviours, revealing tensions between efficiency, comfort and well-being.

This paper explores how a critical approach to health literacy, applied to the domestic environment, helps to better understand a central everyday practice: thermal regulation, with or without the use of home automation technologies. By articulating bodies, norms and residents' narratives, the paper conceptualizes housing as a situated space of health, shaped by technical devices and symbolic meanings mobilized by inhabitants. The growing domotization of housing appears as a revealing socio-technical and political field in which these tensions become visible.

Drawing on the SAPHIR research project, the analysis is based on around forty in-depth individual and collective interviews conducted in different types of apartment buildings and single-family homes across varied forms of housing tenure. Keywords: Health literacy; Housing; Thermal regulation; Home automation; Body.

The Affordability Apex in Housing and Health

Emma Baker

Housing affordability is usually treated as one housing problem among many, alongside poor dwelling conditions, insecurity, overcrowding and instability. This paper argues instead that affordability occupies a more central place in housing–health relationships.

Affordability structures access to tenure, neighbourhood, dwelling quality and residential stability, and in doing so organises patterned exposure to health risks across populations and over time.

Drawing on international evidence, the paper reframes housing affordability as a foundational mechanism through which housing systems distribute opportunity, constraint and vulnerability. This paper reviews how affordability has been conceptualised and measured, from conventional cost-to-income ratios and the Australian 30/40 rule to residual and subjective approaches, and highlights the importance of understanding affordability as a dynamic exposure rather than a static condition. It then synthesises evidence on health effects, showing that the clearest and most consistent associations are with mental health, particularly psychological distress, anxiety and depressive symptoms, while evidence for physical health effects is emerging but less direct.

The paper further examines the pathways linking affordability and health, with particular attention to chronic financial strain, material deprivation, expenditure trade-offs, residential instability, tenure insecurity, and constrained access to health-supportive homes and neighbourhoods. The central argument is that affordability should not be viewed simply as an economic metric or background context for other housing problems. Rather, it is a key organising dimension of the residential context of health – an apex determinant. Addressing housing-related health inequalities therefore requires policy attention not only to housing quality and standards, but to the structural production and distribution of affordable housing itself.

Multi-stage Causal Mechanism of Housing Need Formation

Jiachen Niu

Housing is a fundamental carrier of human survival and development, yet the mismatch between housing supply and demand remains prominent worldwide. A key reason is that both practice and existing studies have largely focused on the observable outcomes of housing demand while neglecting housing need as the core underlying psychological process, thereby reversing the logical order of analysis.

In response, this study takes the formation mechanism of housing need as its central scientific question and focuses on individual housing need as the research object. We posit that housing need arises from a neuropsychological mapping of basic needs onto housing, proposes a novel “Need Frustration-Housing Tool” mapping hypothesis, and establishes a multimodal integrated research paradigm that combines neuropsychological experiments, behavioural experiments, and structural equation modelling to investigate the multi-stage causal mechanism underlying the formation of

housing need. Specifically, the mechanism involves four stages: (1) housing-related factors trigger frustration of basic needs; (2) basic need frustration activates multiple tool schemas; (3) competition among tool schemas leads to housing-oriented decision-making; and (4) housing tools provide feedback to basic needs.

The study is expected to generate an original triangulated evidence chain linking neural circuits, psychological mechanisms, and behavioural motivations, thereby validating the mapping hypothesis and clarifying the multi-stage causal mechanism of housing need formation. The core contribution lies in opening the theoretical “grey box” of housing need, filling the micro-theoretical gap in housing demand theory and in the practice of “good housing”.

By re-establishing human needs as the fundamental logical starting point, the study provides a theoretical foundation for shifting the housing field from a material-oriented perspective toward a human-centered approach, with significant theoretical and practical ...

Beyond Affordability: Neurodiversity, Sensory Environments, and Hidden Inequalities in Housing

Paulina Neisch

City University of Hong Kong

Housing environments are typically designed around normative assumptions of perception and sensory tolerance. For neurodivergent populations, particularly autistic individuals, residential environments may generate significant sensory stress through factors such as noise transmission, lighting conditions, spatial density, and other environmental stimuli.

These characteristics can affect emotional regulation, comfort, and the ability to fully inhabit and use domestic and residential spaces. Despite growing attention to accessibility in housing and planning, the sensory and cognitive dimensions of residential environments remain largely overlooked.

This paper introduces the concept of sensory inequality, arguing that the sensory characteristics of housing environments can produce forms of spatial exclusion that extend beyond conventional understandings of accessibility. The study explores how built residential environments shape sensory experience and perceived comfort among autistic adults.

The research combines spatial analysis of residential environments with physiological and perceptual measurements collected during exposure to different housing-related

spatial conditions. By linking environmental characteristics with emotional and physiological responses, the study identifies features of residential environments that may intensify or alleviate sensory stress.

The findings highlight how housing environments can inadvertently reproduce forms of spatial exclusion for neurodivergent residents. Recognizing sensory accessibility as a dimension of housing justice contributes to broader debates on inclusive housing and calls for greater attention to sensory conditions in residential design and housing policy.

Data-Driven Governance of Damp and Mould in Housing: A Comparative Study of the United Kingdom, Canada, and Japan

Yi-sheng Liu

Dampness and mould in residential housing are increasingly recognised as important environmental health risks and significant determinants of public health. As governments expand the use of housing inspections, environmental monitoring, and digital reporting systems, data-driven governance is playing a growing role in identifying and addressing housing-related health hazards.

These developments raise new regulatory questions regarding how environmental health data should be collected, managed, and used to protect residents' rights to healthy housing.

This article examines how damp and mould in housing are regulated in the United Kingdom, Canada, and Japan, focusing on the role of environmental health data in housing governance. It analyses national regulatory frameworks on housing standards, public health monitoring, and enforcement mechanisms, while drawing on urban examples from London, Toronto, and Tokyo to illustrate how these systems operate in practice. The comparison highlights differences in regulatory design, institutional responsibilities, and the integration of environmental health data into housing governance.

The article argues that while data-driven governance offers new opportunities to identify housing health risks, effective regulation of damp and mould requires stronger coordination between housing law, public health policy, and environmental data systems.

The effect of street greening on residents' mental health and well-being: evidence from a field experiment in London

Catalina Turcu

University College London

Ellen Grubbs

Bartlett School of Planning

Isabelle Sjøvall

Institute of Behavioural Neuroscience, Department of Experimental Psychology,
University College London (UCL)

Hugo Spiers

Institute of Behavioural Neuroscience, Department of Experimental Psychology,
University College London (UCL)

Urban areas increasingly incorporate nature into public spaces through initiatives such as street greening (Ye et al., 2019), sometimes as part of broader strategies to address climate risks and improve public health. As these efforts expand, interest is growing in how greenspace influences mental health and wellbeing – yet, despite widespread claims of greenspace benefits, objective evidence remains limited.

This paper examines the effects of greenspace on residents' mental health and wellbeing across two street redesign projects in North London, using before and after data. It draws on the Neurodesign Index (NDIX) developed by Sjøvall et al. (2025), which measures subjective wellbeing across six dimensions, and on Turcu et al.'s (2026) multi level spatial framework for urban field experiments. Surveys were conducted with more than 200 participants across four sites – the two redesigned streets and their controls – in March and September 2026. Findings show a positive correlation between new greenspace and subjective mental health and wellbeing. However, these benefits diminish when greenspace is perceived as poorly designed, low quality, or implemented without community involvement.

The paper argues that greenspace quality – not merely presence – is critical, and that design, scale, vegetation type, function, and resident engagement shape mental health and wellbeing outcomes.

Residential environments and people

Dweller - Dwelling Ecologies

Lidwine Spoormans

TU Delft

AnneMarie Eijkelenboom

Delft University of Technology

European programmes like Renovation Wave and HouseEurope! advocate shifting the focus to renovating existing stock. Although in renovation more values and resources are preserved, increasing comfort and energy-performance norms are not compromised. Houses are expected to continue fulfilling our needs. However, exceptions exist. Some inhabitants resist the desire for new and better and seem to accept alternative comfort levels. These include, e.g. people who continue an old family home and residential practice, inhabit a listed building with renovation restrictions, or otherwise live in a home with unusual living conditions. What can we learn from these 'birds of paradise', both from the homes and their inhabitants?

This research identifies key attributes in the relationship between dwellers and dwellings. It uses literature research, resident interviews and observations. Means-end theory is applied to identify housing attributes and affordances that fulfil residents' comfort values. The research adopts theories that regard comfort as a cultural and social construct, and as an achievement -how can dwellers make themselves comfortable- rather than a static quantifiable standard (Shove 2003).

Results indicate that alternative conditions demand deeper interaction between dweller and dwelling, as daily practices like cleaning, cooling or heating require more human effort and time. Adaptation occurs at building, behaviour or acceptance level. Attributes that compensate for alternative comfort levels include independence from systems and norms, valuing material and immaterial attributes, direct connection with nature, memories, architectural and family legacies. The residents' attitudes reveal varying standards of comfort, cleanliness, austerity and contentment. Questioning the prevailing narrative of rising comfort expectations, this paper explores how a more mutually beneficial ecology between dwelling and dweller can foster resourceful and resilient housing practices.

Cultivating Socio-Ecological Integrated Urban Housing through Cooperative Housing in Switzerland: The Significance of Collective Outdoor Spaces

Maryam Khatibi

Technical University of Munich

The study highlights the transformative capacity of collective open spaces in cooperative housing, serving as multifaceted socio-ecological environments tied to urban habitability. Cooperative housing involves collaborative organizational models emphasizing sustainability, residents' agency, and neighbourhood repair, linked to intentional socio-spatial sharing. However, the contribution of collective outdoor spaces associated with residential dwellings, particularly within cooperative housing contexts, is inadequately documented. To this end, the study investigates urban gardening through case studies of the Kalbreite and Westfeld cooperative housing projects in Zurich and Basel, Switzerland, highlighting the shift of residents from consumers to creators within the sharing infrastructure.

The guiding research question is: How do collective outdoor spaces within cooperative housing shape the possibilities for urban food gardening? Through onsite observations, stakeholder interviews, and desk studies, the socio-ecological synthesis of these arrangements is disclosed.

The thematic analysis identifies five key areas: concept definitions, barriers and enablers, characteristics of residential collective outdoor spaces as a multifunctional benchmark, inhabitants' participatory role, and a strategic urban planning tool influencing policy. Building on this, the data identifies the types and designs of collective residential outdoor spaces, along with the enabling and constraining factors and usage dynamics.

The findings, then, encompass a typology of collective outdoor spaces enhanced by collaborative socio-spatial proximity, reciprocal relationships among residents based on sufficiency, and urban gardening as forms of intentional, complementary socio-spatial spaces that set the agenda for sustainable housing development. Finally, space-efficient design integrating residential collective urban gardening can serve as a flexible instrument to redefine densification strategies.

Playing with place: from game-based exploration to residential attachment

Paulina Tobiasz-Lis

University of Lodz

Patrycja Grzys

University of Lodz

Residential attachment is often examined in relation to adult mobility decisions, housing satisfaction, and neighbourhood stability. Less attention has been paid to how attachment to residential environments is formed early in life through everyday spatial experiences.

This paper argues that playful, game-based engagement with the immediate neighbourhood can function as a mechanism of early residential socialisation, shaping how young residents perceive, value and relate to the places where they live. Building on experiences from the FACE UP OK (Factory Cities of Europe - United in Partnership, Opened for Kids) project in Lodz, we developed a school-based programme that supports pupils in co-creating location-based games focused on their nearest residential surroundings. Instead of transmitting knowledge about the city in a traditional instructional format, the programme invites children to explore streets, courtyards, housing blocks and local landmarks through problem-solving tasks, local quests and collaborative storytelling. In doing so, participants move from passive users of space to active interpreters of their neighbourhood environment.

The paper presents a pilot implemented in one primary school in Lodz, where pupils designed and tested a neighbourhood exploration game embedded in their everyday residential setting.

Drawing on workshop observations, children's outputs and feedback from teachers, we analyse how playful exploration influenced spatial awareness, sense of belonging and expressions of local pride. We argue that game-based neighbourhood exploration constitutes a replicable tool for strengthening residential attachment in urban contexts. By foregrounding children as co-producers of residential meaning, the study contributes to debates on residential environments, liveability and the social foundations of long-term neighbourhood stability.

Collective decision-making in private multi-apartment buildings: Evidence from a discrete choice experiment

Jan Frankowski

Institute for Structural Research/EUROREG, University of Warsaw

Jakub Sokolowski

Institute for Structural Research/University of Warsaw

Sona Stara

UCEEB, Czech Technical University in Prague

Richard Jedon

UCEEB, Czech Technical University in Prague

Aleksandra Prusak

Institute for Structural Research/University of Warsaw

Joanna Mazurkiewicz

Institute for Structural Research

In multi-apartment buildings, fragmented ownership requires residents to coordinate maintenance and renovation. This study examines how apartment owners evaluate trade-offs between the scale of investment benefits, required personal engagement, and decision-making rules in Poland and Czechia: two countries with distinct housing post-socialist transformation trajectories.

Using a discrete choice experiment with 7,500 residents of private multi-family buildings, we assess the relative importance of governance arrangements and examine how preferences vary across socio-demographic groups and between countries. Findings show that residents strongly value building-wide benefits and majority-based decision-making, while support for board-based governance is weak. Preferences are remarkably consistent across countries, highlighting structural patterns in resident perception rather than context-specific effects.

Results also reveal a preference-behaviour gap, in which support for direct democratic governance weakens as everyday coordination costs increase. This highlights a structural tension between democratic ideals and the practical organisation of collective property.

Utopia and reality: reflecting on the housing crisis and how to overcome it

Pedro Fonseca Jorge
INSTITUTO POLITÉCNICO DE LEIRIA

The “Experimental Habitats” Course taught at the school where the author teaches has a wide audience of students from various fields of study (product design, spatial spaces, cultural curating, arts).

As the programme consists of a journey through various architectural theories, which debated the issue of living at the level of the house or the city, the aim was to broaden its scope by trying to reach those whose training is not limited to spatial or housing issues. To this end, content was enriched with “methodologies for the appropriation of the home space by its inhabitants”, encompassing architecture, design and art (the focus of the lecturer's personal research), while at the same time proposing to the students small exercises that illustrated how, up to that point, they had appropriated their domestic space, shared with family, friends, strangers, or even individually: which spaces are private and which are shared, how often and how they have altered the configuration of these spaces through changes in furniture or other elements, what physical possessions they have and what means of transport they would need to move them, etc.

Finally, with this data and the material taught in class, they were asked as a final reflection to imagine their future independence considering the current housing crisis: different response mechanisms were created, ranging from the most utopian, (like virtual lives or total dematerialisation of goods) to the use of present and past proposals (related to housing, construction, or design) to appropriate pre-existing spaces, and even the need for a legislative and political review, thus illustrating not only contemporary difficulties but also giving students tools to navigate through them, thus reaching a solution which they can call HOME.

The proposed presentation is, therefore, the enunciation of a process led to a pertinent reflection in today’s housing market.

Reasons for moving and residential mobility in urban neighborhoods: A relational approach

Rebekka Atakan

University of Bonn

Alice Barth

University of Bonn, Germany

Housing has become one of the most fiercely contested resources in major metropolitan areas around the world. In this paper, we assess how (the absence of) various factors such as neighbourhood facilities, housing characteristics and affordability contribute to both the desire to move and the eventual realization of residential mobility. Residential mobility is often modelled as the result of rational actors' cost-benefit assessments, emphasizing the role of life-course events and dwelling characteristics.

We argue that such approaches, aiming at assessing the influence of single variables, neglect the complexity of social structure and group-specific differences in expectations towards housing and reasons for moving, especially in tight housing markets.

We therefore propose a relational perspective on residential mobility by drawing on a Bourdieu-inspired theoretical framework of positions in a multi-dimensional "social space" and associated habitus – that is, systems of durable dispositions and cognitive schemes that shape how individuals perceive, interpret, and act in social life.

Using data from a longitudinal study of two urban neighbourhoods in Cologne (Germany), we apply multiple correspondence analysis to a range of indicators capturing economic, cultural and social capital, thereby constructing a neighbourhood-level "social space".

We find that its main dimensions are overall capital volume and seniority, the latter understood both in terms of age and length of residence in the current dwelling. Subsequently, we project reasons for moving as well as residential status in the next panel wave (moved or not), into this space.

Results show that intent to move, reasons for moving, and the realization of this intent substantively differ across the social space. Overall, this contribution provides a differentiated picture of the interplay of socio-structural conditions and subjective perceptions in shaping residential mobility within urban neighbourhoods.

From Expenditure to Exposure: A Multidimensional Assessment of Summer Energy Poverty and Depressive Risks in the Greater Bay Area, China

Yuan Gao

The University of Hong Kong

Shenjing He

Department of Urban Planning and Design, HKU

Climate change increasingly exposes residents to indoor thermal discomfort, especially in high-density subtropical cities. Even with cooling devices, escalating heatwaves challenge areas where housing vulnerabilities persist. Rising energy poverty risks and health consequences in this context remain underexplored.

This study extends the classic expenditure-based energy poverty definition (10% income share) by integrating objective and subjective indoor environmental evaluations. Data were drawn from 172 GBA households (Summer 2025, July–September), including continuous indoor temperature/humidity monitoring, sleep diaries (4,066 valid records), and questionnaires. Results show significant metric divergence.

While expenditure-based energy poverty (EP_Cost) affected 17.45–30.87% of households, subjective discomfort (EP_TooHot) showed prevalence of 24.16–47.65%. Objectively, 52.35% experienced overheating during sleep (=26°C, EP_OverHeat26), with 11.41% enduring even more severe conditions (=28°C, EP_OverHeat28).

Our data showed no significant correlation between EP_Cost and depression risk. However, EP_TooHot was associated with significantly increased risks of depression.

Combining care and paid work in new suburban residential environments – everyday perspectives and structural matters

Sarah Mente

Technische Universität Braunschweig

Johanna Niesen

Technische Universität BraunschweigHenriette Bertram

Henriette Bertram

Technische Universität Braunschweig

Reconciliation of paid and care work confronts caregivers with multiple challenges in their everyday life. In our presentation, we will discuss the everyday use of housing, housing environments and mobility patterns of employed caregivers. We argue that their struggles are linked to structural issues (Mlejnek & Lütke, 2023) of both planning and its political framework. Caregivers support care-receivers to navigate through their everyday routines, thereby co-producing space. In the context of housing environments, the experiences of employed caregivers include not only their own views, but also those of care-receivers like older adults, children, or disabled people.

We therefore posit that a residential environment that works well for employed caregivers and care-receivers will, in general, cater to the needs of most people. We plan to share results from research cluster on new suburban residential areas, funded by Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft. Methods include interviews with planners and employed caregivers as well as photography-based analyses on residential environments within the German suburban neighbourhood of Munich-Freiham. Our presentation will focus on neighbourhood meeting places and communal areas to highlight the positive impact that design with a view to caregiving and its compatibility with paid work can have on people's everyday lives.

Findings suggest that there are significant differences between property developers in terms of design quality and usability. We are interested in carving out the reciprocal influence between the diverse perspectives of different caregiving arrangements and their housing environments, and in providing an outlook on future building processes in terms of addressable stakeholders and participation processes.

An Analysis of the Physical and Semantic Dimensions of the Anonymous Apartment Residents' Causes for Renovation

ILKYZ SAMUR AVCI

Akdeniz University, KEMAL REHA KAVAS

After the Industrial Revolution, urbanization led to a severance between the housing production process and the unique qualities of inhabitants. This resulted in the reduction of those who would live in housing to mere "anonymous residents." The concept of "home," to which the dweller was historically connected through a sense of belonging, disappeared, and the act of dwelling was limited to a framework of mechanical functionality.

This study, part of an ongoing doctoral thesis, examines housing renovations in Antalya, Turkiye, and proposes that renovations be considered a means of analysing the relationship between people and their residential environments. Turkiye's unique modernization and urbanization process has produced similar apartment blocks accommodating the majority of the population.

Despite increasing renovation costs, residents modify their flats to reflect their identities, often after saving for years. The hypothesis is that such renovations do not stem solely from physical concerns but may reflect a desire to transform the "house" into a "home" by breaking the spatial anonymity.

The research examines residential renovations in 21st-century Turkiye as initiatives through which residents develop a sense of belonging and express identity by creating unique living spaces. Thus, the meaning of renovation may expand from a mechanical intervention to a practice that enables residents not only to inhabit houses but to dwell in them. These modifications may reveal how housing is perceived by inhabitants while exposing shortcomings of housing production.

Ultimately, the study aims to interpret resident-initiated renovations through housing perception, everyday interaction with the residential environment and the desire to reshape the house despite its limitations, in order to reveal emotional and physical housing needs and their relation to human well-being.

Perceptions of neighbourhood quality in densifying areas

Hester Booij

Research and Statistics, city of Amsterdam

Christian Lennartz

PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency

To address the housing shortage, a significant number of new homes have been constructed and are planned for development in the coming decades within the Metropolitan Region of Amsterdam. A substantial portion of these new homes is planned on brownfield sites and within existing neighbourhoods. This densification of already highly urbanised areas can place pressure on the residential quality of these neighbourhoods. Literature indicates that densification is often associated with lower levels of residential satisfaction and reduced social cohesion. However, densification can also have positive effects. For instance, it can provide opportunities to invest in public spaces and increase the carrying capacity for neighbourhood amenities, which can enhance the quality of local facilities and services. In this paper, we investigate the perceived neighbourhood quality of newly built locations from the period 2016–2024, as experienced by long-term residents living near these developments and by new residents in and around these areas.

We utilise three waves (2019, 2023, 2025) of a unique survey on residential satisfaction in the Metropolitan Region of Amsterdam, encompassing a total of 150,000 respondents. Within this dataset we focus on those living in or near newly built locations. The aim of this research is to identify the factors that contribute to neighbourhood quality in densifying areas.

Building Preparedness: Multi-Family Housing and Collective Resilience in an Era of Polycrisis

Martine Buser

Chalmers University of Technology

Marli Swanepoel

Chalmers University of Technology

Contemporary societies are increasingly confronted with complex and overlapping crises, often described as a polycrisis, where disruptions interact across social,

economic, and infrastructural systems. In response, attention is growing on how resilience can be strengthened through improved preparedness. In many countries, preparedness strategies are largely organised through institutional crisis management systems, technological infrastructures, and policies that emphasise citizens' responsibility to ensure readiness during disruptions. While these approaches aim to strengthen societal resilience, they often overlook how everyday living environments shape possibilities for coordination, resource sharing, and collective responses in times of crisis. Housing environments therefore represent an important yet understudied site for understanding how preparedness capacities may emerge in practice.

Within this context this paper we explore how multi-family housing may support preparedness and resilience by enabling key resilience principles such as diversity, redundancy, and connectivity. This form of housing offers a relevant setting to explore how such capacities may develop. By bringing several households into closer proximity, sharing walls as well as circulation spaces and common facilities, they create opportunities for interaction, sharing of resources and capacities among residents. These spaces may also help recreate a sense of community often weakened in contemporary urban housing environments. To do, so we build on socio-material perspective, where preparedness emerges through the interaction between built environments and everyday practices. The paper draws on comparative case studies of multi-family housing projects in Sweden, combining spatial analysis of building layouts with resident scenario-based workshops. The findings are expected to show how building configurations and shared spaces can support collective resilience at the scale of the building.

Public Rental Housing Policy Design and Homeownership Aspiration among Young Adults: Evidence from Seoul, South Korea

Yoona Cho

Seoul National University, In Kwon Park

In countries with weak tenant rights, homeownership priority policies tend to overlook the tenure security of renting. As a result, homeownership has increasingly been perceived as the only reliable form of tenure security. Yet, soaring housing prices compared to wages have made homeownership increasingly difficult to achieve. In South Korea, the young adult group shows a prominent gap between actual homeownership and homeownership aspiration, with homeownership attainment delayed amid high rental market instability, which deepens housing insecurity. While public rental housing occupies a relatively small share of housing stock, it provides a residential experience of tenure security for young residents. Then, does this tenure

security experience in public rental housing affect the homeownership aspiration of young adults?

As young adults comprise the major group with housing needs, examining this relationship may advance discussions on tenure-neutral housing welfare systems. However, the relationship between their public rental housing experience and homeownership aspiration has not been sufficiently explored. South Korea has several types of public rental housing, categorized by rent levels, residency periods, and financial eligibility. However, previous studies have paid little attention to how residents' homeownership aspirations vary by the features of each type. Based on the perspective that homeownership aspiration has been socially and politically constructed, this study aims to examine how the institutional characteristics of public rental housing types shape the homeownership aspiration of young adults. Using the 2021 Seoul Public Rental Housing Panel Survey, it constructs a binary logistic regression model with housing type characteristics, housing properties previously resided in, and socio-demographic factors. The findings may offer implications for public rental housing policy design from tenure neutrality perspectives.

Public Housing Effects on Community and Individual Health: A Targeted Literature Review

Hélène Bélanger

Université du Québec à Montréal

Numerous studies have examined, either directly or indirectly, housing as a determinant of health. Research has also focused on the psychosocial effects of improved housing and perceptions of its quality, as well as the benefits associated with different tenure arrangements. Other studies have focused more specifically on public housing, particularly the improvement in living conditions and health associated with moving into public housing, the general effects of public housing on mental health and well-being—including what favors “aging in place”—as part (or not) of Healthy Cities initiatives. However, in a housing system that relies almost exclusively on market mechanisms to meet the needs of the entire population—as is the case in Canada, the United States, and certain European countries—public officials concerned with responsible public financial management see little benefit in increasing funding for public housing.

In parallel, from a public health perspective, little is known about the current state of knowledge regarding the relationship between health (both community and individual) and public housing. A few rare comprehensive literature reviews exist, but they do not provide an overview of the effects of social housing on the health of individuals and

communities according to different types of social/public housing and their inhabitants. Concerned about the housing conditions of society's most vulnerable groups and their effects on the health of these individuals and their communities, and how poor health impact the social and built environment, this paper will present the results of a critical targeted review of the literature on the effects of social housing on the health of communities and individuals, highlighting the different social/public housing models and the characteristics of social/public housing, that may be more conducive to public health.

From Stories to Shared Futures: Dialogical Pathways for Transforming User Participation in Social Housing

Anne Bergljot Gimmestad Fjelnseth

UIT

Background: User participation is a central principle in Norwegian social housing policy, yet tensions remain between institutional frameworks and the experiences of people with substance use and/or mental health challenges. While housing stability is often defined as access to a place to live, service users describe it as a relational and ongoing process shaped by everyday interactions. Aim of this proposal draws on an ongoing qualitative PhD project in Northern Norway exploring pathways between housing stability, quality of life, and social inclusion. It examines how experiential knowledge can support collective learning and service development through dialogical practice.

Theoretical framework: The study is grounded in a social constructivist perspective and combines narrative analysis with dialogical and relational approaches inspired by future dialogues. Methods and data include interviews with six service users, three relatives, and focus groups with twenty-two municipal employees across three municipalities. Following narrative thematic analysis, a dialogical workshop brought together service users, relatives, professionals, and organizational representatives. Participants were invited to imagine improved future conditions for housing stability, quality of life, and social inclusion, and to identify enabling relational and structural factors. **Findings and implications:** Housing stability emerged as relational and dynamic, shaped by safety, dignity, predictability, and belonging. Participants described fragmented services, unstable professional relationships, and stigma, revealing tensions between lived experience and institutional structures. Future dialogues shifted attention from problems to shared possibilities, positioning participants as knowledge holders. The study suggests that combining narrative analysis with future dialogues can move user participation beyond consultation and contribute to more relational and inclusive social housing practices.

Social Housing and Globalization

One Front Door: When social, affordable and private residents meet

Michele Adair

Outcome Management Services

Australia's housing landscape differs sharply from the original vision of social housing. Early public housing was framed as a constructive, post-war nation-building. It used zoning to create building forms for mostly single income working families, clearly separated from private market neighbourhoods. Over time, this spatial separation, the residualisation of social housing, and tax and policy settings have reshaped the system and perceptions. From the mid-20th century, governments mostly delivered public housing through planned estates, either vertically dense or sprawling low-rise. They were designed for low-income, single-earner working family households.

Estate locations, land costs and planning standards encouraged large-scale, mono-tenure development. This reinforced a public versus private geography in many cities. Scarcity now frames social housing as a last resort for those in greatest, and need and the tenant profile has shifted. Households are more often single individuals, with complex needs and very low, welfare-based incomes. This has deepened stigma attached to social housing and its residents.

In parallel, tax and housing policy have transformed private housing into an asset traded for profit and wealth creation. Affordable rental housing emerged in the late 2000s as a distinct tenure between traditional social housing and the private market. Mixed-tenure and mixed-income redevelopment has grown in importance with mono-tenure estates replaced by mixed neighbourhoods. Mixed-tenure buildings are rare.

This case study presents Northsea, the first and only mixed-tenure building in Australia. Located south of Sydney, construction was completed in late 2024. It has 18 social, 9 affordable, and 38 market apartments and all residents share the same front door, lifts and recreational areas. It is the result of a partnership between a private developer, a community housing provider and State Government with support from the Commonwealth Government.

Mind the Gap: Affordable Housing Innovation

Sasha Tsenkova

University of Calgary

Canada needs 5.8 million new homes by 2030 to restore housing affordability. The research explores a solution to the twin problem of massive housing deficit and growing affordability crisis in rapidly growing Canadian cities premised on development of missing middle affordable housing. We argue that historic patterns of neighbourhood development illustrate more successful, diverse, dense and flexible opportunities to respond to economic and social pressures and environmental goals. The affordability crisis in Calgary and the recent move towards city-wide upzoning has provided historic opportunity to focus on innovation that fosters alignment across the entire housing supply ecosystem. Social housing providers could become a champion of this transformative change.

The research develops a conceptual framework drawing on the political market model to explain adoption of certain policies by municipalities, emphasizing the impact of institutional factors on housing outcomes. An important component of the framework is content analysis of municipal housing strategies, regulatory, fiscal and financial instruments.

A central question refers to implementation of new partnership models in the development process to accelerate change. We demonstrate that the missing middle housing typology provides a sustainable solution due to its diversity, efficient housing design, higher density, the use of low-carbon materials, and prefabricated approaches that can radically reduce the cost and the environmental impacts of housing.

The methodology builds on literature review, case study analysis and interviews to explore innovation in missing middle affordable housing across the housing continuum. The approach focuses on several dimensions of housing innovation: diversity of prototypes, diversity of models along the continuum; diversity of living arrangements; diversity of production methods/technologies, and diversity of partnerships to finance/build/maintain affordable housing.

"A tool for whom? The political economy of the Bail Réel Solidaire in the French social housing sector."

Pietro Battaglini

Polytechnic University of Turin

Giorgio de Ambrogio.

Polytechnic University of Turin; Sapienza University of Rome

Over the past decade, a housing model known as the Bail Réel Solidaire (BRS) has spread throughout France, becoming a key tool for promoting homeownership at below-market prices. To date, thanks to the BRS, over 20,000 houses have been built by 124 land trust, known as Offices fonciers solidaires (Foncier Solidaire France, 2025).

This paper examines the political uses of the BRS, focusing on a central contradiction linked to its interaction with other housing policy instruments, which raises questions about its ability to consolidate the French social housing sector as a whole. The interaction between the BRS and other social housing policy instruments has intensified since the 2019 ÉLAN law, when the BRS was incorporated into the quota of social housing to be built to meet the social housing production obligations for most French municipalities established by the SRU law. Specifically, this law requires municipalities to allocate approximately 25% of the total housing stock within their administrative boundaries to social housing. Since 2019, the BRS housing model has contributed to the mandatory 25% quota of social housing.

Drawing on the critical analysis of public policy instruments (Lascombes and Le Galès, 2007) and its application in housing studies (Namian, 2020; Huisman, 2020), this article develops a technical-political analysis of the BRS. Particular attention is paid to the Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur region, characterised by strong socio-economic polarisation and persistent political resistance to social housing.

The analysis addresses some fundamental questions: what political reasons underlie the growing interest in the BRS in that region? How does the heterogeneous configuration of the actors involved in the BRS implementation produce divergent narratives and uses of the instrument? The aim is ultimately to investigate how these policies (re)define the meaning of social housing within the framework of French legality.

"Regulating the social composition in neighborhoods: housing policy and planning in three European cities."

Alessandro Coppola

Politecnico di Milano

Laura Colini, luav

Politecnico di Milano

Often perceived as distinct domains, housing policies and urban planning are intrinsically interconnected in shaping the accessibility and affordability of housing in contemporary cities. This paper questions which, how and to what extent the housing systems and planning instruments might establish conditions to tame real estate speculation and to protect the social mix in diverse but gentrifying neighbourhoods. Adopting a comparative analysis of cities with significant host market pressures, such as Berlin, Milan, and Paris, the analysis focuses on the interaction between national and local regulatory mechanisms, such as rent control, inclusionary zoning, land value capture, and public land leasing, alongside social housing provision strategies.

The paper elucidates the policy mix in a comparative view, drawing on documentary analysis and interviews with public housing providers and urban planning specialists. Notwithstanding the socio-political and historical variances across urban contexts, the findings indicate that specific elements of regulatory frameworks and proactive public sector interventions tend to create enhanced opportunities for inclusive housing stability, thereby informing a broader discourse that intersects with housing policies and urban planning.

Social Housing Institutions, Organisations and Governments

Social housing in accessible locations: Tensions between policy ambitions and practice in Flanders (Belgium)

Lisa Cochez

Vrije Universiteit Brussel

Eva Van Eenoo

Vrije Universiteit Brussel

Nele Aernouts

Vrije Universiteit Brussel

Kobe Boussauw

Vrije Universiteit Brussel

The right to housing cannot be reduced to the mere provision of a dwelling. It implies access to amenities, to public transport, and thereby affects social inclusion. Realising this right presupposes that suitable and well-located land is available to build on. Yet where that land is situated matters: location determines the accessibility of social housing and, by extension, the quality of life of its residents. Location is therefore not a secondary concern in social housing provision, but a fundamental dimension of housing justice.

This paper analyses the institutional and organisational dynamics shaping the location strategies of social housing providers in Flanders, Belgium. Drawing on qualitative interviews with representatives from Flemish housing administrations and social housing agencies, supplemented by a stakeholder workshop, the study examines how accessibility objectives are embedded in organisational practice and what structural barriers prevent their deployment.

We argue that the question of where social housing can be built is a more urgent and underexplored governance challenge than commonly assumed. In practice, the spatial logic of where social housing gets built is frequently subordinated to financial constraints. Social landlords in Flanders operate in a context of passive land policy, a competitive land market, fragmented multi-level governance, and persistent local resistance towards social housing, pushing agencies towards informal strategies and

less accessible locations. The paper concludes with recommendations for a more active land policy and stronger coordination between housing and spatial planning governance.

The Limits of Building Away Segregation: Tenure Mix, Public Housing, and Spatial Inequality in Swedish Cities

Martin Grander

This paper investigates how new housing construction in Sweden's largest cities influences trajectories of socioeconomic segregation, with particular attention to the role of public rental housing (*allmännyttan*).

Drawing on detailed geographical data on socioeconomics and new housing construction from Gothenburg and Malmö (2012–2023), the analysis adopts a relational perspective on segregation, conceptualizing it as the spatial expression of broader socioeconomic inequalities.

The study shows that new construction contributes to increased socioeconomic mixing in several neighbourhoods, particularly where developments include a diverse range of tenure forms. Such mixing is associated with locally reduced income segregation. However, the overall citywide patterns remain largely unchanged—or in Malmö's case, segregation increases—because the number and scale of mixed tenure developments are insufficient to counteract broader structural processes, including widening income disparities and strong upward trajectories in already affluent areas.

Public rental housing emerges as a crucial mechanism for promoting social mix, especially in densification areas where the introduction of public housing fosters more balanced neighbourhood compositions. Yet, its potential is constrained by limited volumes, market segmentation, and persistent economic inequalities that shape residential choices.

The findings suggest that while new construction can moderate segregation locally, significantly reducing urban socioeconomic divides requires systemic, long term transformations in both housing policy and welfare structures.

From planning to execution: implementing the Housing Local Strategies with RRP funds in Portugal

Caterina Di Giovanni

Institute of Social Sciences, University of Lisbon (ICS-ULisboa)

Maria Manuela Rola

Faculty of Architecture, University of Porto (CENP-FAUP)

Bruna Lee Azado

Faculty of Architecture, University of Porto (CENP-FAUP)

The approval of the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) in 2020 made funds available to EU Member States through their Recovery and Resilience Plans (RRP), aiming to support post-pandemic economic recovery and strengthen socio-territorial cohesion. In Portugal, the main instrument for applying these funds in housing policy was the 1.º Direito programme, created in 2018 under the New Generation of Housing Policies (NGHP). Previously underfunded, it became the largest national housing-promotion programme and the first to offer 100% non-refundable EU contributions for investment in social housing. The Local Housing Strategy (LHS), a mandatory document for municipalities seeking RRP funding, is central for comparing planned and implemented measures. With investments to be completed by mid-2026, it is now possible to identify major disparities between these documents and execution.

Two main issues emerge: access to non-refundable financing concentrated in wealthier municipalities with greater borrowing capacity, and several NGHP objectives - integrated, multilevel governance and proactive, data-driven action - remain difficult to sustain. Following the Flyvbjerg's theory, these gaps reveal key "tension points" and the risks of uniform territorial allocation criteria and limited differentiation in technical support, which may reinforce inequalities through a "Matthew Effect" exposing path-dependencies not addressed in the RRP "one-size-fits-all" design, pivotal on new European funding design.

This presentation draws on the LOGO project (2023–2026), which focuses on local housing policies with a focus on governance transformations and their effects on municipal housing shortages. The analysis uses the LOGO database, covering around 80% of approved LHSs, and applies a methodological framework combining Doling's typology of housing state intervention with an assessment of RRP implementation outcomes.

Tenant Management Organisations in the Netherlands: Can it be a promising alternative to grass roots housing cooperatives and institutional social housing provision?

Gerard Van Bortel

Delft University of Technology

This paper examines the organisational, institutional, and governance potential of tenant management organisations as a form of collaborative housing within the Dutch social housing system. In tenant management organisations, residents collectively assume responsibility for the management of their housing, while ownership remains with a housing association. This institutional arrangement creates a hybrid governance structure that combines professional asset ownership with resident-led operational management.

The paper argues that tenant management organisations can strengthen social cohesion, improve housing management efficiency, and contribute to broader societal goals such as wellbeing, informal care provision, and neighbourhood liveability. This collective governance structure reduces transaction costs, enhances accountability, and enables locally responsive management practices.

However, the development and scaling of tenant management organisations are constrained by existing institutional and regulatory frameworks, which are primarily designed for individual tenancy relationships and professionalised housing management. Housing associations play a crucial enabling role by providing access to housing assets, technical expertise, and institutional legitimacy, while also needing to adapt their organisational structures and professional practices to support resident self-governance.

The paper draws from recent initiatives by Dutch housing associations to create Tenant Management Organisations ('Beheercoöperaties) and will compare these developments with initiatives across Europe. Key words: Tenant Management Organisations (TMOs), Housing Associations, Hybrid Institutional Structures, Resident Self-Governance and Empowerment.

Sustainable Finance as a New Layer of Affordable Housing Governance: England, California and the Netherlands

Alejandro Fernandez Perez

Universidad de Granada

Mats Lucia Bayer

Universidad de Granada, (TU Delft)

Since the 1980s, affordable housing provision has shifted from direct public subsidy toward hybrid systems reliant on private capital. At the same time, providers face decarbonisation obligations and stricter building standards linked to net-zero targets.

This paper examines how sustainable finance, through ESG disclosure frameworks and labelled bond markets, interacts with established affordable-housing finance regimes in England, California and the Netherlands.

Drawing on semi-structured interviews with providers, banks and financial intermediaries, we argue that sustainable finance operates as a new layer of housing governance. While emerging within transnational sustainable-finance frameworks, its meaning and effects are shaped by domestic institutional arrangements. In England, ESG issuance overlays an asset-backed bond model governed by regulatory viability and covenant constraints. In California, sustainable bonds interlock with the LIHTC system and the public–private capital stacks structure. In the Netherlands, balance-sheet lending backed by the WSW guarantee and promotional banks limits the scope for ESG-driven pricing differentials.

Across these cases, sustainable finance rarely functions as an autonomous funding stream or produces consistent green premia. Instead, it standardises disclosure, broadens investor eligibility and reinforces accountability to capital markets. Environmental standards remains primarily driven by public regulation, subsidy design and allocation rules. The capacity of sustainable finance to expand deeply affordable provision is uneven and institutionally contingent.

Reverse Social Mix to Tackle Housing Unaffordability. A Case Study of the Cadix Waterfront Development in Antwerp Belgium

Jill Schoeters

Vrije Universiteit Brussel

Michael Ryckewaert

Vrije Universiteit Brussel

This article examines whether an alternative approach to social mixing - integrating social and affordable housing into newly developed projects - could produce better outcomes for lower-income groups than traditional social mix policies. The latter has often been criticized for contributing to gentrification, displacement and housing unaffordability.

This study has two main objectives. First, it investigates how social mixing was originally envisioned in policy documents for the Cadix neighbourhood, a waterfront redevelopment in Antwerp (Belgium) and how it was ultimately implemented within a shifting neoliberal context. Second, it examines whether the anticipated neighbourhood effects - often used to justify social mix policies - have materialized and what the actual impact of the policy has been on the neighbourhood level. This is evaluated through the concept of liveability, which has been operationalised using a range of liveability indicators explored in interviews with neighbourhood residents. In line with previous research, this study finds that the anticipated neighbourhood effects are largely absent. Moreover, the partial implementation of the policy has not adequately addressed the needs of either social tenants or homeowners, highlighting that embedding inclusionary housing instruments in legislation provides greater assurance of their effective pursuit, even during political shifts.

Despite these shortcomings, the article offers a more constructive perspective on urban (housing) development policies when they take the form of embedding social housing within new residential projects. This approach, which we propose to call 'reverse social mix', not only guarantees housing affordability, critical in the face of growing urban housing costs, but also fosters socio-spatial equity. Furthermore, it encourages social diversity in otherwise homogenous middle- and upper-class neighbourhoods and finds that inhabitants of different groups coexist respectfully.

Diverging Trajectories of Mature Not-for-Profit Housing Systems in Austria and the Netherlands: Housing Associations and Revolving Fund Mechanisms

Gerald Koesl

Austrian Federation of Limited-Profit Housing Association

Benjamin Baumgartner

Institute for Spatial and Social-Ecological Transformations

WU Vienna

University of Economics and Business Vienna, Austria

Hans Volmary

Institute of Geography, Technical University of Dresden, Dresden, Germany

Across Europe, political interest in expanding affordable housing has intensified, accompanied by renewed attention to the role of not-for-profit housing providers. This article compares the not-for-profit housing sectors of Austria and the Netherlands, focusing on their key institutional actors: housing associations. Both countries historically developed large and mature not-for-profit housing sectors; however, since the 1990s their trajectories have diverged markedly.

The article analyses the institutional developments underpinning this divergence, consequences on sectoral size, tenant composition, and public expenditure, and examines their implications for housing associations' operational business models. Specifically, it compares legal frameworks, rent-setting and allocation regimes, and financing models, and assesses how these shape the performance of their respective revolving funds. Methodologically, the study adopts a mixed-method comparative case-study design. The findings reveal pronounced differences between the two systems. In Austria, regulatory continuity has enabled limited-profit housing associations to accumulate reinvestable surpluses, sustain stable levels of construction, and serve a broad segment of the population. In contrast, increasingly restrictive regulatory interventions in the Netherlands have curtailed housing associations' operational autonomy, leading to an erosion of reinvestment capacity, negatively affecting new construction.

The article contributes to debates on European housing systems and identifies the institutional conditions under which not-for-profit housing sectors can remain resilient

while maintaining their affordability mission. The findings offer policy-relevant insights for current debates on affordable housing provision.

Can housing cooperatives mitigate the social risks of urban renewal and densification? The case of a working-class neighbourhood in Zurich, Switzerland

Jennifer Duyne Barenstein

ETH Zurich

Daniela Sanjines

ETH Zurich

Hannah Widmer

ETH Zurich

Salome Rohner

ETH Zurich

Luisa Gehriger

ETH Zurich

For over three decades urban densification has been globally advocated as a strategy to counter urban sprawl and reduce soil consumption. In Switzerland urban densification became legally mandatory with the adoption of the revised Spatial Planning Act in 2014. The creation of new housing is particularly challenging in fast growing cities like Zurich, where hardly any green- and brownfields are left for development. Accordingly, new housing can only be created through the demolition of the old, lower density but affordable housing stock.

This paper examines the renewal and densification of Schwamendingen, a working-class neighbourhood in the city of Zurich that has been earmarked for densification. For over 30 years Schwamendingen was crossed by a highway, making it one of the least attractive and poorest neighbourhoods of the city. With the recent enclosure of the highway and the creation of a large park above it, the quality of the neighbourhood has dramatically improved. A social impact assessment conducted by the city of Zurich concluded that the renewal of the neighbourhood was unlikely to entail gentrification and displacement as over 50% of the housing stock is owned by the non-profit sector of which 42.6 housing cooperatives. But was this assumption correct?

The paper examines how the rapid transformation of the neighbourhood and its social impact is being perceived by a wide range of stakeholders, ranging from cooperative representatives, community leaders to local activists. It shows that while housing cooperatives largely protect the housing security of their members, they are simultaneously involved in the demolition of low-density garden-city housing estates that are replaced with denser developments, a process that contributes to the displacement of the neighbourhood's most vulnerable residents.

Homes in Uncertain Times: Taiwan's Housing Crisis and the Politics of Cross-strait Tension

Yi-Ling Chen

University of Wyoming

Taiwan's housing system is marked by the "three highs": high prices, high vacancy rates, and high homeownership rates. Though seemingly contradictory, their coexistence reveals that housing functions primarily as an investment asset rather than shelter; its exchange value far exceeds its use value.

Unlike many European and North American cases, Taiwan's crisis is not a shortage of units but persistently high vacancies. In the meantime, Taiwan faces the crisis of population aging and now it has a very low fertility rate. Since 2010, the social housing movement has successfully pressured the government to initiate social housing programs. However, progress has slowed under the administration of Lai Ching-te since 2025. This deceleration can be attributed both to shifts in policy priorities and to increasingly complex domestic political dynamics under intensifying cross-Strait tensions.

This paper focuses on three central themes. First, it examines the institution that have constructed housing as a commodified asset—one increasingly central to investment strategies and the formation of a homeowner society. Second, it explores the efforts to socialize housing that emerged from the social housing movement beginning in 2010. Third, it investigates the slowdown in social housing development during the Lai administration.

The paper ultimately seeks to explain why attempts to decommodify housing and expand social housing have faced persistent obstacles, highlighting constraints rooted in geopolitics, domestic political dynamics and prevailing ideological commitments.

Relational Governance and Indigenous Housing Innovation: The Kijaté Case Study (Val-d'Or, Canada)

Lisa Van Campenhout

National Institute of Scientific Research

Urban Indigenous populations in Canada face persistent barriers to adequate housing, shaped by systemic inequalities, racialization, and stigmatization. While these challenges emerge in urban contexts, less attention has been paid to Indigenous-led social innovations as expressions of self-determination, particularly in Quebec.

This research asks: How do Indigenous grassroots organizations innovate to meet urban housing needs in Quebec? Grounded in social innovation theory and Indigenous governance theories, this qualitative and collaborative study examines how governance structures and relational dynamics enable innovation.

Based on interviews and document analysis, it focuses on Kijaté, an urban housing initiative by Val-d'Or Native Friendship Centre (24 units with parenting classes, addiction therapy, collective cooking, employment reintegration, clinical services).

Findings show innovation driven not by linear planning or external policies, but by relational, participatory governance fostering experimentation, adaptation, and collective learning. Leadership distributes across levels, with staff and beneficiaries actively shaping the initiative through their lived experiences.

This governance model is relational rather than hierarchical, reflecting a self-determined approach to social innovation in which those most affected by housing precarity actively contribute to social innovation and organizational renewal.

Kijaté demonstrates how relational governance, not merely a neutral administrative structure, constitutes a core mechanism of social innovation that simultaneously transforms housing access while strengthening community autonomy. It challenges dominant models by centring relationships, collective learning, and social impact in complex organizational contexts, applicable to other settings as well.

Misclassification of social housing in statistical surveys: the case of Vienna

Manos Matsaganis

Politecnico di Milano

Francesco Cellino

Polytechnic University of Milan

Andrea Parma

Polytechnic University of Milan

Estimating the value and distributional implications of social housing enjoys a long tradition in housing research. For that purpose, the opportunity cost approach compares social housing units with similar dwellings in the private rental sector, based on their characteristics.

The reliability of the estimates derived rests on the assumption that social housing tenants are correctly identified in statistical surveys. In most housing research in Europe, relying on microdata from the ‘EU statistics on income and living conditions survey’ (EU-SILC), this may not actually be the case.

We highlight the issue by comparing two variables: ‘tenure status’, available from EU-SILC, and ‘legal status of dwelling’, only available from national SILC datasets. We show that in Vienna, where the role of social housing is significantly greater than in any other European city, the degree of overlap between social housing and below-market rent is woefully low.

As a matter of fact, the data reveal that nearly 40% of all dwellings classified as ‘below-market rent’ are actually private, while over three quarters of all municipal housing dwellings (and over two-thirds of those in housing associations) are classified as ‘market rent’.

We discuss the implications of the resulting misclassification of social housing for policy and research, and conclude with a number of recommendations for a possible way forward.

Waiting for a Home: Bureaucratic Temporality and Municipal Housing Allocation in Brno, Czech Republic

Jana Zavodska
Masaryk University

Katerina Nedbálková
Masaryk University Brno, Czechia

Municipal housing is often framed as a solution to housing affordability crises, yet in Brno, Czech Republic, a paradox persists: flats are repeatedly offered but remain unallocated, while approximately 2,000 applicants wait in an untransparent queue. How does a system designed for fair allocation become an obstacle to housing provision? And how do applicants experience and navigate prolonged bureaucratic waiting?

This study draws on an ethnographic study comprising twelve in-depth interviews with housing applicants and allocation commission members. The analysis examines waiting as a technology of power (Auyero, 2012) how extended temporality shapes applicants into "patients of the state" who must engage in continuous bureaucratic labour: monthly monitoring, attendance at viewings, and navigation of shifting criteria, while receiving little clarity about their chances.

The findings complicate narratives of passive waiting. Housing seekers actively negotiate bureaucratic temporality through information sharing and contestation. However, such agency remains constrained by post-socialist housing inequality, where intergenerational wealth transfers have become the primary pathway to homeownership. Those without family resources find themselves trapped between unaffordable markets and bureaucratic limbo.

The study contributes to understanding how procedural fairness can paradoxically obstruct access to housing.

What drives cost disparities and organizational variation in municipal social rented housing in Norway: A contingency perspective

Jardar Sørvoll

NOVA, Oslo Metropolitan University

Kim Christian Astrup

NOVA, Oslo Metropolitan University

Are Vegard Haug

NOVA, Oslo Metropolitan University

What explains variation in how Norwegian municipalities organize and operate municipally allocated rental housing? Are universal solutions possible, or is a more differentiated financing system required?

The study is set against an ongoing debate in Norway and other European countries concerning the funding of housing for disadvantaged individuals who cannot secure accommodation in the private market. Within Norwegian municipal housing, there are marked differences in service provision: net operating expenditure per capita and per dwelling varies considerably, as do coverage rates, which tend to be higher in peripheral areas than in more central urban locations. These disparities challenge core principles of the egalitarian Nordic welfare state model and render the policy field both exciting and controversial.

We adopt a contingency theory perspective, drawing on the work of Fiedler, Woodward, Lawrence and Lorsch. Contingency theory holds that there is no single best way to organize or manage services; effectiveness depends on contextual conditions. In municipal housing, this implies that service provision should be adapted to local circumstances. Relevant factors include municipal centrality, local housing market conditions, and the size and needs of user groups (including refugees and social assistance recipients), as well as municipal finances, organizational design and service capacity. The theory also highlights the importance of flexible organization and cross-sectoral collaboration.

Empirically, we draw on a newly established municipal database on housing-related social variation developed at OsloMet, based on national statistics for all 357 Norwegian municipalities. The database spans the past five years and has been further developed within a commissioned research project conducted for the Norwegian government. Our analysis combines linear regression models with semi-structured interviews with housing administrators and the study of policy documents.

How can service management make a difference in public housing estates? Evidence from Milan

Marco Peverini

Vittoria Baglieri, Massimo Bricocoli, Eleonora Perobelli, Raffaella Saporito

With the decline of social rental housing (SRH), especially state-provided housing, SRH providers' mission has shifted from developing and managing real estate to delivering housing services close to welfare provision for tenants with increasingly complex needs. This transformation challenges traditional management models.

This research investigates how distinct management strategies shape tenants' lived experiences. Bridging housing studies and public management literature, we analyse how management approaches create or destroy value for tenants and SRH providers. We define value as the impact of services on users, stakeholders, and society, drawing on the notions of public and societal value.

Conceptually, the paper proposes a framework to analyse value creation and destruction in SRH, applicable beyond the Milan case. We adopt a qualitative, multi-disciplinary design based on comparative case studies.

The study draws on original data from over 100 interviews with tenants and street-level bureaucrats, analysed through inductive coding. Specifically, we examine two SRH management models identified in Milan—labelled “traditional” and “strategic”—through four case studies (two per model) across two neighbourhoods.

Focusing on public providers, we explore current service management strategies and their implications for tenants' quality of life. Methodologically, the paper is, to our knowledge, the first study to apply a public service logic lens to SRH, bridging housing studies and public management and offering a promising analytical approach for future research.

Findings show that management strategies produce markedly different experiences of value creation. From a policy perspective, the paper highlights how management choices shape multi-level outcomes, suggesting that a more deliberate use of organisational tools can significantly improve the sector.

Segmentation Policy and Congestion in Public Housing: Evidence from Singapore

Kwan Ok Lee

National University of Singapore NUS

Cristian Badarinz

NUS

Hau Wei Teng

NUS, SLA,

Minghang Yu

NUS

Rationed public housing markets designed to deliver subsidized housing often exhibit persistent excess demand in specific segments. Whether such congestion reflects heterogeneous preferences or equilibrium sorting under regulatory constraints remains an open question.

This paper studies how households adjust their housing choices in response to policy-induced market segmentation in a rationed public housing allocation system. We exploit a recent segmentation adjustment in Singapore's public housing location classification that introduced project-level regulatory differentiation while preserving the existing spatial segmentation. We combine administrative new-sale public housing application rate data between 2019 and 2025 with a survey of 506 young Singaporean households eliciting complete rankings of hypothetical housing bundles under pre- and post-adjustment institutional regimes. Our rank-ordered logit estimates show little systematic change in estimated preference parameters across regulatory contexts at the sample level, suggesting that observed behavioural adjustments do not primarily reflect shifts in underlying preferences. However, nearly 30% of respondents revise their top-ranked choice once expected success probabilities adjust under the new segmentation environment. Administrative application data reveal a congestion decline in previously oversubscribed location segments. Counterfactual exercises combining survey-based switching patterns with observed application rates indicate that a substantial share of this change can be accounted for by the reallocation of demand across segments.

These findings highlight a diversion mechanism through which segmentation policies redistribute demand across housing segments and reshape congestion in rationed housing markets without altering underlying preference structure.

The Kymmendö case: a transformative social innovation in affordable housing in Sweden

Linda Lövgren

KTH Royal Institute of Technology

Access to affordable housing has become a global crisis, with rising costs placing pressure on low-income households across Europe. Mission oriented innovation policies have been proposed to address such systemic challenges, yet the innovation field remains theoretically fragmented, and scholars call for stronger conceptual foundations. At the same time, the potential of social innovations in affordable housing is often constrained by unstable funding, limited political and institutional support, and restricted capacity within public authorities to create enabling policies.

This study responds by linking transformative social innovation theory with the practical work required to address complex housing problems. The article applies the transformative social innovation framework by Avelino et al. (2019) and the scaling framework by Moore et al. (2024) in a theory testing case study. It examines the Kymmendö project in Sweden, an initiative led by an NGO that developed an affordability model and constructed housing for households with low or irregular incomes.

The study asks to what extent the project challenges dominant institutional logics in the Swedish housing system and how elements of the model may be scaled to support wider transformations.

The study conceptualizes Kymmendö as a transformative social innovation that reframes homelessness as a structural outcome of market barriers. By targeting households with different experiences of homelessness and applying differentiated rents, the project challenges prevailing logics in the Swedish housing regime. The analysis traces both its transformative potential and the constraints that shape it.

The study provides a process oriented and theoretically grounded account of social innovation in Swedish affordable housing and advances understanding of how mission driven actors navigate regulatory, financial, and institutional barriers to create transformative change.

Between Tragedy and Success: Communal Spaces and the Social-Sustainability Agenda in Vienna's Housing Model – An Ostrom-Informed Institutional Approach Across Housing Sectors

Anita Aigner

TU Wien

In Vienna, the social and housing policy goal of “social sustainability” has been formally embedded as the “fourth pillar” of the developer competition procedures since 2009. In this context, communal spaces have emerged as a key strategic instrument for architects and developers (primarily limited profit housing associations, LPHAs) to demonstrate compliance with this highly normative yet underspecified concept. These spaces are assumed to have an immediate social impact, such as community building, social cohesion, and democratic participation. Empirical reality, however, reveals a more differentiated picture, highlighting marked discrepancies between planning ideals and everyday use. While shared spaces in collaborative housing (Baugruppen; co-housing) often succeed in fostering communal life, conventional subsidized housing more frequently exhibits institutional misfits and problematic forms of appropriation, including underutilisation or misappropriation (such as informal storage).

This paper presents a cross-sector empirical study of communal spaces in five newer Viennese development areas. Based on on-site observations and interviews with residents, property managers and social process facilitators, the study goes beyond purely descriptive research (post-occupancy evaluations, POEs) by applying an Ostrom-informed institutional-analytical framework (Common-Pool Resources, IAD Framework, Design Principles).

The study examines how institutional misfits across different rule levels (constitutional, collective-choice, and operational) can undermine planning ideals. It also investigates to what extent governance types (self-governed, externally governed, and co-governed) relate to the appropriation and use of communal spaces – thereby implicitly relating to their social sustainability. It is argued that the viability of collective spatial resources depends not only on architectural design and user engagement, but crucially on the institutional fit and the robustness of governance structures.

Collaborative governance inclusion – the case of minority groups in Swedish public housing regeneration

Nils Hertting

Institute for Housing and Urban Research, Uppsala University

Strategies for revitalizing marginalized neighbourhoods dominated by public housing landlords often include participatory innovations and collaborative governance arrangements. According to an often-repeated concern, however, such efforts benefit the privileged rather than the poor.

In the present paper, we develop the theoretical argument and suggest some general *mechanisms of collaborative governance inclusion and exclusion* based on a thin and contextual rational choice perspective. The general framework and specific ideal-type mechanisms are illustrated and illuminated through empirical references to the role of ethnic minority associations and their ambivalent and ambiguous roles in the renewal and regeneration of public housing estates in sub-urban Stockholm.

Based on this analysis of exclusion mechanisms, in the final part of the paper I change perspective, asking from the point of view of the “potential loser” what marginalised minority groups may do in order to elevate their input in neighbourhood governance games, in a short and long-term perspective.

The architecture of Housing & It's lived spaces

Common Spaces in Swedish Municipal postwar multi-family housing – from visionary to obsolete?

Sara Brolund De Carvalho

KTH

Common rooms and spaces (Swedish: *gemensamhetslokaler*) were considered important spatial components of the architecture of the Swedish Welfare State and were particularly visible in the plans of several multi-family housing areas built under the Million program era (1965-1974). The municipal housing companies held the main responsibility for the creation, management and maintenance of shared social spaces within a multi-family housing area. Today, these municipal housing companies appear to have a radically different role regarding provision and development of common rooms

and spaces, as well as other forms of shared indoor spaces like assembly rooms, recreational spaces and hobby rooms, compared to their early years.

The main empirical example of the study is Husby, a Stockholm suburb planned (1968-71) and built (1972-77) almost exclusively by Sweden's largest municipal housing company, Svenska Bostäder. This research employs document analysis with a critical discourse analysis approach, examining archival materials, press coverage, and digital sources regarding contemporary spaces in Husby.

This study aims to trace shifts in the perception of these spaces by looking at written and visual material (architectural drawings, illustrations, photos) from two distinct periods. The first period is the planning and initial occupancy (1968-74) and the second is the present (2025-2026). By analysing the historical material and juxtaposing it to contemporary descriptions, this research wants to contribute to an in-depth understanding of the role of these spaces.

One preliminary finding from the first period is that these spaces were presented as having a compensatory function in newly developed suburbs, which lacked established social environments and structures compared to central Stockholm. Another preliminary observation is the compensatory role related to limited living space, where various common spaces acted as extensions of the private home.

Post-Occupancy Evaluation of OMA's 'Oost III' Social Housing in IJ-Plein, Amsterdam-Noord (1980–1988)

Elena Martinez-Millana

Universitat Politècnica de València

This research offers an ongoing Post-Occupancy Evaluation (POE) of social housing in the IJ-Plein urban plan in Amsterdam-Noord, developed by Rem Koolhaas and the Office for Metropolitan Architecture (OMA) (1980–1988), specifically examining the 'Oost III' subplan, which they reserved for themselves to design. The IJ-Plein programme delivered entirely social housing alongside a school, gymnasium, café-restaurant and snack bar, youth and community centres, supermarket, and shops—with 'Oost III' as the most concentrated subplan, embodying Koolhaas/OMA's theoretical discourse on 'a new definition of the culture of congestion' in a very particular way.

Building on previous research outcomes on this subplan, which focused on their theoretical and historical significance—highlighting the innovative social housing and urban renewal policies implemented—this subsequent research examines how these housing and urban spaces are lived today. This approach is methodologically inspired by Philippe Boudon's *Lived-In Architecture* (MIT Press, 1972), a socio-architectural study of

how inhabitants interact with and alter modern architecture, emphasising their agency over architects' intent through interviews, site photos, and inhabitants' diagrams of changes. This study delves into two housing types across Oost III's blocks: the 'HAT units' for one- or two-person households; and the 'centraal women unit' for communal living among people with disabilities, housing larger households.

What can we learn today from Oost III's capacity to foster alternative domestic models beyond the nuclear family—how do residents reveal the project's potential to support diverse households, from young and older adult singles to disabled people living together? Residents' experiences have revealed that the model is two-fold: it facilitates their daily lives by enabling easy access to services, but at the same time exposes them to nuisances for living in 'congestion'.

Sættedammen: Exploring the polyvalent domestic interiors of one of the World's first modern co-housing projects.

Nicholas Lee

National University of Singapore

Sættedammen (1972) designed by architects Theo Bjerg and Palle Dyreborg, is often referred to as the World's first modern co-housing community. It consists of 27 row-houses and a communal house for shared activities. Despite its significance and architectural value, there is a surprising lack of literature relating to Sættedammen, or even an awareness of the housing project, particularly outside of Denmark.

Through a uniquely longitudinal perspective informed by the residents themselves, and the spatial adaptations that have accommodated their evolving domestic practices, this article explores what lessons can be learnt about flexibility in domestic architecture by studying the adaptability and polyvalency of Sættedammen's interiors.

The methodological framework for this study involves a synthesis of anthropological methods (semi-structured ethnographic interviews) and architectural registrations tracing the full evolution of spatial practices since 1972 through a series of furnished floor plans. Herman Hertzberger's seminal writings on "Polyvalency" (1962, 1963, 1991, & 2014), Bernard Leupen's notion of Frame and Generic Space (2009), together with John Habraken's differentiation between 'support' and 'infill' (1972) will form the theoretical framework through which Sættedammen's domestic interiors will be analysed.

While on initial inspection, the plan layouts of Sættedammen seem ruthlessly rational with their long linear load bearing walls and lateral timber roof beams. However, it is argued that the overall dimensions, sizing and relational placement of the rooms in the

houses of Sættedammen, has resulted in a highly polyvalent form of domestic architecture. A highly legible structural ‘Frame’, together with the ambiguity in programmatic use of the resulting spaces, has given agency to the inhabitants to appropriate the different rooms in a multitude of ways. These are valuable lessons for practitioners involved in the production of contemporary housing.

The Architecture of Limited-Profit Housing: Vienna Donaustadt, 1920–2030

Rebekka Hirschberg

Ghent University

This paper examines a case study area in the north-west of Vienna where eight housing developments from the past 100 years can be analysed side by side. All projects were realized as publicly subsidized, limited-profit housing (*gemeinnütziger Wohnbau*), regulated under Austrian limited-profit housing law. Within this legal framework, housing provision is conceived as serving the common good: rents are cost-based, profits are limited, and the housing stock is intended to remain permanently affordable for future generations.

Despite this shared institutional framework, the eight projects—constructed in different decades—vary significantly in their architecture: They range from interwar terraced settlements with collective facilities and productive gardens; to settlement housing on large plots emphasizing subsistence; to dense low-rise housing from the 1990s with private, walled-in gardens for recreation; to housing built above a supermarket in response to rising land prices; and finally to a contemporary large-scale development of up to ten stories—yet to be realized—with projected neighbourhood infrastructure.

The analysis focuses on the architecture and programming of these housing developments, addressing both the individual dwellings and the public, semi-public, and shared spaces in and between buildings as they are designed, inhabited, and used in everyday life. It also examines the actors involved in shaping these spaces, tracing forms of cooperation between limited-profit housing associations, many of them cooperatives, the municipality, and residents.

Methodologically, the paper combines architectural and policy analysis with archival research, urban ethnography, analytical drawing, and expert and resident interviews. Taken together, it demonstrates how the architecture of limited-profit housing in Vienna reflects changing demographic, social, and economic conditions, and how ideas of the household, community, and the common good are materialized in built form.

Adaptive reuse for affordable and new forms of housing

Constanze Wolfgring

Politecnico di Milano, DASTU

Francesca Serrazanetti

Politecnico di Milano, DASTU

Gennaro Postiglione

Politecnico di Milano, DASTU

Cities across Europe face a double housing crisis, driven by declining affordability and the growing environmental footprint of the built environment. At the same time, profound demographic transformations – smaller households, ageing populations, and evolving family structures – demand increasingly diversified housing solutions. Addressing these challenges requires not only increased housing provision, but innovation in housing design and organisation, as well as policy instruments capable of integrating social and ecological objectives. At the architectural scale, this opens space for experimenting with new housing typologies that reorganise the relationship between private dwelling units and shared spaces.

We argue that adaptive reuse – the change of function of a building involving material transformation (Pendlebury & Veldpaus 2022) – can become a strategic vehicle to address these issues together, linking affordable and diversified housing with reduced resource consumption. By mobilising the spatial and material potential of large-scale non-residential buildings, reuse can enable cost containment, tenure diversification, and alternative models of housing provision. When grounded in careful observation of contemporary dwelling practices – the challenges of transformation can foster the identification of innovative spatial paradigms and devices. Such transformations demand an integrated perspective at the intersection of architecture and housing policy, as governance arrangements, ownership configurations, and subsidy regimes determine whether adaptive reuse can contribute to non-speculative, affordable housing.

The paper conceptualises adaptive reuse as a multi-scalar field in which the material reorganisation of buildings and the political-economic frameworks of housing provision are interlinked, framing reuse simultaneously as architectural strategy and housing policy approach in the pursuit of affordability, resource efficiency, and new forms of housing.

Unlocking Residential Potential in Office Buildings. Contemporary Adaptive Reuse Cases

Gérald Ledent

UCLouvain

The reconfiguration of office work, accelerated by the Covid-19 crisis has resulted in widespread vacancy across urban office markets. In cities historically structured around the tertiary economy, vacancy has reached significant proportions, as in Brussels, where they now exceed 1,200,000 m². Rather than a crisis, office vacancy is a strategic opportunity. As Carl Elefante reminds us, ‘the greenest building is one that is already built,’ making this existing vacant stock a lever for future housing.

This research explores the residential potential of vacant office buildings and, in particular, the housing typologies they can accommodate. While previous studies have emphasized the technical and spatial constraints of such conversions (excessive floorplate depth, rigid circulation cores, façade systems ill-suited to terraces, limited daylight penetration, etc.), recent built and speculative projects in Western Europe reveal new possibilities.

These office structures can generate alternative housing typologies, including: cluster units combining multiple bedrooms around shared spaces, dwellings featuring ground-level storage, rather than relegating it to basements, hybrid live-work typologies, co-housing configurations, deeper-than-standard terraces, generous collective spaces and circulation areas, and expansive ground floors operating as direct interfaces with public space.

Such pioneering projects are crucial to show the value of these approaches and tackle common barriers to office-to-residential conversion, from insurance and structural challenges to profitability and vacancy taxes. Beyond these obstacles lies a transformative urban potential.

Just as repurposing industrial structures gave rise to the loft as a new housing typology, large-scale office conversions could spark new forms of living arrangements. In this sense, vacancy is not merely surplus space, but a latent architectural resource capable of reshaping both domestic life and the contemporary city.

The Art of Inhabitation: Incremental Housing in Performance

Nelson Mota

Delft University of Technology

Brook Teklehaimanot Haileselassie,

Frederique van Andel

Peninah Mutonga

Rohan Varma

The contemporary provision of affordable housing in rapidly urbanizing regions is shaped by two competing policy paradigms: resilience and efficiency. Resilience-oriented approaches embrace incompleteness and adaptability, often through bottom-up processes. Efficiency-driven models favour standardized, closed systems implemented through top-down planning. While resilient strategies frequently struggle to address the scale of housing demand, efficiency-led solutions tend to impose one-size-fits-all models that often disrupt livelihoods and quality of life.

This paper investigates incremental housing as a design and managerial strategy capable of reconciling resilience with efficiency. It examines patterns of inhabitation emerging from user-initiated transformations in incremental housing projects developed from the 1950s through the 2000s. Using a comparative analysis of five case studies—three in Africa (Morocco, Ethiopia, and Kenya), one in South America (Peru), and one in India—spanning six decades and diverse geopolitical contexts, the study explores how incremental approaches integrate top-down planning with bottom-up spatial agency. Each case is documented through graphic syntheses of spatial transformation over time, drawing on ethnographic research, archival material, and socio-spatial analysis. Focusing on design features at the cluster scale, the paper highlights how built outcomes and patterns of inhabitation result from the interaction between masterplan decisions and dwelling-level adaptations.

By correlating design strategies, patterns of inhabitation, and incremental development processes, the study challenges the conventional opposition between resilience and efficiency. It argues that incompleteness, when strategically embedded in design, can serve as a productive framework for delivering adaptable, affordable, and context-sensitive housing for low- and middle-income populations, contributing to more sustainable urban development.

Towards a Methodology for Studying Collaborative Housing as Lived Spaces

Zedi Van Oostrom

Delft University of Technology

The renewed interest in Collaborative Housing (CH) in the Netherlands calls for reflection on its architecture. Currently, CH is fragmented and marginal in the Netherlands, yet existing projects are architecturally diverse and experimental, both spatially and technically.

With current policy ambitions at the municipal and national levels to scale up, research on the social and spatial attributes of CH has been lacking. Case studies on CH projects have made some assumptions on the effectiveness of spatial architectural choices yet have been unable to lead to applicable principles or guidelines.

This paper addresses this gap by developing a methodological foundation for studying CH as lived and evolving spaces. Rather than presenting empirical findings, this paper reflects on methods used to study collaborative homes and builds upon hypotheses derived from earlier studies to work towards sampling criteria, relevant variables and analytical methods to assess the resilience of CH projects. The aim of this paper and further studies is to understand the relationship between spatial architectural choices and socio-cultural values.

This study argues that this requires longitudinal and comparative research strategies. The paper proposes a methodological framework for researching collaborative homes that combines quantitative project analysis with in-depth case studies. Quantitative project analysis could inform a categorization within Dutch CH projects based on design approaches.

Case studies could then further explore how these approaches have worked throughout time through path dependency, interviews and fieldwork. By establishing this research design, the paper contributes towards developing socio-spatial design principles for resilient collaborative living and provides a foundation for assessing how collaborative housing intentions are translated and adapted in practice.

Architecture as an Evolving Infrastructure: Adaptability and Exaptation in Southeastern European Socialist Mass Housing

Ludovica Rolando

CAPRIS UKIM

Socialist mass housing remains a defining feature of the urban landscape in South-Eastern Europe, having accommodated over 70% of the regional population by the 1980s (Topham, 1990: 402). These estates were designed according to the ideals of solidarity, equality, and worker self-management. On the contrary, since the 1990s, the neoliberal transition has shifted housing from a collective social good to a market commodity, triggering fragmented ownership, weakened governance, and the erosion of public space.

Drawing on the theories of Brand (1995) and the biological concept of exaptation (Gould & Vrba, 1982), this paper reframes Socialist mass housing as a “learning” legacy that evolves through the contingent co-option of existing built elements for new uses and meanings. This approach positions the urban field as a reservoir of qualities to be actively renegotiated through formal and informal practices, moving beyond a more traditional notion of heritage preservation.

The thin or thick deposit of traces represents the materialized time of the city, intertwined with the bodies that inhabit it. This research navigates two temporalities: the memory of the subjects and the persistent city, slowly modified by its inhabitants. To do so, the study examines two primary cases, Block 5 in Podgorica and the City Wall in Skopje, looking at the interdependence between the architectural enabling conditions, informal practices, and their subsequent institutionalization.

By mapping these physical changes through archival records and oral testimonies, the paper aims to trace the latent potential within the process of city-making. Consequently, the research redefines mass housing as dynamic infrastructure (Habraken, 1972 [1962]), challenging dominant tabula rasa paradigms of new developments.

By advocating for incremental, community-led change, the paper positions architecture as a civic tool and an evolving framework for addressing contemporary affordability and adequacy crises.

Housing People, Birds and Bees? The multispecies architecture of urban lived space

Marie Stender

BUILD AAU

Lene Wiell Nordberg

BUILD AAU

Across Europe, declining town centres produce empty commercial buildings, vacant plots and shrinking high streets, raising architectural questions about how these spaces might better support everyday life, dwelling and urban nature. This paper applies an architectural–anthropological approach to analyse how built environments mediate relations between humans, animals and plants.

Drawing on recent case studies, the paper examines intentionally designed interventions such as bee and bird hotels, bioswales, planting beds and interpretive signage in Sheffield’s Grey to Green initiative with an overarching aim of attracting human residents and upgrading housing architecture. These new elements do not merely provide habitats; they communicate expectations, invite care, and educate human residents. In parallel, the paper explores spontaneous greening in Porto, where fig trees, and morning glory creepers occupy decaying residential structures. Here, multispecies dynamics unfold in openings and cavities, possibly challenging the surrounding housing architecture.

Across both cases, built form becomes a site where interspecies cohabitation and competition unfolds. By reframing derelict buildings and transformed infrastructures as living assemblages animated by more than human inhabitation and by practices of communication, interpretation and care, the paper proposes a broader understanding of housing and its lived spaces. Town centre transformations are not simply about enabling human dwelling; they involve architectures that mediate multispecies relations through material design, maintenance regimes, ecological affordances and communication.

Recognising these processes foregrounds the role of architecture in shaping how people, plants and animals perceive, contest and co produce the evolving habitats of the urban centre.

Male construction – female use: A look at the gap between planning and user needs, using the example of the Werkbundsiedlung Neubühl in Zurich

Henriette Lutz

Bern University of Applied Sciences

This presentation highlights the spatial experiences of residents of the Werkbundsiedlung Neubühl in Zurich and shows how the needs of female residents can be incorporated into planning in the context of a socially sustainable transformation process. In doing so, Neubühl, a Swiss icon of modernism, is viewed from a new perspective and existing narratives are questioned. Historical and current residents of the estate were brought together in a didactic setting to reflect on the relevance of the built and theoretical concepts of modernism and their impact on the housing and everyday lives of women in the estate. It is shown how interviews with residents not only lead to a more inclusive understanding of architectural history, but also to a deeper examination of the social dimension of architecture and the role of women as actors in housing construction. The contemporary female user perspective on a historic housing estate allows for a multi-layered approach to the familiar concepts of modernism.

Methodological inspiration for the study of the Neubühl housing estate was also found in the work of Swiss social worker, Hanni Zahner. She studied new Swiss housing estates from the 1950s, a time of great housing shortage, with a focus on the lives of women and families. Hanni Zahner's concrete and detailed resident surveys provide insights that can be used in today's studies and to raise residents' awareness of their own living environment. In general, resident interviews are a method that enables architects to reflect on the different perceptions and needs of residents in their respective times and contexts.

Learning in and from Tübingen

Sebastian Niemann

UCLouvain

Gerald Ledent

Uses & Spaces, UCLouvain

Situated idyllically on the slopes of the Neckar-River in Southern Germany, the city of Tübingen is highly shaped by its military history and university present. Concerning

housing, it faces a constantly growing and complexifying demand. Since the 1990s, the city administration has pursued an ambitious policy to promote collective and collaborative housing forms matching the financial and functional needs of all inhabitants.

Our research aims to retrace this recent development through a comparative analysis of the residential building production. To this end, we have selected paradigmatic projects from the Tübingen's housing program and analysed them at various scales, from urban setting, architectural forms to residential typologies. For this intervention, three significant urban projects (Französisches Viertel, Alte Weberei, Hechinger Eck) have been selected and analysed through drawings in plans and sections at different scales. This framework allows us to reflect and critically assess the so-called "Tübinger Model": 1. Economically, how does the city balance and articulate subsidised and free-market housing, as well as collective and collaborative forms? 2. Functionally, how does this equilibrium acknowledge and respond to the diversity of the contemporary demand? 3. Spatially, how does this diversity, reshape the components of housing and their thresholds? Tübingen's housing program promotes a form of double-balance with, on the one hand, subsidised and free-market and, on the other hand collective and collaborative housing models. Through the accumulation of experience and a dense network of engaged actors, this double-balance seems to create the conditions for the realisation of housing projects of high social and spatial qualities.

Finally, by unfolding Tübingen's specific contribution, our research aims to integrate it in the wider context of the contemporary discussion about housing in Western Europe.

THE BIOGRAPHY OF A HOUSE. DISSECTING SUBURBAN HOUSING'S TRANSFORMATIONS

Vanhamme Hugo

UCLouvain

Ledent Gérald

UCLouvain

Throughout their occupation, dwellings undergo continuous modifications. These transformations may stem from in-situ needs (e.g., household expansion) or result from ex-situ regulatory frameworks (e.g., PEB requirements). Depending on their magnitude and on the shearing layers affected, such interventions generate material flows and produce spatial reconfigurations.

This paper investigates the (inter)dependencies between matter (building materials and their extractive and environmental footprint) and spatiality (users, spaces, modes of occupation) induced by these transformations. The research is structured around a case study: the Villagexpo in Limal, Belgium. Developed in the early 1970s by the SNPPT, the project reflects public authorities' efforts to expand access to homeownership through low-interest loans. Simultaneously, an open-air exhibition occurred during construction, enabling architects and contractors to demonstrate the variety of industrialised and prefabricated building techniques used to construct the village. Over the past five decades, the Villagexpo's dwellings have evolved. Residents have modified their homes, and in some cases, occupants have changed. The contribution focuses on a specific housing type within the neighbourhood: the Rhodius–Deville houses, constructed using precast concrete façade panels.

By analysing the evolution of its construction cross-section through various archival sources, the study reconstructs the (linear) material history of this housing type. Moreover, the study reveals spatial transformations while elucidating the underlying factors that have driven those alterations. Finally, the paper examines the adaptive and energy-retrofitting capacities of these mass-produced dwellings and discusses the potential heritage value of the Villagexpo in Limal, grounded in both its technical features (diversity of post-war construction systems) and its social dimension (exhibition, traces of the initial village project).

“Is it dripping or splashing?” Practices of negotiating shared homeownership: focus on water pipes

Lukas Vejník

Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences

Hannah Krugmann

Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences

Today, many post-war housing estates are facing the challenge of comprehensive renovations. While housing corporations plan renovations in line with their business and return strategies, the picture is different for homeowner associations: In these cases, the community of apartment owners decides, plans and finances renovation projects itself. Homeowners' associations in large housing estates have hardly been researched.

We aim to analyse the significance of homeownership in preserving housing estates from an architectural and sociological perspective. Our focus lies on negotiation practices developing around shared spaces, such as corridors, green spaces, stairs or

building systems. They belong proportionally to all owners, changes can only be decided upon by majority vote. This means that the joint responsibility for the property must be negotiated democratically and may conflict with the financial plans of individual owners. We aim to take a closer look at waterpipes as an example of infrastructure that significantly affects the apartments utility value. In the negotiation of damage cases and subsequent renovation projects, (conflictual) practices of dealing with shared property crystallise. An analysis helps to better understand residential practices and the relationships between residents and architectural materiality.

Results show that in dealing with bursting pipes as in negotiating pipe renewal, owners and janitors invest social capital; a violation of reciprocity translates to material decay. While some owners integrate to a strong collective that aims to tackle seemingly immense technical challenges, others experience minimal agency, watching their shared spaces deteriorate, unable to sell and relocate. Our analysis relies on qualitative data from our dissertation projects on three post-war modernist housing estates in Western Germany. Using a GT-inspired methodology, we employ open qualitative interviews, ethnographic observations, and archival materials.

Inhabiting the Ground Floor: Retrofitting Modernist Social Housing in Quartiere San Paolo, Bari

António Carvalho

Politecnico di Milano

Alarico Ruffino

Politecnico di Milano

This paper examines the ground floor of modernist social housing as a critical site for addressing contemporary housing challenges. Focusing on Quartiere San Paolo in Bari, a large estate raised on pilotis, it reinterprets the vacant interstitial space beneath residential blocks as a spatial and social resource within the current housing crisis. Originally conceived as open communal space, these ground-level voids have become residual, often degraded or informally appropriated areas, revealing tensions between modernist housing models and present-day needs.

The research asks whether and how these underused spaces can support forms of “unconventional affordable housing” and activate new relationships between dwelling and the public realm. Drawing on theories of thresholds, in-between spaces, and the ground-floor interface, the study frames ground-level inhabitation as a strategy for redefining accessibility, domesticity, and social interaction in collective housing.

Methodologically, the paper adopts a research-by-design approach developed within an architectural design studio at Politecnico di Milano. Design proposals for inhabiting the pilotis operate as exploratory scenarios, testing spatial configurations, user profiles, and degrees of public–private mediation. These projects are analysed not as final solutions but as research instruments that reveal constraints, potentials, and policy implications.

The paper contributes to housing research by reconsidering modernist elevated housing through the lens of spatial retrofitting and incremental densification. It argues that reactivating the ground floor can provide affordable housing opportunities while strengthening neighbourhood cohesion and redefining the interface between architecture and urban life. Keywords: Social housing; Ground-floor inhabitation; Modernist housing estates; Affordable housing; Spatial retrofitting; Research by design; Urban regeneration.

Social housing's 'architectures of inclusion'. The case study of Parkwijk's renovation afterlife, Turnhout, Belgium

Katja Roslevitch

KU Leuven

Most post-war social housing estates in Belgium are originated from the necessity to provide affordable housing for the working class. It came to life as one of the principles to redistribute the welfare that was being generated, with other words to construct a more just society. Renowned architects contributed to the question of how to design for the mass, influenced by the modernist ideologies.

Over the years, this inclusive instrument became increasingly marginal and stigmatized in society because of societal disinvestment and disinterest. In the meantime, the social patrimony has aged, marked by a long period of neglect in terms of necessary care and maintenance. With the European goal to become climate neutral by 2050, social housing started receiving the needed attention. Funds and resources are being made available to tackle the renovation need, which is highly necessary in social housing because of the large amount of unhealthy and energy-consuming dwellings. This, again, can be framed as inclusive measures for social housing residents in our society, but how inclusive are these measures and does the end justify the means?

This contribution wants to investigate the 'architectures of inclusion' of social housing and through renovation from the perspective of the residents, in dialogue with the social housing managers and architects. With 'architectures of inclusion' is meant the systems and their operational choices that have a claim on inclusion and justice. This contribution will discuss the transformation of the social housing estate Parkwijk in

Turnhout, Belgium. It is designed and built as a garden city in the '60s and '70s by renowned Belgian architects from the modernistic Turnhoutse School movement. This contribution will focus on the inhabitation and the life of residents through architectural ethnographic fieldwork.

Affording Participation: The Cultural Geometry of Inclusion in Danish Social Housing

Michael Ulfstjerne

Aalborg University

The expression “having a seat at the table” (sidde med ved bordet) is a widely used idiom for inclusion and participation in contemporary Danish political discourse. In Danish social housing, it evokes local tenant democracy through formats such as “afdelingsmøder, beboermøder, borgermøder” and other forms of citizen involvement. Here, participation is often quite literally organized around tables. As both metaphor and material arrangement, the table affords particular forms of engagement. Thinking through Gibson’s theory of affordances, the table invites participants to sit, drink coffee, face one another, (preferably) speak in turn, and appear formally equal. In doing so, it shapes how inclusion is understood and practiced.

This paper presents reflections from the early stages of a study with and in two Danish housing areas experimenting with new models of citizen involvement. Among housing organisations it’s commonly observed how their tables fall short of recruiting people from a more diverse demography, which points to the existence of a certain kind of “outsideness” (udenforskab), denoting both a social position and spatialized experience. Nevertheless, a closer into the social and spatial dynamics suggest that many do in fact take part, albeit in forms that play out beyond tables. Inspired by Keith Murphy’s notion of cultural geometry (2013), participation is approached as a culturally patterned spatial relation. While both the proverbial and concrete meeting table structures one recognizable geometry of democratic engagement, other practices such as courtyard gatherings, maintenance initiatives, care networks, and digital exchanges operate according to different spatial logics that are rarely acknowledged as participatory or particularly democratic.

By foregrounding housing architecture and shared spaces as material and social infrastructures, the paper explores how democratic inclusion is shaped and constrained through the affordances of built form.

From Green Architectural Icon to Lived Home: Environmental Innovation and Everyday Life in the High-rise Vertikal in Oslo

Nora Berg Tveter

University of Oslo

Per Gunnar Røe

Department of Sociology and Human Geography at University of Oslo

This paper explores how environmental ambitions are materialised in a high-rise housing project, and the lived experiences of people inhabiting such a building. It is based on an ethnographic study of Vertikal, a newly built «green» high-rise in Oslo. High-rises are central to compact city and densification strategies yet widely criticised for their carbon footprints and their problematic social implications.

The study approaches Vertikal as a socio-technical construct where architecture, technology and everyday practices are mutually constitutive, and draws on interviews with key actors and residents, alongside document studies and on-site observations. It traces how environmental ambitions are translated into architectural form and marketing narratives, and how these translations are taken up and reworked through residential practices. The main findings are that Vertikal was framed more as an experimental environmental project than a conventional profit-driven development. Marketing materials ritualise the building as an exclusive green way of life, so that socio-technical relations begin before moving in. However, inhabitants experience that flaws and unfinished details undermine dwelling quality, yet also bring residents together in shared struggles, fostering knowledge-sharing and neighbourliness.

The paper argues that Vertikal is socially sustainable in some respects, while remaining exclusionary in terms of affordability, expert-led environmental innovation and controversial design. While Vertikal demonstrates what green technological innovation in a high-rise can achieve, it also exposes the limits of social sustainability when benefits are enjoyed mainly by privileged residents.

It reveals how environmental and social dimensions of sustainability coexist and are conflicted in high-rise developments, in ways that have to be dealt with if such projects also are to contribute to a socially inclusive green shift.

High-Rise Sustainabilities Between Representations and Realities: Design and Lived Experiences in High-rise developments in Oslo

Per Gunnar Røe

University of Oslo

Rebecca Cavicchia

Norwegian University of Life Sciences and University of Oslo

Roberta Cucca

Norwegian University of Life Sciences and University of Oslo

Nora Berg Tveter

University of Oslo

High-rise buildings are in many ways the uttermost expression of the compact city model. They are extreme versions of physical densification, technological advancement and utilization of horizontal and vertical infrastructures, in ways that are considered crucial in urban sustainability strategies. However, there is a growing literature questioning the carbon footprint of such buildings and their metabolic implications related to materials and energy. The sustainability of the high-rise model depends on and assumes specific social practices, infrastructures and mobility patterns. At the same time, high-rise buildings are embedded in social, economic and material contexts that may or may not support sustainable outcomes.

In this paper we challenge these assumptions, based on investigations of two high-rise developments in the inner city of Oslo. Oslo has adopted a compact city model and a high-rise strategy, which contribute to the transformation of the city. We investigate the implementation of these policies by commissioned architects and real estate developers, and the social realities taking place in these buildings and their vicinities. We base our study on planning documents, architectural designs and renderings, observations of the built environments and social practices, and interviews with actors involved in the development process as well as residents and workers in these buildings.

Our findings reveal that the buildings' design, the microeconomic calculations shaping their development, and the everyday practices and lived experiences of the buildings' users, may contradict the expectations of how high-rise buildings may contribute to urban sustainability. Based on this study and current literature, we provide a critique of

the sustainability claims associated with high-rise development and discuss the gap between high-rise representations and lived realities.

Social Mix and Micro-Segregation in the Densified City: Shared Spaces and Everyday life in a High-Rise Development in Oslo

Roberta Cucca

NMBU

Rebecca Cavicchia

Norwegian University of Life Sciences

Per Gunnar Røe

University of Oslo

Nora Berg Tveter

University of Oslo

This paper examines how social mix produced through urban densification translates into everyday residential practices and micro-scale segregation within housing architecture. In many cities, densification has become an urban development strategy aimed at limiting urban sprawl and promoting compact urban living. At the same time, densification is often expected to foster social mix by bringing different social groups into closer spatial proximity within neighbourhoods and buildings.

The paper explores these dynamics in Oslo, a city historically characterized by low-density expansion and strong horizontal socio-spatial segregation. Recent densification strategies increasingly rely on high-rise residential developments, which may vertically concentrate socially diverse populations within the same housing structures. While such developments may increase social diversity at the neighbourhood level, they also create new architectural environments where micro-scale socio-spatial divisions may emerge within buildings. The study presents an in-depth case study of a high-rise development in Majorstua, an affluent area in Oslo. Particular attention is given to the role of architectural design and the organization of shared spaces (entrances, corridors, and common facilities) in structuring everyday encounters among residents. These spaces constitute key sites where the tension between social mix and micro-segregation becomes visible, shaping patterns of sociability, distance, and belonging. Empirically, the research combines statistical analysis with qualitative methods, including systematic observation of shared spaces and interviews with residents.

The findings suggest that while densification may produce social mix in demographic terms, the material organization and governance of shared spaces often reproduce forms of social distance. The paper therefore highlights how architecture mediates the relationship between proximity and separation in densified urban environments.

Rethinking Health, Housing and the Body through Literacy Narratives

Yankel Fijalkow

ENSAPVS

Yaneira WILSON

ENSAPVS

Health in the home has long been approached through a hygienist perspective focused on preventing disease by combating unsanitary housing conditions. While this approach significantly improved living standards, it also generated forms of behavioural regulation that standardized bodies and domestic practices while contributing to social inequalities.

Today, climate change and energy transition policies have reframed debates on housing and health. Energy renovation is increasingly promoted as both an ecological and social necessity. In France, nearly four million households experience energy poverty, often associated with thermal discomfort and health effects such as respiratory illness, fatigue, and psychological stress. Yet public discourse surrounding renovation largely prioritizes building performance and energy consumption, overlooking residents' embodied experiences of housing. At the same time, the concept of health literacy has gained prominence in public health debates, emphasizing individuals' capacity to access and use health-related information. However, this perspective often shifts responsibility onto individuals while neglecting the material and sensory conditions through which health is experienced within domestic spaces.

Drawing on the SAPHIR research project, based on around one hundred interviews conducted across diverse housing types in the Paris region, this paper proposes a critical reading of health housing literacy through residents' narratives. It shows how bodily sensations—cold, heat, breathability, fatigue—mediate everyday interactions with ventilation systems, heating devices, and energy-saving technologies. By foregrounding these embodied experiences, the paper argues for a broader understanding of health housing literacy that reconnects housing policies, domestic infrastructures, and lived bodily experience.

Dwelt Into Being: The Biography of Socialist Mass Housing in New Belgrade

Dalia Dukanac

University of Belgrade - Faculty of Architecture

Mariolina Affatato
Politecnico di Torino

Caterina Barioglio
Politecnico di Torino

Institute for Philosophy and Social Theory
University of Belgrade

Bežanija Blocks (New Belgrade, Serbia, former Yugoslavia), contain four large-scale mass housing blocks (nos. 61-64) spanning two kilometres in length. Designed and built between 1965 and 1988, they became an icon of the brutalist era of socialist-modernist architecture. Yet, behind these massive stepped volumes and concrete walls hides a tapestry of entangled histories - homes built for an average military family, buildings shaped by strict urban and construction regulations, neighbourhoods adapted to radical demographic and social changes, and space appropriated and reinterpreted through dwelling practices.

Drawing on architectural anthropology, we treat these as sites where designed and inhabited space are co-constitutive. Several cases of recurring trans-scalar practices have been identified and elaborated: the macro scale investigation encompassed various public spaces, while the micro scale included different apartment types dispersed across the Blocks. Both threads of research draw on ethnographic fieldwork, in-situ spatial documentation, and oral histories from long-term residents, tracing how material modifications accumulate into collective spatial biography.

By superimposing these threads we aim to understand how residents enact the boundary between public and private - through thresholds, objects, routines, and appropriations - in comparison to how the designers once drew it. We focus on spaces designed for youth and families, such as “spaces for children’s play” repurposed into annexes of a kindergarten, or playgrounds that turn into sites for communal resistance, but also the typical “children’s half room” which shaped today’s housing standards and market.

Finally, we explore Bežanija Blocks as an urban entity, whose structure, spatial resources and original design principles are able to foster contemporary urban family life, while asking how people make domesticity legible, and how the idea of a common good is not only designed, but dwelt into being.

Renovating futures: Living, working, and belonging through Japan's empty house renovation projects

Natasha Durie

University of Oxford

'I can't say that they are wrong, they can want what they want... But I don't want that!'. This is how Toru-san, a Japanese architecture graduate in his 20s challenges the norm that young people want to marry, move out of their parents' homes, and buy a new house. He continues, 'And there are more and more [empty house renovation] projects like this one across Japan, so maybe what people want is changing'. Across Japan, nine million homes stand empty, yet more and more young people are transforming these unused spaces into something new. From community cafés and art spaces to share houses and private homes, these DIY renovation projects are quietly reshaping ideas of work, home, and belonging in contemporary Japan.

This research draws on 15 months of ethnographic fieldwork with empty house renovators primarily from Gifu and Hiroshima prefectures, as well as Tokyo, Osaka, Kyoto, and Tokushima. By participating in amateur architectural learning and making practices, I explore the people undertaking these projects and the methods and materials that they are using.

Firstly, I discuss the ethics that emerge in on-site problem-solving and decision-making implicit in DIY renovations. This shows how visions of a desired future guide not only the use of space, design choices, and material selections, but also the incremental processes of daily repair.

Secondly, I show how these amateur architectural practices offer a way of building meaningful and fulfilling lives amidst growing precarity. I situate the broader empty house renovation movement within the context of Japan's shifting labour and housing markets, looking at why some young people are turning away from traditional housing solutions and employment and instead towards renovating empty houses.

Before Leisure: Shared Space and the Material Politics of Time in Red Vienna

Jerome Becker

KU Leuven

Since the onset of modern urbanisation, transformations in the synchronisation of living and working have reshaped the daily rhythms and temporal patterns of urban life. These shifts have not occurred without conflict. Time remains a contested resource—whether in struggles against exploitative working hours, in demands for more free time, or in resistance to the gendered and racialised divisions of labour. Although time appears to belong to us, it is continually appropriated, exchanged, and commodified: spent on others or sold as labour time. How time is used and experienced is therefore neither universal nor purely individual; it depends on the political, economic, and spatial conditions that shape social relations.

This paper examines the reciprocal relationship between the socio-political coordination of urban life and the spatial conditions in which multiple temporalities unfold, focusing on the politics of time and the architecture of shared space in Red Vienna's municipal housing programme (1919–1934). This historical case stands out as a rare instance in which time was explicitly treated as a matter of political negotiation and redistribution.

Drawing on archival research, policy documents, discourse analysis, and fieldwork, the paper first examines Austromarxist conceptions of time (abstract, projective, relational). It then investigates how these ideas informed the spatial organisation of municipal housing across different scales, particularly through communal spaces and shared infrastructures for provision, education, leisure, and care. Finally, it considers the lived experiences of current residents of Sandleitenhof, Karl-Seitz-Hof, and Rabenhof. R

evisiting this well-studied case through a chronopolitical lens highlights an underexplored dimension of housing in Red Vienna and invites speculation on how still-existing shared spaces might shape social time relations today beyond isolated households and naïve collectivism.

Towards Sustainable Communities and Housing Actors, Interventions and Solutions

Transformable Public Space as Dual-Use Infrastructure: Co-Producing Climate-Resilient and Inclusive Urban Shelter

Merve Özhan

Gebze Technical University

The project aims to develop a model for transformable public spaces that are both climate-resilient and universally accessible, bridging the gap between everyday urban infrastructure and emergency shelter needs. It frames shelter as a socio-technical system embedded within the city and governance structures, guided by principles of accessibility and inclusivity.

Modular structures act as public amenities, providing shade and regulating microclimates, while promoting social interaction and equitable access. These modules are designed to be secure and easily deployable in emergencies, using screw-free joint systems that allow low-skill assembly for immediate shelter provision.

Drawing on lessons from community-built modular infrastructures after the 2023 earthquake in Türkiye, the project redefines resilience as a collaborative process between communities, volunteers, and spatial infrastructures. In Istanbul, it explores how lightweight structures can shift from daily use to emergency response, tackling earthquake risks and urban heat island effects while ensuring inclusivity.

The project employs participatory action research to generate insights into co-production, universal accessibility, and community capacity building. Data collection combines qualitative feedback, spatial performance analysis, and usability assessments, while prototype evaluation considers usability, joint system performance, and social acceptance under both everyday and emergency scenarios.

Overall, the project contributes knowledge toward creating transferable dual-use infrastructure models that integrate housing resilience, universal design, and public space governance, fostering sustainable, adaptive community development.

Security Without Ownership: Transitional Climate-Resilient Housing in Unequal Urban Systems

Camila Jordan

TETO Brasil

Gabriela Arrastua

TECHO Internatiional

Across Latin America, housing systems are shaped by persistent informality, deep socioeconomic inequality, and incomplete state-led urbanization, leaving millions without access to adequate housing or secure tenure. These structural conditions intersect with climate-related hazards, intensifying risk exposure in informal settlements vulnerable to floods, landslides, and extreme heat or cold. While urban upgrading and land regularization remain central policy strategies, their extended timeframes recurrently leave households without short- and medium-term protection.

This paper examines the role of transitional, climate-resilient housing as a governance intervention within such constrained housing systems. It asks: What role can transitional housing play in producing security and belonging in contexts of unresolved tenure, and how should housing and climate policy frameworks incorporate these interventions? Drawing on a qualitative case study of the “Resilient House,” developed and implemented by TECHO in informal settlements across six Latin American countries, the paper analyses how climate-adaptive design combined with community-based implementation contributes to (1) environmental risk reduction, (2) improved habitability, and (3) strengthened local organization.

The study is based on program documentation, semi-structured interviews with community members and institutional partners, and field-based implementation evidence. The findings suggest that transitional, climate-resilient housing constitutes a critical yet underrecognized component of adaptive housing systems. Rather than serving as a substitute for permanent solutions, these interventions mediate between emergency response and long-term urban integration, reshaping notions of property, security, and belonging in highly vulnerabilized contexts.

The paper argues for their institutional recognition within housing and climate governance frameworks as part of sustainable and equitable urban transformation.

From policy intentions to practice: professionals' perspectives on distressed homeowners in Flanders

Ilke Kerkhofs

University of Antwerp

Promoting homeownership has been a focal point in past and current policies in Belgium, resulting in a majority of households being homeowners, an insufficient social housing sector and a private rental market in crisis for financially vulnerable households.

Within this context, an estimated 4% of homeowners is confronted with inadequate housing quality and major renovation needs without being able to make thorough changes to their living situation. Although policy is implementing measures to support the lower incomes when it comes to renovation, distressed homeowners are more likely to encounter barriers to formal renovation pathways. This possible informal undercurrent is not understood or represented in current data. Furthermore, it needs to be questioned whether the implementation methods are appropriate or sufficient not to lose spatial quality.

How do professionals in the field of housing support, perceive the needs and thresholds they see in practice, compared to studies or policy implications around distressed homeowners? To what extent do they reach vulnerable homeowners in their own practice and are they consolidating a system that is in its core not working?

The research is situated in a post-industrial region in Flanders characterised by high poverty rates, an ageing housing stock of working-class dwellings, relatively low housing prices and limited institutional proximity. A key entry point into the field is a renovation support project funded by the Flemish Distressed Homeowners Fund in collaboration with a welfare organisation.

The present contribution analyses interviews that are currently held with professionals, both from a non-architectural and architectural background, either being based in the case study area, either being part of an organisation involved. These interviews are a key element to understand the renovation challenges of distressed homeowners in Flemish context, coming forth from the experiences and different roles of professionals.

International examples, opportunities and challenges with rightsizing of the single-family home

Mette Mechlenborg

Aalborg University

Jesper Ole Jensen

Aalborg University

The single-family house (SFH) remains one of the most dominant and desired housing types across Europe, North America, and Australia, yet it constitutes a central academic and policy challenge in the sustainable transition of housing systems.

International research shows that the challenge is not limited to building performance. Despite technological improvements and stricter energy standards, average dwelling sizes continue to grow, household sizes shrink, and under-occupancy increases. Across Europe, a substantial share of SFHs are inhabited by one- or two-person households, often older adults aging in place. This creates a structural mismatch between housing stock and demographic realities, intensifying carbon emissions, infrastructure costs, and housing shortages elsewhere in the system.

This paper investigates the international rightsizing agenda, reframes the problem by integrating three strategic approaches: re-union (intergenerational housing and sharing schemes), re-location (mobility incentives and downsizing strategies), and re-structuring (gentle densification and subdivision of existing plots). Cases from Belgium, Germany, Ireland, Australia, Canada, and the United States illustrate how municipalities experiment with advisory services, financial incentives, zoning reforms, and mediated housing exchanges to activate what has been termed the “hidden housing reserve” within underused homes.

The international perspective demonstrates that transforming the SFH is not merely a technical task but a socio-political endeavour requiring voluntary, incentive-based, and context-sensitive governance models capable of aligning climate mitigation, demographic adaptation, and housing equity.

Regenerating Nature, Reinforcing Inequality? Housing (In)Justice in Post-Socialist Cluj-Napoca

Diana Andreea Galos (Pogacean)

Center for Housing Research Paris

Silviu Medeşan

University of Oradea

Vlad Sebastian Rusu

Technical University Cluj-Napoca

Romania records one of the highest homeownership rates in Europe, reaching 97% in the early 2000s after the post-socialist privatization of public housing. In the 1990s, the state sold former social dwellings to tenants at symbolic prices, marking a structural withdrawal from housing provision and consolidating a privatized housing regime. Housing became a predominantly private asset, embedded in a cultural and financialized ownership model sustained by mortgages and banking mechanisms.

Against this background, the paper examines the regeneration of Feroviarilor Park in Cluj-Napoca, a rapidly growing secondary city shaped by a strong university presence and the expansion of high-income sectors such as IT, banking, and business services. These dynamics have intensified real estate pressure, making Cluj the most expensive housing market in Romania in terms of rents and sale prices. Originally a neglected green space in a former railway workers' neighbourhood, the park was threatened by privatization in the 2000s. Following sustained grassroots mobilization, it was reclaimed as a public good and became the first park in Romania redeveloped through an architectural design competition preceded by participatory processes. While celebrated as a model of commons recovery and nature-based regeneration, the project has also triggered green gentrification. Rising land values and speculative housing developments nearby have reshaped both the built environment and the area's social composition. Lower-income residents are gradually excluded or displaced, while an upwardly mobile middle class redefines the neighbourhood.

The paper argues that environmental regeneration, in a hyper-ownership and weak-policy context, can reinforce socio-spatial inequality. Drawing on document analysis, media discourse, planning documents, and field observations, the study highlights the need to govern green regeneration through robust public housing and anti-speculative policies.

Care-full housing as a bridge between social and ecological goals

Hans Volmary

Dresden University of Technology

Anna Pagani

King's College London

As Europe faces a deepening housing crisis, the gap between social and ecological considerations is widening. In England, regeneration – largely entailing the demolition and reconstruction of (social) housing estates – continues to be promoted as a response to an apparent shortage of housing across the market and social sectors. This approach overlooks negative environmental impacts as well as effects on residents' health and wellbeing.

Our contribution proposes an alternative narrative by reconsidering regeneration through a care-ethical lens that integrates social and ecological dimensions. We follow Fisher & Tronto's (1990) conception of care as everything we do to maintain, preserve and repair our shared world, and draw on feminist geographers' view of housing as an infrastructure of care to position regeneration as an act of non-care.

We argue that demolition normalises a replace-over-repair logic which disrupts practices of maintenance and long-term stewardship, thereby contributing to a “care-less” system that is highly profitable for developers and investors but undermines the ability to sustain socially and ecologically viable housing futures. We operationalise our theoretical framework in two steps.

First, we analyse 38 interviews with stakeholders in the English social housing sector. The interviews support the identification of causal links between housing demolition, and its social and ecological implications (e.g. noise and pollution; displacement and loss of networks). Second, we present initiatives in England that demonstrate how “care-full” housing practices, centred on maintenance and repair, are already underway, and discuss the extent to which these initiatives reconcile the social and ecological dimensions of housing.

Overall, our contribution provides new insights to advance research and practice to bridge the gap between socio-ecological objectives in the face of an ever more complex polycrisis.

Housing Precarity by Design: Governing Licensees in Ireland's Informal Housing Sector

Valesca Lima

Dublin City University

This paper examines a largely invisible but expanding segment of Ireland's private rental sector: residential licence arrangements. These informal occupancy models that fall outside core tenancy protections.

Drawing on mixed-methods research including focus groups with licensees, interviews with housing experts, and analysis of Residential Tenancies Board tribunal decisions, this study conceptualises licence housing as a form of state-sanctioned informality. While promoted as a flexible supply solution during a housing crisis, licence arrangements systematically exclude occupants from security of tenure, regulated eviction procedures, deposit protections, and formal dispute resolution.

The result is a precarious sub-market characterised by short-notice evictions, ambiguous legal status, and limited access to justice. The paper argues that sustainable communities cannot be built upon legally precarious housing foundations.

By incentivising lightly regulated room rental through tax policy while withholding reciprocal protections, the current framework externalises social risk onto vulnerable households, including students, migrants and low-income workers. Rather than treating licenced housing as marginal or temporary, it should be understood as an embedded feature of contemporary housing governance.

The paper concludes by outlining proportionate regulatory reforms that would strengthen tenure security, improve standards, and align informal rental practices with broader sustainability and resilience goals.

The Research of Housing Component in the Quality of Life Initiative on the Example of the City of Kragujevac, Serbia

Branislav Antonic

University of Belgrade - Faculty of Architecture

Ivan Radulovic

City of Kragujevac

Jovana Stefanovic

University of Belgrade - Faculty of Architecture

The quality of life (QoL) is a certain city is always among the main determinants in developing local urban policy. The United Nations Human Settlements Programme (UN-Habitat) kicked off a new global programme – the Quality of Live Initiative (QoLI) – in 2023. The reason for this is the challenging implementation of QoL at local level: to understand, measure, and apply the development elements that will enhance it. A starting point in this process is Sustainable development goals (SDGs), which are essential to form the tools that will enable the evaluation of QoL indicators and advancement in local policy development relating to the QoL.

This research presents the implementation of the QoLI in the City of Kragujevac in central Serbia in 2025. The implementation was a comprehensive process based on two types of indicators and different types of data to be evaluated in local context. Global-layer indicators are the same for all global cities involved in the QoLI, but they are evaluated locally. In contrast to them, local-layer indicators had to be first determined in city and, then, evaluated. The whole process is tailored to be inclusive, comprising the different forms of citizen participation.

The focus of this research is on the housing in the QoLI implementation, which makes on nine QoLI domains. Basically, two global-layer indicators directly refer to the evaluation of the quality of local housing, while several others are indirectly linked with it. Furthermore, several additional housing-related indicators were created through urban participation to analyse the local layer in the QoLI implementation. Understanding critical findings from measuring the indicators and their implications are key inputs for shaping human-centred local policy documents. In Kragujevac, this is evident for the findings of housing quality, as they confirm a gap in obtained values between by quantitative- and qualitative-based indicators.

Housing and transport emissions: ensuring a just transition to sustainable communities?

Nessa Winston

University College Dublin

Monika Pedroso

University College Dublin

Ciaran McDomhnaill

University College Dublin

A Just Transition requires implementing equitable mitigation strategies to reduce carbon emissions. However, in designing such policies it is important to examine structural inequalities in emissions and the consumption of wealthy households. In addition, it is essential to investigate the impact of mitigation policies on more vulnerable households and their ability to transition to clean and affordable energy. Eco-social policies and sustainable welfare have been proposed as ways of transforming the social situation of more vulnerable households while also reducing emissions.

This paper examines inequalities in Irish household CO₂ emissions to highlight those groups who emit most and least in key sector, particularly residential energy, and transport. In addition, it explores policy options which might be both socially and ecologically just and their likely impacts. We constructed a novel dataset to examine household-level energy consumption in Ireland by socio-demographic characteristics. We linked microdata from the 2022-23 wave of Ireland's Household Budget Survey (HBS) with environmental stressor coefficients extracted from a multi-regional input-output database, EXIOBASE 3.

We find some significant social inequalities in consumption patterns. Emissions vary by energy domains (e.g. residential energy and transport) and by socio-demographic factors such as household income, size and composition, education and rural/urban location. It highlights that consumption patterns, including under-consumption, and the resilience strategies of more vulnerable households can have significant negative impacts on the physical and mental health of people living in these homes.

We highlight the emission reductions achievable by reducing the energy use of higher emitters, while raising energy requirements for the wellbeing of households at the bottom.

Unlocking the Delivery of Green Space–Oriented Housing Development

Nicky Morrison

Western Sydney University

Rapid housing growth in many metropolitan regions is occurring alongside increasing exposure to extreme heat and declining access to green space. While the benefits of urban green infrastructure for cooling, health and liveability are well established, integrating these assets into housing development at scale remains a persistent governance and funding challenge.

This paper examines how green infrastructure can be delivered as core public infrastructure within housing developments, and what institutional and funding conditions are required to make this viable. The analysis draws on in-depth interviews with key stakeholders in New South Wales, Australia, a high-level policy roundtable involving state government agencies, infrastructure finance actors and planning stakeholders, and subsequent policy briefings with government departments focused on implementation pathways.

These engagements highlight persistent barriers, including fragmented responsibilities for funding and delivery, misaligned planning and infrastructure frameworks, and weak mechanisms for recognising the long-term public value of green infrastructure.

The paper argues that positioning green infrastructure as core public infrastructure linked to housing delivery creates a pathway for implementation rather than treating it as a discretionary amenity. The policy engagement explored how this framing can unlock new delivery mechanisms, including state–local cost sharing and potential access to sustainability bond financing for green infrastructure associated with housing development.

In doing so, the paper contributes to international debates on the governance and funding arrangements required to embed green infrastructure investment within housing development in an era of intensifying climate risk.

Recentering "Community" in Resilience: Understanding the potential of Community Land Trusts in local climate adaptation

Amber Khan

University of Washington

Disasters and the global affordable housing crisis are intensifying in tandem, necessitating creative community-led land tenure and housing solutions that advance climate justice while moving beyond exclusionary, dominant models.

Community Land Trusts (CLTs) hold promise as an emergent, yet underutilized, approach to improving local climate adaptation efforts. Case studies demonstrate that CLTs can prevent displacement of low-income communities after disasters (Barger et al., 2024; Leckie, 2013; Veronesi, Algoed, & Hernández Torrales, 2022), promote decarbonization through climate-resilient and energy-efficient housing design (Wang et al., 2023), and foster shared equity structures that enable collective governance, a vital practice for effective climate adaptation and resilience (Wannowitz, Petzold, & Garschagen, 2023). However, a comprehensive framework outlining how CLTs contribute to climate resilience remains undeveloped.

This study draws on semi-structured interviews with CLT staff and board members across Europe, the United States, Canada, Brazil, Australia, and India to address two key questions: What mechanisms enable CLTs to support climate resilience? And what best practices, barriers, and opportunities shape implementation of climate resilience strategies within CLTs? Preliminary findings suggest that CLTs advance resilience through sustainable building practices, policy and advocacy, community education, rematriation, and programming that strengthens social connection.

Concurrently, CLTs face significant financial, structural, and environmental barriers, which they navigate through innovative strategies, such as building regional networks tailored to local needs.

Together, these insights contribute to a clearer understanding of how CLTs can offer critical, community-led resilience strategies in the face of compounding climate and housing crises.

Housing Inequalities and Ecological Transition Policies: Insights from Italian Cities

Constanze Wolfgring

Politecnico di Milano, DASTU

Marco Peverini

Politecnico di Milano, DASTU

Lorenzo Caresana

Politecnico di Milano, DASTU

Anita Susani

ÖGUT, Vienna

The relationship between environmental and energy policies and housing inequalities is becoming increasingly relevant. While innovation in the construction industry and the residential sector plays a crucial role in the green transition, its social and distributive implications have so far been under investigated. Drawing on the Horizon Europe project ReHousIn (Reducing Housing Inequalities in the Green Transition, 2024-2027), which aims to fill this gap, this paper presents first findings from three Italian cities – Milan, Reggio Emilia, and Assisi – on how this relationship unfolds.

The paper investigates the role of three policy fields – energy retrofit, urban regeneration and densification, and nature-based solutions – and their intersection with housing and affordability conditions. The analysis combines quantitative indicators on housing inequalities, policy and document analysis, around 40 semi-structured qualitative interviews with key actors, and insights from two Policy Labs involving stakeholders from the fields of housing, planning, and environmental policies. First findings show that ecological transition policies clearly generate value(s) – improved energy performance, environmental and neighbourhood quality, and housing conditions – but that benefits are socially and territorially unequally distributed.

Recent energy retrofit schemes have predominantly benefited private homeowners and areas with higher real estate values, while public tenants, low-income households, and municipalities with weaker administrative capacity have been largely excluded. Similarly, regeneration and densification interventions are often market-led and risk exacerbating socio-spatial inequalities. Nature-based solutions, on the other hand, while increasingly present in strategic frameworks, show limited effects on housing

inequalities. Besides specific and transversal lessons across the three cities, the paper identifies key issues and challenges for perspective urban research.

Regeneration, Retrofitting, and Inequality: Green Transition Programmes in Urban and Rural Housing Contexts

Judith Lehner

Universidad Autónoma de Barcelona

Michael Friesenecker

TU Wien, Research Center for New Social Housing

Nina Lobnig

TU Wien, Research Center for New Social Housing

Green transition policies increasingly position housing as a central arena for climate mitigation and adaptation, linking urban renewal, building retrofitting and decarbonisation measures. At the same time, housing systems across Europe are marked by growing inequalities in affordability, access, and housing quality. Building on these recent debates on housing inequality and just transitions, our paper examines how green transition policies, when translated into concrete programmes, interact with existing housing inequalities.

Adopting a process-based comparative perspective, we analyse how action programmes emerging from shared EU and national green transition objectives address housing inequalities when implemented under highly differentiated urban and more rural conditions. It analyses two programmes embedded within the same multi-level policy framework: an EFRE initiative targeting vacancy and regeneration in the small town Gmunden, and the WieNeu+ urban regeneration programme in Vienna. While both pursue similar climate-related goals in tight housing markets, they face distinct housing typologies, ownership structures, and governance capacities. Methodologically, the paper brings together quantitative housing market data alongside document analysis, expert interviews, and focus groups to trace how housing inequalities are problematised within programme design and implementation.

The findings show that common policy objectives can give rise to divergent programme logics with uneven distributional effects, particularly regarding affordability, access to renovated housing and inclusion of vulnerable households. The paper argues that without stronger differentiation at the programme level and closer integration of housing market preconditions and climate policy objectives, green transition measures risk

reinforcing existing housing inequalities rather than supporting socially sustainable communities and resilient transitions across urban and rural contexts.

Negotiating Social, Environmental, and Economic Value within the Pension-Fund–Real-Estate Nexus: The Case of Swiss Federal Railway Real Estate Division

Dasha Kuletskaya

ETH Zurich

Susanne Schindler

Joint Center for Housing Studies, Harvard University, USA

This paper examines how the social, environmental, and economic value of housing intersect within the pension-fund–real-estate nexus, taking the relationship between SBB Immobilien, the real estate division of the Swiss Federal Railways (SBB), and PK SBB, its pension fund, as an example.

We trace how SBB Immobilien’s housing development strategies transformed since the division was founded in 2003 to generate revenue for the restructuring of PK SBB following the Dot-com-crisis till today. We highlight the apparent contradiction between pension funds’ primary mission to secure and maximize the social and economic value of retirement income and their central role in the financialization of real estate – particularly housing – which often undermines social, environmental, and ecological value of housing (Berg 2021; Bonizzi and Churchill 2017; Fraser 2025; Theurillat, Corpataux, and Crevoisier 2010).

Focusing on three projects in central Zurich, we trace how social, environmental, and economic value were defined, negotiated, and produced through and within real estate development by SBB Immobilien. These projects exemplify shifts in the development approach by SBB: the high-end residential and office neighbourhood Europaallee was completed in 2017; the nonprofit housing cooperative Zollhaus is occupied since 2022; and Neugasse, a proposed housing development was derailed by voters in 2024 who demanded the project contain more affordable housing. We focus on the roles played and value-based arguments made by three actors: the quasi-public private developer SBB Immobilien; the pension fund PK SBB; and Zurich’s voters.

Empirically, the paper draws on publicly available records and stakeholder interviews. Theoretically, it builds on interdisciplinary research on social, environmental, and

economic values in the built environment (Chegut et al. 2025; Kockelkorn, Schindler, and Hirschberg 2024; Kuletskaya 2023, 2025; Lake 2024; Schindler 2026; Weber 2002).

(Re)Valuing Housing Renovation in the Circular Transition: A Cross-Disciplinary Review

Paula Femenias

Chalmers University of Technology

Jonatan Forsman
Chalmers University

Elena Bogdanova
Gothenburg University

Martine Buser
Chalmers University

Renovation practices in the housing sector are currently undergoing rapid transformation, driven by the introduction of circular economy principles and the anticipated enforcement of climate-neutral targets in the building sector. Increasing emphasis is placed on reuse, transformation, and repair, rather than demolition and replacement. While these shifts open up new opportunities for preserving architectural, cultural, and historical values, they simultaneously challenge established models for property valuation, investment logic, and regulation and practices regarding functionality and use, including rent setting. Moreover, a stronger focus on repair and limited interventions questions dominant approaches to assessing energy conservation and the ways in which energy efficiency measures are implemented and valued within renovation processes.

This paper focuses on housing renovation, a field that has been extensively studied across a wide range of research traditions and disciplines, including engineering, architecture, facilities and construction management, and housing studies. These fields approach renovation from differing perspectives, reflecting the interests of diverse stakeholders and engaging with distinct value frameworks and evaluative criteria. The aim of this paper is to provide a comprehensive overview of how qualities and values associated with housing renovation are defined, conceptualised, and operationalised across different research areas.

The study is based on a scoping and narrative literature review. Four main research fields are examined: renovation in relation to circularity and energy efficiency; facilities and construction management; housing studies; and architecture and heritage. The review encompasses both peer-reviewed scientific literature and selected grey literature, including policy documents and reports in English and Swedish. The paper demonstrates that housing renovation is shaped by fragmented, often conflicting value frameworks.

How Grassroots Actors Shape Pathways to Residents' Low-Carbon Behaviour in State-Led Community Regeneration: Evidence from Beijing, China

Yiru Jia

Beijing Forestry University

Neighbourhoods are critical sites for shifting residents' behaviour toward low-carbon patterns, as they structure daily routines producing and consuming carbon. In China, old neighbourhood renewal has become a major urban strategy for improving living conditions, while promoting low-carbon practices has emerged as an important policy objective. Yet how regeneration projects can serve as vehicles for low-carbon behavioural change remains underexplored, particularly regarding how grassroots actors create pathways that shape low-carbon action.

Drawing on a case study of Beijing, this paper examines how different grassroots actors deploy strategies and generate interventions targeting residents' low-carbon behaviour. The research employs semi-structured interviews with residents, residents' committees, NGOs, planners, and property managers, complemented by on-site observation between 2024 and 2025. The findings reveal that within top-down regeneration that encouraged resident participation, residents' committees, NGOs, and planners crafted spatial and governance strategies generating three interconnected pathways: 1) design pathways, through which planners reshaped the material environment to nudge green energy use and recycling; 2) norm-building pathways, through which residents' committees and NGOs embedded waste sorting and recycling into social expectations; and 3) demonstration pathways that strengthened residents' efficacy beliefs by making low-carbon outcomes visible. The effectiveness of these pathways depended on trust and cooperation among grassroots actors.

The paper concludes that low-carbon behavioural change in regenerated communities is actively constructed through actor-driven pathways rather than arising automatically from physical upgrading or individual choices. These findings suggest designing

regeneration projects as participatory platforms for low-carbon transitions, contributing to discussions on sustainable community solutions.

Unequal influence of households in the energy transition: housing types and political representation in the digitalisation of the smart grid

Hilda Wenander

Linköping University

This study concerns the political participation and influence of households in the energy transition in Sweden. The importance of households in the energy transition has been highlighted in the existent scholarship, but with less consideration of household agency related to different types of housing, such as occupancy form. Political marginalisation, which is not necessarily aligned with other forms of marginalisation such as socioeconomic, has been identified as an issue in need of further investigations. Depending on the type of housing, households have more or less influence over the domestic energy system. Tenants, for example, have significantly less influence than homeowners over the domestic energy use and costs.

In this study I approach the question of political representation and the inclusion of different types of households in the energy transition by focusing on how interests of different households, residing in various types of housing, are articulated in the formulation and implementation of policies concerning the digitalisation of the electric grid and smart grids. The aim is to contribute to a better understanding of the political representation in the formulation and implementation of smart grid policies in Sweden as part of how households in different types of housing gain influence in the energy transition.

How and by whom are households represented in the digitalisation of the electricity grid? Who is included and who is excluded in the formulation and implementation of policies regarding the digitalisation of the electricity grid? The study intends to map different configurations, forms, moments and mechanisms of political representation and inclusion of households in the digitalisation of the electric grid.

In doing this, this study contributes to timely discussions about housing sustainability, energy democracy and energy justice with focus on the consequences for how residents in different types of housing are included and excluded

Women's participation in housing for sustainable post-disaster reconstruction

Elif Cemre Çelikcan

Baskent University

Ahsen Özsoy

Isik University

Disasters are critical thresholds that shatter the social and spatial structure beyond merely destroying physical infrastructure. The 2023 Turkey Earthquakes have brought about challenges on an unprecedented scale in terms of the right to housing and social resilience. The existing literature demonstrates that low-income women are affected differently and more severely by these processes than men, due to their domestic care responsibilities and their profound relationship with place. Nevertheless, conventional post-disaster housing policies exclude women from the design process.

This study aims to explore the critical role of housing models that prioritize women's active participation in architectural design and planning processes in the construction of sustainable communities. Top-down, standardized and gender-insensitive housing projects fail to meet the need for spatial justice and resilient communities which are not merely a housing issue but a structural problem that threatens social and environmental sustainability.

Within the scope of this study, the ways in which the participatory and open-ended design opportunities offered by the self-help housing model empower women's roles in sustainable post-disaster reconstruction are discussed. Methodologically, the barriers to effective community participation in post-disaster reconstruction and women's potential to organize collective labor, pool resources, and manage community support services are firstly framed with the lessons learned from participatory models implemented following the previous earthquakes.

Self-help housing model's characteristics for answering post-disaster housing problem are explored within this framework to identify its potential for allowing women's participation for the long-term success of housing and social resilience.

Welfare policy, homelessness and social exclusion

Beyond the Shelter: Institutional Trust and Access to Welfare as Determinants of Homelessness Exclusion in Barcelona

Wellington Migliari

UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA

This paper presents empirical findings from a mixed-methods study (N=24) examining the relationship between institutional trust and the effectiveness of welfare policies for homeless individuals in Barcelona. While housing policy often focuses on physical infrastructure (shelters, social housing), this research argues that the perceived legitimacy of service providers is a critical, yet overlooked, factor in combating housing exclusion.

Drawing on semi-structured interviews, we analyse how participants' experiences with social services and public administration affect their pathways out of homelessness. Our data reveals a strong correlation between negative interactions with institutional "gatekeepers" and the perpetuation of street homelessness.

Many participants reported that services, rather than facilitating autonomy, employ coercive measures such as communicating with mental health clinics without consent or threatening the withdrawal of benefits. This dynamic creates a profound sense of distrust, discouraging individuals from seeking the very support designed to help them.

By foregrounding the voices of those experiencing exclusion, this paper provides a critical evaluation of welfare implementation, arguing that eradicating homelessness requires not only robust policies but also a fundamental reorientation of administrative practice towards dignity, transparency, and co-produced solutions.

Navigating Precarity: How Evolving Housing Arrangements Shape Young People's Perceived Social Exclusion in Europe

Niels Broekman

Radboud University

Caroline Dewilde

Tilburg University

Stéfanie André

Radboud University

Young adults across Europe face increasingly precarious housing pathways shaped by rising housing costs, labour market instability, and stalled access to homeownership. This paper examines how these evolving housing arrangements, private renting, co-residence with parents and rent free living, relate to perceived social exclusion among non-student adults aged 25–40. Using 2022 EU-SILC Quality of Life data from 29 countries, we apply multilevel models to disentangle the independent and combined effects of housing and labour market insecurity.

Results show that renters and co-residing young adults report significantly higher levels of perceived exclusion than homeowners, even after accounting for education, income, employment status, and demographic factors. Higher education and income mitigate these penalties, while unemployment amplifies them, particularly for renters. Contrary to expectations, national housing regimes, homeownership prevalence, rental regulation, and family solidarity norms, provide limited moderation. Our findings highlight housing precarity as a distinct axis of disadvantage shaping young adults' social integration across Europe.

The impact of Finnish Housing First on the use of social and substance abuse services

Elisabetta Leni

Y-Säätiö sr

This study evaluates the impact of the Finnish Housing First approach on the utilization and cost of social services and services for substance abuse. Since 2008, Finland has adopted Housing First as a systemic strategy to reduce homelessness. This strategy provides immediate access to permanent housing with individually tailored support,

regardless of sobriety or treatment compliance. While the Finnish model is internationally recognized for reducing homelessness, evidence on its economic consequences is limited.

We conducted a retrospective cost-offset evaluation of Housing First in the Finnish cities of Helsinki and Espoo. Our focus was on formerly homeless individuals who were placed in supported housing units and scattered-site apartments in 2018 and 2019. Using linked administrative data from municipal social and health services, secondary healthcare, and population registers from 2016 to 2021, we tracked service use from two years before to two years after placement. As a counterfactual, we used a comparison group of individuals who were assessed for placement but remained on waiting lists. Using a difference-in-differences framework, we estimated changes in service use and associated costs. Leveraging administrative data enables this study to provide a large-scale evaluation of the Finnish Housing First model.

The findings will have important policy implications both nationally and internationally by shedding light on the service use and cost implications of implementing the Finnish Housing First model.

An Examination of the Evolution of Japan's Homelessness Policy

Yoshihiro Okamoto
Chukyo University

This study aims to examine the fundamental structure, evolution, and coordination with peripheral policies of the ‘homelessness policy’ implemented over more than 20 years, which drastically reduced the number of rough sleepers, and to consider its challenges and future direction. Following the post-World War II period of hardship, street dwellers receded from being a social problem during the period of high economic growth from the 1960s to the 1970s and the bubble economy of the late 1980s. However, after the end of the bubble economy, which peaked in 1990, street dwellers became visible again and have remained a significant social problem to the present day. The enactment of the 2002 ‘Special Measures Law for the Prevention of Homelessness’ marked the implementation of comprehensive national homelessness countermeasures. Consequently, the number of homeless people, which stood at 25,296 in 2003 (according to the ‘National Survey’), decreased to 2,591 by 2025.

The Homeless Special Measures Act provided a fundamental framework for homelessness policy, encompassing “surveys”, “basic policies”, and “implementation plans”. Its core policy was to classify homeless individuals as either “employable” or requiring “protection”, with a focus on promoting employment. However, the 2008-09

Lehman Shock and subsequent recession caused many to lose both housing and employment. During the COVID-19 pandemic from 2020 to 2022, women working primarily in commercial sectors such as food and beverage and tourism lost their jobs. Situations leading to homelessness arose in succession, and the increase in the “invisible homeless” began to be highlighted as a social issue. This study examines the evolution of Japan's homelessness policies, focusing on the “Basic Policy” documents enacted roughly every five years, utilizing legislation, various reports, and newspaper articles.

Hidden, Homeless, and High-Risk: Neurodivergent Children and Families in Temporary Accommodation

KATHERINE BRICKELL
KING'S COLLEGE LONDON

ROSALIE WARNOCK
KING'S COLLEGE LONDON

MHAIRI-JEAN ROSS
KING'S COLLEGE LONDON

The Sensory Lives study examines the lived experiences of neurodivergent children and their families residing in Temporary Accommodation (TA) in the United Kingdom. In England alone, there are 172,000 children who are homeless and living in TA which ranges from hotels to B&Bs, private hostels, short-stay Houses of Multiple Occupation (HMO), to other emerging forms of provision such as modular developments, shipping containers, and converted office blocks. Families' stays in TA can stretch from months, to years, to entire childhoods. Research has combined (1) creative and inclusive methods to engage with and learn from neurodivergent children and their families in London and Greater Manchester, and (2) the first ever UK-wide Call for Evidence delivered collaboratively with the All-Party Parliamentary Group for Households in Temporary Accommodation and the charities Shared Health Foundation and Autistica.

In this paper we first make the case for closer interdisciplinary academic attention to the daily material, affective and care challenges that families face in raising neurodivergent children in TA. We then set out the creative and playful methods we have developed to work inclusively with neurodivergent children and their families in the Sensory Lives project. Finally, we share our key findings and child- and family-led calls for change. For more information about the study visit <https://www.sensorylivesproject.org>

Estimating the Annual Scale of Homelessness in Poland Using Administrative Data

Magdalena Mostowska

University of Warsaw

Assessing the scale of homelessness is crucial for evidence-based policymaking. Until now, the only nationwide data on the scale and characteristics of homelessness in Poland has been the point-in-time (PIT) count conducted irregularly by the Ministry of Family, Labour and Social Policy. In this paper, I draw on administrative data compiled by Statistics Poland on beneficiaries of social assistance. To date, these data have only been used to estimate homeless mortality (Mostowska et al., forthcoming), but in fact, they are the best source of information on homelessness in Poland. I use this administrative register to estimate the number of people who experience homelessness over the course of a year. I present several estimation strategies. First, I rely directly on the register and information on the duration of benefit receipt. Second, I compare the administrative data with the PIT count using shared or comparable variables, such as shelter use, benefit receipt, age, sex, and province. Third, I estimate the number of individuals who never access social assistance using the PIT count and mortality data. By applying multiple estimation approaches, I highlight both the limitations and caveats of each method and demonstrate how they can complement one another. Taken together, these strategies provide a more nuanced and dynamic picture of homelessness in Poland than a one-off point-in-time count.

Unsettled ground: England's rural homelessness, the 'grey zones' of social welfare and the tentative emergence of a 'right to the rural'

Helen Carr

Southampton University Law School

Carin Tunaker

University of Kent

Rural homelessness in England has been understood as an overlooked social problem distinct from urban homelessness (Cloke et al 2002) yet the lack of tailored policy responses and the implementation of 'austerity localism' (Featherstone et al 2012) means that it continues to grow in pernicious and increasingly acute forms. Here we explore the reasons for and the consequences of continued policy failure.

We draw on a small research project commissioned by a consortium of rural and housing charities to capture the causes of increased rural homelessness in England and to make policy recommendations. In our discussion of those findings, we make two distinct contributions to knowledge. In the first substantive section of the paper, we update Cloke et al's seminal research into rural homelessness (Cloke 2002) explaining and reflecting upon the continuities and disjunctions between that research and our own, noting the persistence of a corrosive form of rural imaginary and the impact of variegated neoliberal policies. In the second substantive part of the paper, we offer a more conceptual analysis of the continued omission of rurality from policy discourse on homelessness.

Our starting point, drawing on explorations of urban normativity (Fulkerson and Thomas 2019) is to suggest that rural areas of England exist in a 'grey zone' of social welfare. We then suggest that our research demonstrates some progressive potential in the more fragmented social landscape, facilitating local mobilisations around rural homelessness, potentially reconfiguring 'existing communities around emergent agendas for social justice, participation and tolerance' (Featherstone et al 2012;179). However, any remaking of rural social welfare, we argue, will require animating via an inclusive political framing. We suggest that the emergent academic discourse around a 'right to the rural' with its Lefebvrian connotations of socio-spatial injustice may have the necessary generative potential.

Exit by design: temporary housing policies in Italy

Tommaso Frangioni

Politecnico di Milano

Housing policies in Italian metropolitan areas have been increasingly reliant on temporary accommodation to answer to the needs of evicted families/individuals and of people experiencing specific housing vulnerabilities (e.g. care-leavers, victims of gender-based violence, refugees). Even if the characteristics of these accommodations may vary (e.g. type of funding, degree of shared spaces, number of people involved), they have in common the emphasis on activation programmes devised to improve the socioeconomic status of beneficiaries in the near future, so that they are able to access the private rented market instead of "traditional" social housing (Italy has a strongly dual system), which is highly stigmatized and considered to be dedicated only to chronic poverty.

This paper is centred on an analysis of two local housing regimes (Hoekstra 2020) carried on in Turin and Milan for the last ten years across different research projects. Departing from an analysis of the discourses developed by street-level workers of public

and third sector services about their work, this paper presents a reflection on “exit” as both the premise and the goal of housing policies. These housing programmes are built around the strategy of “exit-by-design” to avoid welfare-dependency and to foster active inclusion in the labour market by relying on the responsabilisation and activation of beneficiaries. Being presented as a temporary measure (up to 18 months), these housing accommodations set a fixed and limited timescape to the beneficiary, during which they are urged to take responsibility for improving their own condition, seizing the opportunity provided by the system of local policies.

Looking at these policies allows a reflection on how time itself can become a policy tool (Lascoumes, Le Galès, 2009), mobilized by loosely referencing the social investment paradigm. This also allows a broader conceptualisation of housing in its relationship with other welfare pillars.

When Housing Becomes Risk: Disaster-Related Deaths and Solitary Deaths in Japan’s Post-Disaster Housing System

Masato Tanaka

Otemon Gakuin University

Japan has experienced many natural disasters throughout its history. In response, a legal system has been developed to support people who lose their homes. This system provides three forms of housing according to the stage of recovery: evacuation shelters, temporary housing, and disaster public housing. Together they form Japan’s housing safety net.

However, serious health and social problems occur within this system. Evacuation shelters are usually located in elementary school gymnasiums. In these spaces, it is difficult to maintain proper health conditions, privacy is limited, and the environment is not suitable for people with disabilities. Under such conditions, disaster-related deaths caused by health problems have often been reported. Temporary housing is built within several months after a disaster. Most units are simple prefabricated structures and rent is free under the legal system. While this housing provides immediate shelter, many residents become separated from their original communities. This often increases social isolation, especially among the elderly and unemployed young adults. In some cases, this isolation leads to solitary deaths (kodokushi). About two years after a disaster, disaster public housing is constructed as a more permanent solution. These units offer better living conditions and affordable rent based on income. However, solitary deaths continue to occur after residents move in, and the number is often higher than in temporary housing.

This paper examines disaster-related deaths and solitary deaths across the three stages of post-disaster housing and reveals structural weaknesses in Japan's housing safety net. It asks why some victims become dependent on the system, why lives collapse even in improved housing, and what conditions are necessary to rebuild stable livelihoods after disasters.

Beyond Housing: A Mixed Methods Investigation of Psychosocial Supports for Persons Experiencing Homelessness

Carrie Smith

Jane Sanders

King's University College at Western University Canada

Stephanie Baird

King's University College at Western University Canada

M.K. Arundel

King's University College at Western University Canada

Laura Herbert

Faculty of Education at Western University Canada

Paige Logan

King's University College at Western University

Sarah Collins

The Salvation Army London Centre of Hope, Ontario, Canada

Homelessness is a complex, pressing, and ongoing concern across Canada. Amid this crisis, policy and service responses have understandably focused on housing status as a key outcome, with Housing First (HF) interventions emerging as a leading intervention approach. Although HF has demonstrated clear efficacy in rapidly securing housing for persons experiencing homelessness (PEH), there is increasing recognition that HF approaches cannot serve as the sole solution to homelessness, nor that housing status alone equates to the meaningful improvements in health and social functioning that shape well-being and long-term stability.

Unmet psychosocial needs diminish quality of life, drive reliance on acute care systems, and impact critical outcomes such as housing stability and participation in education and employment. Despite this knowledge, evidence on how to best meet these needs remains limited. In response, interest in interventions to address these needs is growing; however, the evidence base remains limited, with a notable lack of lived-experience perspectives and limited articulation of the mechanisms through which interventions produce change.

This study sought to address these gaps by investigating a psychosocial support program developed through a community-academic partnership between King's University College School of Social Work and the Salvation Army London Centre of Hope (COH), a key service provider for PEH in London, Ontario.

Using an exploratory mixed methods design, the study examined how psychosocial supports were experienced and navigated by PEH, the impacts of these supports from the perspectives of PEH, and the extent to which they addressed unmet needs.

Findings are expected to contribute new empirical knowledge about lived experiences of psychosocial supports, illuminate mechanisms of change from a service user perspective, and lay the groundwork for future inquiry into embedded and practicum-based models of psychosocial support delivery.

Mapping and Measuring Severe Housing Deprivation in an Irish city

Joe Finnerty

University College Cork

This paper will present proposed research that (a) explores the classification and measurement of households experiencing various kinds of severe housing deprivation in Cork; (b) proposes overcoming deficits in relation to definition and measurement of severe housing deprivation in Cork by advancing a framework for its mapping and measurement; (c) will engage with relevant stakeholders in this process; (d) place the issue of monitoring severe housing deprivation on the local policy agenda.

From principles to Policy: Evaluating Housing-First Policies and Implementation Strategies in Eindhoven

Valentina Cortés-Urra

Eindhoven University of Technology

Oana Druta

Eindhoven University of Technology

Pieter van Wesemael

Eindhoven University of Technology

Housing affordability, the lack of adequate housing and rising homelessness have become pressing social challenges worldwide. In response to these challenges, some European countries, Australia and the United States have adopted Housing-First approaches. In the Netherlands, approximately 33,000 people are experiencing homelessness. In 2022, the Dutch government proposed the ‘Nationaal Actieplan Dakloosheid: Eerst een Thuis’, calling on municipalities to incorporate Housing-First into their local policies. Although this plan aims to sustainably reduce homelessness by 2030 through prevention and housing provision, the institutional changes needed to advance Housing-First at the regional and local levels remain unclear. Moreover, little is known about how policy ambitions align with Housing-First Principles, and the frameworks for assessing their translation into policy remain limited.

This paper proposes and applies an evaluation framework for Housing-First policies and implementation strategies at different scales. The framework builds on a review of the literature on Housing-First, the right to housing, and homelessness, the operationalisation of the Housing-First principles, and interviews with 18 key stakeholders, which we use to refine the framework. Using this framework as a lens, we analyse the case of Eindhoven to identify policy alignments and gaps across policy levels, implementation strategies, and target groups.

We found a multi-level gap where most local policies were internally coherent, the six national Housing-First principles were barely reflected in their ambitions, and their implementation actions lacked specificity regarding stakeholder alliances and timelines. Our findings provide insights to inform policy strategies that can support the implementation of Housing-First and help drive systemic change in homelessness and housing policy. Keywords: Housing-First, Homelessness policy; Systemic change; Policy Evaluation framework; the Netherlands.

“White knuckling until you can't sleep”: A mixed-methods study of the experiences of those working in the health and homelessness sectors

Jane Sanders

King's University College at Western University Canada

Paige Logan

King's University College at Western University Canada

Carrie Smith

King's University College at Western University Canada

Stephanie Baird

King's University College at Western University Canada

M.K. Arundel

King's University College at Western University Canada

Laura Herbert

Faculty of Education at Western University Canada

Service providers and leaders in the health and homelessness sector form an invaluable workforce. Yet they are rarely asked about their own experiences and resource needs when doing this work. Given the important and challenging nature of this work, it is important to understand how to support this highly committed workforce and increase sector stability. The Checking in on the Frontlines Study aims to explore the needs and experiences of Canadian service providers and leaders in the health and homelessness sector to inspire public discourse and inform policy and programmatic changes to empower the workforce and promote job security.

Through an exploratory, multistage mixed-methods design, qualitative data collection in the first stage, using focus groups and interviews (n=31), informed the subsequent quantitative phase and the development of a Canada-wide online survey (n=1326). An integrated knowledge translation approach and participatory action research model ensured knowledge users and frontline workers were involved throughout the research process.

Our findings reveal a dedicated workforce that overwhelmingly (74%) intends to remain in the sector beyond the next two years despite high levels of moral distress. We will identify obstacles to the work, such as workload, insufficient resources, and safety concerns. As the need to support those experiencing or at risk of homelessness grows, we are seeing service providers and leaders under immense pressure to meet communities' diverse and evolving needs. Resources, training, safety and collaboration across the sector provide opportunities to address moral distress and well-being. Perhaps most important is shifting the social discourse in Canada related to homelessness to allow adequate support for those working in this sector. The knowledge created through this research will foster discussions and actionable recommendations to improve working conditions and, subsequently, service delivery.

Hidden Evictions: Self-Initiated Moves and Eviction Prevention during the Formal Eviction Process

Ida Nilsson

Stockholm University

Across Europe, housing evictions are a major societal challenge and an important pathway into homelessness. While research over the past decade has expanded knowledge of enforced evictions, less is known about hidden forms of housing loss that occur earlier in the process. One such form is self-initiated moves during the formal eviction process, when households leave before enforcement takes place.

Drawing on national register data from the Swedish Enforcement Authority, previous studies show that such moves are more common than enforced evictions, disproportionately affect vulnerable groups, and display a partly distinct pattern of risk factors. This has implications for efforts to prevent eviction and homelessness. Against this background, this study examines how locally organised structures for eviction prevention shape the circumstances under which self-initiated moves arise in Sweden. The study draws on qualitative interviews with professionals working with eviction prevention in Swedish municipalities selected to capture variation in resources, eviction risk, and geography.

The findings reveal gaps in coordination, communication, and early intervention. While formal routines often exist in relation to public housing providers, households renting from private landlords are frequently excluded, limiting opportunities for timely support. Informal collaboration and local discretion shape outcomes, producing uneven responses across municipalities and household groups. Families with children are typically prioritised, whereas younger adults, single-person households, and

households with irregular incomes are more often left without support. Cases involving self-initiated moves, or in which the housing outcome remains unknown, are rarely documented or followed up. The study highlights the need for stronger national guidance, earlier intervention, and greater recognition of self-initiated moves in policy, practice, and research.

Rising demand for temporary accommodation as an indicator of structural challenges in housing and welfare systems

Inger Lise Skog Hansen

Fafo

Maja Flåto

Institute for Labour and Social Research

In Norway, as in many European countries, both homelessness and the use of temporary accommodation are increasing.

This paper discusses how rising demand for temporary accommodation may be understood as an indicator of structural challenges in both the housing and welfare systems. It analyses how structural features of the Norwegian housing model – a limited rental sector and highly residual municipal social housing, together with the welfare system - social and health sector, shape both the demand for temporary accommodation and the profile of those who rely on such arrangements.

The analysis approaches the situation as a complex or “wicked” issue (Bramley & Fitzpatrick 2018; Rosengard et al. 2007; Rittel & Webber 1973). The Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration (Nav) are obliged to assist individuals without a place to stay in securing temporary accommodation (Social Services Act §27). The paper draws on data from a research project on assistance with temporary accommodation provided by Nav, including a survey of local Nav offices and case studies in five municipalities. The case studies include qualitative interviews with Nav employees, municipal representatives, providers of temporary accommodation, and residents living in such arrangements.

The findings show that Nav offices in general experience an increase in the number of individuals experiencing difficulties in the housing market and demand for temporary accommodation. Those in need of temporary accommodation constitute a diverse group.

While some face acute problems primarily related to financial constraints and difficulties finding a place to live in a housing market with high prices and limited availability, many experience health problems, substance use and mental health issues, or social challenges that make it difficult to navigate the housing market.

The Role of Real-Time Data in Ending Homelessness: Insights and Perspectives from Nordic Countries

Hermund Urstad

Husbanken

Elisabetta Leni

This paper examines how real-time data can accelerate progress towards ending homelessness across the Nordic countries.

Drawing on OECD recommendations, it contrasts the limits of infrequent point-in-time counts with dynamic systems, such as by-name lists and integrated homelessness information platforms. A municipal case from Kolding, Denmark, shows how a by-name list and dashboard support early identification, coordinated responses, and monitoring of inflows, outflows, and returns. A European comparator, Ireland's PASS, illustrates standardized monthly and quarterly reporting that informs policy while supporting case management.

Using research literature and the authors' practical experience in homelessness work, the paper examines data practices in Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, and Sweden. It then maps implementation barriers—privacy laws, fragmented governance, uneven IT capacity—and opportunities, including leveraging existing administrative registers and shared standards.

The paper argues for cross-Nordic data strategies that pair real-time measurement with policy and service reforms, aiming for homelessness to be rare, brief, and non-recurring.

Service Exclusion Among Young People Experiencing Homelessness: The Role of Disability

Kira Jaechel

Griffith University, Australia

Christopher Ambrey

Griffith University, Australia

Katie Hail-Jares

Griffith University, Australia

Young people experiencing homelessness face persistent challenges accessing welfare services, yet the role of disability in shaping these barriers remains underexamined. This study investigates the association between disability, homelessness, and service exclusion among young people aged 15–24 in Australia, using longitudinal data from the Journeys Home survey.

The analytic sample includes 614 young people contributing 2,469 person–wave observations. Descriptively, service exclusion is relatively uncommon (5.79%) but occurs at approximately twice the rate among young people with disability compared to those without. In adjusted regression models, both disability (OR = 2.15, 95% CI [1.09,4.23]) and homelessness (OR = 2.62, 95% CI [1.41,4.88]) are independently associated with significantly higher odds of service exclusion. However, the interaction between disability and homelessness is not statistically significant, suggesting no evidence of multiplicative disadvantage.

Overall, the findings highlight disability as an important dimension of inequality in welfare service access among young people experiencing homelessness.

Technopolitics: Digital Activism and Data Governance against Housing Exclusion in Lisbon

Ana Luisa Melo

CRIA/ISCTE and NESTUFAL

Lara Silva Fagundes

(CRIA – Centre for Research in Anthropology / NOVA School of Social Sciences and Humanities) Lisbon, Portugal

In contexts where homelessness is increasingly governed through administrative data systems, populations without stable residence become structurally invisible to the institutions that should protect them.

This paper examines this dynamic in Lisbon, drawing on the Lisbon Invisible project, an action-research and digital observatory initiative that combines collaborative ethnography, citizen-generated data, and quasi-experimental evaluation. The paper introduces the concept of epistemic housing exclusion to designate the structural absence of marginalised populations from the data infrastructures through which housing, welfare and citizenship are governed.

Preliminary findings from eight co-creation workshops with 80 participants experiencing homelessness reveal that bureaucratic invisibility operates as an embodied condition shaping access to healthcare, employment, mobility and social protection. The findings further suggest that participatory data infrastructures may function as counter-infrastructures, redistributing epistemic authority and contesting dominant regimes of visibility.

The paper contributes to European debates on welfare policy and social exclusion by arguing that addressing homelessness requires not only the redistribution of material resources, but also of visibility, knowledge and epistemic power.